

**How do educational cultures, discourses and practices shape the retention of disabled students in Higher Education in Scotland?
A Feminist Poststructuralist exploration**

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Author's Declaration

I, Patricia Castellano Verdecia, hereby certify that this thesis, submitted for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) at the University of the West of Scotland, has been written by me. This work has not previously been submitted, in whole or in part, for a degree in this or any other institution.

Personal details withheld.

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Date: 22nd September 2024

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Abstract

Disabled students in Higher Education (HE) face lower retention rates than their non-disabled peers (Lee et al., 2015; Koch et al., 2018). These lower rates stem from the many complex and dynamic factors impacting their experiences, making disabled students' retention a difficult challenge to address (Fichten et al., 2014; Thompson-Ebanks, 2014; Kutscher and Tuckwiller, 2019). While this has traditionally been an under-researched topic, the factors influencing disabled students' risk of withdrawal are gaining attention due to international efforts to widen participation across HE. Yet, existing literature lacks detailed accounts of disabled students' experiences regarding their persistence and retention. Moreover, this evidence tends to focus primarily on policies and practices without critically exploring the structures that create and reproduce them.

To address these gaps, the present research study explored how cultures, discourses and practices across HE in Scotland help fulfil or foreclose disabled students' aspirations and how this shapes their retention. The study employed a qualitative approach, using semi-structured interviews as the data generation tool. As a result, 29 participants collaborated in this investigation. The generated data was analysed using Reflexive Thematic Analysis and Feminist Poststructuralist Discourse Analysis while adhering to a Feminist Poststructuralist framework.

The data analysis revealed two main areas influencing the retention and persistence of disabled students who participated in this study: Disability Support and Pedagogy. Furthermore, the study uncovered how the current HE system in Scotland is not designed for disabled people, with support provision and pedagogical practices often marginalising disabled students. These practices are maintained by existing discourses that perpetuate an idealised notion of disabled students that excludes those who cannot adhere to the standards underpinning that notion. The data also illustrate that this notion is sustained by the sector's neoliberal principles of normalcy and hyper-productivity.

In contrast, participants advocate for care-based approaches that value disabled students' complex experiences as a strategy to challenge marginalising discourses and practices, calling for more inclusive HE cultures in which disabled students can thrive. The study discusses the multiple possibilities related to the implementation of these approaches and offers a comprehensive list of recommendations for research, policy and practice that could promote transformation across the sector.

Finally, this research also emphasises the need for a broader understanding of student retention, particularly when exploring the experiences of disabled students. According to the present evidence, this conceptualisation should consider disabled students' complex experiences, the role of aspirations in their progression and persistence and how educational cultures, discourses and practices shape their retention.

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Chapter 1:

Introduction

This thesis examines how educational cultures, discourses, and practices influence the experiences of disabled students in Higher Education (HE) in Scotland and how this shapes their retention. More specifically, this study has investigated the way in which cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose disabled students' aspirations and how this influences their persistence and retention in the sector. I believe in the benefits of participating in HE, which can be life-changing, reporting multiple individual and societal advantages (Van Hees, Moyson and Roeyers, 2015; Butler *et al.*, 2016; Peercy and Svenson, 2016). For me, HE has been an experience of fulfilment, exploration and growth. However, I am aware of the difficulties associated with this level of education, often known for being discriminatory, which puts some students at risk of attrition (Park *et al.*, 2020; Hussain and Jones, 2021). This is the case for disabled students, who are under-represented and marginalised in a sector that poses countless challenges (Dolmage, 2017; Cotán Fernández, 2019; Hendry *et al.*, 2020; Shaw, 2024).

However, as someone with an educational and professional background in the field of education and with a personal interest in inclusive education, I noticed that the inclusion of disabled students in HE was not often part of the discussion. Thus, through my undergraduate and postgraduate education, as I undertook an undergraduate degree in Psychology, one master's degree in Disability Research and one in Educational Guidance, I perceived that there was great interest in promoting inclusion across early childhood, primary and secondary education (Klang *et al.*, 2020; Woodgate *et al.*, 2020; Love and Beneke, 2021; Fernández-Batanero *et al.*, 2022). Yet, although the interest in promoting disability inclusion across HE is increasing (Gallego-Noche *et al.*, 2021; Moriña, 2022; Moriña-Díez and Orozco Almario, 2023; Gibson *et al.*, 2024) in general, these efforts seemed to end at the secondary level instead of being carried into HE. I thought this was counter-intuitive because the natural progression should be that, after secondary school, disabled students could transition to HE and meet their goals and aspirations. So, I wondered why we were stopping there.

Hence, my curiosity about educational inclusion at the HE level started while I undertook my master's degree in Educational Guidance, which informed my master's dissertation exploring the transition of disabled students into a Spanish university (Castellano and Rosales, 2021). With this PhD thesis, I have expanded my interest and work in this area by investigating the

retention of disabled students in HE, aiming to understand how HE sectors could be more inclusive and a place for disabled students to thrive, instead of being excluded.

Accordingly, as will be illustrated in the Literature Review chapter (Chapter 2), this research also responds to the increasing evidence demonstrating that disabled students are graduating at lower rates than their non-disabled peers and to the limited research investigating this issue (Thompson-Ebanks, 2014; Sue Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2017; Carroll *et al.*, 2020). Although literature investigating the retention of disabled students in the Scottish context is scarce, there is some evidence indicating that disabled students in the nation are also graduating at lower rates than their non-disabled peers, particularly autistic students, students with mental health conditions and students with more than two diagnoses (Commissioner for Fair Access, 2019). This highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the experiences of this group of students in the nation. Moreover, this research also responds to the limited qualitative research that can offer an in-depth investigation of the experiences of disabled students in relation to their persistence and retention and to the need to examine the perspectives of different stakeholders, like students and staff, to gain a broader understanding of this topic (Collins, Azmat and Rentschler, 2019).

Moreover, the relevance of understanding how educational cultures, discourses and practices influence the experiences of disabled students is particularly relevant at the current time, as an increasing number of disabled students are joining HE (Shaw, 2024) while we adjust to the post-pandemic HE landscape (Bones and Ellison, 2022). Thus, on the one hand, we must understand how these factors hinder or enhance the educational journey of disabled students in HE through a critical lens, as there is a need for more inclusive sectors that respond to the diversity of students who have been traditionally under-represented and silenced (Dolmage, 2017). On the other hand, doing so in the post-pandemic scenario allows us to explore what has been learnt in the past four years and what implications this could have in the future of a more inclusive HE sector in Scotland.

Therefore, considering these gaps and research interests, the following research objectives have guided this study:

- To examine ways in which educational cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland.
- To analyse how the influence of these cultures, discourses and practices shapes disabled students' retention in HE in Scotland.

- To discuss the implications of this influence in the future of HE in Scotland in order to promote the retention of disabled students in the sector.

Considering these aims, this thesis investigates the role of cultures, discourses, and practices in the experiences of disabled students, how they allow for the fulfilment or foreclosure of disabled students' aspirations, and, consequently, how this shapes their retention. Additionally, this research has examined how relevant stakeholders consider that change could be brought to the sector to foster the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. Considering these aims and the context of the study, the following two research questions have guided the development of this investigation:

- **Research Question 1:** How do cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland? How does this shape their retention in the sector?
- **Research Question 2:** In which ways do the stakeholders involved consider that there is room for improvement when it comes to fostering the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland?

To meet these aims and address these research questions, I designed and implemented a qualitative research study based on the use of semi-structured interviews while guided by a Feminist Poststructuralist epistemological framework. As a result, 29 participants from three different groups collaborated with this study: a) disabled people currently and b) formerly enrolled in HE in Scotland, and c) disability advisers and educators working within the sector. The data generation phase of this study took place amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, which allowed for increased accessibility during the data generation phase, as interviews took place in different formats such as over the phone, via email or through online communication platforms like Microsoft Teams. Furthermore, in line with the feminist nature of this research, this thesis puts participants' voices at the centre of the study and offers a detailed account of the experiences of disabled students in HE in Scotland. Also aligning with that feminist stance, I created opportunities for open dialogue and non-hierarchical relations with participants, which was reinforced with actions such as sharing the study's findings with participants so they could provide feedback, ensuring that participants agreed with the use I have made of their data. More detailed information about the study's methodological approach can be found in Chapter 3.

Hence, this thesis demonstrates that the experiences of HE disabled students in relation to retention are complex and are influenced by two main areas: Disability Support and Pedagogy. Moreover, the data analyses revealed the existence of an idealised notion of disabled students

across the sector, underpinning a series of discriminatory policies and practices that put those considered *non-ideal* at higher risk of exclusion. The data also illustrates that the sector's neoliberal principles of normalcy and hyper-productivity inform this notion and related discourses and practices. Yet, participants in this study were vocal about the need to face cultures, discourses and practices that marginalise disabled students, calling for care-based pedagogical approaches that recognise and value their overall and complex experiences. Care-based approaches, increased educational choices via Universal Design for Learning (UDL; CAST, 2018), and hybrid learning are positioned as practical strategies to promote inclusion across HE, nurturing a post-pandemic sector that enables disabled students to fulfil their aspirations and foster their retention. This research also proposes a more comprehensive understanding of disabled students' retention, in which the role of cultures, discourses and practices, and the capacity in which disabled students can fulfil their aspirations is considered.

Consequently, this thesis aims to add to the existing literature that investigates the retention experiences of disabled students in HE while taking a critical and broad approach, focusing on cultural, discursive and practical elements that help fulfil or foreclose their aspirations.

Therefore, this manuscript offers a detailed account of the steps and processes I followed to meet these aims, a summary of which can be found at the end of this chapter. Still, before focusing on the main chapters of this thesis, I will use the remainder of this chapter to address and define concepts that have been essential to the development of this study, while setting the scene and research context. Accordingly, the following sections address first, the concept of disability as used in this project, an explanation of my use of disability language, the definition of terms relevant to this research, an overview of the HE context in the United Kingdom (UK) and Scotland, and, finally, a summary of all the chapters of this manuscript.

1.1. Understanding disability

When I started working on this project, my understanding of disability aligned with the conceptions of the social model of disability, which conceives disability not as an inherent personal attribute but as a consequence of societal barriers that hamper the participation of people with impairments (Oliver, 2013). My positioning resulted from previous academic experiences and my work engaging with the literature around the topic. More specifically, I liked the way in which the social model challenged the medical model, which was still dominant in the environments I grew up in. More specifically, according to Dolmage (2017), the medical model defines disability purely in pathological terms and as something to be treated

legalistically. In the context of education, this model perceives inclusion as the implementation of accommodations that are the minimum legally required (ibid). In this regard, I agreed with the social model's aim to challenge this view to understand disability as something to be "depathologized" (Evans *et al.*, 2017, p. 63) and understood not as a characteristic of the body but as a social conception (Llewellyn and Hogan, 2000; Kimball *et al.*, 2016).

According to this model, disability is not located in the individual's body, but it is rather external and situated in the environment, which is, most of the time, limiting and constraining (Marks, 1999). Moreover, the social model argues that disabilities are the obstacles that people with impairments face daily in countless different spaces because those environments are oppressive and not accessible (Marks, 1999; Thomas, 2004). Hence, the participation of people with disabilities in different domains of life is restricted by broader and deeper social rules that become barriers (Oliver and Barnes, 2010; Brown and Leigh, 2018). Therefore, the social model was an alternative point of view to think critically about a system still based on segregation, focused on pathology, and very far from achieving full inclusion and participation, as the one in which I grew up. In an educational context, the social model of disability focuses on promoting inclusive practices as a default strategy, aiming to restructure existing policies and practices across the HE sector instead of only offering individual accommodations and adjustments (Office for Students, 2019).

However, my understanding of disability has also been shaped by other theories, such as Critical Disability Theory (CDT). In this regard, I agree with CDT in terms of acknowledging that impairment and environment are not two independent constructs but that there is a causal and changing relationship between them that might lead to disability (Meekosha and Shuttleworth, 2009). My ideas also align with CDT's views of disability as an intersectional and fluid concept (Shildrick, 2009). In this sense, the experiences of disabled students are not only shaped by their disability but also by other elements of their multiple identities (ibid). Furthermore, I also see disability as a fluid concept, which is indispensable within a HE context. This is because the understanding that disability can be acquired at any time in life and that its impact on the person's experience is likely to fluctuate (Evans *et al.*, 2017) is essential in the development of inclusive cultures and practices. Hence, I argue that an understanding of these three ideas – interaction impairment/environment, intersectionality, and fluidity – is essential in the development of this project because they help to comprehend the impact of educational cultures and discourses on the experiences of disabled students, but also why not all students that have a might be considered legally disabled identify as so. This last one is an issue strongly

linked to disclosure, disability services and accommodations, all concepts that will be discussed later as this thesis unfolds (see Chapter 2).

Additionally, I believe that the principles of social justice (SJ), which are interconnected with CDT, are also applicable to my understanding of disability and the particularities of this research. In this context, ableism is understood as a system that discriminates, disadvantages and excludes people with disabilities while favouring those with no disabilities (see Evans *et al.*, 2017). It also implies that specific capacities are indispensable to live a regular existence, stigmatising certain types of support and ignoring the interdependent nature of human lives (*ibid*). According to Evans *et al.* (2017) the SJ approach does not aim to modify individuals with disabilities to fit into ableist environments. Instead, it focuses on exclusionary and oppressive contexts to ensure that everyone is included and valued for who they are, and taking an intersectional perspective by considering and understanding the person as a whole (Castañeda and Peeters, 2000 as cited in Evans *et al.*, 2017).

Applied to (Higher) Education, this model aims to educate the educational community about disability oppression to change structures and discourses that sustain this oppression (Castañeda and Peeters, 2000 as cited in Evans *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, according to Brown (2014), following the principles of SJ implies creating environments where the provision of disability support is not a legal matter but an issue of humanity and decency. Some of the tools the social justice approach uses to achieve those goals are Universal Design, transforming legislation and promoting awareness and equity (Hackman, 2008). Consequently, I will use this lens to look at discriminatory practices and the role of oppressive systems that disabled students might be facing in HE while considering the different aspects and layers of their identity as a whole.

Moreover, my understanding of disability is also shaped by the epistemological framework I have adopted for the development of this project: Feminist Poststructuralism (FPS; which will be addressed in more depth in Chapter 3). In this case, the ideas of Tremain (2017) gain relevance, as the author rejects most of the prevalent definitions of disability. Tremain, who is a disabled woman, an academic and a philosopher, believes that those definitions are not critical and ignore the “*sociopolitical conceptions of disability*” (2017, p. 37). The definitions the author is referring to understand disability as an “*intrinsic, unfortunate, and politically neutral characteristic (pathological property) that some individuals possess and embody*” (Tremain, 2017, p. 38). Consequently, the author moves towards a poststructuralist Foucauldian view of disability as an “*apparatus of force relations*” (2017, p. 37) that is constituted and constitutive of

other “*apparatuses of power*” such as “*gender, race, sexuality, ethnicity, class, age, and nationality*” (Tremain, 2017, p. 38).

In line with this, Tremain (2017) maintains that force relations are internal to the knowledge production about disability, as understanding disability as an apparatus implies acknowledging its production of disciplinary social rules. Those norms are a result of a series of artificially pre-established conditions “*of unequal power*” (Tremain, 2017, p. 40) that shape authoritarian perceptions, leading to negative sociopolitical and personal consequences for some people. For example, this author says that medical classifications derived from those background circumstances produce certain social groups and people (subjects) through their practices. Although the claim is that those groups of people are only being named, according to Foucault, and seconded by Tremain, they “*come into being because we make them that way by and through the practices that we use to describe them*” (Tremain, 2017, p. 40). As a result, people who do not adhere to strict social norms - such as certain people deemed as “*mentally ill*” - are “*ignored, vilified, and stigmatized*” (ibid).

Applied to HE and this project, I consider that pre-established situations of unequal power, easily identifiable in a hierarchical system, are leading to the creation of authoritarian rules with negative consequences for disabled students. For example, the current policies and practices in disability support provision processes are underpinned by ableist notions of excellence and normalcy that position some disabled students as more or less deserving of support, preventing those who do not adhere to established policies to access the accommodations they need to succeed in a sector known to be exclusionary. Therefore, I adopt this approach to identify and examine existing dominant discourses and practices that result in the discrimination of disabled students, limiting or enhancing the capacity in which they can achieve their goals and aspirations and influencing their persistence and retention.

Hence, these theories and understandings of the concept of disability have shaped the development of my ideas and this project. This impact can be seen in different places throughout this thesis but will be particularly addressed in Chapter 3 and applied and discussed in the findings and discussion chapters (Chapters 4, 5 and 6). Finally, considering some of the terms addressed in this section, the following segment defines concepts critical for this study's development, including cultures, discourses, practices, ableism, and discrimination.

1.2. Relevant definitions

This section defines the key terms at this project's core, enabling its development. Since I address a significant number of terms, I decided to offer these definitions in a narrative way instead of in a bullet-point format to enhance readability. Moreover, I have grouped concepts into subsections that offer relevant definitions and a discussion of these concepts in relation to each other. Therefore, the section contains three subsections that address the following constructs: inclusion, discrimination, ableism and neoliberalism; retention, attrition and aspirations; and cultures, discourses and practices.

1.2.1. Inclusion, discrimination, ableism and neoliberalism

Gibson (2009) believes that *inclusion* can be considered a form of educational philosophy. Moreover, Gibson, drawing from the work of Ainscow (1999) and Allan (2003), points out that inclusion is influenced by social justice principles, aiming for education to become “*a transformatory and positive experience for all as opposed to an exclusionary process*” (p. 12) where there is an ideological and practical commitment to equality. For Liasidou (2014), the term inclusion embodies an ideological imperative for transformation and change to promote disabled people's full participation in all spheres of social and educational life.

However, for some, like Florian (2014), defining inclusion is a rather elusive task. This is echoed by the work of Atkins (2016, p. 18), who wonders if inclusion might only be an abstract construct, impossible in our diverse societies in which we see others from our own specific “*and often more powerful position*”, defining our lives by the measure in which “*we are more or less equal than others*”. Thus, it is important to consider the words of Slee (2013), who warns about being distracted by trying to define inclusion when the focus should be on understanding and challenging educational exclusion.

According to Ainscow, Dyson and Weiner (2013), inclusion and *exclusion* are interlinked, as inclusion implies fighting exclusion, and therefore, it is an endless process. Similarly, Youdell (2006) understands exclusion as a complex, continuous process through which students are relegated from education. For Youdell (2006), exclusion does not only happen at a physical level but is also enacted through educational practices, such as offering a limited representation of students' experiences and interests throughout the curriculum or treating students differently. These experiences can have a long-lasting influence on students' lives and identities (ibid).

Youdell (2006) also highlights the influence of power relations and overlapping social categories that create unequal and exclusionary educational experiences.

Discrimination is a term widely used across the research exploring the experiences of disabled students in HE, although it is not often directly defined. Consequently, in this study, I address the definition offered by the Equality Act (2010). This definition refers to the protected characteristics established by this legislation and understands discrimination as the unfavourable treatment of people with one or more of those protected characteristics. The protected characteristics under the Equality Act (2010) include age, disability, gender reassignment, race, religion or belief, sex and sexual orientation. Traditionally, disabled people have been refused access to HE, which, according to Liasidou (2014), has positioned disabled students at a disadvantage, maintaining their systemic discrimination and marginalisation in the sector. Yet, despite the anti-discriminatory nature of this policy, discriminatory practices are often ingrained across UK's HE, to the extent that even those working towards inclusion stop questioning them (Atkins, 2016).

In addition, according to Dolmage (2017, p. 7), *ableism* in the academy, or academic ableism as the author called it, is the ideology that conceives “*able-bodiedness*” as the norm, the ideal or default condition for human beings, while disability is perceived as invisible, insignificant and “*less than human*”. For Nieminen (2023), ableism conveys powerful messages about “*bodies and minds*”, leading people to understand their own selves in specific ways that are associated with narrow understandings of the lens of normalcy and ability. Thus, we are all affected by ableism, as only a highly reduced group can adhere to ableism's neoliberalist standards of normalcy and excellence (Nieminen, 2023). Yet, according to Nieminen (2023), disabled people are the ones directly affected and excluded through ableism, which is known as *disablism* (Goodley, 2014). More specifically, Campbell (2009) understands *disablism* as the practices that lead to discrimination based on ability. In the context of education, *disablism* tends to manifest as the exclusion and separation of disabled students (Nieminen, 2023).

Therefore, the current conceptions of normalcy and ability that influence ableism are permeated by neoliberal ideologies that value performativity, productivity and competition (Goodley, 2014). For Mintz (2021), *neoliberalism* is an ideology or paradigm that favours free, unregulated markets, privatisation, self-reliance and individual responsibility, disregarding collective well-being and the inequalities that can derive from this model. This ideology has also shaped HE, which, from a neoliberal lens, is seen as a private good aimed at individual gain, emphasising personal responsibility instead of as a public good with societal benefits and

seeing students as consumers (ibid). This translates into decreased public funding and increased tuition fees, leading Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to function as businesses that compete for customers in a market-driven environment (ibid). In this context, HE students are expected to meet a certain level of ability that matches the market's competitive and high-performance principles (Alajoutsijärvi, Alon and Pinheiro, 2021; Wertans and Burch, 2022; Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild, 2024). However, this does not enable a supportive educational environment for diverse students, including disabled students, who cannot meet these standards (ibid).

1.2.2. Retention, attrition and aspirations

The literature review conducted for the development of this study illustrated the varied terminology used to refer to students' retention and associated concepts. Although there are slight differences, all these terms fall under the umbrella of student retention and are often used interchangeably.

The first relevant term is that of *retention*. According to Jones (2008), in the context of HE, retention applies to the extent to which students finish their studies within a specific and specified period. Moreover, Burke (2019) defines student retention as the act through which students maintain their enrolment from the first to the second year of their degrees.

Furthermore, according to Manyanga, Sithole and Hanson (2017), retention is an institutional term that applies to the process through which students continuously enrol in the same HEI until graduation. Along the same line, Webb and Cotton (2018) also agree with the widespread institutional view of retention, which they maintain reflects whether students stay at the same institution or not.

Persistence is another term commonly used in this research field, often as a synonym for retention. In this regard, Burke (2019) maintains that the typical understanding of persistence is the students' sustained enrolment from the second year of studies until they graduate.

Additionally, Kutscher provides a similar definition of persistence (2019) which equals degree completion. For Manyanga, Sithole and Hanson (2017), persistence is the process through which the students meet the programme requirements that will allow them to graduate.

Furthermore, *completion* is defined by Kutscher (2019) as the act of fulfilling the requirements of a certain study program, which provides the student with a specific certificate or type of degree. For this author, "*success and graduation*" (Kutscher, 2019, p. 16) are synonyms of completion. Moreover, according to Manyanga, Sithole and Hanson (2017), completion refers to

finishing a degree and achieving the students' desired objectives. Additionally, Webb and Cotton (2018) argue that completion is typically used concerning students who continue their degree, regardless of whether they stay at the same institution or not. Therefore, completion is a more open and less institutionalised concept, considering students changing conditions, which may lead to institutional changes. However, students who leave HE before graduating will fall under the non-completion rate (ibid).

Likewise, organisations like the Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) define *continuation* rate as the proportion of full-time students who remain in HE for one year after they start their degrees (HESA, 2020). For part-time students, the continuation rate includes students who are still in HE two years after enrolling (ibid). Contrarily, the non-completion rate is represented by the students who are not in HE one or two years after commencement, depending on their mode of enrolment (HESA, 2020).

Attrition is also a term considered in this research field, but in this case by opposition, as it implies students' act of leaving their HEI before graduating (Manyanga, Sithole and Hanson, 2017). For Webb and Cotton (2018), attrition also applies to students who transfer to continue their studies at a different institution. Other terms related to attrition are *withdrawal* and *dropout*. Yet, these two concepts, as Tight (2020) maintains, were more common in past research and are losing popularity due to their negative connotations.

Thus, there is significant variability within the key terms used in this research field, as there is no shared international consensus regarding the most appropriate ones (see Soilemetzidis and Dale, 2013). Moreover, these varied terms and their evolution (such as the reduced use of dropout and withdrawal) reflect the evolution of the field and the resulting improved understanding of the student retention phenomenon (Tight, 2020). This evolution also reflects the field's shift away from a psychological approach that puts all responsibility on students to one where more responsibility is put on HEIs to promote student retention (ibid). In this study, I understand attrition as leaving HE before completing the student's programme of interest, regardless of the stage at which this happens. To use positive language around this term, I use early exit as a synonym for attrition and avoid using terms like withdrawal or dropout.

Therefore, there are different layers to what is understood as student retention. I understand retention and persistence as the act of staying enrolled in the student's preferred programme(s) until completion, regardless of the time it takes to do so and how many institutions they need to do it. I am also interested in the complex experiences that shape student retention and persistence, which means that *aspirations* become a central construct in this study's

investigation of student retention. Considering this, the discussion of Spohrer (2011) gains relevance as the author highlights that aspirations play a key influential role in students' educational attainment, life outcomes and well-being. For Spohrer (2011), aspirations encapsulate students' ambitions, motivations and incentives to work towards their goals. For Grant (2017), aspirations result from the interplay of future-oriented goal-setting, hope and the social context, implying a sense of agency over one's life and a close link to hopefulness.

Consequently, aspirations are not simply theoretical desires but constructs with substantial impact on students' future lives. Thus, aspirations are complex in nature as they are shaped by psychological and social factors and should not be considered solely as individual traits (Spohrer, 2011; Grant, 2017). As a result, Spohrer (2011) challenges policy discourses that focus on individual responsibility and do not consider the structural elements that shape people's aspirations and related life outcomes. In the context of the retention of disabled students in HE, aspirations gain relevance as they can play a vital role in this group of students' persistence and progression, not only seen as personal choices but also influenced by the extent to which HE can help them achieve their aspirations and goals, or not.

1.2.3. Cultures, discourses and practices

Three additional concepts (cultures, discourses, and practices) are crucial to the development of this study, as it is important to understand how they shape the experiences of disabled students in HE. Considering this, Roxå, Mårtensson and Alveteg (2011) define *cultures* as a process of group sense-making guided by "*shared norms, beliefs, values and traditions of the group*" (p. 100). These processes, the authors argue, produce behaviours specific to the group, in this case, the HE educational community. Similarly, Rhoads and Hu (2012) acknowledge that HE institutional cultures reveal "*patterns of behaviour, consistent with commonly accepted norms, values and attitudes*" (p. 354).

The concept of cultures is relevant when studying the experiences of disabled students in HE as these shared traditions, values and beliefs that make academic cultures influence the HE sector's approach to inclusion. Freire (1985) considered that educational cultures are linked to power and the implementation of the values and norms of the dominant group. These cultures, Freire argues, favour students from the dominant group (such as non-disabled students) and exclude and demerit the experiences and aspirations of the marginalised groups (such as disabled students). Therefore, authors like Burke (2015) stress the importance of focusing on

the cultures, traditions and practices that privilege certain groups instead of concentrating on personal attitudes to transform the widening participation discourse in HE.

The two other areas of focus of this research question (*discourses* and *practices*) are closely linked to the concept of *cultures*. In this regard, in their review of the literature Pedraja-Rejas, Rodríguez-Ponce and Labraña (2022, p. 7) cover various definitions that address this relationship. For instance, Gomes Silva and da Silva Bezerra (2018, p.4) - based on the work of Bizzocchi (2003) - define academic cultures as “*a complex set of processes of production, circulation, and consumption of meanings realized through academic practices and shared through pedagogical discourses in educational institutions*”. Similarly, Schugurensky and Naidorf (2004, p. 998) understand academic cultures as “*the discourses, representations, motivations, ethical norms, conceptions, visions, and institutional practices of university actors*”.

Hence, *cultures* can be considered a broader term that encapsulates other constructs such as discourses and practices. Still, I differentiate these three ideas in this study because, as seen above, they each have analytical significance, enabling the examination of direct practices that influence the experiences of disabled students and the discourses and practices that create and reproduce these practices.

Considering this, I understand *discourses* in line with the ideas of FPS, which, according to (Cheek, 2000), can be perceived as common and shared assumptions that are so ingrained that they are not always perceived. Yet, dominant discourses create the “*basis for conscious knowledge*” (Cheek, 2000, p. 23) and a representation of accepted ways of existing (Baxter, 2016). For Dolmage (2017), current dominant discourses in HE create a sense of normativity that excludes disabled people from being accepted as valid members of the HE educational community. This means that HE disabled students are often positioned lower in existing hierarchies, keeping them out of the system or denying them access to opportunities and resources (ibid). Moreover, authors like Atkins (2016) highlight that educational systems can exercise oppression and control over students, like disabled students, through the discourses used to, for example, describe them, which are often associated with models of deficit.

Finally, Kemmis, McTaggart and Nixon (2014) defined *practice* as a form of socially recognised collaborative human activity. The authors add that as part of this activity, certain actions and doings are perceived through particular ideas and discourses, and the people and objects involved in this activity are connected in specific ways towards a shared goal (ibid).

1.3. HE in the United Kingdom and Scotland

This section covers the current HE landscape in the UK and Scotland, offering a general overview of the sector and then focusing on how it has evolved in relation to the inclusion of disabled students. The final part of this section focuses on the available (although limited) data that illustrates the experiences of disabled students in Scotland, the difficulties they face and their lower retention rates. This discussion helps build this study's research argument.

1.3.1. Overview of the HE sector in the UK and Scotland

The Quality Assurance Agency for HE (QAA; 2022, p. 15) defines HE as the level of education “*after secondary and further education, leading to a qualification or credit awarded by a degree-awarding body*”. These qualifications or credits generally lead to a degree, diploma, certificate or other relevant awards as appropriate (ibid). However, according to Plester (2023), multiple legislation pieces and authorities define HE in the UK, with definitions often varying across the four nations of the country. This is because although there is a shared history of HE across the UK, in the past 30 years, the devolution process has returned responsibility for HE to each of the four nations (Atherton, Lewis and Bolton, 2024). Devolution, understood as “*the process of transferring power from the centre (Westminster) to the nations and regions of the United Kingdom*” (Torrance, 2024, p. 5), has given England, Wales, Northern Ireland, and Scotland independence over HE, creating four different sectors with their own policies, funding councils and regulatory frameworks (Atherton, Lewis and Bolton, 2024).

For example, the Higher Education and Research Act (HERA; 2017), which only concerns England and Wales, considers that HE is defined by educational courses beyond the advanced level, according to Schedule 6 of the Education Reform Act (1988). The Schedule 6 of this act includes a series of qualifications considered to be HE, including teacher training courses, first degrees, postgraduate courses and diplomas of HE. In Scotland, the Further and Higher Education (Scotland) Act (2005) defines HE as the courses that can be classified as “*fundable higher education*” (p. 2). The fundable courses included under this definition are first degrees, teacher training degrees, postgraduate qualifications, and those that prepare students to participate in any of the courses identified in this definition. This definition was later supported by the Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Act (2016).

Besides these different definitions, Plester (2023) acknowledges that there is a consensus in using qualification levels across the UK to define HE, which aligns with the definition offered by

the Government Analysis Function (2022). Thus, as also covered by the Office for Students (2022), HE courses in England, Northern Ireland and Wales are defined as qualifications between levels 4 and 8. Alternatively, according to the Scottish Funding Council (SFC; 2022), HE in Scotland covers qualifications between levels 7 and 12 of the Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework (SCQF). Additionally, the QAA (2022, p. 15) highlights that HE qualifications in the UK are those delivered by “*universities, colleges or other organisations*”, which have the authority to award degrees under the relevant legislation and are known as Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) or Providers (HEPs). According to Atherton, Lewis and Bolton (2024), a vital principle of the UK’s HE system is that these institutions are autonomous and have considerable governance and financial independence (ibid).

Thus, the four different systems have multiple differences and commonalities, making them interconnected but independent HE sectors (Atherton, Lewis and Bolton, 2024). In the case of Scotland, the HE sector is made up of 19 HEIs, including 16 universities, a school of art, a conservatoire and a college of HE (Scottish Government, 2024b). Additionally, the funding body with responsibility for HE management in Scotland is the Scottish Funding Council (SFC), which is tasked with distributing funds for learning, teaching and research across the sector, liaising with the Scottish Government, developing relevant policies, protecting students’ interests and generating and disseminating relevant data, amongst others (Atherton, Lewis and Bolton, 2024). However, the SFC is different from England’s Office for Students as it is not a regulator; the SFC also has responsibility for further education (FE) as well as for HE, and it funds research activities, not only teaching and learning (ibid). Another distinctive feature of HE in Scotland is its manageable size, which encourages collaboration (Kemp and Lawton, 2021).

Furthermore, HE in Scotland prioritises four-year undergraduate programmes instead of three-year degrees, as the other nations, and students can enter the sector when they are 16 or older, instead of 18 as the rest of the country (Atherton, Lewis and Bolton, 2024). Another particularity of HE in Scotland is the funding approach as although tuition fees paid by students have increased across the rest of the UK since they were introduced in 1998, the tuition fees for undergraduate degrees are significantly lower and are covered by the Scottish Government for home students (Hubble and Bolton, 2020; Atherton, Lewis and Bolton, 2024). Thus, undergraduate students living in Scotland can apply to the Student Awards Agency Scotland (SAAS) to help them cover their tuition fees if they study in Scotland or elsewhere in the UK (Scottish Government, 2024a). This fee has remained stable since 2009 and capped at £1,820 (Miller, 2024). However, the number of funded places is limited, and the tuition fees of

postgraduate programmes and certain part-time degrees are not covered, nor are the fees of students enrolled in multiple programmes (ibid).

Additionally, it is worth noting that the UK HE system experienced changes in March 2020, when the World Health Organisation (WHO) declared the COVID-19 pandemic (Khan, 2021b). To reduce the COVID-19 virus' spread, many countries around the world adopted safety measures, which included social isolation and lockdowns (Khan, 2021a). These measures had a significant impact on educational systems worldwide as institutions at all levels had to close, which, in the case of HE, led to emergency online learning while students and staff were isolated at their places of residence (Crick *et al.*, 2020; Watermeyer *et al.*, 2021). These emergency measures impacted students' educational experiences since, although online learning was the most straightforward strategy to maintain educational provision, there were concerns about the quality of teaching and learning under those specific circumstances (ibid).

The traumatic nature of the pandemic, which caused the death of millions of people around the world, the isolation that resulted from it and the overall troublesome nature of the event had a profound impact on the educational community. This includes academics in the UK who saw their professional and personal lives significantly disrupted (Watermeyer *et al.*, 2021).

Furthermore, according to Defeyter *et al.*, (2021), students across the UK faced low levels of mental health and well-being during the first year of the pandemic (2020), having low trust in how their universities and the government faced the pandemic-related challenges.

Yet, others like Khan (2021b) emphasise that the shift to online learning resulting from the pandemic has positive and negative elements. On one side, the positives include enhanced flexibility and access to digital learning materials, which fostered accessibility across HE in the UK and other countries (Imran *et al.*, 2023). The most relevant difficulties were related to the limited social engagement and interactions during and after the lockdowns. Additionally, students perceived a lack of institutional support during these periods (Khan, 2021b). As the state of emergency related to the pandemic and the safety measures eased in 2022, HEIs have adopted different approaches to post-pandemic instruction; however, increased use of technology and hybrid learning modes (which combine digital and on-campus learning) is expected (Imran *et al.*, 2023).

1.3.2. Student participation and disability inclusion in HE in the UK and Scotland

The number of students, including disabled students, enrolling across the UK's HE sectors has steadily increased in the past years (Higher Education Statistics Agency, 2024c), which is the result of the country's efforts to widen participation (Shaw, 2024). However, existing data illustrate that despite these efforts, disabled students are still under-represented and marginalised in the sector (Shaw, 2024). It is essential for this study to understand the sectors' evolution toward inclusion. Consequently, this section explores existing data regarding disabled students' participation and inclusion in HE in the UK and Scotland and the legislation and policies' role in this regard.

The Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) provides expert data about the HE sector in the UK, as the agency collects, analyses and disseminates data about the sector on behalf of their statutory customers, which include the Department of Education, the Welsh and Scottish Governments and the Scottish Further, the Higher Education Funding Council (HESA, 2024b, 2024a). The data collected by HESA about students mainly comes from the student record, which provides information about students enrolled in HEIs in the UK (HESA, 2024c). These data allow for a better understanding of the HE sector in the UK as they offer information about student enrolment, progression and characteristics. In this regard, the latest data provided by HESA (2024c) shows that a total of 2,937,155 students were enrolled in HE in the UK in the academic year 2022/2023, which is slightly higher than the 2,857,855 students enrolled in the academic year 2020/2021. In Scotland, the total number of students in HE was 292,240 in the academic year 2022/2023, slightly lower than the 2021/2022 total of 301,230 students in the nation.

Furthermore, according to the latest HESA (2022) data available, since the academic year 2014/2015, the non-continuation rate of full-time undergraduate students following the year of entry has remained reasonably stable in the UK, only increasing from 6.5% to 6.7% in the academic year 2018/2019 (please see Table 1). These data (2022) also show that in the academic year 2019/2020, this non-continuation rate decreased to 5.3%, the lowest figure portrayed on their website. Moreover, these figures illustrate that in Scotland, this shift was from a 6.7% non-completion general rate in 2014/2015 to 7% in 2018/2019; this number decreased to 4.5.% in 2019/2020 (HESA, 2022). Unfortunately, more recent information is not available on the HESA website, as the COVID-19 pandemic impacted some of the data collection and analysis processes (Van Essen-Fishman, 2023).

Table 1. Higher Education student non-continuation rates in the UK and Scotland for the academic years 2014/2015 to 2019/2020

Academic Year											
2014/2015		2015/2016		2016/2017		2017/2018		2018/2019		2019/2020	
Full-time undergraduate students											
UK	Scot.	UK	Scot.	UK	Scot.	UK	Scot.	UK	Scot.	UK	Scot.
6.5%	6.7%	6.6%	6.4%	6.5%	6%	6.8%	6.1%	6.7%	7%	5.3%	4.5%

Adapted from: HESA (2022) Non-continuation: UK Performance Indicators. Available at: <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/data-and-analysis/performance-indicators/non-continuation>

Additionally, the information available reflects that the HE student population in the UK is becoming more diverse and was made up of 12% undergraduate students from low-participation neighbourhoods, 12% mature undergraduate students and 16% of students who shared their disability status in 2022/2023 (HESA, 2024c). While overall, these figures are positive concerning diversity and inclusion in the sector, due to the focus of the study, in this section, I take a closer look at the figures relating to disabled students and explore the widening participation policies in the UK and Scotland and how have these shaped the access and experience of disabled students in HE.

More specifically, 16% of the UK’s HE students declared their disability status, reflecting the slow but steady increase of disabled students across the sector (HESA, 2024c). In addition, in the academic year 2014/2015, students with a known disability represented 11% of HE students in the UK, increasing to 14% in 2018/2019 and remaining stable at 15% from the academic year 2019/2020 to 2020/2021 (HESA, 2024c). A similar trend is reflected in specific nations of the UK, such as Scotland, where the proportion of disabled students in HE in 2014/2015 was 10%, rising to 15% in 2020/2021 and 17% in 2022/2023 (HESA, 2024c). More detailed information about these figures can be found in Table 2 below.

Yet, the number of disabled students across the UK is likely higher than what is reflected in statistics because there is evidence that many choose not to share their disabilities due to a fear of stigma and negative repercussions (Vickerman and Blundell, 2010; Redpath *et al.*, 2013; Kendall, 2016; Newman *et al.*, 2021). Thus, although this issue will be addressed in more depth in the literature review chapter (see Chapter 2), it is essential to note here that the disability disclosure process is complex (Pearson and Boskovich, 2019) and that this means that it is difficult to estimate how many disabled students are indeed enrolled in HE programmes (Atherton, Lewis and Bolton, 2024). According to the Commissioner for Fair Access (2019), since disability is self-declared by students, it is unclear if these increased numbers are mainly

due to a rise in the number of disabled people who enrol in HE or due to disabled students' increased willingness to declare their disabilities.

Table 2. Percentage of disabled students enrolled in the UK and Scotland between the academic years 2014/2015 and 2022/2023

UK						
2014/2015	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	2020/2021	2022/2023
11%	12%	13%	14%	15%	15%	16%
Scotland						
2014/2015	2016/2017	2017/2018	2018/2019	2019/2020	2020/2021	2022/2023
10%	11%	12%	13%	14%	15%	17%

Adapted from: HESA (2024) Who's studying in HE? Available at: <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/data-and-analysis/students/whos-in-he#characteristics>

The increased participation of disabled students in HE is still a positive indicator of increased diversity in a sector that is known for its hierarchical and exclusionary structures (Madriaga, 2007; Macleod and Cebula, 2009; Dolmage, 2017). However, in the past two decades, there have been substantial changes to policy and legislation that aim to tackle the discrimination faced by disabled students and enhance their representation across HE in the UK. One example is the Disability Discrimination Act (DDA), which in 2002 established HEIs' responsibility to avoid discrimination towards disabled students (Kendall, 2016). Later, the Disability Equality Act (2005) emphasised the HE providers' duty to actively promote inclusion and equality for disabled students. According to Shaw (2024), the most recent piece of legislation offering a legal structure against discrimination and marginalisation under a series of protected characteristics, including disability, is the Equality Act (2010). The Equality Act (2010) compiled and integrated existing documents, such as the Disability Equality Act (2005), and is the legislation that currently informs inclusive educational approaches in the UK, although it does not apply to Northern Ireland (Kendall, 2016; Shaw, 2024).

Under the Equality Act (2010), someone is disabled if they *“have a physical or mental impairment that has a ‘substantial’ and long-term,’ negative effect on [their] ability to do normal daily activities”*. According to this definition, a substantial negative effect is understood as *“more than minor or trivial”*, for example, taking *“much longer than it usually would to complete a daily task like getting dressed”*, and *long-term* is perceived to be *“12 months or more”*. The Equality Act (2010) specifies that disabled people have rights that aim to prevent discrimination in areas such as employment and education. This means that it goes against the law to offer

disabled students unfavourable treatment, which includes direct and indirect discrimination, harassment and victimisation, via practices such as refusing admission to students due to their disability or penalising disabled students if they complain about harassment (ibid).

Nonetheless, although Brown (2014 as cited in Shaw, 2024) acknowledges that one of the difficulties associated with the Equality Act's legal definition of disability is its close links to the medical model of disability, putting the focus on impairment, this legislation has helped widen participation in the sector and changed the landscape regarding HE inclusion. As Kendall (2016, p. 2) points out - after drawing from the work of Goode (2007) and Jacklin and Robinson (2007) – in the past, *“it was not unlawful for HE institutions to discriminate against individuals with a disability, often offering limited or no support”*.

Moreover, according to the guidelines of the Equality Act (2010), education providers, including HEIs, have a duty to make reasonable adjustments to avoid discrimination against disabled students at their institutions, which includes a duty to make anticipatory arrangements to remove barriers from their institutions that could prevent the participation of disabled students (Kendall, 2016; Bunbury, 2020). Yet, there is no fixed definition of reasonable adjustments, which shows a lack of clarity (Kendall, 2016) but also illustrates the open and individualised nature that these adjustments should have, adapted to students' needs and programme characteristics (Elcock, 2014). Still, that lack of clarity might lead to discrepancies regarding what different HEIs consider (un)reasonable (Scope, 2024). According to Disability Information Scotland (2024) what HEIs consider reasonable depends on elements such as the institution's size or the course's length.

Some examples of reasonable adjustments include accommodations related to learning and teaching practice, including curriculum and assessment (Redpath *et al.*, 2013; Riddell and Weedon, 2014; Bunbury, 2020). According to Lead Scotland (2019) reasonable adjustments in this part of the UK include making arrangements to ensure students with frequent hospital admissions can keep up with the learning content, providing accessible learning materials in different formats such as Braille and allocating additional time for exams and deadlines. Moreover, Lead Scotland (2019) and Disability Information Scotland (2024) point out that HEIs in Scotland have departments focused on providing disability and student support, and advisers who work within those departments can support disabled students in accessing reasonable adjustments. Disability advisers in most HEIs in the nation will work with disabled students to develop a learning plan considering the programme requirements and students' needs (Disability Information Scotland, 2024). These plans are implemented in partnership with educators (ibid).

Another way in which disabled students in the UK get support is via the Disabled Students' Allowance (DSA), which consists of non-repayable grants aimed at helping disabled students with the additional costs that they face in HE because of their disabilities (Shaw, 2024; UK Government, 2024a). DSA is not means-tested and is available to all UK disabled students, regardless of whether they are studying full-time or part-time at the undergraduate or postgraduate level (UK Government, 2024a). Students eligible for DSA support must

“(a) meet the personal eligibility criteria for student finance within the Education (Student Support) Regulations 2011 and be studying a course designated for student support; and (b) have a disability as defined in the Equality Act 2010” (UK Government, 2024b, p. 6).

DSA comprises three different allowances to address students' different needs: large items of equipment allowance, non-medical personal helpers' allowance and basic allowance (Lead Scotland, 2019). According to the latest HESA (2022) data available, in 2020/2021, 96,365 undergraduate students received DSA support, which equals 7% of UK-domiciled undergraduate students across the four nations (N = 1,373,835). Although DSA is not available to international students, HEIs have a duty to provide reasonable adjustments for this group of students to ensure they do not face discrimination in areas such as admissions and student services (Lead Scotland, 2019).

In the case of Scotland-domiciled students, DSA support is accessed via the Student Awards Agency for Scotland (SAAS), which pays said allowances directly to the students (Lead Scotland, 2019). According to SAAS (2023), 5,555 students received DSA in the academic year 2022/2023, representing an increase of 6.1% from the academic year 2021/2022 (N = 5,235). In this case, students must provide medical certification for disabilities or conditions that affect their learning experience (Lead Scotland, 2019). According to Lead Scotland (2019), students can receive support from the disability support office at their institutions to help them apply for DSA. Yet, this application is only valid for one academic year and must be repeated each year of their course (ibid).

The DSA system has experienced changes in the past decade; however, it is unclear if these changes positively impact disabled students' experience. For instance, one of the main changes was the 2015/2016 reform in England, which took away some of the government's responsibility and put it on HEIs (Shaw, 2024). More recently, in April 2024, new changes were introduced to the DSA process in England and Wales (which also applies to English and Welsh students studying elsewhere in the UK), as DSA support in these parts of the country is now provided via

suppliers StudyTech and Contact Associates (Capita) on behalf of the Student Loans Company (Thomas Pocklington Trust, 2024). The rationale for these changes was to increase accountability and responsibility in the DSA application process and to reduce delays and bureaucratic difficulties related to the system (Thomas Pocklington Trust, 2024). Whilst it is too early to determine the impact of the most recent changes, press communications (Jack, 2024) reported that some key stakeholders, such as the National Association of Disability Practitioners and the National Network of Assessment Centres, have expressed their concerns about the quality and the rationale of these changes. These organisations believe that the new DSA systems are worrying as the quality of assessment and support is likely to decrease, adding pressure on HEIs to reduce costs despite DSA being a crucial resource to enhance disabled students' retention in the sector (ibid).

Yet, despite the legislation and strategies aimed at fostering disabled students' inclusion across HE in the UK, disabled students in the UK still face substantial barriers across the sector and are marginalised and under-represented (Madriaga, 2007; Disabled Students UK, 2022; Gibson *et al.*, 2024). In this regard, the Office for Students (2021) highlights that there is an attainment and outcomes gap between disabled and non-disabled students, as the former have lower academic results and post-graduation employment rates than the latter. Moreover, via the Policy Connect and Higher Education Commission (HEC) report "Arriving at Thriving", Hector (2020) identified some of the most significant challenges faced by disabled students in HE, including financial struggles and barriers related to a lack of teaching and learning accessibility. These types of difficulties put disabled students at higher risk of early withdrawal than their non-disabled peers (Meehan and Howells, 2019; Shaw, 2024). Considering this landscape, Gibson *et al.* (2024) conclude that current UK policies and practices do not take effective consideration of the lived experiences of disabled students in the HE.

Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic had a specific impact on disabled students across the UK, often hindering their educational experience. More specifically, according to the report elaborated by Disabled Students UK (DSUK; 2022), the move to online learning during the pandemic resulted in positives and negatives for disabled students. One of the main positives was the flexibility that resulted from this learning mode, including online delivery, recorded lectures and online assessment, which were strategies for inclusion that disabled students had requested for years and felt were long overdue (DSUK, 2022). Still, the limitations resulting from the pandemic affected disabled students' quality of life and educational experience as they were less likely to have effective access to digital resources and the internet, and many struggled to receive adequate support from their institutions during the period (DSUK, 2022).

The Disabled Students' Commission report conveyed similar results (2021a), as nearly 50% of the respondents to their survey declared that they did not receive effective support from their institutions, and 80% saw their mental health decrease during this period. Yet, as highlighted by DSUK, the pandemic was also an opportunity to rethink traditional pedagogical practices and enhance disability inclusion in HE. Therefore, in their 2022 report, the organisation proposes a post-pandemic “*new normal*” for the UK's HE, implementing the lessons learned from this event and advocating for a more inclusive future. These lessons include taking an anticipatory approach to inclusion, providing sufficient resources for accessibility, fostering positive attitudes and cultures, reducing disabled students' administrative burden and taking responsibility.

Therefore, while diversity has increased across the UK's HE, the effectiveness of policies aimed at enhancing inclusion is unclear, as disabled students still face exclusion and discrimination. However, the post-pandemic landscape offers an opportunity to rethink and reshape the sector, aiming for more effective approaches to enhance disabled students' inclusion and participation. Moreover, despite the evidence indicating that disabled students are at higher risk of attrition, existing data rarely addresses this difficulty in depth, leaving several questions unanswered. As this study investigates the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland, the following section discusses the available data regarding this specific area, helping justify this research's specific focus of study.

1.3.3. Retention of disabled students in Scotland

The data exploring the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland is limited, which does not allow an appropriate understanding of the current landscape. Nonetheless, although the number of disabled students entering the sector has increased (HESA, 2024c), there is evidence that despite quantitative improvements regarding student diversity, little is known about the quality of the experiences of under-represented students in HE in Scotland (O'Toole *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, existing literature also demonstrates the many challenges experienced by disabled students in the sector, illustrated, for example, by the work of Hendry *et al.* (2020), discussing the exclusion of deaf students in FE and HE. These issues, considered alongside the evidence showing that disabled students in HE in Scotland graduate at lower rates than their non-disabled peers (Commissioner for Fair Access, 2019), call for a deeper understanding of the experiences of disabled students in the sector and the factors that influence their lower retention rates. Therefore, this section discusses the available data that helps set the scene

regarding this issue, reinforcing the need for more research that helps shed light on such a crucial area, justifying the current study.

More specifically, according to the available data, disabled students in Scotland represented around 17% of the total HE student population in the academic years 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 (SFC, 2023; HESA, 2024c). Yet, we know little about their progression and the quality of their experiences. For example, the Report on Widening Access 2021/2022 offers some information, illustrating that 90.4% of disabled students and 91.8% of non-disabled students in the nation continued their studies into the second year (SFC, 2023). Although overall, these results are positive, the inequality between disabled and non-disabled students persists. Furthermore, the available data does not offer detailed information about disabled students' academic journey after the second year.

Additionally, research exploring the quality of disabled students' experiences in HE is also scarce or was published more than 20 years ago (Tinklin and Hall, 1999; Tinklin, Riddell and Wilson, 2004; Riddell and Weedon, 2014; Weedon, 2016). However, this evidence offers a clear illustration of the challenges faced by disabled students in HE in Scotland. In this regard, Tinklin and Hall (1999) identified obstacles like physical barriers, difficulties in accessing information and low levels of disability awareness. Tinklin and Hall (1999) also recognised that one of the difficulties observed in the HE sector in Scotland is that disabled students are offered "*a model of assisted access to a system which inherently includes obstacle to their participation*" (p. 193). This system, based on individualised support instead of challenging structural barriers, has been the most common in the sector, as reported by more recent research, such as the work of Tinklin, Riddell and Wilson (2004). Considering the recurring barriers affecting this group of students, Tinklin and Hall (1999) called for a different system to support provision and advocated for one in which policy and practice have the inclusion of disabled students at their core, striving to value student diversity genuinely. This is echoed in Tinklin, Riddell and Wilson's work (2004), which states that HE educators should question traditional learning and teaching strategies and adopt strategies that could benefit all students. Yet, they acknowledge that the cultural change required for a change of these characteristics does not happen overnight (ibid).

Despite the challenges reported and these authors' call for more effective inclusion (Tinklin and Hall, 1999; Riddell, Wilson and Tinklin, 2002; Tinklin, Riddell and Wilson, 2004; Riddell and Weedon, 2014), disabled students are often disregarded in actions and research aimed at widening access, participation and retention. This could be the result of the nation's commitment to widening participation from a socio-economic perspective, focusing on

students from socio-economically deprived areas, reflected in reports such as “*Higher Education - Renewing the Alliance for Fair Access: Annual Report 2024*”, published by the Commissioner for Fair Access. While the value of this report is clear, it did not consider disabled students, despite this being one of the weaknesses of its 2016 predecessor: “*A Blueprint for Fairness: Final Report of the Commission on Widening Access*”. This was acknowledged in 2019 by Professor Sir Peter Scott (then Commissioner for Fair Access) in the discussion paper related to the 2016 report, highlighting that it was necessary to pay further attention to the challenges experienced by students with different protected characteristics. Yet, once again, disabled students were left out, also despite the evidence that recommends taking more detailed consideration of students’ identities regarding the intersection of disability type and socio-economic background (Weedon, 2016).

Considering this weakness, the Commissioner for Fair Access (2019) published a discussion paper addressing the lower retention rates of disabled students in HE in Scotland by reflecting on data provided by HESA. In this regard, the Commissioner for Fair Access (2019) discussed the lower retention rates of students who had multiple disabilities, those who reported a mental health condition and those who declared to be autistic. More specifically, as seen in Figure 1, between the academic years 2011/2012 and 2016/2017, the retention rate of students with more than two disabilities (2+) is 88.6%, and that of autistic students and students with a mental health condition (MH/ASD) is 87.3%, which is remarkably lower than those of non-disabled students (91.6%). This is particularly relevant considering that the number of students who declare a mental health condition or autism has tripled since 2011/2012, going from 370 to 1,140 in 2016/2017, representing 3% of the total of students in the nation (Commissioner for Fair Access, 2019).

However, as seen in Figure 1, it is positive that, as the graph shows, the retention rates of students with a specific learning difficulty (SpLD), students with a physical or sensory impairment (Phys/Sens) and students with other disabilities (other) had retention rates closer to that of non-disabled students ranging from 90.4% to 92%. While the Commissioner for Fair Access (2019) acknowledged that socio-economic deprivation can have a more significant impact on Scotland’s HE students’ retention and degree outcomes, this is no reason to underestimate the circumstances of disabled students in the sector. Instead, according to Riddell, Wilson and Tinklin (2002) it is advisable to consider both identity markers in relation to disabled students’ progression and retention, as disabled students from disadvantaged backgrounds can have more difficulties finishing their degrees.

Source: HESA (2011/12 to 2016/17)

Figure 1: Full-time first-degree retention rates by disability group

Extracted from: *Disabled students at university: discussion paper (Commissioner for Fair Access, 2019)*

Therefore, widening participation and access efforts are only the first step towards disabled students' inclusion in HE in Scotland, and a closer exploration of the sector is necessary to foster their success, persistence and retention. The study of this topic gains relevance in the post-pandemic landscape since, according to the Scottish Funding Council (2023), students could have faced more struggles to complete their degrees during that period due to the medical impact of the virus on them and their close ones. It is necessary to explore the experiences of disabled students in the country in more depth, as these circumstances might have only exacerbated the difficulties experienced. Thus, the present study gains relevance considering this context and the lack of evidence available regarding the retention of disabled students, considering their lower retention rates in Scotland. As the rest of this thesis will demonstrate, the current study offers a much-needed comprehensive discussion of the experiences of disabled students in the sector, addressing the cultural, discursive and practical factors that shape their retention and persistence.

1.4. Approach to disability-related language

Before this chapter ends, it is necessary to address the approach to disability-related language that I take in this manuscript and throughout the development of this research. By approach to disability-related language, I mean the vocabulary that I will use to talk about disability and related constructs, particularly about individuals who are part of the disability community. I

believe that an important part of this project is to represent the voices and identities of the participants appropriately, and the language I use plays a crucial role in that regard. Consequently, I decided to (mostly) use identity-first language based on the participants' most common preference. Nevertheless, in some instances, I will use person-first language to align with the stance of researchers cited in this thesis and with the preferences of some participants who preferred this approach. This section addresses the rationale behind these choices and their implications for the writing of this thesis.

Traditional views of disability have been negative and stigmatising, with derogatory terms historically being used to refer to the disability community. For example, the vocabulary linked to the medical model ("deaf-mutes", "the retarded"; Dunn and Andrews, 2015, p. 258) has helped create and maintain the oppression and marginalisation of this group (Flink, 2021). Fortunately, the language related to disability has always been alive and evolving, as it continues to do. Thus, the social model of disability, born at the end of the 20th century, created the space for new disability terminology to arise (Dunn and Andrews, 2015). This model brought a change of views, which also meant a change in language, claiming that the person always comes first than any other of their characteristics (ibid). Hence, according to this model, a person-first approach to language is most desirable as it uses terms like person/people with disabilities (Dunn and Andrews, 2015). The aims behind person-first language are to eliminate barriers, reduce marginalisation, promote inclusion, participation and well-being, and preserve people's humanity, personhood, dignity, and individuality (Flink, 2021). It also intends to help spread positive views of those who have disabilities and debunk the many myths, stereotypes, negative attitudes and barriers they have historically faced (Dunn and Andrews, 2015; Gernsbacher, 2017).

However, the use of person-first language is controversial within the disability community. For example, Sinclair (2013) believes that a person-first approach reinforces negative views of disability, implying that it is something so terrible that it cannot be used to define a person while maintaining their dignity. This creates a paradox since by trying to establish a more positive term, the disability is highlighted as something negative (Bury *et al.*, 2020). Collier (2012) also recognises the good intentions behind the person-first approach but stresses that it can lead to narrow views of disabilities as it implies that to be human, we must ignore characteristics deemed negative by the larger group, which might set limits on what being human means (ibid). Consequently, Collier (2012, p.1) asks, "*Why not see both the person and the disability? Is a disability something one should be ashamed of? Does it make you less human?*" Along similar lines, Sinclair (2013), who is autistic, reminds us that no one avoids using adjectives

“considered positive or neutral” (2013, p. 2), but it is only when it has been decided that a characteristic is negative, that there is a need to “separate it from the person” (ibid).

In the context of HE, there is an existing debate as to which of these is the most appropriate approach (Lister, Coughlan and Owen, 2020). Some claim that the duty of HEIs is to promote inclusion and positive environments for students and staff with disabilities by using person-first language (Flink, 2021). Lister, Coughlan, and Owen (2020) agree with this viewpoint, especially when it comes to contacting large groups of students. Nevertheless, they also remind us that there is a great variety regarding the language students prefer to use, which might depend on the context of communication. Consequently, these authors recommend the use of a personalised approach for individual interactions, considering the student’s preferences. For bigger audiences, they suggest the use of inclusive language involving different terms that could resonate with the heterogeneity of the disability community (ibid).

I believe both styles have advantages and disadvantages, but I find myself more closely aligned with those claiming that a person-first approach unintentionally shines a negative light on disability as something not good enough to define a person. Considering that this study takes a feminist poststructuralist approach that supports that meaning can be created “*within language*” (Weedon, 1987, p. 23), I support the arguments of authors like Sinclair (2013), who emphasises that a person-first approach perpetuates an understanding of disability as something to be separated from the person because it makes us less human. Thus, I use identity-first language by default in this document and in the rest of the work related to this research to represent my personal stance and the participants’ preferences as a group.

However, I also support the ideas of Dunn and Andrews (2015), who believe that both positions are valuable in their own way and that using only one of them would exclude part of the disability community. This means that there will be occasions in which I use person-first language to respect the views of researchers whose work I discuss in this manuscript and of specific participants who prefer a person-first approach.

Hence, I will mostly use terms such as “*disabled students*” or “*neurodivergent person*”, but I also use “*student(s) with disabilities*” when appropriate. This choice is supported by my engagement with the literature, and participants directly involved in this project, but also by my experiences with the disability community and the dominant cultural preferences in Scotland and the rest of the UK. More precisely, since I returned to Scotland to develop this project in October 2020, I have engaged with the local disability community in my educational, professional and personal experiences, in which I have also acknowledged the preference to

use identity-first language. Therefore, I argue that using identity-first language as my default choice is the best way to represent the disabled people who collaborated in this research and those who might be interested in its outputs. Yet, I will use person-first language when appropriate. Adopting this flexible approach allowed me to reflect on the variability of identities and experiences within the HE disability community.

1.5. Thesis overview

This thesis is made up of a total of seven chapters, including the current one, which come together to offer a detailed account of the rationale and steps I undertook to meet the objectives set out at the beginning of the chapter. In doing so, this thesis discusses the research findings in relation to the role of cultures, discourses, and practices in the experiences and aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland and how this shapes their retention in the sector. Thus, this section offers a brief discussion of the focus of each of these chapters and their role in the thesis and overall research study.

The current chapter (Chapter 1) provides an overview of the study's aims and addresses the context in which it has been developed, alongside definitions and discussions of the key constructs that set the basis for this research. These concepts include those of cultures, discourses, practices and ableism, together with my understanding of disability, my use of disability-related language and the current overview of the thesis organisation.

Chapter 2 offers a review of the literature relevant to the student retention phenomenon, first focusing on the general body of students and then on the retention experiences of disabled students in the sector. This chapter takes a narrative approach to review the literature, and it first offers an overview of the most relevant models and recent research on student retention that focuses on the overall student body. The second part of the chapter explores literature that examines the experiences of disabled students in HE and then concentrates on research that addresses their retention and attrition by addressing risk and protective factors. The chapter ends by reviewing strategies to promote the persistence of disabled students in HE and a conclusions section that addresses the gaps that justify this study and its research questions.

Chapter 3 focuses on the methodological approach adopted to conduct this study. Thus, this chapter starts by acknowledging and justifying the suitability of the epistemological framework that guided my research: Feminist Poststructuralism. After this, the chapter addresses different elements of the research design and implementation. These elements include a justification of the research questions, an overview and explanation of the research design, including the

participant's recruitment strategy, a description of participants, and the data generation tool and process. Furthermore, the chapter addresses the ethical considerations I took to develop this study and write this thesis. It also includes a section where I discuss researcher reflexivity and positionality and ends by offering a visual outline of the thematic framework I developed from the data generated and a justification about the structure of the findings chapters.

Chapter 4 is the first empirical chapter, discussing the findings that relate to the first thematic area identified: Disability Support. More specifically, this chapter offers a detailed discussion of how different cultures, discourses and practices related to disability support shape the experiences and retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. The key findings in this chapter illustrate the mismatch between disability advisers' and disabled students' perceptions of the effectiveness of this process, as the latter emphasise their struggles accessing support, while disability advisers had a more positive understanding of the process. Moreover, this chapter addresses the existing idealised notion of disabled students across the sector, which leads to harmful hierarchies. These hierarchies position disabled students who do not meet the criteria of ideal disabled students that characterise the sector's cultures, discourses and practices. According to the present data, this idealised notion refers to undergraduate disabled students who can access medical certification; those who do not meet these criteria are at risk of experiencing further discrimination. Additionally, the chapter discusses the role of responsibility in disability support provision and difficulties related to the lack of accountability enabled by current cultures, discourses and practices. The chapter ends with my discussion of the participants' recommendations to address the challenges discussed.

Chapter 5 is the second empirical chapter, focusing on the second thematic area identified: Pedagogy. In this case, the chapter starts by offering an overview of the influence of neoliberal principles on the HE sector in Scotland and their influence on the experiences of disabled students in the sector. This is followed by a discussion of participants' efforts in challenging and resisting the consequences of neoliberal principles by proposing care-based educational approaches that recognise and value the diverse and often complex experiences of disabled students. These proposals are embodied in participants' interest in adopting an anticipatory approach to promote inclusion in the sector and maintain a hybrid learning approach after the COVID-19 pandemic that allows for the development of disabled students' sense of belonging. According to the current data, these approaches have the potential to promote inclusion across the sector by challenging current power structures that position disabled students as passive subjects within the educational community and by promoting cultures, discourses and

practices that recognise and celebrate student diversity as an inherent part of the human experience.

Chapter 6 offers a general discussion of these findings and their implications for HE in Scotland. More specifically, it highlights the importance of adopting a more comprehensive understanding of disabled students' retention and discusses the need to adopt an intersectional approach to challenge the current idealised notion of disabled students across the sector, which is perpetuating ableism and discrimination. Moreover, in this chapter, I address the need to put an ethics of care and responsibility at the centre of educational cultures, discourses and practices in order to bring positive change and transformation to the sector. The chapter also discusses the possibilities and challenges of adopting these approaches to create a HE sector that helps fulfil the aspirations of disabled students and promotes their persistence and retention. This is followed by a discussion of the strengths and limitations of the study and by multiple recommendations to different stakeholders in the sector concerning the focus of the study.

Finally, Chapter 7, the shortest one in this thesis, offers the main conclusions I extracted after conducting this research, alongside concluding remarks that bring closure to this study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The present chapter offers a narrative literature review that synthesises and examines a broad range of evidence relevant to the current research topic. Thus, this literature review covers, first, broader areas such as retention models and the factors that shape the retention of the general body of students in Higher Education (HE). Furthermore, this review offers a more detailed exploration of literature that examines the retention of disabled students, addressing the factors that enhance or prevent their attrition from HE and the approaches used to promote the persistence of this group of students. This literature review takes a comprehensive approach to retention, acknowledging the diverse terminology and methodology used in the literature and the need to explore disabled students' retention from different angles to address their complex educational experiences. Considering all these factors, the aims of this literature review are as follows:

- To explore relevant evidence that discusses the area of HE students' retention, including models and current research.
- To discuss the factors, as discussed in previous literature, that influence the experiences of disabled students and, therefore, shape their retention in the HE sector.
- To explain different approaches used to promote the retention of disabled students in HE.

As a result of meeting these aims, the chapter showcases the complexity of understanding the educational factors that shape disabled students' retention, highlighting the methodological inconsistencies still present in this knowledge field. The evidence analysed in this chapter also demonstrates the need for more qualitative research that leads to an in-depth and comprehensive analysis of HE disabled students' experiences for a better understanding of the factors that shape their retention in the sector. This literature review also portrays the increased interest in adopting more critical approaches in the exploration of disabled students' experiences and retention. Moreover, this literature review acknowledges that current models of inclusion and retention need to be rethought in favour of sector- and institution-wide approaches that do not require disability disclosure or medical certification and that consider disabled students' motivations and aspirations.

Therefore, meeting these aims supported the research argument and questions of this study, which focuses on examining how cultures, discourses and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland and how this shapes their retention. Moreover, this chapter offers a detailed account of the literature review process in order to add transparency and avoid one of the most common criticisms of narrative literature reviews, which tend to lack clarity about the search and analysis processes (Dekkers, Langhorne and Carey, 2022).

Thus, the first part of this chapter explains my approach to the literature review, to then offer, in its second part, an overview of the research and theory around the retention of the general body of students. The third part concentrates on the experiences of disabled students in HE, exploring factors that prevent or promote their persistence in the sector, along with the strategies adopted by HEIs to enhance the retention of this group of students. The chapter ends by offering the main conclusions extracted after reviewing the literature and how these support the current study's aims and research questions. The final discussion of this chapter emphasises the need for further research exploring the experiences and retention of disabled students in HE and the importance of rethinking current models of inclusion and support as a strategy to foster HE sectors that value disabled students' diversity and in which they can flourish.

2.1. Approach to literature review

Low student retention rates are a complex phenomenon due to the multiple and dynamic factors that influence students' persistence in HE (Beer and Lawson, 2018), and certain groups of students, like disabled students, are at higher risk of early exit (see Kendall, 2016; Shaw, 2024). Yet, this is an under-researched area, particularly when compared to the broad range of evidence covering the retention of the general body of students. However, as will be illustrated in this chapter, the experiences of disabled students are particularly complex due to the multiple challenges they face in HE (Vickerman and Blundell, 2010; Thompson-Ebanks, 2014; Cotán Fernández, 2019; Grimes *et al.*, 2021; Sánchez-Díaz and Morgado, 2022). This is something that calls for a more robust understanding of this phenomenon in order to tackle current barriers and promote HE sectors in which disabled students can fulfil their aspirations.

Considering these elements, I argue that there is a need for a comprehensive review of the existing evidence that covers not only the literature that directly addresses the retention of disabled students but also the literature that offers a broader understanding of their

experiences in HE. Taking this comprehensive approach means there is scope to review studies which have empirically (qualitative, quantitatively or using mixed methods) researched factors that influence the persistence of disabled students in HE. Yet, it also opens opportunities to engage with previous reviews of the literature that enhance our understanding of the topic and with literature that, although it does not exclusively focus on the retention of disabled students in HE, examines facets of their experiences that could be shaping their retention and persistence in the sector.

Considering this broad approach and the existing difficulties with a body of research characterised by its terminological and methodological variability, I decided to take a narrative approach to this literature review as it was the method that could best allow me to meet the literature review's aims defined above. According to Dixon-Woods *et al.* (2005), a narrative literature review or summary involves selecting, documenting and organising research evidence to present a story or argument based on that evidence. Dekkers, Langhorne and Carey (2022) maintain that narrative reviews can outline a field of knowledge, including its development and progression, highlighting controversies over time. Moreover, Dixon-Woods *et al.* (2005) argue that narrative reviews allow for the flexible integration of a large and varied evidence base, including the integration of qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods studies. Additionally, narrative reviews can be analytical, interpretive and reflexive, permitting the analysis of existing dynamics within an area of study (*ibid*). Thus, narrative reviews can be thought-provoking and offer novel viewpoints on the topic researched (Dekkers, Langhorne and Carey, 2022). Therefore, narrative reviews are an appropriate tool for a comprehensive literature review relevant to the experiences and retention of disabled students in HE, helping enhance the theory and understanding of these areas.

Moreover, the broad approach allowed by this strategy facilitates the exploration of varied sources and types of evidence, which permits an interrogation of the foci of interest in the existing literature. While narrative literature reviews are often criticised for their lack of clarity regarding the search strategy and review aims (Dekkers, Langhorne and Carey, 2022) I decided to take an open approach to the search strategy as I argue this can foster critical engagement with such a complex body of literature, leading to an expansion and examination of the topic's understanding. Therefore, instead of defining a strict search strategy, during the past four years, I have engaged with the existing literature in an iterative manner, regularly searching for new publications that could help enhance my critical understanding of HE disabled students' retention.

My search started in the summer of 2020 as I engaged with literature related to keywords like “retention”, “persistence”, “attrition”, “withdrawal”, “disability”, “disabled students”, “higher education” and “university”. I repeated this literature search several times over these years, up until the summer of 2024, reading academic journal publications, book chapters and reports that were relevant to this study. Although I first limited my search to sources published after 2010, I realised that the scarce literature available and the relevant literature published before then called for a more comprehensive search, which means I also searched for materials published before that date. Most of my searches focused on materials published in English due to the study’s context, but since my first language is Spanish, I also searched for resources published in this language. Initial materials selected from this broad strategy also led to further literature engagement, as I checked the reference list of relevant studies, reports and book chapters, which allowed me to identify other sources of interest.

This approach did not allow me to follow a systematic approach to the literature review, which means I cannot provide a detailed account of the databases and sources consulted. However, this strategy led to a robust, comprehensive and critical engagement with the literature as I analysed sources that were directly related to the topic of study but also others that partially addressed it, considering different methodologies, geographical locations and understandings of students’ retention. While protocol-driven approaches to literature reviews, like systematic reviews, would have allowed for easier replication, the narrative approach followed in this study enabled the comprehensive nature of this chapter’s literature review (Dekkers, Langhorne and Carey, 2022).

Moreover, the flexibility of the narrative approach allowed for a more intricate interrogation of the existing evidence, helping paint a more comprehensive picture of the experiences of disabled students in HE. It also enabled the exploration of pieces of literature that otherwise would have been overlooked as they were not apparently relevant to the topic, but were valuable upon further engagement. Thus, the narrative approach I took to this literature review aligns closely with some of the tenets of Feminist Poststructuralism (FPS), which is the epistemological framework (see Chapter 3) that guides the empirical part of this study, such as an interest in challenging the status quo and a focus on the experiences of marginalised groups (Aston, 2016), like disabled students.

2.2. Retention of the general body of students in HE

2.2.1. Models of student retention

Higher Education (HE) plays an essential role in helping advance and develop many areas of current societies, including social equity (Peercy and Svenson, 2016) and national potential and production (Ademe and Singh, 2016). At a personal level, obtaining a HE qualification is linked to positive outcomes in adulthood, including general well-being, higher earnings, more prestigious occupations, personal satisfaction, and broader employment and career opportunities (Grebennikov and Shah, 2012; Lee, 2014). However, despite the benefits of obtaining a HE qualification and the improved opportunities for accessing them, non-completion is a widespread phenomenon and one of the biggest concerns faced by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) worldwide (Aljohani, 2016b; Manyanga, Sithole and Hanson, 2017).

Due to the importance that HEIs give to retaining students, student non-completion has been a widely researched area within HE (Thomas, 2016); however, at the start of this research tradition, the literature lacked systematicity. It also should be noticed that until the end of the 20th century, this field of study was characterised by its focus on student characteristics and circumstances as the main reason to explain students' early degree exit, adopting, therefore, a psychological approach (Aljohani, 2016a). In this sense, the responsibility was solely attributed to the students, who were perceived as mentally ill (Ryle, 1969 as cited in Tight, 2020). This approach led to victim-blaming and put excessive responsibility on the students, ignoring the role of external factors (Tinto, 2006; Tight, 2020). Nevertheless, around 1970, the approach started to change, and the study of other factors started to gain relevance in the research on student attrition and retention in HE (Burke, 2019).

This change in trend fuelled the development of different models that tried to explain the phenomena of student attrition and retention. In this sense, Burke (2019) found in their review of the literature that The Undergraduate Dropout Process Model developed by Spady in 1970 is accepted as one of the first interdisciplinary ones. This model was novel for considering student characteristics, as well as their relationships with institutional and environmental factors, when explaining student withdrawal. Spady talked about the academic and social systems, which influence students differently depending on their interactions with the environment. The main variables considered by this model are: *“intellectual development, social integration, satisfaction and institutional commitment”* (Burke, 2019).

Later, Vincent Tinto (1975), one of the most prominent researchers in the field, established the Institutional Departure Model (Burke, 2019). Tinto's model also draws attention to the social and academic systems, maintaining that integration within these two structures acts as a protective factor against student withdrawal (Tinto, 1975). This model understands attrition as a longitudinal (Kerby, 2015) because the interactions between social and academic systems vary depending on the student's performance, which is impacted by their characteristics.

In the 1980s, John Bean created the Student Attrition Model. For Bean, dropout is a syndrome defined as "*the failure of a student enrolled at a particular university in the spring to enrol in that same university the next fall semester*" (Kerby, 2015, p. 152). This syndrome refers to the student's manifested intentions to interrupt their studies "*meshed with actual attrition*" (ibid). Bean found that "*institutional commitment*", "*institutional satisfaction*", "*organisational rules*" or "*value of education*" were some of the most significant variables influencing student attrition (Burke, 2019, p. 17).

These models are considered appropriate when it comes to explaining student's early exit from HE (Kerby, 2015). However, according to Manyanga *et al.* (2017), they are too general and do not consider students' individualities. Similarly, some as Fichten *et al.* (2014) consider that these educational models are limited when it comes to explaining the retention of students with disabilities. Therefore, while it is not the scope of this study, I argue that more research is needed to develop models that attempt to explain the retention of disabled students in HE, as they could support future research and practice.

2.2.2. Retention of the general body of students

As stated above, non-completion is one of the biggest concerns for HEIs worldwide (Aljohani, 2016a; Manyanga, Sithole and Hanson, 2017). For example, in Australia, the attrition rate has fluctuated around 20% in the past decade (Kirk, 2018), whereas in Latin America and The Caribbean, the non-completion rate has reached 57% (Munizaga, Cifuentes and Beltrán, 2018). Nonetheless, as discussed in the introductory chapter (see Chapter 1), in the whole of the UK, including Scotland, there is a more positive trend with recent non-continuation rates for full-time undergraduate students following the year of entry at 5.3% for the UK and 4.5% for Scotland (HESA, 2022). However, certain groups of students, such as part-time students, experience lower non-completion rates, as 29.5% of them are not in HE after the year of entry at the UK level and 27.2% at the Scottish level (ibid).

Nonetheless, not all students may wish to complete the degrees they start, and in some cases, withdrawing might be the best option (McCluckie, 2014). Still, not completing HE tends to have negative consequences for students, including impacted self-concept and reduced life and professional projections (Cunningham, 2007; Crosling, Heagney and Thomas, 2009; Torenbeek, Jansen and Hofman, 2010). For HEIs, low completion rates imply a damaged reputation and financial loss from direct income and government support (Grebennikov and Shah, 2012; O’Keeffe, 2013; Beer and Lawson, 2017). Therefore, since HEIs play an undeniable role in reducing premature exits, their efforts should focus on avoiding non-voluntary and preventable withdrawals (Bilodeau and Meissner, 2018).

Additionally, authors like Maher and Macallister (2013) maintain that student attrition should not be attributed to unique and single causes. Instead, it should be considered a complex process caused by multiple intricate factors (Crosling, Thomas and Heagney, 2008; Beer and Lawson, 2018), since according to Schmitt and Santos (2013), at least 89 variables influence students’ retention and attrition. Considering these elements, Beer and Lawson (2017, p. 773) believe that there are no simple solutions to tackle such an intricate phenomenon, leading them to deem high HE student attrition as a wicked problem so complex that it cannot be addressed with conventional strategies.

Consequently, this literature review has identified recurring themes in the existing evidence, illustrating common factors that influence HE students’ persistence and retention. One of these themes refers to students’ personal characteristics. Thus, despite the change in trend as more responsibility is put on HEIs (Tight, 2020), there is still a great interest in the role of personal characteristics on students’ persistence and attrition. One of these factors is gender, although there are no clear conclusions. In this regard, authors like Eshetu *et al.* (2018) concluded that female students in Ethiopia were at higher risk of withdrawal, while other studies, like the work of Wessel *et al.* (2009) and Willging and Johnson (2009) conducted in the United States (US) indicate that male students have increased chances of non-completion.

Moreover, a low socioeconomic background (Slanger *et al.*, 2015; Harvey and Szalkowicz, 2017), poor academic readiness (Viljoen and Deacon, 2013) and term-time employment (Callender, 2008; Willcoxson, Cotter and Joy, 2011; Kocsis, Alter and Pusztai, 2022) have also been linked to a higher likelihood of early exit. Additionally, Viljoen and Deacon (2013) categorise academic readiness, motivation and informed career choices as protective retention factors. Elder (2020) also acknowledged the role of individual characteristics on HE student retention and persistence and concluded that better secondary education outcomes, high

institutional compatibility and having access to funding predicted retention in the first academic year. Moreover, Wessel *et al.* (2009) also concluded that international and disabled students were at higher risk of early exit.

Research about student retention in online programmes has surged since the COVID-19 pandemic started in 2020. Some like Meneses and Marlon (2020) found out in their literature review that students' personal features, such as motivation, satisfaction and time management, were some of the factors putting online students at higher risk of attrition. Similarly, Seery *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that affect clearly influences students' persistence, including attitudes, beliefs, motivation and satisfaction with their online programme. Yet, these authors also identified other factors, such as course structure, students' academic and technological abilities, and institutional relations between students, faculty and the overall organisation as elements that influence retention in online courses (*ibid.*).

Another theme identified in this literature review related to the relational and social factors influencing student retention is a sense of belonging. More specifically, a strong sense of belonging (Kirk, 2018), and positive relationships between lecturers and students (Farr-Wharton *et al.*, 2018) have been identified as protective factors that encourage persistence. Pedler, Willis and Nieuwoudt (2022, p. 397) demonstrated that a higher sense of belonging increases students' "*motivation and enjoyment*", reducing their intentions to leave HE. Likewise, Boyd, Liu and Horissan (2022, p. 357) discuss that a sense of community strongly predicts students' "*thriving and psychological well-being measures*", which play an essential role in students' intentions to persist and overall satisfaction with the educational experience (*ibid.*).

Additionally, student engagement is gaining relevance in the research of student retention and persistence (Tight, 2020). In this regard, Wolf, Kelly and Kinzie (2009) define student engagement as a two-faceted construct. Its first element relates to the time and effort students put into their academic workload to produce outcomes that lead to success. The second element concerns HEIs' allocation of resources to develop services and learning strategies to promote student involvement with these resources and activities (*ibid.*). Thus, as Tight (2020) highlights, a strong and clear relationship exists between student retention and engagement. In this regard, Tinto (2022) highlights how student engagement is at the centre of many student retention models, but also that research exploring its role in student persistence is still in its infancy.

Another area commonly explored in the student retention literature is the influence of academic factors. Ashton-Hay and Doncaster (2021) observed that students who received academic skills

support had improved academic performance and completed their studies at higher rates than those who did not engage in academic skills sessions. Moreover, access to appropriate support (Nevill and Rhodes, 2004) and high-quality teaching and learning practice, curriculum and assessment design (Crosling, Heagney and Thomas, 2009) have also been identified as elements that promote student persistence and retention.

Thus, there is still a strong focus on the impact of students' characteristics and circumstances on persistence and retention, although more attention is being paid to relational and institutional elements. Still, I must highlight the methodological and terminological inconsistencies in the field, which make it difficult to identify and synthesise relevant sources. Moreover, something that becomes clear from the research available is that even the influence of protective factors is complex (Schmitt and Santos, 2013). As Aljohani (2016b) stated, each one of the variables affects individuals and institutions in different ways, depending on their changing circumstances. Another shared conclusion across the research on student retention is that students from “*non-traditional backgrounds*” (Naylor, Baik and Arkoudis, 2018, p. 329) are the ones who tend to be at higher risk of early exit. In this regard, Kemp and Norton (2014) maintain that students from minority groups might have unclear expectations regarding HE and increased home and personal responsibilities. In addition, Harvey, Szalkowicz and Luckman (2017) argue that students from lower socio-economic backgrounds are at higher risk of non-completion since they seem to have limited support and information about career choices and might also face increased health and financial difficulties.

Consequently, the literature also offers evidence of HEIs' targeted strategies aimed at supporting specific groups of students who are thought to be at higher risk of attrition. For example, some, like McEvoy (2012), opted to follow proactive approaches, engaging with students before enrolment in a summer bridge program and aiming to prevent the increased risk of withdrawal associated with the first year. McEvoy's intervention was based on a learning community that included English and Maths courses, support and study groups. It proved to be effective in preparing underrepresented and underprepared students (from low-income backgrounds or first-generation students) before starting their degrees in a university in the US, which had positive effects on retention and graduation rates, reaching the same, or even better levels than those of the control (and better prepared) group (ibid).

Other strategies focused on broader elements of HE, such as curriculum and pedagogy. In this regard, Webb *et al.* (2017) conducted a literature review to identify strategies demonstrably impacting student retention rates. The authors described studies that, for example, focused on

student-centred pedagogies and relevant curriculum design and delivery (Crosling, Heagney and Thomas, 2009). Thus, teaching and learning practice that includes active and engaging learning, positive relationships between peers and educators, as well as induction and support programmes or formative - rather than summative assessment - have positive effects on retention (see Webb *et al.*, 2017). Other examples point to the positive effects of flexible and innovative approaches to teaching, such as blended learning (Lee, 2012) or flipped classroom (Amaral and Shank, 2010). According to Webb *et al.*'s (2017) these strategies succeeded because they focused on the protective factors identified by the literature, such as a sense of belonging.

Therefore, after reviewing this part of the general student retention literature, I conclude that the field has experienced a significant evolution as the focus has shifted from blaming the students for high attrition rates to acknowledging and considering the different interrelated factors that affect said rates. However, this is still a complex area of study and practice due to the several interconnected factors influencing the persistence of HE students. Thus, this evidence emphasises that there cannot be simple, one-sided approaches to address low-retention rates but rather that HEIs must be aware of their students' needs to develop context-relevant interventions. Nevertheless, this evidence also demonstrates the scarce research available on the retention of students who are at higher risk of non-completion, such as disabled students. Consequently, the following section explores the literature that specifically concentrates on the experiences and persistence of disabled students with the aim of understanding the retention experience of these students in more detail.

2.3. Retention of disabled students in HE

Disabled students have been traditionally underrepresented in HE (Madriaga, 2007; Macleod and Cebula, 2009; Shaw, 2024). However, due to an increase in policies oriented at promoting inclusion and respect for diversity, this tendency started changing, and the number of disabled students enrolled in HEI has steadily been increasing internationally (Kendall, 2016; Vlachou and Papananou, 2018; Hector, 2020). As addressed in Chapter 1, recent HESA (2024c) data shows that the number of disabled students enrolled in HEIs in the UK has also been progressively growing, representing 16% of all home students in the UK in the academic year 2022/2023. In Scotland, this proportion increased to 17% in the same academic year (*ibid*).

Nonetheless, despite this positive trend, available data shows that disabled students graduate at lower rates than their non-disabled counterparts (Newman *et al.*, 2011; Lee *et al.*, 2015;

Kendall, 2016; Sue Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2017; Cotán Fernández, 2019; Carroll *et al.*, 2020; Shaw, 2024). As discussed in the introductory chapter, this also applies to Scotland as disabled students are at higher risk of early exit, particularly autistic students, those with mental health conditions and those with more than two diagnoses (Commissioner for Fair Access, 2019). Yet, the reasons behind these lower completion rates seem to be even more varied and complex than those affecting non-disabled students (Thompson-Ebanks, 2014). According to Nieminen and Pesonen (2022), there is an indication that disabled students are not entirely accepted within the HE, often being seen as outsiders (Dolmage, 2017; Pesonen *et al.*, 2023). Thus, the sector is defined by ableist principles and exclusionary principles that determine who is considered valuable within HE: those who can meet specific ability standards (Nieminen and Pesonen, 2022).

Graduating at HE level is associated with personal and socioeconomic advantages at individual and social levels, which are also reflected among the members of the disability community (ANED, 2018). Existing literature shows that students with disabilities who obtain HE degrees experience increased employment opportunities, are more engaged citizens and make healthier choices (Newman *et al.*, 2021). Yet, the consequences of starting a degree but not completing it include financial hardship and higher job instability, which can have a significantly negative impact on disabled people, who face disadvantages in the job market compared to non-disabled individuals (Baum and Payea, 2004; Newman *et al.*, 2011; Mann and Wittenburg, 2015). Thus, although the increasing number of students with disabilities entering HE has been a valuable step towards diversity and inclusion, it is only the beginning (Bartz, 2020).

Unfortunately, the data meant to provide clarity regarding the current and evolving situation around retention and persistence rates of disabled students is either vague, fragmented or does not exist. For example, no figures have been identified for different Hispanic countries such as Mexico or Chile (Rodríguez Molina and Valenzuela Zambrano, 2019). Something similar happens in Spain, where, despite the efforts to promote the inclusion of students with disabilities in HE, I have not been able to find records referring to the rates at which they are graduating. The best example of this situation is the most recent version of the annual report published by Fundación Universia (2023). This report explores how inclusive the HE system is in Spain by looking at the presence of disabled students enrolled in the country's universities (1.6% of the 1.386.981 HE students in the country in the academic year 2021/2022) and the barriers and enablers they encounter. However, persistence or retention are not even mentioned in the 136-page-long report. This is surprising as the report goes on to discuss disabled students' employability aspirations and goals, taking retention for granted and ignoring

the evidence that points out the lower completion rates amongst disabled students. This reflects a limited approach that focuses on providing access and ensuring participation but ignores the effectiveness of these strategies on degree completion, despite it providing tangible benefits for students (Newman *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, it is an illustration of a common gap across HE inclusion research, which focuses on access, overlooking that this is only the first step towards HE-disabled students' academic progression and success (Bartz, 2020).

Alternatively, most of the evidence that is, indeed, available highlights that disabled students graduate at lower rates than non-disabled students in different parts of the world. For example, in Australia, authors such as Kilpatrick *et al.* (2017) noted that disabled students' retention rates were significantly lower than that of the rest of the students across Australia. In the US, Koch *et al.* (2018) found similar results in their study where students with disabilities, regardless of the rest of their personal characteristics, left HE at higher rates than their peers without disabilities. These conclusions are also consistent with the results obtained by Lee *et al.* (2015), who found out that two-thirds of the students with disabilities who participated in their study (N = 770), also conducted in the US, did not complete post-secondary education. It must also be noted that this rate was nearly twice as high as the non-completion rate of the students without disabilities involved in this research (N = 9.990).

Although most studies researching the topic determined that disabled students graduate at lower rates, some authors (Wessel *et al.*, 2009; Knight, Wessel and Markle, 2018) found no differences between students with and without disabilities. Conversely, they did find disparities in the time each group took to finish their degrees, as students with disabilities needed more time to graduate. Another example supporting this finding is Reed and Curtis's study (2012), where students with visual impairments living in Canada had high graduation rates but needed additional time to complete their degrees - 1.5 extra years on average.

Therefore, the evidence exploring the retention and persistence of disabled students is often inconsistent and complex, probably due to methodological and theoretical discrepancies (Fichten *et al.*, 2014). Consequently, there is no simple answer to the question of why disabled students leave HE at higher rates than non-disabled students. Still, the existing literature offers insights into the elements that can put disabled students at higher risk of attrition and into the protective factors and approaches that can, instead, support their HE experience and retention. These factors and approaches are essential for understanding this topic and implementing strategies to enhance the retention of disabled students in the sector. Consequently, the rest of

this section addresses and discusses the main risk and protective factors and approaches that shape the retention of disabled students in HE, as identified in the literature.

2.3.1. Risk factors

HE has traditionally been the most exclusionary level of education, and although the landscape has greatly improved, there is additional room for progress to achieve more welcoming systems (see Lopez-Bastias, Moreno-Rodriguez and Diaz-Vega, 2020) that promote the retention of disabled students. Thus, despite efforts to widen participation, HE is especially challenging for disabled students (Moriña, 2017) who encounter obstacles that start from the moment they begin their transition from secondary education (Madriaga *et al.*, 2007; Vickerman and Blundell, 2010) and persist throughout their academic journey. The impact of these challenges can lead to poor performance, success, and persistence, ultimately leading to lower completion rates (Sue Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2017; Cotán Fernández, 2019). The focus of this section is identifying and discussing the most significant risk factors identified in the literature, and how they shape disabled students' experiences and retention.

More specifically, some of the barriers faced by disabled students include stigma and negative attitudes (Hopkins, 2011) and difficulties in accessing curriculum activities, social situations or fieldwork (Taylor, Baskett and Wren, 2010). Furthermore, concerns about physical accessibility (Moriña and Morgado, 2018) and difficulties related to teaching and learning activities, including exams, coursework, or lectures (Fuller, Bradley and Healey, 2004) also affect disabled students. Many disabled students also lack knowledge about the support and accommodations available to them on campus, or are reluctant to disclose their disability – due to fear of stigma – and cannot access support (Redpath *et al.*, 2013). According to Betts *et al.* (2013), improved access to HE does not directly lead to improved teaching and learning accessibility in areas such as content, learning strategies or assessment. Thus, easing access is only the starting point when it comes to degree progression and success of disabled students in HE (Bartz, 2020).

According to Moswela and Mukhopadhyay (2018), negative attitudes can also act as a barrier to disabled students' academic success. In this regard, Goodall *et al.*, (2023) acknowledge that educators involved in their survey-based study conducted in Norway believed that disabled students were less likely to be employed and complete their degrees than non-disabled students. The authors highlight the role of ableist notions behind this belief and maintain that it is necessary to challenge this notion to bring inclusion to HE. More precisely, Goodall *et al.* (2023) recognised that current HE cultures perpetuate principles of hyper-productivity and over-

achievement, promoting a notion in which successful students are those who are young, not disabled and are motivated. Hence, it is important that institutions identify attitudes across the educational community and challenge existing discourses and cultures that position disabled students as less than their non-disabled counterparts. Yet, while citing Gilberg (2020), Goodall *et al.* (2023) acknowledge that ableism cannot be addressed at an individual level, although it is at that level that its impact is felt the most.

Consequently, multiple factors can put HE disabled students at risk of exclusion and attrition, including stigma, negative attitudes and difficulties accessing educational activities and support. However, when looking at risk factors, some researchers also maintain that the characteristics of students with disabilities also put them directly at higher risk of early withdrawal. This is the case for Mamiseishvili and Koch, who have consistently studied the retention and success of students with disabilities. Based in the US, these authors have mainly used secondary data obtained from the Beginning Postsecondary Students Longitudinal Study to explore the persistence rates of students with disabilities, either as a big group (Mamiseishvili and Koch, 2011, 2012) or focusing on students with specific diagnoses (Koch, Mamiseishvili and Higgins, 2014; Koch *et al.*, 2018).

Some of their main findings over the years point to personal characteristics as risk factors, showing that students with physical disabilities (Mamiseishvili and Koch, 2011, 2012), depression (Mamiseishvili and Koch, 2012) or with learning disabilities or attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD; Koch *et al.*, 2018) seem to be at higher risk of attrition. Additionally, those with psychiatric disabilities seem to be at increased risk of withdrawal when compared with students with other disabilities (Koch, Mamiseishvili and Higgins, 2014; Koch *et al.*, 2018). Despite controlling other variables, many times, these authors found that the said diagnoses had stronger effects on the students' persistence than other personal or in-college characteristics (Koch *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, Mamiseishvili and Koch (2011) argue that students with disabilities have many of the characteristics associated with non-traditional and at-risk students. Some examples include higher average age - possibly due to delayed HE enrolment - being the first-generation HE students in their families or not living on campus. Moreover, these characteristics have been identified as factors that could put any student at higher risk of non-completion, but for students with disabilities, it might mean additional challenges and barriers to be faced (*ibid*).

Along similar lines, Carroll *et al.* (2020) concluded that students with ill mental health were more likely to leave their undergraduate degree before completion than students with physical

disabilities and students with no reported disability. These authors also conducted their study in the US using the Beginning Postsecondary Students Longitudinal Study but suggest that difficult institutional systems and lack of academic preparations could be putting students with mental health conditions at a disadvantage. However, Carroll *et al.* (2020) add that these difficulties are similar to those experienced by other under-represented groups in HE who also experience marginalisation. Thus, the authors highlight that the way in which HEIs function can play a key role in the lower completion rates of these students.

Therefore, despite changes in the field of student retention (Tight, 2020), there is still a great focus on student characteristics, which some deem as non-modifiable factors. Yet, some, like Fichten *et al.* (2014), are also interested in the role of modifiable factors, which can be addressed. In this regard, Fichten *et al.* (2014) analysed the self-reports of 611 students with different disabilities attending junior and community colleges in Canada. These authors found that the relationship between grades and intention to graduate was weak but that studying part-time and having been on a leave of absence were risk factors against graduation. The authors also studied non-modifiable factors, but most of them were not related to intentions to graduate. For example, there was no relationship between gender and intention to graduate. However, other factors, like the number of disabilities, had a negative relationship with their intentions to graduate. The authors also highlight that many of these variables interacted with each other, and changes in some could affect the other ones (*ibid*).

Following a qualitative approach, Thompson-Ebanks (2014) interviewed five students with invisible disabilities in the US who had voluntarily withdrawn from their HE studies to find the factors that influenced the participants' exit from HE. Thus, the results of the study address nine personal factors common to all participants. These factors include characteristics of their disabilities, health issues, a low sense of belonging, low college motivation, low self-advocacy skills, issues related to disclosure, low involvement in campus life, financial problems, and feeling inadequate. Thompson-Ebanks highlights that these factors do not have an individual impact but are rather interconnected in the participant's experiences, shaping their exit from the sector (*ibid*).

To illustrate this claim, Thompson-Ebanks (2014) described that participants' disability symptomatology (for example, memory issues and low attention spans) affected participants' decisions to withdraw. Yet, these symptoms interacted with environmental factors such as not having accessed support services and accommodations, since not all students used them and believed this might have negatively impacted their experience. Furthermore, this issue was also

linked to participants' feelings of inadequacy since they did not disclose their disabilities due to the fear of stigma and, hence, could not access appropriate support. These claims emphasise the negative attitudes still existing on campus and the internalised stigma of the participants, and how these limited their capacity to access support and how this had a negative effect on their academic journeys. Some institutional factors mentioned by the participants concerned the size and characteristics of their HEI, believing that attending smaller institutions could make things, like accessing accommodations, easier to access (Thompson-Ebanks, 2014).

In a qualitative study conducted in the UK, Cage and Howes (2020) interviewed 14 autistic students who had left their degrees before completion. While this narrative review focuses on exploring the overall retention experiences of disabled students in HE, not focusing on groups with specific groups of diagnoses, Cage and Howes' study offers an in-depth perspective of students who have left HE before graduating, which is not easy to find. Thus, Cage and Howes identified interrelated systemic issues such as difficulties in accessing diagnosis, understanding autism, mental health struggles and feeling like outsiders as some of the reasons influencing participants' early exit (ibid).

More specifically, most participants received their autism diagnosis after leaving HE but wished they had known earlier, which could have helped them make appropriate course choices and access support (Cage and Howes, 2020). Additionally, participants in that study acknowledged a lack of understanding about autism across their institution, which led to a lack of accessibility and inclusion. Furthermore, participants' mental health decreased due to the difficulties experienced in HE, where they always felt like outsiders. Other challenges identified included a lack of engagement and uncertainty about who could offer support and what support was available. Moreover, one of this study's key findings is that due to the impact of these challenges on their academic performance (difficulties submitting coursework or meeting course criteria), participants felt like leaving their degrees was inevitable and out of their control. In addition, the study offers an insightful look at "*life after dropping out*", which was characterised by participants' need to process trauma and feelings of shame, but also by their focus on doing what felt right for their lives (Cage and Howes, 2020, p. 1664).

Moreover, while most studies in the field focus on personal, social and academic factors, Nieminen (2022) took a more critical approach, exploring the influence of ableism and disablism in the assessment experiences of disabled students in HE in Finland. Thus, after analysing the results of a qualitative survey responded to by 139 participants, Nieminen offers a detailed account of how test-driven assessment practices and assessment accommodations

that require students to disclose their conditions continuously promote student marginalisation. This is a consequence of putting the responsibility on disabled students for their own marginalisation, instead of putting it on the exclusionary nature of assessment and support practices. Additionally, this author offers a novel and critical discussion of the impact of ableist assessment and accommodation practices on disabled students' retention. More specifically, Nieminen (2022, p. 630) acknowledges that assessment tasks positioned disabled students as "*abnormal*", othering from their non-disabled peers, resulting in disablism and exclusion as participants either failed their modules or had to opt-out. These circumstances resulted in students' aspirations being foreclosed as their income was affected, and they had to put their plans on hold (ibid).

Finally, one of the main gaps identified in this literature review refers to the experiences of disabled postgraduate students, particularly PhDs, as literature exploring their educational journey and retention is extremely scarce. This lack of research was acknowledged by Farrar (2006) nearly twenty years ago, although not much has changed. Back then, Farrar pointed out that there was a shared assumption that disabled postgraduate research (PGR) students who had reached the PhD level of education would have acquired, along with their previous educational experience, all the necessary tools and strategies they needed to succeed. These tools and strategies included confidence, "*learning management strategies*" (Farrar, 2006, p. 177) or the necessary assistive technology. Thus, this meant that adjustments were seen as "*unnecessary and possibly detrimental to the independence of a research student*" (ibid). Similarly, Mullins and Preyde (2013) point out that graduate students who participated in their study also believed that students at this level of education did not need accommodations anymore.

However, these perceptions contradict the lived experiences of disabled PGRs, as Farrar (2006) also acknowledged, maintaining that PGR students do experience barriers that are different to those faced during previous degrees and have not necessarily acquired the set of skills needed to succeed at this level of education. In more recent evidence, McKinney and Swartz (2022) emphasise that not all disabled people acquire their disabilities before enrolling in HE and that some can become disabled while being HE students. This means that some will need to adjust to their newly acquired needs while already being (postgraduate) students, which can affect retention and persistence (ibid). Additionally, available evidence indicates that the general body of PhD students often faces high attrition, delays in completion and low satisfaction levels (van Rooij, Fokkens-Bruinsma and Jansen, 2021). Despite the limited evidence, it is likely that disabled postgraduate students face similar or worse circumstances as they experience more

substantial challenges (University and College Union, 2022), and are less satisfied than their non-disabled peers (72% versus 81%, respectively; Neves, 2022). Yet, little attention has been paid to this group of students, which calls for the need to understand their experiences and needs in more depth to understand the factors that could be hindering their educational experience and how they shape their persistence and retention.

Therefore, existing research illustrates modifiable and non-modifiable factors that put disabled students at higher risk of attrition. The non-modifiable ones tend to be linked to personal characteristics and disability diagnoses. However, there is an increased interest in modifiable factors that can be changed and addressed. These include negative stigma towards disability, difficulties accessing support, inadequate access to teaching and learning and low sense of belonging and social participation. Additionally, this literature also shows an increased interest in critical analyses of the phenomenon, pointing out that current ableist HE cultures and practices are putting disabled students at risk of exclusion, foreclosing the capacity in which they can meet their aspirations. Moreover, there is also preliminary research illustrating the experiences of disabled students after withdrawal, which reflects the trauma and shame that many experience. Still, this research illustrates the need for more in-depth, qualitative studies that explore educational factors in more detail and how they shape disabled students' retention, alongside a more comprehensive exploration of the experiences of those who had to leave the sector before graduating and of postgraduate disabled students. The following section addresses the protective factors that could help disabled students stay in HE.

2.3.2. Protective factors

Perhaps as a reflection of a more proactive approach towards the retention of disabled students, much of the research on the topic has focused on identifying protective factors that promote retention. This section summarises the main findings of my literature research in this regard.

In this regard, Kutscher and Tuckwiller (2019) conducted a literature review that identified 13 protective factors and facilitators from their analysis of 26 articles following quantitative (16 of them) and qualitative (10 of them) methods. These facilitators include areas such as peer and faculty interactions, self-advocacy, empowerment, or quality of student accommodation, which the author classified into three main dimensions: personal attributes, academic and social engagement, and accommodations or adjustments. Following their findings, Kutscher and Tuckwiller (2019) claim that disabled students with high levels of empowerment are more likely

to persevere and finish their studies, regardless of the challenges they might face. The authors also point to areas such as goal setting and the students' attitudes towards them or the power of self-determination. Therefore, the students' sense of control over their learning, as also expressed by Verdinelli and Kutner (2016), could be acting as a protective factor towards the retention of students with disabilities. Consequently, Kutscher and Tuckwiller (2019) suggest that HEIs should focus on supporting their students' development of their levels of empowerment and self-determination since this could help disabled students progress during their HE journey.

However, Kutscher and Tuckwiller (2019) not only focused on the importance of certain personal characteristics, as shown above, but the authors also highlighted the influence of social integration, as students with disabilities who feel isolated are less likely to finish their degrees. Additionally, Kutscher and Tuckwiller (2019) also highlight the need for institutional interventions to address the difficulties related to disabled students' retention rates. In this case, the authors mention the relevance of staff disability-related training and development since this can increase inclusive approaches and positive attitudes towards disabled students in HE (Dallas and Sprong, 2015).

The studies of Mamiseishvili and Koch also looked at protective factors that could promote the retention of students with disabilities and obtained findings that are, in part, reflected in Kutscher and Tuckwiller's (2019) literature review. More specifically, Mamiseishvili and Koch (2011) found out that the factors associated with persistence from the first to the second year were, on the one hand, access to certain accommodations such as "*classroom note takers*" (p. 100). On the other hand, the authors point to integration (social and academic) as a factor positively associated with persistence, but social integration had a stronger effect, evidencing the importance of participating in extra-curricular activities and peer interaction. Sadly, this finding contrasts with the fact that 57.6% of their sample had never taken part in informal social activities.

Additionally, Koch *et al.* (2014) concentrated on the persistence of students with psychiatric disabilities, describing that academic and social integration were linked to "*first-to-second year persistence*" (2014, p. 73). The authors used informal meetings with faculty, seeking academic advice and participating in study groups as indicators of academic integration; whereas social integration referred to participating in sports, arts or club activities. The results show that the frequency in which students met with their academic counsellors during the first year, but also participating in social integration activities (sports, school clubs, and fine arts) had a positive

relationship with students persisting through the second year. However, once again, not many of these students participated in extra-curricular activities, but those who did were more likely to persist.

In their review of the literature, Moriña and Biagiotti (2022) identify a series of personal and external academic factors that lead to HE disabled students' success. Personal factors include “*self-advocacy, self-awareness, self-determination, self-esteem and executive functioning*”, (Moriña and Biagiotti, 2022, p. 729). Relevant external factors included family support, disability support services, and positive student-staff partnerships and peer relations. Similarly, Cotán Fernández *et al.* (2021) highlight that faculty's attitude is crucial in the promotion of inclusive pedagogies. However, these authors emphasise the positive influence of affect, relations and care in the promotion of inclusive pedagogies; inclusive faculty in their study were approachable, respectful, compassionate, flexible, engaged, and attuned to students' emotions. According to Moriña, López-Gavira and Morgado (2017), those are the attributes disabled students use to define effective inclusive educators. Along similar lines, disabled students who participated in Stein's study (2014) benefited from educators who were willing to implement accommodations, were available, approachable, understanding, enthusiastic, willing to provide support, committed to effective communication and cared about their success.

Other studies focused on the malleable factors that affect retention, as these factors can be altered to potentiate or diminish their effects (Kutscher, 2019). Following this idea, Fichten *et al.* (2014) studied elements of HE students with disabilities' lives, communities and schools that could be altered to promote better student performance and retention. After analysing the self-reports of 611 students attending junior and community colleges in Canada, the authors found eight important factors. These factors include self-efficacy skills, positive school environments, personal facilitators (social support or motivation), social self-efficacy, being registered with the disability support services, full-time enrolment and no social alienation. Social alienation was the most important predictor of intention to graduate, and the students with higher intention to graduate also had the highest levels of social and course self-efficacy. Personal facilitators included motivation, good study habits, having friends, a positive family environment, and previous education experiences. Similar effects were observed from school-related facilitators, such as positive attitudes, physical accessibility to buildings, and an acceptable workload. In addition, Fichten *et al.* (2014) also conclude that students intending to graduate had higher probabilities of registering with disability support services than those who did not plan on graduating.

Therefore, multiple factors seem to promote the retention of disabled students, including access to support, social integration, and positive relationships. Another facilitator found in the literature is studying online, compared to face-to-face instruction. Still, this contrasts with previous literature suggesting that online and distance learning tend to be linked to an increased risk of attrition for students with and without disabilities (Edwards and McMillan, 2015). Yet, whereas not all online courses are accessible and accommodating for students with disabilities, distance-learning courses might be perceived as more flexible and adaptable, which allows disabled students to better manage their needs (Verdinelli and Kutner, 2016).

Consequently, online learning environments seem to be preferred by disabled students, in comparison to traditional settings in which they suffer increased stigma and stress (Verdinelli and Kutner, 2016). In this regard, Verdinelli and Kutner (2016) observed that disabled students felt a lower level of stress while being enrolled in online courses mainly due to the flexibility allowed by distance learning, which minimised stress from time constraints. Other elements positively affecting the experience of these students were an increased sense of control over their education promoted by the flexibility and reduced exposure to negative attitudes inherent to distance learning (ibid). Hence, Verdinelli and Kutner (2016) conclude that all these factors combined, along with the sense of self-efficacy students obtain from them, in addition to their motivation, commitment, and external support, are all factors that could lead to increased persistence rates.

Online and hybrid learning gained recognition during the COVID-19 pandemic, as this situation forced HEIs to implement emergency responses based on distance learning (Manase, 2021). While these changes to traditional modes of education and the trauma of the circumstances are associated with student difficulties and disadvantages, they also created a new set of possibilities to enhance the experience of disabled students in HE (ibid). Thus, after interviewing four students with learning disabilities in South Africa, Manase (2021) concludes that online learning strategies that surged during the COVID-19 pandemic were a blessing in disguise for students with learning disabilities, albeit with some difficulties. More specifically, the author emphasises that online learning eased participants' learning experience, who felt on-campus learning hindered their learning capacities (ibid). Nevertheless, participants in Manase's (2021) study also faced some difficulties, such as the lack of student-faculty interactions and increased distractions. Consequently, Manase (2021) concludes that online learning influences the experiences of disabled students in different ways, being an advantage for some and a disadvantage for others.

Bones and Ellison (2022) also highlight the negative impact of the pandemic on disabled students, who were more likely to be affected by the virus and were disregarded in the development of emergency educational alternatives. Yet, after interviewing 17 disabled students (14 postgraduate and three undergraduate) in the US, Bones and Ellison (2022) conclude that despite existing difficulties, disabled students in their research thrived during this period. The authors conclude that autonomy was key to this success, as disabled students had increased control over their educational experience and learning environment. Moreover, online learning removed physical barriers and the need to commute, which allowed them to preserve their energy and manage their health, allowing them to learn at their own pace. While some participants did not benefit from online learning, Bones and Ellison (2022, p. 35) acknowledged how participants believed this experience made them want a new normal that included the *“flexibility and grace that had previously been denied to them”*. This aligns with DSUK’s (2022) findings, as disabled students who responded to their survey exploring the lessons learned from the pandemic by HEIs in the UK believe that this flexibility and grace was long overdue.

Thus, while the pandemic was a challenging time for many, it was also the time some disabled students were most accommodated as learning online eliminated several of the barriers they had experienced before (DSUK, 2022). Therefore, although this new research exploring the impact of online and hybrid learning on the experiences of disabled students has not directly addressed retention, the fact that new learning modalities reduce barriers and increase disabled students’ control over their educational experiences is promising. Particularly considering that these types of barriers put disabled students at higher risk of early exit.

Consequently, the evidence available illustrates a series of protective factors that could enhance the experience and retention of disabled students. These factors include social integration, positive relationships with peers and faculty, effective access to support and increased control over students’ educational experiences. Moreover, the literature portrays an increased interest in the role of online and hybrid education in post-pandemic HE, as it could facilitate disabled students’ persistence and retention due to its potential to eliminate accessibility barriers often faced by disabled students. Nonetheless, more research is needed in this area, alongside the difficulties associated with online and digital learning tools. However, the overall body of literature illustrates different approaches to disability inclusion across HE, which shapes the experiences of disabled students at this level of education, some based on individualised support and others taking broader approaches. The following section addresses these different approaches and how they relate to the experiences and retention of disabled students.

2.3.3. Approaches to enhance the experiences of disabled students

In addition to the factors that enhance or hinder the retention of disabled students in HE, the existing literature has also explored the approaches used to promote the persistence of this group of students. These approaches tend to concentrate on promoting inclusion across HE to improve disabled students' academic experience and increase their likelihood of completing their studies. While most of this research has focused on individualised adjustments and accommodations, there is an increased interest in broader and more critical approaches. This section offers an overview of four of these approaches.

Individualised support

According to the Equality Act (2010), HEIs in the UK have the responsibility and legal duty to provide accommodations that ensure that disabled students are not disadvantaged. These accommodations are also known as reasonable adjustments and range from ensuring physical accessibility to inclusive practices that ensure equality between disabled and non-disabled students (Hector, 2020). The situation is similar in many countries around the world, where institutions have the legal duty to ensure equal access and participation for disabled students (Fossey *et al.*, 2015; Moriña, López-Gavira and Morgado, 2017).

Considering this, some authors like Fossey *et al.* (2015), many of the initiatives implemented by HEIs come in the shape of learning accommodations offered to balance inequalities between students with and without disabilities. Moreover, Fossey *et al.* (2015, p. 20) developed the following classification of the available adjustments they encountered while reviewing the literature exploring the topic: “*flexibility in assessments*”, “*changed exam conditions*”, “*provision of adaptive equipment*”, “*in-class supports*”, and “*other academic supports*”. Additionally, Fleming, Oertle and Plotner (2017) maintain that some of the most frequently used strategies are improving physical accessibility, promoting in-campus disability awareness, ensuring students receive transition support and preparation, and supporting students in developing self-advocacy skills. After consulting 132 students registered with disability services in three HEIs in the US, Fleming, Oertle and Plotner (2017) add that some of the most effective individualised supports available to students are academic services, housing and accommodation support, and reasonable adjustments. Yet, while most students were satisfied with the support they received, others were frustrated and wished the whole accommodations process were different, and they were treated better. In addition, participants claim that on occasions, adjustments were denied to them, came in too late or were too complicated to arrange (*ibid.*).

Another example of research exploring the accommodations available for disabled students and their effectiveness is the study of Schreuer and Sachs (2014). This research was conducted in Israel with a total sample of 170 students with disabilities using the Physical, Human and Academic Accommodation Services scale and the College Student Experiences Questionnaire. As a result, the authors conclude that the participants mainly use four types of accommodations: “*physical, academic, human and organizational*” (2014, p. 29). The results show that nearly all participants had accessed reasonable adjustments, which were positively linked to student satisfaction, participation, performance, and engagement. Students accessing support also perceived their HEIs as positive and supportive environments. Yet, one of the difficulties the participants found in this case was that some accommodations were implemented automatically without considering the student’s needs or preferences. This mismatch meant that other, potentially more appropriate and effective, adjustments were not delivered. It is also worth mentioning that in this study, universal and institution-level strategies were rare, something that ended up raising the demand for more personalised academic accommodations.

Moreover, there is an undeniable heterogeneity within the disabled students’ community, which means that they have a varied set of needs. Thus, defining and implementing the most appropriate accommodations in each case is important and is something that comes as the result of a process of successfully identifying the students’ needs and negotiating and arranging the appropriate support (Fossey *et al.*, 2015). Hence, disability support services have many roles, but they are normally characterised by being the bridge between the students and the adjustments (Moriña, López-Gavira and Morgado, 2017). In general, the outcome of a process like this is an individualised learning plan comprising the students’ needs and how to put into practice the support they need to succeed in HE (Macleod *et al.*, 2017). Nevertheless, Fossey *et al.* (2015) argue that this can be an intricate procedure that needs the involvement of different agents, such as the student, teaching staff, and the institution’s disability service.

One barrier to the effectiveness of this support is the discrepancies regarding whose responsibility it is to request and implement support. Hence, a collaborative approach, including disability services, students, and teaching staff, seems essential to identify students’ needs and the best way to tackle them (Claiborne *et al.*, 2011; Fossey *et al.*, 2015). According to Redpath *et al.* (2013) educators, students and specialist disability staff should create a network that generates a safe space for communication and negotiation. A network of these characteristics should protect the central position that the students themselves have in the

process. It could also be a valuable resource in reviewing and updating support when needed (ibid).

Nevertheless, recurring barriers hinder this process, such as miscommunication between the parties involved, lack of teaching staff's awareness and understanding of disability, their excessive workload, and the temporary employment situation of many of them (Fossey *et al.*, 2015). Thus, while the positive impact of individual accommodations is undeniable, there is also evidence of the many difficulties linked to this approach. According to Dolmage (2017), this could be because individualised adjustments often represent the medical model of disability, which focuses on fixing students' problems instead of acknowledging environmental barriers, which can lead to minimalistic accommodations and adjustments that are just enough to avoid legal consequences.

Furthermore, while an increased use of online learning resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic was beneficial for some disabled students specifically, it might have hindered support provision. For instance, DSUK (2022) distributed an online survey amongst disabled students across 69 HEIs in the UK to investigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on their HE experiences, including overall accessibility and access to support. According to the study's findings (ibid), only 23% of the participants in their survey (N = 326) received the support they needed during the pandemic. Similarly, Gin *et al.* (2022) developed a survey to explore students' experience of undertaking science courses online in the spring of 2021 in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic in the US. The survey included specific questions for disabled students, concentrating on their experiences with accommodations during this period. As a result, 51.8% of the disabled students who responded to this survey (N = 114) mentioned they were still not being accommodated one year after the pandemic started.

Along similar lines Goegan, Le and Daniels (2023) explored the experiences of six undergraduate students with learning disabilities learning online amidst the COVID-19 pandemic in Canada. The researchers used semi-structured interviews to analyse the experiences of these participants and uncovered that although some did not need specific accommodations while learning online, such as using voice recorders because recorded lectures were already available, most of them (five out of six interviewees) struggled to access support or were denied accommodations. According to DSUK, the difficulty in accessing support was due to educators perceiving that accommodations were unnecessary while learning online. Although online learning can increase with online learning, disabled students still need support while learning in this modality (DSUK, 2022; Goegan, Le and Daniels, 2023).

Additionally, the role of educators has been widely discussed in the literature due to its strong influence on disabled students' experience and according to Moriña Díez, López, and Molina (2015), faculty can create both barriers and bridges for disabled students. For example, faculty can create barriers to inclusion due to negative attitudes, which lead to the refusal to provide individualised adjustments (Moriña Díez, López and Molina, 2015). Moreover, according to Hansen and Dawson (2019) some educators lack appropriate knowledge and training to understand the needs of the students, especially those with invisible disabilities such as learning disabilities, and to provide appropriate support as a result. Furthermore, lack of institutional support is an essential obstacle towards the implementation of accommodations, which meant that many times, adjustments were mainly the result of staff's kindness (Moriña, 2015; Moriña Díez *et al.*, 2015).

In their qualitative study based on in-depth interviews with 15 HE educators in South Africa, van Jaarsveldt and Ndeya-Ndereya (2015) observed that some faculty actively avoided the responsibility of providing accommodations and adjustments for disabled students. These authors observed that these educators refused to collaborate with disability services to support disabled students and did not see the role of educators in promoting inclusion. These faculty created a categorisation where support provision pertained to "*them*" (disability support services) and not to educators, acknowledging an exclusionary discourse that created an "*us versus them*" categorisation, positioning disabled students as outsiders within HE (van Jaarsveldt and Ndeya-Ndereya, 2015, p. 207). Thus, the authors argue that these educators in their study showed a lack of responsibility and involvement with disabled students' learning, which reinforced segregation, marginalising disabled students and demonstrating a lack of respect towards their human needs and dignity. The authors also argue that these attitudes can negatively influence students' motivation, performance and outcomes (*ibid*).

Furthermore, despite their observed potential in supporting students with disabilities, many of these students still decide not to use these services due to various reasons (Newman *et al.*, 2011). Some of the reasons behind this decision are a lack of knowledge about the services or how to access them (Redpath *et al.*, 2013), and students' reluctance to disclose their disability due to fear of stigma (Fossey *et al.*, 2015; Moriña and Carballo, 2020). For instance, Getzel (2008) claims that it is far too often that students are "*made to feel*" (2008, p. 208) that they do not fit in HE if they need additional support. Moreover, some students decide to "*wait and see*" (Fossey *et al.*, 2015, p. 26) if they need support from disability services or not. This decision can be problematic since students can face unexpected difficulties and might need emergency and not as good support. Alternatively, others preferred to disclose their disability and needs directly

to the teaching staff (Fossey *et al.*, 2015), while presumably trying to avoid the process of going through disability services.

Therefore, in the context of individualised support processes, disability disclosure is often the only pathway for disabled students to access accommodations (Vickerman and Blundell, 2010; Goodall *et al.*, 2023; Nieminen, 2023). However, this can be a complex and controversial process which can act as a barrier between disabled students and inclusive practices instead of promoting inclusion and accessibility (Smith, Woodhead and Chin-Newman, 2021). Thus, there is extensive evidence illustrating the difficulties around this process alongside disabled students' reluctance to share their disability status with their institutions (see Kendall, 2016). One example is the work of Newman *et al.* (2021), who acknowledged that two-thirds of the students in their sample (N = 2330) had not disclosed their disability to their institutions. Some like Kendall (2016), Moriña and Carballo (2020) and McKinney and Swartz (2022), recognise that fear of stigma and negative attitudes tend to be the reason behind this choice, as students perceived their disability status could hinder their educational experiences and aspirations. Smith, Woodhead and Chin-Newman (2021) add that students with non-apparent or hidden disabilities experience additional barriers and stigma than students with more apparent conditions.

Consequently, disability disclosure as a requirement to access support in HE is an increasingly contested condition, as the analysis of its problematic roots gains interest. In this regard, Pearson and Boskovich (2019) recognise that the need for disability disclosure to access support in HE is a complex process underpinned by ableist discourses. According to Valle *et al.* (2004), disability disclosure is a multilayered, ongoing, personal process that can be linked to trauma and oppression because it challenges the status quo by giving voice to those traditionally silenced. Others like Goodall *et al.* (2023) or Brown (2020) maintain that the neoliberal principles of hyper productivity and ability can contribute towards disability disclosure-related difficulties, as disability is often associated with weakness and difference. Moreover, Shpigelman *et al.* (2022) and Nieminen (2023) acknowledge that disability disclosure can *other* disabled students, emphasising their identities as outsiders within HE, particularly when they are required to share their disability status repeatedly. According to Chouinard (1997, as cited in Campbell, 2009) ableist notions presume that able-bodiedness is the norm across sectors like HE, which means that disabled people are marginalised and rendered unseen *others* within these sectors, which leads to them being *othered*.

However, others like Jain (2020) highlight that disability disclosure has the potential to be a political strategy to challenge existing disability stigma and resist ableist notions. Thus, this author recommends that disabled students share their disability-related experiences and identities to challenge existing stigma and ableist cultures (ibid). Similarly, Pearson and Boskovich (2019, p. 26) believe that disability self-disclosure can be a brave and productive choice that opens opportunities towards more equitable and holistic learning environments, “*for in silence, nothing can change*”. Still, this vision is linked to the understanding that educational institutions can create and perpetuate ableist discourses around disability disclosure (Pearson and Boskovich, 2019). Thus, some like Goodall *et al.* (2023) propose that if HEIs will continue to require disability disclosure to provide support, then they need to create cultures in which disabled students feel safe to make this decision without fear of retribution. Likewise, Jain (2020) acknowledges the need for structural approaches to challenge stigmatising discourses and encourage the development of positive disability-related identities. Thus, individualised support provision can positively impact the experiences of disabled students, which is crucial in ensuring effective access to education for many. Yet, existing difficulties around this approach to support the call for other models that can be more accessible to all disabled students. Three of these approaches are addressed in the rest of this section.

Widely available support

Considering the difficulties related to accommodations and disclosure, there is an increasing interest in support strategies that are available to the whole body of students and can be accessed without medical certification (Newman *et al.*, 2021; Bones and Ellison, 2022). In this regard, the value of institution-level approaches to inclusion is increasingly being recognised as they acknowledge that all students might need assistance at some point and that students are a heterogeneous group with diverse needs (Schreuer and Sachs, 2014; Fossey *et al.*, 2015).

Some of the widely available support mentioned by Fleming, Oertle, and Plotner (2017) includes counselling, health promotion or career guidance. Others like Getzel (2008) and Garrison-Wade (2012) advocate for the promotion of students’ self-determination and self-management and establish effective transition plans into HE. Garrison-Wade (2012) also highlighted that HEIs need to identify and eliminate barriers (physical, attitudinal, informational, and programmatic) and improve disability knowledge and awareness. Nonetheless, despite the attractiveness of these strategies, there are some important barriers preventing their expansion, which mainly

come in the form of scarce financial and practical resources, but also as the excessive workload teaching staff already face (Fossey *et al.*, 2015).

Moreover, Newman *et al.* (2021) used secondary data analysis to study the effect of accessing disability-related and widely available support on the persistence of HE students with disabilities in the US. These authors used data from the National Longitudinal Transition Study-2 (NLTS2), a 10-year longitudinal nationwide study investigating the experiences of 11270 young people across the country as they transitioned into young adults. Newman *et al.* (2021) worked with a sample of 2330 students from the resulting dataset, which were the ones who had been reported to have disabilities in secondary school and were attending postsecondary education, regardless of their decision to disclose their disability status to their HEI (two- and four-year college courses). The authors used propensity score modelling to test the hypothesis that accessing support improves the persistence of disabled students in HE. As a result, they concluded that students with disabilities who accessed “*universally available*” (Newman, 2021, p. 1) support, for which they did not need to disclose their disability or present medical evidence, were more likely to persevere (80% of those students persisted). The universally available supports the authors discuss include the services available for all university students, such as tutoring or writing and study support (*ibid*).

Additionally, the authors believe that the academic integration portrayed by the students by being aware of and using these services positively impacted their persistence (Newman *et al.*, 2021). These authors noted that two-thirds of the students in their sample had not disclosed their disability to their institutions. This meant they could not access specialist services and relied on the support available for the broad student body, which positively affected their outcomes (*ibid*). Therefore, there is a need for further exploration of the impact of universally available support and the role it can play on disabled students’ retention, as it eliminates the most significant barriers related to individualised support provision.

Anticipatory approaches

Under the Equality Act (2010), HEIs in the UK also have the responsibility and legal duty to take an anticipatory approach to promote inclusion and prevent the exclusion of disabled people in sectors such as HE. This approach responds to the social model of disability, which seeks to reduce environmental barriers to promote disability inclusion (Office for Students, 2019). Thus, these anticipatory approaches address the general body of students, promoting inclusive education for all, reducing the need for disability disclosure, individualised accommodations, and decreasing the negative feelings related to stigma (Fossey *et al.*, 2015; Griful-Freixenet *et*

al., 2017; Office for Students, 2019). Some examples of this type of intervention include flexible assessment tasks, the appropriate use of technology, Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and having more than one educator per course that could provide simultaneous support to the students (*ibid*). Therefore, inclusive curriculum design and teaching approaches which aim to include students with different backgrounds and needs have great potential to promote inclusion across HE (Macleod *et al.*, 2017).

While the literature directly linking teaching and learning practice to the retention of disabled students is scarce, there are reasons to believe this is one of the most critical factors shaping the experiences of disabled (and non-disabled) students since it is a constant aspect of HE for all (Tinto, 2003; Thomas, 2016). In this regard, Thomas' report (2012) shows that the most common reason for which students would think of leaving HE (between 21% and 42%) was related to their courses. Considering the differences between programs, the author believes that the practices of the academic teams strongly influence the students' experiences and, consequently, their attitudes, expectations and sense of belonging. Therefore, Thomas (2012) emphasises the importance of pedagogy, institutional climate and culture, strong and supportive leadership, continuous staff development, inclusive teaching practices, and close contact between students and educators. Additionally, this author argues that "*mainstream, proactive, relevant, well timed, and using appropriate media, collaborative and monitored*" (Thomas, 2016, p. 143) strategies are the key to moving towards inclusive HE that promotes engagement and a sense of belonging. For Thomas (2012), sense of belonging is at the core of student success and retention, and the best way to promote a sense of belonging is through engagement in academic activities in which all students participate.

While looking at anticipatory approaches to inclusion, Griful-Freixenet *et al.* (2017) studied the extent to which Universal Design for Learning (UDL) met the needs of students with disabilities in HE in Belgium. The Universal Design for Learning Implementation and Research Network (UDL-IRN; as cited in Cumming and Rose, 2022) defined UDL as a pedagogical framework that puts students at the centre of education, acknowledging their diversity and varied needs. Based on these principles, UDL-IRN maintains that all learners would benefit from educational curricula that consider students' varied needs and concentrate on eliminating barriers to education (*ibid*). The Centre for Applied Special Technology (CAST, 2018) developed the UDL guidelines, which revolve around three key principles to guide curriculum development and educational instruction: providing multiple means of representation (different ways to acquire knowledge), multiple means of expression (varied approaches for students to demonstrate what they learn) and multiple means of engagement (addressing learners interests and

motivation). These principles are supported by nine evidence-based guidelines and 31 checkpoints (CAST, 2018).

Thus, Griful-Freixenet *et al.* (2017) point at the role that UDL plays in addressing the willingness to engage in their studies that the participants had. More specifically, these authors discuss the role of UDL's third principle (multiple means of engagement) and Guideline number 8 (provide options for sustaining effort and persistence). These elements align with the importance that students with disabilities in their study gave to a positive and engaging educational environment based on communication, timely and continuous feedback, and cooperative learning and peer discussions.

Therefore, Griful-Freixenet *et al.* (2017) believe that UDL could enable inclusive pedagogical approaches in HE. Nevertheless, these authors maintain that it does not seem possible to implement a curriculum that addresses all the students' needs without creating barriers along the way. Still, it would still be positive and more effective to consider including accommodations from the moment of curriculum design instead of simply adopting the *"traditional model of providing retrofitting accommodations depending on the student's disability type"* (Griful-Freixenet *et al.*, 2017, p. 1643). This is one of the main advantages of UDL as it takes an anticipatory approach that tries to foresee and respond to varied student needs (Dolmage, 2017).

As Griful-Freixenet *et al.* (2017), and others (Edyburn, 2000) say, there is a strong alignment between UDL and the needs of students with disabilities, and UDL is a framework that could potentially help eliminate barriers and enhance teaching and learning in HE. Hence, UDL can enhance flexibility and variety across all teaching and learning experiences since rigid approaches do not seem to be appropriate for heterogeneous cohorts of students (Fuller, Bradley and Healey, 2004; López Gavira and Moriña, 2015; Bartz, 2020). In addition, the authors argue that sometimes, in cases where students have additional specific needs, a more targeted, flexible, and dynamic approach might be more desirable than only using general UDL guidelines. Burgstahler and Cory (2008, as cited in Griful-Freixenet *et al.*, 2017) suggest that UDL could be something that educators start using gradually and slowly until they feel ready to fully incorporate it into their practice.

Consequently, there is currently an increasing body of researchers moving towards approaches similar to Thomas' ideas (2016), highlighting the importance of having both individual accommodations and anticipatory principles that promote overall inclusion, which is likely to positively impact disabled students' outcomes. In this regard, Macleod *et al.* (2017), Bartz

(2020), Frank, McLindedn and Douglas (2020) and Newman *et al.* (2021) support inclusive approaches to HE that conceive accessibility, meaningful learning, the promotion of positive relationships with peers and faculty. Approaches like this have the potential to reach more students and are also likely to reduce the need for disabled students to access and request individualised accommodations, as well as the extra effort, time, and bureaucracy linked to them (see Thomas, 2016). Still, these approaches should also respect and consider the individualised needs that students might additionally have. These are not opposite standpoints but rather complementary ones (Griful-Freixenet *et al.*, 2017).

Additionally, some authors point to the importance of relational aspects as the way forward in promoting teaching and learning practices that could enhance disabled students' experiences and promote persistence and retention. One example of this approach is the work of Thomas (2012, 2016), which focuses on the importance of developing a sense of belonging in students as a result of feelings of engagement. Through a review of the literature, Thomas (2016) points at the promotion of student belonging in relation to improved retention and success rates of students from diverse backgrounds, including those in the disability community. Thomas adds that all-inclusive approaches to education are more likely to promote engagement and a sense of belonging amongst these students than targeted or add-on strategies. More specifically, Thomas mentions that student-centred approaches to education are "*at the heart of improving student retention and success*" (2016, p. 141) and adds that academic experiences are strongly linked to some students' decisions to leave HE.

Furthermore, the positive role of educators and the bridges that they build is highly appreciated by disabled students, who highlighted the positive impact of approachable and flexible faculty, adapted resources, flexible deadlines, and extra time on exams (Moriña, 2015; Moriña Diez *et al.*, 2015; Frank, McLinden and Douglas, 2020) as did the participants of Fuller *et al.*'s studies (2004; 2004). Additionally, according to Hansen and Dawson (2019), despite the need for improvement in certain areas, lecturers tend to have positive attitudes and are willing to improve their knowledge and gain skills to support disabled students. Likewise, educators have a positive role in supporting, empowering and educating students with disabilities (Moriña, Cortés-Vega and Molina, 2015).

Yet, in addition to this positive influence, there is also evidence that faculty's negative attitudes can influence the experiences of disabled students in HE (Goodall *et al.*, 2023). This mixture of positive and negative experiences echoes Fuller *et al.*'s (2004) belief that members of the educational community are still at different places on the ladder to inclusion. Along similar

lines, van Jaarsveldt and Ndeya-Ndereya (2015) acknowledge the difficulties of promoting inclusive cultures across HE and the negative influence this has on disabled students' learning. However, while these authors recognise the need for institutional approaches to improve inclusion, they also highlight the importance of staff's personal responsibility in doing so. Thus, these authors advocate for enhancing faculty's knowledge and skills about inclusive pedagogies but also point out the need to promote more inclusive discourses and personal responsibility. To overcome existing barriers, Moriña (2015) suggests that universities should conceive inclusion as a core part of their policies and strategies, take responsibility for eliminating barriers, identify exclusionary practices and implement an overall inclusive climate. In addition, Moriña and Orozco (2020) recommend disability-related staff training to support them in implementing inclusive pedagogies that consider the needs of disabled students and promote their full participation, persistence and retention.

Hence, there is an increased interest in anticipatory approaches that take a proactive stance toward inclusion. These approaches are based on the promotion of more inclusive cultures and the implementation of pedagogical approaches that are inclusive by default. Once again, approaches that do not single out disabled students and create overall inclusive educational environments that can benefit all are promising in enhancing the experiences of disabled students, helping fulfil their aspirations and fostering persistence and retention. Nonetheless, as the following subsection illustrates, there is an increasing interest in taking a more critical examination of current approaches to inclusion, which could foster more significant transformations across the sector aimed at meaningful inclusion.

Moving forward: transformative approaches

Although existing approaches to support tend to focus on providing individualised adjustments, as the previous subsections illustrate, there is increasing evidence highlighting the need for broader approaches disabled students can access without needing to provide medical evidence and request specific support (Newman *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, while this evidence has mainly focused on educational practices, there is an increasing interest in taking more critical approaches to investigate the conditions that put disabled students at a disadvantage in HE (see van Jaarsveldt and Ndeya-Ndereya, 2015; Goodall *et al.*, 2023).

In this regard, authors like Nieminen and Pesonen (2022) recognise that despite efforts to widen access and participation, HE systems are still influenced by ableism. Additionally, these authors recognise that, although valuable, earlier research that has explored inclusive pedagogies has not considered the role of cultures and pedagogical approaches in the

marginalisation of disabled students. Thus, for Nieminen and Pesonen (2022), current strategies that focus on providing individual accommodations perceive students as problems to be fixed instead of concentrating on the inaccessible pedagogical strategies that marginalise them, which reflects the ableist underpinnings of this approach (Nieminen, 2022).

Hence, these authors question “*whether disabled people are invited to belong in higher education communities in the first place*” (Nieminen and Pesonen, 2022, p. 1). Yet, according to Podlucká (2020) and Nieminen and Pesonen (2022), approaches focused on promoting student belonging have failed to acknowledge the role of ableism in students’ inclusion and exclusion. Considering this, Nieminen and Pesonen (2022) proposed the implementation of anti-ableist pedagogies as a transformative strategy towards learning and belonging.

Relatedly, Shpigelman *et al.* (2022) recognise the key role of disability services in the participation and success of disabled students in HE by providing support and enhancing their knowledge and abilities, but they also acknowledge that this approach is not enough. More specifically, these authors refer to the Fraser’s (1997) redistribution/recognition dilemma to acknowledge that this is a remedy approach to inclusion, limited to the redistribution of resources while not recognising the value of students’ diverse identities. Consequently, Shpigelman *et al.* (2022) believe that there is a need to address this dilemma by adopting inclusion strategies that do not only focus on specific groups but challenge existing structures that perpetuate discrimination and foster a recognition of difference and diversity (*ibid.*). Hence, they call for transformative approaches (Fraser, 1997) that do not only focus on students’ outcomes (affirmative approaches) but also address social and political structures that create discrimination and inequalities. Therefore, these approaches align with critical disability theory, which seeks transformation in order to challenge oppression (see Goodley and Lawthom, 2019).

Accordingly, anti-ableist and transformative approaches can be the way forward to provide true inclusion to the sector, as they challenge ableism, promote educational environments that value students’ diversity, create safe and inclusive learning spaces (Nieminen and Pesonen, 2022) and do not other disabled students (Shpigelman *et al.*, 2022). These transformative approaches can be based on caring pedagogies that call for the recognition of the social, relational and affective elements of pedagogy (Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild, 2021) and require the disruption of currently inaccessible educational practices to be anti-ableist (Nieminen and Pesonen, 2022). Moreover, for Nieminen and Pesonen (2022), anti-ableist approaches bring disability to the fore in the discussion of what it means to be human, helping to dispel disablism and marginalisation. These authors also highlight the need to use an anti-ableist lens to

examine the different systems and levels at which discrimination acts because this complex issue must be addressed from different angles and not only focus on identifying good practices. Instead, in line with the words of Dolmage (2017) and Podlucká (2020), Nieminen and Pesonen (2022) advocate for a critical analysis of HE systems as a strategy to bring transformation and inclusion to the future of the sector, which can foster a sense of belonging for diverse students.

These transformative elements have been essential for the development of this study, as I emphasise the need for more critical approaches to researching the experiences of disabled students in HE. Consequently, Chapter 3 addresses how this need for more critical approaches in this research field has guided the current study's methodological choices. Moreover, the role of caring pedagogies in relation to disabled students' experiences and retention is discussed in chapters 5 and 6, as it is one of the key findings and areas of discussion of this research.

As this section illustrates, approaches to disability inclusion in HE tend to be based on individual adjustments and accommodations. Although these approaches are essential for the retention of disabled students, they can also be complex and exclude students who do not have access to medical evidence and prefer not to share their disability status with their institutions. Considering this, the interest in alternative approaches is increasing, illustrating the potential of universally available support and anticipatory and transformative approaches to inclusion. These strategies would allow disabled students to access support without medical certification, would ensure inclusion across HE overall cultures and practices and would enable the examination of ableist structures that marginalise students in the sector.

2.4. Conclusions and research questions

This narrative literature review has covered different research areas related to the retention of disabled students in HE. Thus, after offering an overview of the retention literature relating to the whole body of students, this review focused on the evidence that discussed the experiences of disabled students in HE. Most of this research explores the factors that influence disabled students' experiences in HE, increasing or decreasing their risk of leaving the sector before graduating. Nevertheless, while it must be noted that most of the studies reviewed only acknowledge the perspective of one stakeholder, being students or staff, and rarely considered them both at the same time. Moreover, the body of literature reviewed is complex and characterised by terminological and methodological inconsistencies, and it offers additional insight into elements that shape disabled students' persistence and retention. More specifically, according to existing evidence, some of the factors that put disabled students at

risk of early exit are associated with certain personal characteristics and disabilities, such as having a mental health condition, reduced social integration and sense of belonging, studying part-time or working during term time. Yet, it is important to note that these factors do not operate in isolation, and it is usually a combination of factors what puts disabled students at higher risk of non-completion. While there is little evidence about the post-withdrawal experience of disabled students, emerging literature illustrates that this can be a process characterised by feelings of shame but also as an opportunity to start over.

Considering this, there seems to be an increasing interest in the elements that enhance disabled students' educational experiences and aspirations, acting as protective factors towards retention and persistence. These factors include social integration, self-advocacy skills and access to effective support. There is also an increased interest in the role of hybrid learning in the retention of disabled students, as it appears to be a facilitating factor, thanks to the increased control and flexibility it provides. Yet, online learning can be linked to lower social interaction and a sense of belonging, hindering retention. Additionally, it must be noted that most of this research focused on the experiences of undergraduate students, highlighting a significant gap in the research that explores the experiences and retention of postgraduate disabled students.

Hence, I conclude that there is evidence of the many factors that shape the experiences of disabled students in HE, and therefore, their retention and persistence and that it is challenging to design straightforward strategies to tackle low graduation rates amongst this group of students. Consequently, it is possible to state that the HE experiences of disabled students are complicated, and there are many different factors helping enhance or hinder their journey in HE. These different factors can make the difference between HE being an enriching opportunity that allows disabled students to meet their educational and life aspirations, or it being a difficult and even traumatising experience of marginalisation. These conclusions support the need to consider disabled students' retention as a complex process influenced by a series of dynamic factors.

While this literature review portrayed some of the complexities that make up disabled students' experiences, it also illustrated a change of focus that offers a more critical overview of the issue. This more profound approach to disabled students' experiences and retention can help uncover the structural factors that prevent more successful inclusion in the sector. One clear example is the evidence around individualised disability support provision, which, despite being mostly seen as a protective factor, recent research reveals that it can be a challenging process that

does not always lead to effective inclusion. This happens due to this approach's potential to marginalise students who cannot comply with policies related to disability disclosure and medical certification, othering them and putting the responsibility on students instead of on existing cultures and practices. Consequently, there is an increased interest in support strategies that disabled students can access without requesting specific accommodations. These approaches often come in the form of universal student support and UDL.

Moreover, this change in focus, in which support is no longer seen as a strategy to tackle individual problems, has also given rise to research that takes a more critical approach. Thus, while most of the evidence reviewed focused on identifying personal, social or institutional factors that could increase or prevent disabled students' persistence in HE, the body of literature exploring structural issues behind these students' attrition is increasing. Thus, this narrative literature review illustrates this transition as, in recent years, this field of research has gone from mainly focusing on students' demographics and educational practice to exploring the ableist notions present in the sector. Accordingly, newer research is starting to explore underlying ableist discourses and cultures that promote the discrimination of disabled students, foreclosing their aspirations and, therefore, their retention and persistence.

This change of approach is starting to illustrate how existing discourses, cultures and practices prevent disabled students from accessing education effectively, thus putting the focus on how those narratives, conceptions and resulting practices perpetuate ableism and marginalisation. This change also calls for transformative approaches that recognise and celebrate the diversity of disabled students, promoting their effective inclusion and belonging in HE sectors that value the full experiences of students. While evidence about the landscape in HE in Scotland is limited, the existing examples and international cases highlight the need to explore the retention and persistence experiences of disabled students in the sector in more depth and to do so from a more critical stance.

Consequently, as part of this emerging body of literature taking a critical exploration of disabled students' retention, this PhD research study investigates how cultures, discourses and practices influence the experiences of disabled students in HE in Scotland and how this shapes their retention in the sector. Thus, the aim of this study is to identify existing educational practices that influence disabled students' persistence and retention, as well as the underlying notions that enact and perpetuate the resulting practices and cultures. Moreover, this study explores ways in which change can be brought to the sector in order to promote the retention of

disabled students. Considering this, I posed the following research questions, which will be further explained and justified in Chapter 3:

- How do cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland? How does this shape their retention in the sector?
- In which ways do stakeholders consider that there is room for improvement to foster the retention of disabled students in HE?

Therefore, these two questions guide the empirical development of this study. Subsequently, the following chapter addresses the methodological steps I followed to address these questions and analyse the data generated as a result. Hence, Chapter 3 offers a detailed account of the epistemological framework that informs this research, alongside a justification of the above research questions and an overview of the research design and implementation, including the ethical considerations adopted.

Chapter 3:

Methodology and Methods

This chapter concentrates on the methodology adopted in this study to address the research questions posed at the end of the previous chapter. More specifically, the chapter offers a discussion of the epistemological framework that guides the empirical part of this research, which is followed by a detailed account of the research design and implementation processes, considering elements such as the data generation tool and a description of participants. Moreover, the chapter offers an overview of the data analysis strategy and the ethical considerations relevant to this study. It ends with a discussion of my positionality and reflexivity as the researcher undertaking this project. Hence, this section offers a comprehensive overview of the methodological choices and steps I followed in conducting this study and responding to the gaps acknowledged in the literature, the research questions posed, and the epistemological framework chosen.

3.1. Epistemological framework: Feminist Poststructuralism

Feminist Poststructuralist (FPS) theory is the epistemological framework that guides the development of this project. In this section, I offer a discussion of FPS as a research methodology and how its principles align with my research interests and objectives, followed by a discussion of FPS' implications for this study's data analysis.

It is difficult to systematically conceptualise FPS since, as Gavey (1989) says, part of its core is a reluctance to be defined since such an endeavour threatens to oversimplify its ideas. However, the literature available provides a series of principles that help understand this approach. In this regard, Weedon (1987, pp. 40–41) maintains that FPS is

“a mode of knowledge production which uses poststructuralist theories of language, subjectivity, social processes and institutions to understand existing power relations and to identify areas and strategies for change”.

In addition, FPS understands discourse as a structural part of societies (at institutional and individual levels) since discourse is societies' tool to analyse and explain the effects of power relations that respond to certain interests and the chances for resisting that power. FPS also highlights that language socially produces subjectivity and consciousness and can be the site for conflict and change. As Price *et al.* (2015) add, the focus of FPS is the social and

institutionally constructed experiences, including constructs such as “*gender, abilities, race, ethnicity, class, socio-economic status, and culture*” (2015, p. 78), amongst others.

According to Ollivier (2022) FPS can be a philosophical, theoretical and methodological approach to guide research in areas such as education. Thus, Aston (2016) maintains that FPS can be used to study a wide range of topics since it provides a comprehensive “*combination of methodologies that are both inclusive and responsive to relations of power in general*” (2016, p. 2256) while focusing on participants' voices, experiences, language and the meaning they give to situations while acknowledging intersectional identities. This definition is key for this project since it addresses essential concepts in this research, such as inclusion, intersectionality, and the focus on the participants' voices and experiences. As well as other constructs such as “*critical pedagogy, oppression, power and social construction*” (2016, p. 2251) that are also intertwined with FPS. According to Aston (2016) and Weedon (1987) FPS' nature is to critique how things are while enabling deconstruction and paths of action, which makes it a timely and relevant approach.

Moreover, the poststructuralist nature of this framework means that it shifts the previous interest in universal phenomena to focus on political, social and contextualised conceptualisations of power, language and knowledge (Baxter, 2016; Ollivier, 2022). FPS is also interested in what is not always evident or “*the invisible*” (Ollivier, 2022, p. 55), offering a theoretical framework to investigate social constructions while considering the complex nature of the human experience in relation to, for example, ability, race, or sexual orientation (Ollivier, Aston and Price, 2020). As acknowledged by Ollivier (2022), thanks to its critical nature, FPS can be employed as a theoretical framework or methodology to study misunderstood topics (Baxter, 2016). Therefore, FPS is a critical social theory (Ollivier, 2022) that offers pertinent theoretical guidance for a project aiming to explore the experiences of a traditionally oppressed and underrepresented group of students attending a hierarchical stage of education.

As HE is an environment known for being reluctant to change (Anderson, 2020), an epistemology that supports challenging the status quo, as FPS does (Aston, 2016), is particularly suitable. Hence, considering that most of the key concepts of FPS are of value in developing this project, the remainder of this section concentrates on defining those concepts and linking them to this PhD research.

3.1.2. Connecting Feminist Poststructuralism to this study

Power relations: One of the most important concepts in FPS is power, greatly influenced by Foucault's (1982) ideas. Therefore, FPS scholars understand power as relational, a relation in which actions affect each other in a dynamic and situational way. Thus, according to FPS, power does not belong to specific individuals or is intrinsically negative (St. Pierre, 2000). Instead, and drawing from Foucault's work (1984), power is inherent to human relationships since one person might try to exert control over the other's behaviour. However, those power relations are not rigid but rather modifiable and unstable. In addition, an explanation of power also requires an explanation of freedom and resistance. Regarding freedom, Foucault (1995) says that the presence, at least to a certain degree, of freedom on the parties involved is what makes relations of power possible. Regarding resistance, Foucault (1995) argues that it is indispensable for the existence of power relations. This means that subjects can perpetuate or challenge the status quo in different ways, and those who disrupt it are positioned as "*abnormal*" (Foucault, 1995).

Consequently, power is everywhere, but so is freedom and subjects' capacity to negotiate power using their agency (Ollivier, 2022). However, resistance is not always located in discourse, institutional contexts, and daily experiences as individuals reject norms influenced by predominant discourses (Foucault, 1995; Mease, 2017). Yet, these ideas do not ignore that often the imbalance is so great that those power relations become everlastingly asymmetrical. Power is not conflict between people, but the meaning of their interactions, where personal intentions and social and institutional contexts are important (Aston, 2016). Power is productive and applied within existing discourses to compose and regulate individuals (Foucault, 1980; Weedon, 1987).

A concept linked to power is that of binary opposites, which is necessary as a starting point in the critical analysis of many different circumstances (Foucault, 1982). Binary opposites are understood as social and institutional constructions that relegate different agents into fixed unilateral power structures, for example, men/women, which represents "*the power of men over women*" (Foucault, 1982, p. 780). Nevertheless, Foucault goes beyond these structures and maintains that said critical analysis needs to acknowledge the connection between power and knowledge as well. Different ways of exchanging knowledge illustrate the power relationships in those different exchanges. They also illustrate the nature of people's feelings while communicating ideas between them and how this affects them in terms of conflicts, confrontation, and understanding the hierarchical order of knowledge. According to Price *et al.*

(2015) Foucault's understanding of power – as complex and relational – can also be used to deconstruct oppressive binary constructions of power.

Thus, in this project, I explore power relations across the experiences of disabled students in HE, focusing on the dominant discourse of normalcy across the sector and how it shapes the experiences of disabled students and their persistence and retention. As a result, in Chapter 4, I uncover power imbalances in the disability support provision process as disabled students as positioned as passive subjects who should be grateful for the support they receive. However, as this support is not always effective, disabled students who challenge the status quo and refuse to be quiet, passive recipients of whatever support they are offered, are met with resistance and a lack of accountability. Moreover, the most significant binary opposite identified in this study is a result of the sector's focus on normalcy, as disabled students are positioned as ideal/non-ideal depending on their capacity to adhere to policies and practices.

Feminist principles: FPS adheres to the feminist principles that highlight the importance of listening to people and the stories they tell, which should be trusted as accurate when it comes to studying and understanding people's experiences (Aston, 2016). When applied to research, this means that there is no need for triangulation (contrasting the veracity of information with others involved) since a particular individual is the only one who has the authority to tell their own story (Aston, 2016). As Weedon (1987) maintains, at an individual level, FPS helps explain the origins of people's experiences, why they might be incoherent or whether they can be changed. In addition, it offers a lens for understanding the relevance of motivation and subjectivity for people to interact with the world. However, this makes analysis and interpretation a great challenge since it must be done with care to reflect the person's experiences truly (Aston, 2016).

In this study, FPS' feminist focus on gender (Ollivier, 2022) is not as predominant as the experiences of participants are analysed through the lens of disability. Yet, an interest in feminist pedagogies takes over as I wish to understand the role of relation and emotion across disabled students' educational journey. This interest is based on whether these elements, gaining increased traction in the educational inclusion-focused research (see Chapter 2), create environments that help them thrive and promote retention. Moreover, I am interested in the potential that feminist pedagogies have to disrupt the status quo across HE (see Lambert and Parker, 2006; Gibbs *et al.*, 2021; Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild, 2024).

Thus, the relevance of feminist approaches in this project is reflected in my interest in participants' experiences and voices, which are consistently covered in chapters 4 and 5, and

my aim to respect and honour their perspectives. The fact that extensive recommendations offered in this study are developed from participants' recommendation (see Chapter 6) is also another illustration of this commitment. This focus has helped me understand the participants' experiences and how their subjectivity plays a key role in their actions. Moreover, as discussed in chapters 5 and 6, this study illustrates the potential that care-based and critical pedagogies have to transform HE in Scotland, creating a sector that recognises, and values disabled students' complex experiences as an inherent part of students' humanity. Additionally, the feminist ideas of Weedon (1987) are reflected in this project through the efforts made to understand the social and educational practices that uncover relations of power that are "*constituted, reproduced and contested*" (1987, p. vii) in relation to teaching and learning practice and the retention of disabled students in HE. For example, relations of power between educators and students are discussed in Chapter 5, alongside ways in which disabled students challenge them.

Language: FPS is interested in language as, in line with feminist principles, it could be a tool for liberation but also for oppression (Aston, 2016). Weedon (1987) maintains that from the lens of FPS, language's function is not to label the world, understanding that meanings do not abstractly exist before they are articulated through the use of language. Conversely, FPS understands language as changing and located in contextually, socially and historically-specific discourses, which rejects the existence of fixed and universal meanings (Weedon, 1987; Aston, 2016). Therefore, according to Weedon (1987), language allows us to think, talk and make sense of the world, considering that language and consciousness do not occur beyond language. This understanding of language is essential to comprehending and valuing people's different experiences as conceived through a feminist lens. Thus, even if people's meanings of experiences do not fit into a broad shared linguistic understanding, they are still valuable as individual interpretations give them significance, which is *produced "within language"* (Weedon, 1987, p. 23; Baxter, 2016), and not reflected by it. Moreover, FPS draws attention to beliefs, values and practices, which are also crucial concepts within feminist theories when studying individual experiences (Aston, 2016). According to Ollivier (2022), when language reflects individual subject's experiences, meaning can be enacted, appreciated or changed.

This understanding of language and meaning is central to my own conceptions of experience and meaning. In this regard, the experiences of disabled students and the meaning they give to these experiences are the central pieces of this project. This is reflected in the data-driven nature of this study, which concentrated on understanding disabled students' experiences of HE in relation to their persistence and retention in the sector. For example, in Chapter 5, one

participant (Nicole, a master's student) gives her own meaning to an assessment task she completed, which she sees as a reflection of her educators' interest in students' learning and development. While we cannot know if that was the original intention of said educators, my analysis of this episode is based on Nicole's sense-making of it. Hence, it might be that similar events are experienced in different ways by different members of the educational community. Instead of this being a weakness of this research, I welcomed these personal meanings, as Gavey (1989) recommends, something that offered a nuanced understanding of the topic here researched.

Subjectivity and agency: According to Butler (1992) subjectivity applies to the capability individuals have to interact with and face the discourses that influence their behaviours while being reflexive and conscious. For Weedon (1987), subjectivity is constructed by individuals' conscious and unconscious feelings and reflections, their perceptions of themselves, and their understanding of how they relate to the world. Additionally, Gavey (1989) maintains that, from the lens of FPS, subjectivity is a dynamic, fragmented and inconsistent construct. Consequently, the different subjectivities of an individual might be reflected in contradictory desires within their practices, beliefs and values. But instead of seeing those contradictions as opposed to liberation, they should be understood in the way that they are produced, which means they could be changed (Henriques *et al.*, 1984 as cited in Gavey, 1989).

Referring to agency, Scott (1988) argues that discourses, besides being a part of social relations, can also shape people's behaviours, feelings, thoughts, and therefore, their agency. Thus, agency refers to the ability to reflect on existing discourses and alter and reconstruct them through reflective practice (Alcoff, 1988; Aston, 2016; Weedon, 1987). Scott (1992) claims that agency is the result of socially constructed individuals. This is something with which authors like Butler (1992) agree, maintaining that agency refers to the individuals who are active in confronting and participating in political actions, using them to create impact. According to Ollivier (2022), feminist discursive conceptualisations position language and meaning within one's capacity to act and challenge the status quo.

Furthermore, Butler (1992) introduces the term deconstruction to this debate, referring to individuals having to challenge their positionality as subjects and arguing that deconstruction can help reveal power relations located in different discourses and the relation between discourse and individuals. Moreover, Scott (1992, p. 26) talks about experience while aiming to make the perspectives of the oppressed visible, arguing that individuals do not have experiences but are instead "*constituted through experience*" and therefore, discursively.

In the context of this study, I have explored subjectivity and agency through disabled students' use of their abilities to reflect, interact and face oppressive practices and discourses that influence their academic progress and success. Thus, different subject positions have been uncovered in this study, as disabled students are often expected to be passive recipients of education/support, an expectation that they consistently challenge. Yet, some, like June (undergraduate student) in Chapter 5, position themselves as active members of the educational community, being able to bring positive change to their programmes. Agency is also reflected in June's determination to take longer breaks between classes to avoid pain even if the programme only considered short breaks and her discussed accommodation to have longer breaks had not been acknowledged (see Chapter 5). Moreover, I have also considered my own subjectivity and my role in this research by reflecting on my positionality as an insider/outsider in relation to the topic explored here and the participants of the study (please see section 3.7. of this chapter).

Discourse analysis: Through the lens of FPS, discourse is a "*historically, socially, and institutionally specific structure of statements, terms, categories, and beliefs*" (Scott, 1988, p. 35), and not simply language or texts. According to St. Pierre (2000) discourses are what organise thinking into actions and, consequently, discourses cannot be simple linguistic entities. In addition, discourses are a tool through which subject positions are offered to people, helping them constitute their subjectivity (Weedon, 1987; Gavey, 1989). However, that subjectivity will vary according to the power they offer to people. For example, in societies, there is always the presence of dominant discourses, which establish and perpetuate power relations (Gavey, 1989). In contrast, marginalised and underrepresented discourses have limited power since they are not available as subject positions to the public (ibid).

Therefore, the principles that guide discourse will "*allow certain people to be subjects of statements and others to be objects*" (St. Pierre, 2000, p. 485). In this sense, St. Pierre (ibid) says that the rules of discourse determine who gets a chance to speak or who is spoken about. In addition, Weedon claims that discourses can potentially direct feelings and emotions and that meaning could only be created "*within discourses through a network of power relations*" (1987, p. 108). This means that the interpretation someone makes of their experiences will depend on how they understand the world and the discourses available to them in specific contexts. And as Gavey (1989) maintains, since there is a multiplicity of discourses that can offer conflicting meanings to the world, sometimes people will have to make choices. Furthermore, power can exert control over individuals through discourse. In this sense, and while linking the ideas of

Foucault and Weedon, Aston (2016) points to the latter's (Weedon, 1987) words that illustrate that since discourse constitutes individual subjects, power is enacted within discourse.

Discourse plays a key role in this study, as I have looked at how social and institutional discourses position disabled students within HE in Scotland. As addressed above, this conceptualisation is often linked with notions of normality and an expectation for them to be passive, grateful recipients of support. Moreover, this study has allowed me to uncover conflicting discourses between different members of the educational community. For example, disability advisers have a more positive discourse about the disability support provision than disabled students, indicating a contradiction between how these processes should work and how they function in reality (see Chapter 4). Furthermore, as illustrated in Chapter 5, for some, hybrid learning became a tool to promote inclusion, and for such reason, it should be kept in post-pandemic HE in Scotland. Yet, institutional discourses across the HEIs in which participants were involved advocated for a return to full-time on-campus delivery, which for some represented an ableist discourse (see Chapter 5).

Considering the relevance of discourse to explore individual experiences while uncovering power relations between dominant and underrepresented groups, and the relevance it has within FPS, one of the data analysis methods used in this study is Feminist Poststructuralist Discourse Analysis (FPDA). Baxter (2008) was the first to conceptualise FPDA, which she understands as an approach to analysing discourse in text and spoken language while focusing on poststructuralist tenets of multiplicity, recognition, transformation, complexity and uncertainty. Still, while Baxter's (2008) feminist approach to discourse analysis focused on gender differences, in the present adaptation, I shifted the focus from gender to disability as a construct from which to analyse the experiences of participants. Yet, as explained above, I maintain the feminist spirit of the approach by adopting feminist principles across the research process and by paying attention to elements relevant to feminist pedagogies and how they influence disabled students' experiences.

In Gavey's (2011) and Ollivier's (2022, p. 68) words, FPDA is "*critical and optimistic*", discovering multiple opportunities to exist, think and do. This offers, as Breau, Aston and MacLeod (2018) say, unique perspectives of how education can be conceptualised differently. Therefore, in line with Ollivier's (2022) discussion of the approach, my aim by using FPDA was to question what is considered normal in HE in Scotland, uncover dominant discourses around disabled students and the structures that sustain them, and the implications these can have to bring transformation to the sector in order to allow disabled students to thrive and persist as HE

students. These aims highlight the flexible nature of FPDA, which, beyond being a method for exploration, can also promote transformation and renovation (Ollivier, 2022). Moreover, Baxter (2008) argues that FPDA can promote bottom-up transformation to resist existing dominant discourses. In this study, FPDA has allowed me to illustrate how discourses shape the individual and unique experiences of disabled students who participated in this study, uncovering necessary changes within HE in Scotland while being a tool for transformation (Aston, 2016).

Suitability of FPS: Feminist poststructuralism and FPDA offered a suitable epistemological and methodological framework for this research, as I explored the experiences of a marginalised and traditionally silenced group of HE students. The value of this epistemological framework is the possibilities it offers to explore individual and unique experiences while looking at broader social and institutional issues and examining opportunities to deconstruct and challenge them (Baxter, 2016). Thus, this approach opened possibilities to explore the retention of disabled students while challenging what is taken for granted, exploring the underlying discourses that perpetuate exclusion across the sector and uncovering the ways in which different members of the educational community resist these structures. By using FPS and FPDA, I analysed the topic of study while taking a much-needed critical approach and maintaining an optimistic and hopeful search for transformation. Therefore, FPS and FPDA as methodology and method provided a valuable framework for this research study, allowing me to shape this PhD study into a piece of research that offers a comprehensive and critical exploration of the experiences of disabled students in HE in Scotland while looking into the multiple possibilities that could bring more inclusion to the sector, allowing disabled students to flourish and persist. The rest of this chapter outlines the design and methods used in the empirical facet of this study, addressing the influence of FPS on its development.

3.2. Objectives, aims and research questions

As discussed in the previous chapter, the overall aim of this study was to investigate the experiences of disabled students in HE in relation to their persistence and retention and what implications this can have across the HE sector in Scotland. As seen in Chapter 1, this is a significantly under-researched field despite the evidence illustrating disabled students' challenges and lower retention rates in the sector (Tinklin and Hall, 1999; Commissioner for Fair Access, 2019; Hendry *et al.*, 2020). Considering this, the following research objectives have been developed:

- To examine ways in which educational cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland.
- To analyse how the influence of these cultures, discourses and practices shapes disabled students' retention in HE in Scotland.
- To discuss the implications of this influence on the future of HE in Scotland in order to promote the retention of disabled students in the sector.

With these aims, my objective was to investigate the role that current educational cultures, discourses and practices play in disabled students' retention within HE in Scotland while considering the way in which they allow for the fulfilment or foreclosure of disabled students' aspirations. Thus, my research focus was on analysing how structures, shared beliefs, and notions in the sector can create educational environments in which disabled students can thrive and progress or, instead, how they can create an inaccessible landscape that excludes disabled students from successfully participating in HE. Moreover, my aim with this research was also to identify the ways in which relevant stakeholders (such as former and current disabled students, disability advisors and educators) considered that change could be brought to the sector to enhance the experience of disabled students and their retention in HE in Scotland. Considering these aims and taking into account the context of the study, I developed the following two research questions, which are followed by an explanation and justification of each of them:

- **Research Question 1:** How do cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland? How does this shape their retention in the sector?
- **Research Question 2:** In which ways do the stakeholders involved consider that there is room for improvement when it comes to fostering the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland?

3.2.1. Research Question 1

How do cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland? How does this shape their retention in the sector?

Originally, the focus of this research was to analyse how teaching and learning practice shapes the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. However, different factors influenced my thinking and this research, meaning I considered this initial aim to be too narrow. One of these factors is the evidence illustrating the importance of other elements beyond practices, such as

discourses and relations on the experience of disabled students and their link to persistence and retention (see Goodall *et al.*, 2023; Nieminen, 2023). Yet, the most important one has been the data generated in this study, which offered a nuanced account of the elements that can shape the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. These elements are complex and intricate, demonstrating the multifaceted nature of the retention of disabled students and the role that cultures and discourses, not only practices, play in the persistence of disabled students in the sector. Additionally, I adopted a critical epistemological stance in this study based on Feminist Poststructuralism (FPS; as discussed in section 3.1. of this chapter), which called for a broader and more in-depth exploration of the issue, considering discourses, power relations, subjectivity and the ways in which disabled students and other members of the educational community negotiate these in relation to retention.

Therefore, it became apparent that my analysis could not only be based on practices, but it also had to investigate the cultures and discourses that create and reproduce these practices. It also became apparent that the study should not solely focus on an understanding of retention and persistence based on disabled students' intentions to stay in or leave HE. Instead, it also had to acknowledge disabled students' multifaceted interactions with the HE system and how these allowed them to achieve their goals or, instead, limited their capacity to fulfil their aspirations. This broader analytical interest developed during discussions with my supervisors and during the data analysis and writing phases, as the stories told by participants in relation to the elements that influenced their retention were much richer than I had originally anticipated. This led to a more comprehensive and critical overview of the elements that influence the experiences and retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland.

The suitability of this approach was confirmed by one participant in the summer of 2024 when I shared by email a summary of the research findings with participants to discuss my approach to data analysis and the use I did of the data they provided as part of this study's ethical considerations (please see section 3.6. of this chapter for more details). More specifically, one participant (Kate, PhD student) replied and mentioned that she was *“really struck”* by my use of terms like fulfilling or foreclosing aspirations to articulate the study's findings. This was because Kate believed that areas of HE like disability support services have a great capacity to fulfil or foreclose disabled students' aspirations, something that she believed was *“powerful and important, and needs to be highlighted”*. The reasons Kate was so drawn to these terms were

“being aware, through my experiences, of how my PhD and dreams were now part of this massive university institution with all these other stakeholders and individuals and

organisations involved... And yet this (comparatively) tiny little cog [delays in accessing support] in this massive machine [the PhD research process] basically caused the whole thing to grind to a halt. Disability services do indeed have the power to fulfil or foreclose on PhD's- and it should never have been up to my brilliant supervisor or my own stubborn tenacity to fix that machine and get it moving again”.

Moreover, Kate believes that there is an element of responsibility and wonders,

“Who is responsible if a student's success is foreclosed? Non-disabled students don't have this tiny cog in their machines, and therefore don't have a part that can stop the whole machine working”.

Kate's words are insightful and emphasise the need to look beyond practices and consider the element of aspirations when studying disabled students' experiences and retention, which this study set out to do.

Therefore, this expansion is justified by my engagement with a wide range of relevant and emerging literature related to the persistence and inclusion of disabled students in HE, the data-driven nature of this project and the critical analytical approach adopted. Thus, with this research question, I identified and analysed how cultures, discourses and practices help fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE Scotland and how this influenced their persistence and retention. This means the focus of the analysis was on examining traditions, values and beliefs shared across HE in Scotland, the practices they underpin and how all these elements help fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in the sector. Taking this analytical approach helped provide a critical understanding of the sector and illustrate the cultural, discursive and practical elements that influence the experiences of disabled students in HE in Scotland. This stance helped uncover relations of power and participants' agency and subjectivity.

However, as this project's original and current aim is to investigate the experience of retention and persistence of HE disabled students in Scotland, the first part of the research question is supplemented by a second one, which aims to link the experiences and aspirations of disabled students in the sector with their retention. While it could be argued, and I have considered, that these are two separate questions, I decided to work with one overall question (with two parts) due to the nature of the data generated and its analysis. This is because participants addressed educational cultures, discourses and practices in close relation to disabled students' experiences and aspirations and their retention, which required a joint discussion of them, as

illustrated in Chapters 4 and 5. Therefore, I did not consider it appropriate to separate the discussion of the key elements of this study's data, and instead, opted to intertwine the discussion of participants' experiences in relation to cultures, discourse and practices and disabled students' aspirations and retention. I argue that this approach offers a more comprehensive overview of the data generated.

In conjunction, the two parts of this question explored the influence of underlying structures and practices on disabled students' experiences and how HE becomes a place of fulfilment that enhances disabled students' retention or a place of marginalisation that forces them out of the system. Hence, this study's analytical focus and approach contrasts with previous research that concentrated on the influence of practices and attitudes without exploring the structures that create and perpetuate them (see Chapter 2). Alternatively, the two parts of this question and the broad approach it takes, support the increased interest in the critical exploration of the academic journey of this group of students and how that relates to their persistence or attrition in the sector, something necessary in the current HE landscape as noted in the literature review chapter.

3.2.2. Research Question 2

In which ways do the stakeholders involved consider that there is room for improvement when it comes to fostering the retention of disabled students in HE?

As mentioned above, one of my research aims was that this study could bring applicable, positive change to the HE sector in Scotland by enhancing the experiences and retention of disabled students at this level of education. Therefore, this second research question aimed to identify how participants believe this change can be implemented.

Participants shared their willingness for change, as they took a proactive approach during the interviews, sharing several suggestions to tackle the challenges we discussed. For example, at times, Tiffany (PhD student) asked me to *"please recommend this"*. Others like Lydia (disability adviser) acknowledge the relevance of the research and how timely it was in the post-pandemic HE landscape: *"We should be looking for a better normality than the normality that we had previously, and yeah, maybe now is the time"*. Others like Mark (PhD student) mentioned this applicability was the reason he was interested in participating in the study: *"Your research I am really interested in because, you know, implications can be possible; direct implications to real life. (...) So, whatever I can contribute, I am happy to do it"*.

Therefore, I aimed to reflect participants' interest in transforming the sector through the following chapters of this thesis. This means that, while addressing the current research questions, the two findings' chapters directly discuss participants' recommendations and suggestions for change, including the need to rethink support provision processes and the importance of maintaining hybrid learning provision in post-pandemic HE (see chapters 4 and 5). These suggestions significantly influenced the comprehensive list of recommendations included in the discussion chapter (see Chapter 6). Although the focus of the study was on the experiences of disabled students, I argue that these recommendations can also benefit the whole body of students, and particularly other under-represented students in the sector.

Finally, considering these research aims and questions, I designed a research project that allowed me to address these objectives in line with the epistemological framework defined in section 3.1. of this chapter. This led to the design of a research study that adopts a critical qualitative approach guided by FPS and based on the use of semi-structured interviews with three different groups of participants. The following sections offer a detailed account of each of the main elements of the design and implementation of this research study, including processes such as participant recruitment, data generation, data analysis and ethical considerations.

3.3. Participant recruitment

The current section focuses on the recruitment phase of this study. Therefore, it discusses different steps relevant to this phase, such as the participant's inclusion criteria, the participant recruitment strategy and a description of the participants who participated in this study.

3.3.1. Participants' inclusion criteria

This study focuses on the experiences of disabled students, looking into how their aspirations are fulfilled or foreclosed while attending HE in Scotland and how that influences their persistence and retention. Consequently, the need to improve our understanding of their experiences concerning retention is why this study came to be. Therefore, my main interest is in the experiences of disabled students in this sector; yet, since this study also explores educational discourses, cultures and practices, I was also interested in the testimonies of other members of the educational community, such as educators and disability advisers, who can aid our understanding of these elements. Thus, while the study focuses on the experiences of

disabled students formerly and currently enrolled in HE in Scotland, the perspectives, knowledge, and experiences of those working in the sector are also valuable in addressing such a broad topic. This means that to participate in this study, participants had to meet at least one of the following three criteria:

- Identifying as disabled and being enrolled in HE in Scotland at the time of the interview.
- Identifying as disabled and having been enrolled in HE in Scotland at some point in their lives, regardless of completion status.
- Working in HE in Scotland as an educator, disability adviser, or related roles.

The classification of disability I use across this study is broad and based on participants' self-identification and identities. Thus, people who met the above criteria and wanted to participate in this study did not need a medical diagnosis to be considered disabled. Instead, this depended on their perceptions and experiences, and it was only necessary for participants to consider themselves part of the disability community to be welcome in this study. Therefore, current and former students seeking a diagnosis, in the middle of a diagnosis process or self-diagnosed were invited to participate. The main reason I took this broad approach is to acknowledge the varied experiences of disabled students and the many difficulties related to accessing medical certification and disability disclosure (see Bones and Ellison, 2022; Hutcheon and Wolbring, 2012; Cage and Howes, 2020).

Moreover, there was no need for current and former disabled students to be or have been registered with the disability services at their HEIs. I acknowledge that many disabled students choose not to register with disability services to avoid disclosing their disabilities or needs, often due to the fear of stigma (see Getzel, 2008; Moriña and Carballo, 2020; Smith, Woodhead and Chin-Newman, 2021; McKinney and Swartz, 2022), meaning that as little as 35% register with support units, and only 24% of disabled students access support (Newman and Madaus, 2015). Hence, I believe that the most appropriate approach for this project is a flexible one that can be relevant for the heterogeneous members of the disability community and focuses on their lived experiences and identity, not on medical labels.

Additionally, disabled people who were currently or had been enrolled at some point in their lives in HE in Scotland could take part in this study regardless of their completion status. Consequently, disabled people who had graduated, were currently working towards their degree, had decided not to finish their current degree or had left HE before completion at some point were all invited to participate. These broad criteria were intended to reach potential

participants with varied experiences related to degree retention and attrition, with a particular interest in exploring the experiences of those who had to leave HE before graduating. While the voices of disabled people who left HE before graduating are particularly valuable for retention-related research, they are under-represented in the literature, and scarce evidence of their post-attrition experiences is available (see Cage and Howes, 2020).

Those who were currently working as educators, disability advisers or similar (such as student success officers or academic developers) were also invited to participate. This opened the possibility of some overlap, as someone who identifies as disabled could be currently working in HE after being an HE student in the same sector. This would give these participants an additional insight into the topic researched here, recognising the value of disabled staff's experiences and points of view, which are often neglected in HE inclusion research (see Merchant *et al.*, 2020; Lindsay and Fuentes, 2022; Dolan, 2023). Moreover, inviting HE professionals to participate in this study helps address one of the gaps identified in the literature review (see Chapter 2), as most studies researching the retention of disabled students only address the perspective of one group, either staff or students. Thus, authors like Collins, Azmat and Rentschler (2019) and Schreuer and Sachs (2014) recommend the involvement of different stakeholders when it comes to researching topics related to HE inclusion.

3.3.2. Recruitment strategy

I started the recruitment phase for the study in early autumn of 2021 after this project received ethical approval, a process I discuss in more depth in section 3.7. of this chapter. Although at that time, the COVID-19 lockdowns had been lifted, the presence of the virus and shared preferences for online communication channels meant that most of the recruitment process had to take place online. Therefore, emails were my primary way of sharing information about the research, which I used to share information about the study and ask others to collaborate in sharing this information. I also used social media like Twitter (now known as X) and Facebook with the same aims. Additionally, I created a series of resources to share information about the study and enhance potential engagement. These resources included a participant information sheet (see [Appendix 3](#)) and three participant information Microsoft Sway sites. Although these resources contained the same information, their different formats allowed me to use them as appropriate since I could adapt them to different platforms and audiences, enhancing the means by which participants could engage with this information.

According to Dworkin *et al.*, (2016), effective research participant recruitment can be difficult as the researcher must find appropriate ways to contact participants. Thus, I was initially unsure about the effectiveness of solely using online recruitment strategies without combining them with other formats, such as printed flyers or information sheets. At first, I thought this gave me limited opportunities to engage with potential participants. Yet, online recruitment proved to be successful due to its flexibility and opportunities for different means of engagement, which allowed for a flexible and tailored approach. For example, to reach out to disability support services across HEIs in Scotland, I drafted a detailed email with information about the study and how to get involved while also providing a link to the Microsoft Sway site I created with additional information about the research. However, I drafted shorter messages to be shared on other platforms, such as the Scottish Graduate School of Social Science's (SGSSS) weekly newsletter, the Scottish Higher Education Developers mailing list and my institution's e-bulletin. Moreover, in X/Twitter, I used visual, colourful posters (see [Appendix 2](#)) to attract attention to the study, which I complemented with alt-text descriptions.

Furthermore, using online resources increased the channels for potential participants to respond to my call. Hence, one way of contacting me was to send an email, as my contact details were included in all my communications. Other ways included reaching out via Twitter/X, as I created an account associated with the project (@RetAndDisab_HE), or expressing their interest in a Microsoft Form I created in which participants could share their emails confidentially for me to contact them. Thus, online recruitment helped me reach a significant number of groups and individuals in a time-effective manner and without additional costs. In all my communications, I either attached a copy of the participant's information sheet or provided a link to the appropriate Sway site that offered more information about the project. This means all those interested in participating could access enough information to make an informed choice to participate in this study. When participants expressed their interest in being interviewed, I shared the consent form (see [Appendix 4](#)) for them to sign. Only after participants had returned their signed consent forms were interviews scheduled.

I implemented this recruitment strategy between October 2021 and June 2022, which started by contacting all HEIs in Scotland through their disability support units according to the contact details available on the HEI's online sites. I also emailed or contacted various disability-related organisations across Scotland via X (then Twitter) to ask for their collaboration in sharing information about the study. Moreover, I shared different posts on X/Twitter using the flyers shown in [Appendix 2](#) to attract attention and potential participants.

This was a challenging process at times because I am not an avid social media user and had never reached out to such a vast number of people before. Thus, I was often weary of the impact of my communication strategies, particularly during the first three months of the process when I struggled to engage with potential participants. Yet, the information shared on newsletters and e-bulletins was well received, leading to an increased participation rate. Thus, since January 2022, interest in the project peaked, and I started getting more responses, which allowed me to interview 29 participants by the end of June 2022, which resulted in 42 interviews (more information about the data generation process can be found in section 3.4. of this chapter). I do not know why some modes of engagement led to more responses than others, but I am confident that the reason the project received such a high and diverse participation rate is the multiple dissemination formats used.

Participants from the three groups were interviewed in no specific order, only depending on their availability (section 3.4. of this chapter offers more information about semi-structured interviews as this study's data generation tool). Most interviews took place online via Microsoft Teams, but others used different platforms to suit the needs and preferences of participants, such as phone, email or instant messaging interviews. These interviews lasted between 28 and 85 minutes and focussed on different topics related to the retention of disabled students in HE, depending on the participant's perspective and lived experience (please see tables 3, 4 and 5 below for more details information about the duration and characteristics of each interview). The following section offers a description of participants in the three different groups, followed by a section that discusses the data generation process via semi-structured interviews.

3.3.3. Description of participants

As mentioned above, a total of 29 participants from the three different groups identified, collaborated with this study. This section offers demographic data shared by participants during our interviews upon my direct questioning or shared by participants' own initiative. In all cases, I reminded participants that they were free to share as much or as little information as they wished and that I would anonymise their personal details. Thus, in this section, I provide a general description of the three groups of participants to help the reader understand their characteristics, accompanied by three tables that offer some more specific information about each participant, according to their group.

However, these descriptions do not provide detailed personal information about each participant to protect the identity of participants and avoid them being recognised as much as

possible. Confidentiality is particularly important in the context of this research, as some participants shared painful and difficult experiences in relation to the focus of the study. In addition, others were vocal about their concerns about their HEI's approach to the inclusion, support, and retention of disabled students and did not want to be linked to this study. Therefore, it is essential that I do everything that is in my power to minimise the likelihood of participants being recognised.

Considering this, I decided to avoid including specific information about the individual participant's condition and diagnoses in the text or the table. Instead, I offer generic information about the conditions shared by participants, without directly linking these to any specific participant. Additionally, to maintain my alignment with this approach, I decided to offer broad information in other areas, such as age and years of experience in the sector. Consequently, instead of providing participants' specific age and years of experience, I include age bands (for example, 18 – 24 and 25 – 34) and bands of years of experience in the sector (for example, 0 – 5 and 6 – 10). Although my anonymisation and confidentiality strategy will be discussed in more depth in section 3.7 (Ethical Considerations), I believe it is also important to emphasise it here. Thus, the following subsections offer a general description of the demographic characteristics of participants in this study according to the group in which they were classified.

Disabled students enrolled in HE in Scotland during interviews

A total of 14 disabled students enrolled in Scottish HE at the time of interviews participated in this study. Five of them were undergraduate students, two were master's students and seven PhD students. The participants' ages ranged from 22 to 60 years old at the time of the interviews. Most of them (11), except three, were mature students as they had started their undergraduate degrees after the age of 21 or their postgraduate degrees after the age of 25, in line with the Universities and Colleges Admissions Service's definition of mature students (UCAS; 2024). Moreover, only three participants from this group started university after finishing secondary school or college and had been enrolled full-time since then. The rest of the participants had joined or returned to HE later in life to enrol in the programmes they were attending at the time of the interviews. Most participants had done so after being in employment for several years, but some had returned to HE after taking a break due to personal circumstances. The study areas of participants varied and included psychology, education, health sciences, humanities, and social sciences. All participants were currently enrolled in full-time, on-campus programmes, although they had adapted to hybrid learning due to the COVID-19 restrictions. A total of 10 of these participants were enrolled in modern, post-92

Scottish universities, while two were enrolled in ancient Russell Group universities, and two were enrolled in chartered universities.

All of the participants in this group identified as disabled, although one preferred to use terms such as additional support needs, and three preferred the term neurodivergent. While it was not required to participate in the study, all participants from this group shared at least one disability or diagnosis during the interview. All participants, except one (Lynsey), volunteered for the two interviews planned with this group. Lynsey could not participate in the second interview due to health and personal circumstances. This means that a total of 27 interviews were carried out with this group of participants, lasting between 28 minutes and 1 hour and 44 minutes.

The disabilities and diagnoses declared by participants included depression, autism, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), post-traumatic stress disorder, borderline personality disorder, myalgic encephalomyelitis, back pain, hearing loss, stuttering, sight loss, rheumatoid arthritis, functional neurological disorder or Guillain-Barré syndrome. Some participants had received a medical diagnosis at the time of the interviews, and others were going through diagnostic processes. All mentioned that they have shared their diagnoses with their HEIs in some form, either through the disability support services or directly with teaching staff. Seven participants in this group identified as male, and seven as female. Nine were white Scottish, three were white British, one was Western Asian, and one was European. Two participants in this group identified as queer. Table 3 below (page 102) offers additional demographic information on participants in this group, including the duration of each interview.

Disabled people formerly enrolled in HE in Scotland

Three participants from this group participated in the study. One had to leave their undergraduate degree before completion, a second had completed their undergraduate degree and master's, and the third had to leave various degrees before completion, but completed other HE certifications. The ages of participants in this group ranged from 22 to 49 years old, and all identified as disabled. One participant was also working as a disability adviser at a Scottish HEI. Nevertheless, I only included this participant's student (not professional) experience as the participation rate in the "Disabled people formerly enrolled in HE in Scotland" group was lower than that of disability advisers. A total of three interviews, in different modes, were conducted with this group of participants. One of them was conducted via video call. The second one was conducted via email as I sent the questions to the participant via a Microsoft Word file, which the participant completed in their own time and then returned to me via email.

The third interview in this group was conducted simultaneously via Microsoft Teams video call and the instant messaging function of the call. In this case, the participant typed the answers to the questions I asked verbally via the video call.

Two participants in this group started HE after secondary school, and one joined HE later in life. These participants' study areas included computer science, events management and autism studies. All participants discussed their experiences in relation to full-time, on-campus programmes, although one experienced online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The other two participants were no longer HE students when the pandemic started. The three participants were enrolled in three different chartered universities. The diagnoses reported by these participants included autism, mast cell activation syndrome, primary immune deficiency, pulmonary fibrosis and a rare genetic condition that affects muscles and bones, creating weakness and stiffness. Two participants identified as female and one as male. Two were white Scottish and one was white British. Additional demographic information of this group of participants, including the duration and length of their interviews, can be found in Table 4 below (page 103).

Table 3. Demographic and interview information for the group of participants “Disabled students enrolled in HE in Scotland during interviews”

Pseudonym	Age Band	Gender	Ethnic Origin	Level of studies at the time of the interview	Length of 1st interview	Length of 2nd interview
Tiffany	25 - 34	Female	White Scottish	PhD	50 minutes	1 hour and 15 minutes
Felicity	18 - 24	Female	White Scottish	Master’s Degree	1 hour and 4 minutes	58 minutes
June	45 - 54	Female	White Scottish	Undergraduate Degree	1 hour and 4 minutes	1 hour and 26 minutes
Jordan	45 - 54	Male	White Scottish	Undergraduate Degree	1 hour and 44 minutes	45 minutes
Lynsey	35 - 44	Female	White Scottish	PhD	1 hour and 4 minutes	N/A
Joe	45 - 54	Male	White British and Scottish	Undergraduate Degree	57 minutes	1 hour and 5 minutes
Kate	35 - 44	Female	White British	PhD	58 minutes	1 hour and 10 minutes
Richard	35 - 44	Male	White European	PhD	1 hour and 2 minutes	1 hour
Anthony	45 - 54	Male	White British	PhD	58 minutes	49 minutes
Henry	25 - 34	Male	White Scottish	Undergraduate Degree	28 minutes	53 minutes
Mark	25 - 34	Male	Western Asian	PhD	1 hour and 10 minutes	1 hour and 16 minutes
Nicole	25 - 34	Female	White British	Master’s Degree	43 minutes	1 hour and 12 minutes
Stella	18 - 24	Female	White Scottish	PhD	1 hour and 7 minutes	1 hour and 23 minutes
Colin	55 - 64	Male	White Scottish	Undergraduate Degree	1 hour and 1 minute	1 hour and 40 minutes

Table 4. Demographic and interview information for the group of participants “Disabled people formerly enrolled in HE in Scotland”

Pseudonym	Age Band	Gender	Ethnic Origin	Level and Progression of Studies Undertaken in HE in Scotland	Length of Interview
Nina	20 - 24	Female	White British	Master’s Degree: Completed	1 hour and 46 minutes – Video/Instant message interview – The Interviewer asked questions verbally, and the interviewee typed their answers
Kevin	20 - 24	Male	White Scottish	Undergraduate Degree: Early exit	1 hour and 2 minutes
Lauren	45 - 54	Female	White Scottish	Undergraduate Degree: Completed Professional Graduate Diploma: Early Exit Postgraduate Certificate: Completed	Email interview - 3469 words

Table 5. Demographic and interview information for the group of participants “Educators and disability advisers working in HE in Scotland”

Pseudonym	Gender	Ethnic Origin	Area of Work	Years of Experience (band)	Length of Interview
Charlotte	Female	White Scottish	Disability Adviser	0 - 5	1 hour and 18 minutes
Lydia	Female	White Scottish	Disability Adviser	16 - 20	1 hour and 10 minutes
Lois	Female	White Scottish	Disability Adviser	11 - 15	52 minutes
Caitlin	Female	White Scottish	Disability Adviser	0 - 5	1 hour and 7 minutes
Sarah	Female	White Irish	Disability Adviser	16 - 20	1 hour and 7 minutes
Helen	Female	White European	Educator	0 - 5	58 minutes
Lola	Female	North African	Educator	16 - 20	1 hour and 15 minutes
Morgan	Female	White Scottish	Educator	21 - 25	1 hour and 2 minutes
Sophia	Female	White Scottish	Educator	0 - 5	1 hour and 10 minutes
Amelia	Female	White Scottish	Educator	16 - 20	1 hour and 20 minutes
Sally	Female	White Scottish	Educator	6 - 10	1 hour and 26 minutes
Cara	Female	White Scottish	Educator	0 - 5	1 hour and 4 minutes

Educators and disability advisers working in HE in Scotland

A total of 12 participants make up this group. Seven of them worked in educational activities and were based at the same two universities. Although some of these participants were lecturers, others also had roles in enhancing education, inclusion or student retention at their institutions. Since not all of them held a lecturer role, I will refer to them as “educators”, which is an overarching term that addresses their different positions. Additionally, five participants in this group worked within disability support services across four different Scottish HEIs. All participants in this group identified as female, and three identified as disabled or neurodivergent. Seven of them were white Scottish, two were white British, two were white European, and one had North African origins. Their ages ranged from 31 to 58 years old. The lengths of interviews for this group range from 52 minutes to 1 hour and 26 minutes.

In conjunction, these participants represent 11 of the 19 HEIs in Scotland, according to the classification offered by the Scottish Government (2024). Yet, there is no direct overlap between the institutions attended by former and current students and those at which educators and disability advisers worked. This means that not all institutions are represented in the same capacity as, in most cases, HEIs were only represented by either staff or students (currently or formerly enrolled). I decided not to disclose which HEIs are represented in this study to protect participants’ identities and confidentiality. More detailed demographic information in relation to this group of participants is covered in Table 5 above (page 104).

3.4. Semi-structured interviews

This section addresses the data generation tool chosen for this study: semi-structured interviews. Therefore, this section will first offer an overview of the rationale behind this methodological choice. Afterwards, the section concentrates on the implementation process, detailing the process through which these interviews were conducted.

3.4.1. Semi-structured interviews: Rationale

As acknowledged above, I chose one-on-one semi-structured interviews as the data generation tool in this study. Semi-structured interviews are often used in qualitative research due to their flexibility and potential to open dialogues and explore the points of view of different participants, who can take the lead in the story told while there is a defined focus of study (Bryman, 2016; Ruslin *et al.*, 2022). Hence, as I was looking for rich, in-depth answers that could

provide insight into the experience of disabled students in relation to their educational experience and intentions to persist in HE, this seemed to be the most appropriate tool. One-on-one semi-structured interviews were also chosen due to their value in exploring the world and perspectives of participants (Hesse-Biber and Leavy, 2007), making them an essential tool in feminist research (Braun and Clarke, 2019).

Although I explored the value of other data generation tools like focus groups, I decided this was not the most appropriate strategy for this study due to the nature of the topic. As acknowledged by Marshall and Rossman (2016), focus groups are based on group discussions that bring together a number of participants (ranging from four to 12) who share traits relevant to the research focus. Yet, one of the concerns related to this strategy is that participant's anonymity and confidentiality could be compromised, particularly if the discussion is recorded in video (ibid). The nature of the topic discussed called for a more private setting, as many of the experiences shared by participants were confidential and often reflected their pain and frustrations. While the sensitivity of the topic could have called for data generation tools like questionnaires that can guarantee participants' anonymity to the researcher, particularly if delivered online (Leavy, 2017) I was interested in the nuance of participants' experiences and aimed for a detailed discussion of the questions posed. Therefore, I decided questionnaires were not a suitable option for this study as they would not allow for the individualised discussions that I argue are the most appropriate approach for such a complex and sensitive topic. Instead, semi-structured interviews carried out using different formats (please see section 3.4.2.) allowed for in-depth discussions while giving participants agency to decide in which way they wanted to be involved in the study, protecting confidentiality and anonymity in a personalised way.

Thus, semi-structured interviews are a suitable tool considering the epistemological framework taken to develop this project, as this tool allows for the exploration of key FPS concepts such as agency, subjectivity and dominant discourses (Weedon, 1987). It is also a suitable tool to allow participants to tell their stories and demonstrate trust in them as they are the only ones with the authority to tell them (Aston, 2016). Moreover, semi-structured interviews are also suitable for feminist research because they challenge hierarchical relationships between the interviewer and interviewee (Brown and Strega, 2015). Additionally, in line with FPS, I consider interviews as a collaborative approach to producing knowledge (DeVault and Gross, 2006). This approach creates more equal relationships with participants in this study, which challenges the perceived notion of interviewers as experts and acknowledges the value of interviewees' experiences, values and beliefs.

However, the way in which I used semi-structured interviews changed, considering the different participant groups defined in section 3.3.3. of this chapter. In this regard, I conducted one interview with disabled people formerly enrolled in HE in Scotland and with educators and disability advisers. Alternatively, I invited disabled students currently enrolled in HE in Scotland to two different interviews. The rationale for doing this was that the focus of this study is the experience of disabled students in Scottish HE, as I was particularly interested in the journey of current students and the cultures, practices and discourses that shaped their retention. Hence, I considered that conducting two interviews would give us more time to explore these experiences in depth. Additionally, as these interviews took place a few weeks or a few months apart, according to participants' availability, there were more opportunities to discuss potential changes to their educational experiences and whether these had impacted their intentions to persist.

Considering this choice and the different standpoints of the three groups of participants, I designed three different interview schedules, one for each group, which helped me ensure that certain areas of interest were addressed while allowing participants to take the lead as preferred (Hesse-Biber and Leavy, 2007). Each of these schedules can be seen in Appendices 5 – 8. Most of the questions in these interview schedules aligned with FPS as they were open and encouraged participants to share their experiences and beliefs openly and genuinely (see Ollivier, 2022), including feeling probes and questions as suggested by Aston (2016).

3.4.2. Semi-structured interviews: Implementation

After beginning participant recruitment in October 2021, I started conducting interviews from November 2021 until June 2022. Although I conducted all the participant recruitment communication online, interviews were conducted in each participant's preferred format, as COVID-19 lockdowns had been lifted. Thus, interviews were conducted in varied ways, including email interviews, instant messaging interviews, phone interviews, and in-person interviews, although the most popular ones were online live interviews. All live interviews were recorded, using a voice recorder for phone and in-person interviews or the recording function on Teams and Zoom, the platforms where online interviews took place. While at first, I worried that the pandemic/post-pandemic context was going to hinder the data generation process, the reality is that it promoted accessibility and inclusion. I believe that if this research had been conducted before the COVID-19 pandemic, when online communication platforms were not as widely used, this data generation process might have been less accessible.

Instead, circumstances in which we were still figuring out how to face life with COVID-19 created a mindset and practical opportunities to increase accessibility and eased the process of researching a sensitive topic, as in this case. Thus, participants had increased options to choose from, which enhanced their engagement with this project. Participant's choice of interview format was sometimes related to their needs, as, for example, engaging online was not as energy-consuming as travelling to a physical site for an in-person interview. However, in other cases, this choice depended on participants' desire to maintain their confidentiality while discussing a sensitive topic. In this case, participants opted for phone or email interviews as they could answer the questions in the privacy of their homes, without sharing visual information with me, the interviewer.

Additionally, some participants chose instant messaging interviews because their only or preferred way of communication was written language. However, other participants preferred communicating in person, so they chose on-site interviews. In these cases, I ensured interviews took place in private, safe locations within public spaces, such as pre-booked rooms within the University of the West of Scotland's library and the Mitchell Library in Glasgow, guaranteeing privacy during the interview process. This addresses one of the suggestions in the ethical approval letter ([Appendix 1](#)), which recommended using interview settings that allowed participants to discuss sensitive topics in privacy. I also took measures to avoid exposure to COVID-19 and transmission to participants, including reduced social engagement before interviews and testing on the interview day.

Hence, a context that promoted alternative means of communication and active dialogue between participants and me allowed for an inclusive data generation phase, which was more productive than if the default option had been in-person interviews. Nevertheless, I was aware of the limitations of alternative approaches, which include a sense of disconnection (De Villiers, Farooq and Molinari, 2022), the need for appropriate technology and reduced non-verbal communication (Saarijärvi and Bratt, 2021). Hence, I took an active approach to overcome these limitations and maintain the feminist nature of the research, keeping the interviewee/interviewer relationship at the forefront. To do this, I focused on making participants feel at ease during the interviews, reminding them that I considered them to be experts in the topic and that my aim was to learn from their experiences.

I also reminded participants that there were no right or wrong answers, that they could share what and how much they wanted and that I was grateful for their time and willingness to share their experiences. Moreover, participants were encouraged to take a break whenever they

needed it and were reminded that we could interrupt the interview and their participation in the study if they wished. At times, I also shared my experiences with chronic illnesses in HE (this is discussed in more depth in section 3.6. below), which created a dialogue between us. Thus, in line with the approach followed by Ollivier (2022), I took a responsive, thoughtful, courteous disposition, avoiding judgment and being aware of power dynamics and of the influence of my identities (for example, as a student or as a researcher) across the interview process.

The result was that in all cases, I built a positive rapport with participants who felt at ease sharing their experiences and expressing their thoughts about the research and interviews. Participants were vocal about how taking part in this study had been a positive experience that allowed them to reflect on their experiences of HE. For students, this meant further analysis and understanding of some of their experiences and the HE context. For staff, this meant further reflection on their practice and their HEI's approach to inclusion and retention. This was often followed by a desire to implement inclusive pedagogical practices and become more aware of the experiences and retention of disabled students in their classrooms. Thus, the benefits of these varied modes of interaction outnumbered their disadvantages, creating an unthreatening interviewing space in which participants felt comfortable discussing a complex and often sensitive topic (Creswell and Poth, 2018, as cited in Ollivier, 2022).

3.5. Data analysis

As seen in previous sections, low student retention amongst disabled students is an issue difficult to face (Mamiseishvili and Koch, 2011; Thompson-Ebanks, 2014; S. Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2017; Koch *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, the research available on the topic is limited, most of it takes a quantitative approach (Fichten *et al.*, 2014), only focuses on one stakeholder – students or staff (Collins, Azmat and Rentschler, 2019) or lacks criticality. Hence, although previous research acknowledges the complexity of the topic, it also often ignores the value of richer data to shed light on the subject and the need to identify discourses and structures that shape the retention of HE disabled students. Considering the nuances of the topic, the research questions developed, and the epistemological framework chosen, I argue that taking a critical qualitative approach that combines the perspectives of different stakeholders is the most appropriate way to address the research questions defined. This choice is supported by the work of others, like Barkas, Armstrong and Bishop (2022, p. 7) who acknowledge the benefits of using “*critical qualitative enquiry*” to research disabled students’ inclusion as it allows us to make sense of students' experiences and “*uncover, discover and debate inclusion*”. Thus, in line with Barkas, Armstrong and Bishop (2022), I have also used critical qualitative enquiry to uncover and

discover some of the cultures, discourses and practices at play in this scenario, which I discuss in relation to the experiences and aspirations of disabled students and how this shapes their retention (see chapters 4 and 5).

To meet this aim, I used Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA; Braun and Clarke, 2021) and Feminist Poststructural Discourse Analysis (FPDA; Baxter, 2008) to analyse the data generated.

Combining these two approaches helped me manage a large dataset while keeping the research aims and questions at the centre of analysis. Therefore, I first used RTA to familiarise myself with the data and develop a data-driven structure that could help me meet the aims of this study and balance the theoretical analysis with the applicability of the findings. Then, I returned to the data and conducted additional layers of analysis through the lens of FPDA. Considering this, the current section first explains why I used these specific data analysis techniques. Secondly, the section offers an overview of the implementation of each approach, first covering the RTA process, followed by the FPDA strategy.

The combination of RTA and FPDA allowed me to identify the areas of practice that were most relevant to the experiences of disabled students and then explore how elements like discourses, power dynamics and subjectivity were enacted. This means that instead of developing themes solely based on the idea of a shared, unifying construct (Braun and Clarke, 2021), I also considered the context in which these shared ideas took place. For example, the first findings chapter focuses on participants' experiences in relation to disability support provision, where I analyse a shared notion through which some disabled students are considered more *ideal* than others. Thus, instead of organising the theme around that notion, I organised it around how that notion impacted disabled students in different circumstances. I revisit this notion in the second findings chapter as participants proposed pedagogical approaches that valued disabled students' realities instead of working with an abstract conception of who can be a disabled student in HE. This approach helped contextualise the scenarios where different cultures, discourses and practices occur and how they influence different areas of the disabled student journey. This aligns with Aston's (2016) approach to discourse analysis, in which context is essential to uncovering existing discourses and how participants respond to them. I argue that this strategy offers an effective overview of the educational spheres in which dominant discourses and power imbalances occur across HE in Scotland, as it provided me with a map of areas that need attention when it comes to promoting inclusion across the sector.

3.5.1. Reflexive Thematic Analysis

Using RTA as the first analytical strategy helped me map the most relevant themes using a data-driven strategy, which enabled me to make sense of the rich data with which I worked and provided me with a flexible approach to develop the foundations of the overall data analysis. Additionally, RTA allowed me to manage the large dataset generated in this study, made up of 42 interviews and over 40 hours of interview content. In this regard, I used RTA's focus on identifying common and unifying ideas across the dataset as a strategy to disentangle the stories that were being told by participants and how they related to the study's research questions. This means that RTA allowed me to identify the main areas of relevance, regarding the educational cultures, discourses and practices that shape the retention of disabled students in the sector, which I believe would not have been as effective if the analysis were solely based on FPDA. As will be illustrated in more detail below, during this first analytical stage, I went from working with a series of initial codes to recognising the existence of two main thematic areas under which the most relevant discourses, cultures and practices discussed by participants could be classified: Disability Support and Pedagogy.

While these two areas are closely interlinked, RTA allowed me to identify how, during interviews participants often talked about these two areas separately, each being a clear area of interest for interviewees, encompassing a series of themes that illustrate and contextualised how these discourses, cultures and practices shaped the experiences of disabled students in HE in Scotland. Therefore, RTA allowed me to highlight the commonalities and shared points of interest across the large and nuanced data generated as part of this study. This analytical phase had great value as it helped me make sense of the stories being told and allowed me to draft an overall structure in which I could organise these stories into the overall story that this thesis tells. However, as the poststructuralist and feminist nature of this study also called for a more critical data analysis, which explored nuances, contradictions, discourses, relations of power and agency, I decided that the RTA had to be complemented by using FPDA. As discussed in section 3.1.2., FPDA also pays attention to individual experiences, considers multiple meanings and studies what is considered normal, the discourses that maintain shared understandings of normalcy and those that challenge it, crucial elements for this study.

Therefore, RTA was used as a strategy to lay the foundations of this thesis' data analysis, helping me build the general structure that would then be enhanced by the critical lens offered by FPDA (as discussed in the next section). Thanks to both of these analytical approaches, I have been able to offer a comprehensive but nuanced account of the data generated here, which

discusses common difficulties in the sector while uncovering new areas of study. More details about how I conducted the RTA phase of this analysis are offered below, as I discuss how I followed the six phases described by Braun and Clarke (2021) in an analytical process that began when I started conducting and transcribing interviews. The different phases of RTA took place as follows:

- 1. Data Familiarisation:** This phase started during the transcription stage as I started to familiarise myself with the interviews' recordings and scripts. During this process, I started writing memos and taking notes about analytical ideas that arose. This phase helped me identify key discussion areas in each interview and develop an interpretation of them (Byrne, 2022). The familiarisation phase continued as I revisited the transcripts several times while making sense of the overall data. These key, overall ideas gave me a general understanding of the stories being told by participants. These stories were often related to disabled students' difficulties navigating HE and accessing support, and frequently reflected a HE sector that was not designed for disabled students. This was illustrated in participants' discussions around support that was not effectively implemented and about educational practices that did not consider the experiences of disabled people. Moreover, this general overview also allowed me to see that educators and disability advisers who took part in this study had a commitment to promote inclusion and understood the responsibility of their roles in doing so. However, this did not always match the experiences shared by disabled students.
- 2. Data Coding:** During this phase, I focused on identifying areas that could be relevant to the study and used labels (codes) to describe them and their meaning. These codes looked at the semantic and latent (Braun and Clarke, 2021) meaning of data extracts and covered areas such as *“not appropriate support for disabled postgraduate students”*, *“the importance of perceiving that educators care”*, *“disabled students seen as passive subjects in support provision”*, *“the role of PhD supervisors”*, *“sense of belonging and the impact of the pandemic”* and *“promoting educational choices”*. I used the software NVivo to code the data, and I engaged in training and opportunities within supervision during these initial phases to increase my analytical skills as I became more confident coding and using this software. Due to the large dataset with which I worked, I quickly developed a significant number of codes, some of which were repetitive. The coding process was iterative and organic for me, which meant returning several times to each interview and refining the multiple codes I developed in this phase. Yet, after repeated engagement with these interviews and the code-refining process, I reduced

the number of codes by grouping those that were similar and discarding those that were not relevant to the research focus.

- 3. Generating Initial Themes:** In this phase, I grouped codes that shared a central, unifying idea and were relevant to my research aims and questions. This helped me develop initial candidate themes which illustrated shared patterns across the data. Some of these initial themes were Pedagogies of Care, Online Accessibility, Responsibility, Individualised Support Provision, Wider Support Strategies, The Experience of Postgraduate Students, Flexibility and Choice in Education, Sense of Belonging and Bureaucratic Burden for Support Provision. In this stage, themes were somewhat independent, as although interrelated, I worked on them independently as I had not developed a clear thematic structure yet. Links between some of these themes were clear, such as those that revolved around the difficulties of accessing disability support or pedagogical approaches to enhance the experience and retention of disabled students. Yet, I was still navigating the way in which each of them would fit into the broader narrative of this thesis.
- 4. Theme Development and Review:** Upon further engagement with the data and the existing literature, I refined these initial themes by merging, discarding and splitting them. In addition, I started developing the structure of the stories these themes could tell. This is the point where the split into two thematic areas (Disability Support/Pedagogy) started as participants' separate discussions of these two areas became more apparent. Thus, in this process, it became evident that there were two clear areas of discussion, which would then become the two main thematic areas addressed in chapters 4 and 5 of this study. These two thematic areas were "*Disability Support*" and "*Pedagogy*", and according to the data generated, are the two main educational areas that shape the experience and retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. I decided to make this division once I realised that all themes pertained to either one of these areas, which reflected how participants' interviews also revolved around these two spheres. Although some elements overlapped between these themes, such as the importance of care and responsibility, discussions manifested differently depending on the area(s) on which the participant focused during their interview. For example, Kate's (PhD student) discussion about a lack of care towards the experiences of disabled students focused on access to individualised disability support, while in the case of Felicity (master's student), this discussion focused on the sector's disregard towards disabled students' educational experience. Therefore, I considered that

analysing each of them in their specific context (Disability Support or Pedagogy) would be more effective as this would allow for more detailed, contextualised discussions.

- 5. Theme Refinement:** This phase entailed the further organisation of themes and subthemes and the clarification of the concept addressed by each of them. In accordance with Byrne's (2022) guidance, I aimed to create a clear narrative that reflected the dataset and was relevant to the focus of the study. However, I did not consider these themes to be the final ones, as I intended to revisit them when conducting FPDA. Thus, instead of defining final themes and subthemes, I used this phase to create a classification of themes that was open to being modified in the following phase. A mind map of the resulting thematic framework can be found in Figure 2 (section 3.5.5 of this chapter). NVivo was also used in this and the following phases of the analysis.
- 6. Writing Up:** The writing up phase was a constant throughout the RTA analysis, as the main strategy I used to make sense of the data as themes evolved was to write. Therefore, writing and theme development took place simultaneously, helping me find the narrative link between the themes and subthemes. Thus, this study's findings chapters were first made up of the themes developed throughout this stage, which included my interpretation of them alongside the participant extracts that best illustrated those themes. I worked on this process iteratively, returning to this interpretation and the data extracts to refine my writing. This process was also accompanied by an exploration of the relevant literature, which helped the interpretation process. This way, I supported the initial analysis and interpretation of the data, with existing discussions and theory that helped me contextualise and examine the draft themes and chapters developed in this phase. My engagement with the literature and the development of the data analysis and discussion was also continued while carrying out the FPDA, as explained in the following section. This stage of the data analysis process was carried out using Microsoft Word software, supported by the analysis developed in NVivo.

As discussed above, RTA was suitable to make sense of a large and complex dataset. However, this was only the beginning of the writing process as I revisited and modified these themes and chapters several times to keep expanding the discussion of the findings in relation to existing literature and to conduct FPDA.

3.5.2. Feminist Poststructuralist Discourse Analysis

Once I had used RTA to develop the general structure of the themes that make up these study's findings chapters, I returned to the data and conducted a more critical analysis following the principles of FPDA. This approach is consistent with Aston's (2016) ideas, who acknowledged that discourse analysis is multifaceted and iterative. Having used RTA to identify participants' relevant areas of practice that could help me address the research questions, I used FPDA to identify participants' values, beliefs, subjectivity, agency and existing discourses and power relations within the areas of relevance I had already defined. These elements are crucial for FPS and are significantly influenced by the context in which they occur (Aston, 2016). In line with Ollivier's (2022) approach, and while acknowledging that discourses can occur at individual, social or institutional levels (Aston, 2016) and that power relations are changing but always present (Foucault, 1995), I used this analysis to uncover and examine cultures, discourses and practices, including those that are "*taken for granted*" as well as those that "*challenge the status quo*" (Ollivier, 2022, p. 78). This part of the analysis took place using Microsoft Word and NVivo simultaneously, as it involved working with the codes and expanding the writing done during the RTA phase.

While RTA helped me manage a large dataset by finding shared patterns and commonalities in the data, FPDA allowed me to shine a light on and honour participants' unique experiences (Aston, 2016). Therefore, it offered a deeper level of analysis and understanding, helping me uncover the influence of discourse and power relations on participants' experiences, illustrating how they fulfil or foreclose disabled students' aspirations and shape retention. Inspired by Ollivier (2022), I followed Aston's (2016) guidance to conduct FPDA. While I mostly worked from the themes resulting from the RTA, I frequently returned to the transcripts to enhance the analysis. While Aston's and Ollivier's work focuses on the health and life sciences field, their guidance provides clear steps to conducting FPDA, which have been invaluable in this study's data analysis. The way in which I followed their guidance is described below:

- 1. Recognise Important Issues:** Aston (2016) recommends that this first step focuses on identifying issues that are relevant for participants and relate to the research questions.

Although I had already done something similar with RTA, I revisited the established themes to identify relevant issues and extended this with data from the transcripts. Aston (2016) recommends avoiding coding at first to prevent restricted meanings and the assumption that all participants will have shared experiences. Considering this, I engaged with the themes and data, searching for new meanings and unique experiences. This means that although all themes and subthemes are based on commonalities between participants, some themes focused on participants' distinct experiences as they revealed unique issues. This is the case of Felicity, a master's student who was particularly articulate and analytical about her struggles in HE. While experiences similar to Felicity's were not discussed by many of the other disabled students who collaborated in this study, her words offered a unique perspective on how cultures, discourses, and practices enhance or hinder the experiences of disabled students in HE. This means that in Chapter 5, I often use her quotes to uncover how neoliberalism influences these experiences and how the adoption of care-based pedagogies could help resist this influence. This approach aligned with Aston's (2016, p. 2262) belief that themes must capture similarities while also being "*open*" to identify unique occurrences.

- 2. Apply Beliefs, Values and Practices:** According to Aston (2016), focusing on participants' beliefs and analysing their perspectives helps us deconstruct the issues identified in the previous phase while putting aside our perceptions as researchers. In this context, Aston defined beliefs as participants' articulations that go beyond description and have an element of opinion, meaning these interventions are relevant to discourse analysis (ibid). Values are broader constructions based on participants' perceptions of what matters and why, shaping beliefs and influencing practice (Aston, 2016). This component enables the critical examination of people's actions and inaction based on tensions with the status quo (Aston, 2016; Ollivier, 2022). In the context of this study, this is illustrated by students' different ways of navigating ineffective support provision based on conflicting beliefs and values. For example, Kevin (former undergraduate student) did not complain about the distracting role of his tutor meant to offer exam support while the tutor did not offer the help Kevin needed, he offered friendly company, which Kevin appreciated. I might also interpret that Kevin felt this was the best support he could get and it was better than receiving no support. However, others like Nicole (master's student) decided to search tirelessly for someone who could implement the adjustment she needed but could not access. This resulted from a

tension between what Nicole believed was fair (implementing this accommodation) and her institution's response (no one taking responsibility to do so).

- 3. Identify Social and Institutional Discourses:** After identifying participants' quotes that portray beliefs, values and actions, Aston (2016) indicates that searching for discourses (institutional and social) that illustrate power relations is necessary. This step helps meet FPDA's aim to explore the *"taken for granted and the invisible"* and how *"underlying narratives that dictate how [...] individuals should live their lives are met with overlapping discourses that are multiply sourced and sustained"* (Ollivier, 2022, p. 80). Following up on the previous example, institutional discourses across HE often take a medicalised and minimalistic approach that conveys the belief that disabled students should be grateful for any support they get (see Dolmage, 2017), constructing an image of passive and grateful subjects that should not complain.
- 4. Responses to Power Relations:** This step explores how participants respond to and navigate power relations that result from social and institutional discourses (Aston, 2016). This step emphasises the importance of context to uncover co-existing discourses (Aston, 2016) and how they create experiences and conditions that lead to oppression (Johnstone, 2018, as cited in Ollivier, 2022). Thus, according to Ollivier (2022) each circumstance creates new opportunities for power relations that individuals must navigate; but these same relations of power that shape participant's experiences also make room for change by identifying how these relations affect individuals (ibid). Thus, in line with Aston's guidance (2016), it is essential to identify moments of tension between participants' values and beliefs and what is, for example, expected of them as the result of existing discourses and relations of power. This is reflected in one of the extracts analysed in Chapter 5 as June (undergraduate student) decided to record the oral presentation she was expected to give as part of an assignment. June developed this idea as an alternative in case she struggled to deliver the presentation orally due to mental health struggles, but her actions represented a way of challenging teacher-student power relations. Thus, June found tension in this power relation, as she perceived the assessment guidance to be inaccessible and identified thereby an opportunity for change.
- 5. Agency and Subjectivity:** By exploring experiences like June's shared above, in which participants navigate and negotiate power relations we can observe how participants use agency and subjectivity (Aston, 2016). As discussed in section 3.1., subjectivity is defined by Weedon (1987) as the conscious and unconscious feelings and thoughts of

how individuals position themselves in relation to the world. For Aston (2016), agency is enacted through participants' actions, in line with their values and beliefs, as a response to existing discourses. However, in the PFDA analytical context, agency is not only observed in explicit or complex acts of resistance (Aston, 2016) as, according to Ollivier (2022, p. 83) *“it is important to note that there is no better, more correct, or ‘braver’ way to enact agency”*. This conceptualisation has allowed me to identify how participants used their agency to resist marginalising discourses and practices. These included examples like Colin's (undergraduate student) decision to bring a cushion to class to avoid pain as he could never access adapted furniture. Moreover, agency was also enacted by educators like Helen and Amelia, who kept advocating for hybrid learning options to accommodate more students at their institutions amidst the resistance they faced.

Using these two approaches to qualitative data analysis has given me the tools to analyse a large dataset while adhering to the study's methodological underpinnings and aims. While this was a long process that entailed repeatedly revisiting my writing, I argue that this helped me develop a detailed account of participants' experiences, illustrating how different cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE and how this shapes their retention. Additionally, it is worth noting that the coding, theme development, overall analytical work, and thesis writing experienced a significant delay due to the cyber-attack experienced by the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) in the summer of 2023 (see section 3.6. for more information). Since this incident led to losing the NVivo file I used for coding, theme development, and preliminary analysis processes, I had to repeat these steps, which delayed the writing process significantly. Yet, it allowed for additional engagement with the data and a more thorough analysis.

3.5.3. Thematic framework

The data analysis and writing process described above led me to identify two main thematic areas: the ones on which most of the participants' discussions focused. These two areas are Disability Support and Pedagogy. These two areas guide the organisation of this study's findings, which are divided into two chapters (chapters 4 and 5), one per thematic area. The decision to have two findings chapters is linked to the richness of the data generated in this study. Therefore, having only one findings chapter would have limited my analytical capacity, which meant it was more appropriate to dedicate one chapter per area and explore the relevant data in appropriate depth. These thematic areas are divided into themes and subthemes that illustrate

the most relevant analysis outputs in relation to the study’s research aims and questions. In line with the work of Goegan, Le and Daniels (2023), these themes, subthemes and the way in which they relate to each other are visually represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Mind map of themes and subthemes

More specifically, the first findings chapter explores how disability support provision in HE can either help fulfil or foreclose disabled students' aspirations and retention. This chapter illustrates that an idealised notion of disabled students exists, leading to the marginalisation of those who don't fit this mould, such as postgraduate students, who struggle to access support. Additionally, the chapter discusses a lack of accountability and responsibility across support systems, which hinders adequate support provision. The second findings chapter examines the impact of neoliberal principles across HE in Scotland, which often exclude and harm disabled students. In this landscape, participants discuss the need for care-based cultures and pedagogies that recognise and value the complex human experiences of disabled students. According to participants, this could be implemented by taking an anticipatory approach to inclusive HE, making hybrid learning common practice across the sector and promoting disabled students’ sense of belonging.

3.6. Ethical considerations

Conducting qualitative research using interviews raises many ethical concerns, some of which can be predicted in advance, whereas others cannot (Mason, 2017). Considering this, I elaborated a proposal for ethical review, which was submitted to UWS’ Ethical Committee. This proposal discussed the ethical concerns that can be anticipated in this study (such as confidentiality and anonymity) and the strategies I adopted to address them. This ethics proposal and the research design and implementation adhered to UWS’ principles for good

practice of honesty, rigour, transparency, respect and care, with a focus on respecting human dignity and participant-centred research (University Ethics Committee, 2021).

My proposal was approved by the Ethics Committee in August 2021 via a letter of approval (see [Appendix 1](#)). This letter also contained some suggestions to enhance the ethical nature of my research, which I discussed with my supervisors and addressed as appropriate. For instance, following the Ethics Committee's advice, I conducted in-person interviews in private spaces within public environments such as pre-booked library rooms (see section 3.4.2. for more information).

Therefore, throughout this research project, I strived to adopt and maintain an ethical stance towards participants and the research project. This is reflected in my approach to undertaking qualitative research with disabled people, which is defined by being cautious, flexible and respectful towards participants, their needs and preferences, aiming to do no harm (Leavy, 2017). Moreover, I demonstrated my understanding of the potential risks associated with this research (participants feeling distressed by negative feelings linked to the subject matter) and my approach to minimise them (such as adopting an approachable disposition and encouraging participants to take breaks during interviews).

Additionally, I ensured participants had several opportunities to confirm or refuse their informed consent to participate in this project voluntarily. These opportunities were enabled by my sharing detailed information about the study so that participants could make informed choices regarding their participation in this study. To do so, I elaborated a Participant Information Sheet ([Appendix 3](#)) and a general Consent Form ([Appendix 4](#)), which I then adapted to participants' involvement preferences (for example, email interviews, online interviews, etc.). In line with the guidelines offered by Leavy (2017), these consent forms gave participants the opportunity to consent to their voluntary participation in the study, with an understanding that they could withdraw their participation without needing to provide any reasons.

These forms also addressed different elements of the research process, such as their voluntary involvement in one-on-one interviews, which, if taken place live, via phone, online meeting platforms or face-to-face, would be video or voice recorded. Yet, they also gave participants the opportunity to refuse to have their interviews recorded, in which case I offered the alternative of taking notes during our interviews for data analysis purposes. The consent forms also allowed participants to give or withdraw consent from the anonymous use of extracts from their interviews in the documents derived from this study.

Moreover, before the interviews started and when they finished, I reminded participants that they could choose to withdraw at any point (up to thesis submission) without needing to provide a reason and without negative consequences. Participants were also reminded about the possibility of withdrawing their participation in a follow-up communication, such as the post-interview email I shared containing a debriefing form. Thus, I addressed the Ethics Committee's concern about participants potentially having a fluctuating capacity to provide informed consent (see [Appendix 1](#)) by ensuring participants had repeated opportunities to reassess their willingness to participate in the study. As all participants consistently manifested their disposition to participate in this study, their capacity to consent was assumed.

Furthermore, I took different measures to enhance anonymisation across the research process (Leavy, 2017), which included using pseudonyms to refer to participants and conceal the contextual information they provided. At first, I assigned random pseudonyms to participants, but in later email communication, I asked participants for their preferred pseudonyms. While not all participants responded to this question, I have respected the choice of those who did, using their preferred pseudonyms throughout this manuscript. Moreover, during the data analysis phase, I worked with anonymised transcripts and ensured that original transcripts were kept in password-protected Microsoft Word files within a password-protected UWS laptop.

One potential risk linked to this research was the cyber incident experienced by UWS in the summer of 2023, as some of the institution's data were stolen. Although there is no evidence that the data generated in this study was affected during this incident, the files containing participants' personal data are password-protected, which reduces the likelihood of information being compromised. Another risk is the possibility that the participants' identities are revealed while disseminating the research outcomes, despite anonymisation efforts, because complete anonymity can be nearly impossible to reach (Mason, 2017). I addressed this risk in the participant information sheet and consent form to mitigate it. I also discussed what anonymity implies for participants across the recruitment and interview processes, as it does not mean the same to everyone (Saunders, Kitzinger and Kitzinger, 2015).

Likewise, I aimed to ensure that participants agreed with the treatment that I made of their information, being faithful to their words and portraying an accurate reflection of their experiences. In this regard, participants had the opportunity to let me know if they were interested in receiving updates on the project's progression. Nevertheless, I have not been able to engage in this process as expected due to the impact of the cyberattack that affected UWS in the summer of 2023, which caused the loss of most of the relevant analysis files. This meant

that I had to repeat the coding and theme development processes, as the NVivo file that contained this analysis was lost when my UWS laptop was cleared in the aftermath of the cyber incident.

This difficulty also had an important impact on the development of this study, as the analysis and writing process were significantly delayed. This setback also meant that I could not share individual interview analyses with specific participants due to the limited time available. In the summer of 2024, I contacted participants who chose to be updated about the study's progress to provide a summary of the research findings and discussion (see [Appendix 9](#), which was supported with a recorded narration of these findings and discussion) and used this opportunity to let participants know about these circumstances. I also used this opportunity to reassess participants' interest in this analysis, which entails a coded version of their interviews. I will share this analysis with those still interested after September 2024, when I can finalise this more detailed analysis. Therefore, in line with the work of Saunders, Kitzinger and Kitzinger (2015), I have aimed to maintain an open conversation and negotiation with the participants to ensure that this study's research outputs represent their experiences, values and beliefs.

3.7. Reflexivity

Understanding research as a process instead of a product requires us to pay attention to the role of the researcher in that process, which highlights the importance of reflexivity in research (England, 1994). According to England (England, 1994, p. 242), reflexivity is understood as a critical and analytical introspection regarding "*the self as researcher*", critical to fieldwork and feminist research in the social sciences. Referring to research ethics and reflexivity, Leavy (2017) talks about the importance of identifying the context of discovery in research processes, which refers to what was discovered and how. Thus, Leavy (2017) defines the context of discovery as the researcher's acknowledgement of their role in the research process, which includes accountability and awareness of power in research. Reflexivity in research is about concentrating on how the researcher's role shapes research, which, in qualitative research, relates to "*hierarchy and authority*" (Leavy, 2017, p. 48). Considering these approaches, this section discusses how I considered reflexivity across this research, focusing on issues of power, hierarchies, the influence my identities and experiences had on this research, and how this research has impacted me, addressing my personal journey while conducting this research.

Navigating power relations and hierarchies in the research context

Following the steps of Ollivier (2022), as a feminist researcher focusing on participants' experiences and aiming to challenge hierarchies in the interview process, it was essential to consider and share with participants my positionality in this research process. Throughout this study, my position as researcher has been that of a simultaneous insider and outsider, influencing perceptions of hierarchies and power (Murphy, 2020). Hence, in pre-interview communications, I shared information with participants about the study and my motivation to conduct this research, highlighting my role as a PhD student. Discussions about this role were followed up during the interview process as my identity as a PhD student and researcher positioned me differently depending on participants' standpoints. Thus, although I focused on shifting away from hierarchical interviewer/interviewee relationships to align with the feminist framework (Hesse-Biber and Leavy, 2007; Bryman, 2016) that guides this research, I believe perceptions varied depending on the participant, according to the group they belonged to (staff, undergraduate or postgraduate students).

For example, when interviewing undergraduate students, I noted that some participants viewed me as a sort of expert due to the more advanced level of education I was undertaking. Yet, this fluctuated as this imbalance shifted when interviewing mature undergraduate students, whom I perceived to be more knowledgeable and experienced. Moreover, as a PhD candidate and student myself, many of my experiences overlapped with those of other PhD students whom I interviewed. Still, while engaging with undergraduate or master's students, there was a bigger distance between the interviewer and interviewees, as these overlaps were not as salient.

Although I cannot speak for participants, I did not perceive power imbalances and evident hierarchies while interviewing PhD students, as we could both relate to the nuances of the interview process and the importance of participants' voices. In these cases, participants spoke freely, and there were opportunities for dialogue. Yet, some doubted the appropriate length of their responses, wondering, for example, if I wanted "*the long story or the short one*" (Mark, PhD student). Similarly, some undergraduate students assumed an unequal position between us, in which they thought I was in charge of the stories they could tell. This is something that led participants to comment on how I, as the interviewer, might expect specific responses from them. In these cases, I always clarified that they had control of the information they wanted to share or not share with me and how they wanted to share it. Usually, after this, I felt participants relaxed and were less constricted in their responses, something we both appreciated.

When I interviewed staff, I never felt like I was in a position of power, as although I was the one asking questions, they were expert researchers, educators and disability advisers, and some even had lived experience of disability. Additionally, in many cases, participants had graduated from their PhDs, some quite a few years ago and some in similar topics to the one explored here. Therefore, in these cases, I felt I lacked experience and expertise and saw myself as a student and a curious outsider. Moreover, it was apparent that participants who volunteered to participate in this study were clearly interested in inclusion and supporting disabled students in HE. Therefore, building a positive rapport driven by that curiosity was easy. This was reflected in this group of participants' interest in the project, wanting to read the final findings and mentioning that they enjoyed the interview, which gave them much to think about: "*It's really interesting actually; it's made me really think this interview*" (Morgan, educator). Thus, I adhered to my epistemological framework and ethical approach to research by ensuring the interviews were safe and that interviewees had control over how they wanted to participate in this study. Thus, I believe that power imbalances and hierarchies were modulated, which led to rich discussions and the nuanced data analysis portrayed in chapters 4 and 5.

However, the management of power dynamics in this study has been a complex task, considering how power was negotiated in the different participant groups due to the challenges of navigating power relations in a research context, and how these can lead to potential re-interpretation of participants' words (see Ellsworth, 1989). Thus, as discussed above, I believe that in this specific context, the multiple identities of participants, but also the different elements of my own identities, interacted in varying ways, requiring me to continuously reflect on my assumptions about the power dynamics at play. This means that as a simultaneous insider and outsider, it was often complicated to determine if these assumptions aligned with participants' perceptions. Although participants gave positive feedback during the interviews, manifesting that they found this research relevant and necessary, I might never be certain if their attitudes and the information shared during the interviews were shaped by their understanding of the power relations existing. Despite my efforts to reassure them that they were the experts in this situation and to ensure they had control over how interviews were carried out, they might have still perceived the relationship as unequal. For example, it is unclear if processes such as the fact that I would be analysing and writing about the information they shared during our exchanges were perceived as an element that tilted the power balance in our relationship. Therefore, in line with Ellsworth's (1989) discussion, there cannot be an acceptance that, because a dialogue existed between the participants and me, we reached a

shared understanding of the topics discussed or the nature of the power (im)balance in our relationships.

Thus, while I aimed to interpret the data generated in this study from the perspective of a learner who analysed content provided by experts, the research design did not allow me to discuss this with participants and ensure that our interpretations always aligned. This becomes one of the limitations of the study, which did not have participant input during phases such as the data analysis, hindering my capacity to determine if participants believed I misinterpreted the information they shared with me (see Gibson *et al.*, 2017). Thus, in line with researchers in Gibson *et al.*'s (2018) study, I acknowledge that my own experiences as HE student, educator and researcher could have shaped the data generation process and my interpretation of the data, influenced by my own biases and the power dynamics that arise from my identities as linked to those experiences.

While I would have liked this project to follow a participatory research framework, this was not possible, mainly due to the constraints imposed by the pandemic and post-pandemic context in which this PhD research took place. Although one of the strategies I used to allow participants to give their input regarding this study's results was to share a summary of these findings (see [Appendix 9](#)) and encourage them to provide their feedback, not all participants did so. At first, I thought this was mainly the result of their busy schedules or an active way of choosing how they participated (or did not participate) in this research. Yet, I now wonder if participants felt constricted by the perception they had of the existing power relationship, limiting the feedback they were willing to share.

Hence, this is an example of the potential of using participant-led research approaches to explore the experiences of traditionally marginalised groups, such as disabled students. According to Gibson *et al.* (2017), participatory research in which participants are positioned in an equal position as the researchers, ensuring they play a key role in research design and data analysis, reduces the likelihood of reinterpreting or misinterpreting participants' understandings. Furthermore, positioning participants as co-enquirers in research allows for enhanced critical data analysis (Welikala and Atkin, 2014) and can lead to research that can be applicable to participants' lives, having a positive impact on these (Gibson *et al.*, 2017), which Oliver (2002) considers to be a key tenet of emancipatory disability research. Additionally, working with students as co-enquirers and co-researchers highlights the value of the research process, and not only of research outputs (Hall, 2014; Seale, Nind and Parsons, 2014). Yet, this participatory and participant-centred research process can lead to ambiguity regarding the

roles and expectations of those involved in the research process, which calls for a clear definition and discussion of their boundaries and responsibilities (see Black-Hawkins, 2014; Seale, Nind and Parsons, 2014; Welikala and Atkin, 2014).

Therefore, although not without its difficulties (see MacLeod, Lewis and Robertson, 2014; Gibson *et al.*, 2017), this research approach could have helped me face some of the challenges discussed above, concerning existing power dynamics throughout the research process such as those arising from the interviewers/interviewee roles, leading to a more genuine interpretation and analysis of the data generated. This approach also has the potential to disrupt traditional hierarchies and power relationships in research, particularly when research participants are students from marginalised groups, highlighting the importance of their voices and experiences (Black-Hawkins and Amrhein, 2014; Gibson *et al.*, 2017). This would help address some of the difficulties discussed by Ellsworth (1989) concerning how power dynamics shape whose students' voices are heard or silenced and who interprets them. It could also help move away from pathological and deficit research frameworks that are defined by narrow categorisations and understandings of the student experience (Gibson *et al.*, 2018).

Personal journey

In the current discussion of researcher reflexivity, I believe it is important to address my on personal journey in relation to this study. Considering this, it is important to start by noting that this study is the result of a PhD studentship promoted by UWS Academy, now Learning Transformation at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). When I first saw the advert for this opportunity, I knew my professional and educational experience would make me a suitable candidate to undertake this research because of my background in the fields of disability research and education and my passion for inclusion. Still, I was unaware of how much my personal experiences would be reflected in this study's development and findings. The element that has been most salient to me has been the changes to my health, their influence on my educational experience, and how much this mirrored participants' discussions. For example, shortly after I started working on this research study, I was diagnosed with a rare autoimmune condition called Indolent Systemic Mastocytosis (ISM).

The diagnostic process was lengthy, painful, and filled with confusion and uncertainty, mainly because it occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdowns. Through this process, the pandemic context, ISM's fluctuating symptoms, and other difficulties, I sometimes thought

about abandoning this project. Yet, the care, compassion, understanding and flexibility I have been shown during the past four years, particularly by my supervisors, helped me get to the finish line. My circumstances echoed participants' discussions that reflected on the elements that promote the retention and persistence of disabled students in HE. Although I do not consider myself to be disabled and have not had to request formal accommodations, as, so far, my symptomatology has not had a significant, long-term impact on my daily activities, I wonder if this is precisely the result of the care, compassion and flexibility I have been offered.

Therefore, my connection with this study grew over time in ways I had not anticipated, and so did my passion for the topic of study. Yet, the data analysis process was sometimes overwhelming as I tried to make sense of data with so much personal meaning. Memos, keeping a reflexive journal and discussing my struggles as an insider/outsider in this study helped me navigate participants' stories from an analytical perspective.

This process helped me analyse the data generated, but it also allowed me to further reflect on my own life and educational experiences and gain a deeper understanding of them.

Consequently, it was not that these personal experiences guided the development of this research, but that as it unfolded, I discovered similarities between participants' experiences and my own. This overlap emphasises the value of participants' voices in illustrating HE students' under-represented experiences (Leavy, 2017), shedding light on the diversity of HE students. Moreover, this interlink demonstrates the nuances of these experiences and the need to reflect this in research.

Finally, I believe that this reciprocal process highlights my awareness of the influence of my identities and experiences on the study and how they influenced me. Hence, my experience as a PhD researcher has been marked by reflection, as I often had to reflect on these influences across the different stages of the study and acknowledge how they guided the research process, which was sometimes difficult but also deeply productive. Moreover, through this reflexive process, I have learned how this research has influenced my professional experience as an Associate Lecturer at UWS, a role I undertook shortly after finishing the data generation phase. This means that the study findings have profoundly influenced my educational practice as I am more aware of the diverse experiences of disabled students in HE and strive to be an inclusive, caring and responsive educator. Therefore, being reflexive during this research has allowed me to gain awareness of how my experiences and identity have influenced this research process and my own ways of thinking and working.

Chapter 4:

Disability Support: Hierarchies and Responsibility

According to the data, disability support is one of the main areas that, from an educational point of view, has a significant influence on the experiences of disabled students, fulfilling or foreclosing their aspirations and, potentially, their intentions to persist or leave their HE studies. Hence, in line with this study's epistemological framework (see Chapter 3), this chapter presents a critical analysis of disability support provision in HE in Scotland concerning the experiences of disabled students through the lens of feminist poststructuralism. This analysis helps address the first research question, which aimed to identify how cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland and how this shapes their retention in the sector. This analysis also illustrates different areas of relevance, such as a mismatch between the discourses of disability advisers and the discourses of disabled students and the existence of a shared *idealised* notion of disabled students in HE, assuming they are mostly undergraduate students who have access to medical evidence.

Therefore, this chapter discussed how disability advisers can have a more positive perception of the support provision process than disabled students. More specifically, the discourse of disabled students who participated in this study constructs an image of ableist and complex support processes that can become a source of stress instead of easing their HE journey. Thus, some of the current disability support provision policies and practices in the sector perpetuate the marginalisation of disabled students, hindering their overall educational experiences, foreclosing their aspirations and putting them at higher risk of early exit.

As demonstrated by the data, I argue that these policies and practices are influenced by a shared idealised notion of disabled students in HE, assuming them to be undergraduate students who have access to medical evidence. This idealised notion enables existing ableist cultures and practices and creates hierarchies that put those who do not meet these criteria at higher risk of marginalisation. Thus, disabled students who do not adhere to this idealised notion are not always considered in current inclusion policies and practices as they are not viewed as *ideal* disabled HE students. This means that *non-ideal* disabled students often experience significant, additional difficulties in accessing disability support at their HEIs as they cannot easily comply with the established policies and practices. These circumstances are worsened by ableist discourses and practices that fuel institutional uncaring attitudes and a

lack of perceived responsibility. This often leaves disabled students in a precarious position without educational support and without compassionate responses to help them face the flaws of the system, as compliance with existing policies and practices triumphs over students' needs.

The chapter ends with a discussion of participants' recommendations for improvement when it comes to fostering the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland, directly addressing this study's second research question. Therefore, this chapter addresses this study's research questions as it uncovers how cultures, discourse and practices related to disability support provision fulfil or foreclose disabled students' aspirations, how this shapes their retention in HE in Scotland, and the ways in which stakeholders could bring change to the sector and promote disabled students' retention.

4.1. “Adjustments feel like a real weight off their shoulders”: disability support provision in the promotion of inclusion and retention

According to the Equality Act (2010), Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the UK, including Scotland, have the responsibility and legal duty to provide accommodations to ensure disabled students are not at a disadvantage. These accommodations are also known as reasonable adjustments and range from physical accessibility to inclusive educational practices that promote equality between disabled and non-disabled students (Hector, 2020). According to Terras, Anderson and Grave (2020), accommodations tend to have two functions: to ease access to the educational content or to aid comprehension of this content. Accommodations and adjustments are also included under the umbrella term of support.

The positive role of accessing support on the experience of disabled students in HE has been discussed by previous research (Schreuer and Sachs, 2014; Moriña and Orozco, 2020) as it can play a key role in the progression of disabled students, determining if they stay or leave HE (Newman *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, it is essential that disabled students can access the support they need to progress within a system that is still full of challenges (Moriña, 2017). Yet, accessing them can be a difficult process (Fleming, Oertle and Plotner, 2017; Fossey *et al.*, 2017). This section will provide an overview of the support provision process in Scottish HE and existing discourses, as addressed by disability advisers who participated in this study, to help set the context for disabled students' views as discussed in the rest of the chapter.

In this regard, disability advisers had a mostly positive perception of the processes of accessing and implementing individualised disability support, which were discussed as unproblematic. Thus, although disability advisers recognise difficulties in these processes, in their view, accessing disability support was generally a straightforward process, and disabled students were satisfied with the support provided. Moreover, disability advisers who participated in this study identified a wide range of support practices implemented at their institutions, some maintaining they can offer more than 100 different types of support strategies. Some of the most common adjustments they facilitate include giving access to assistive technology and software or ensuring students can work with readers and scribes. Disability support staff also promote or provide other types of resources, such as study skills, mental health support and employability advice, which can be part of disability-specific programmes or provided according to the individual student's needs. Overall, disability advisers maintain that their role is mainly characterised by taking a proactive and holistic, but individualised approach where disabled students are contacted as soon as possible, ideally at the beginning of their course, or before, if possible. After this, there is a discussion of the student's needs and the adjustments that can be implemented for them.

Participants also talk about the option of having regular follow-ups and mentoring programmes, highlighting that students can contact advisers whenever it is necessary. According to disability advisers, not all students use these follow-up opportunities, but they are all made aware that they can get in touch with the service at any point, generally through a person of contact. Thus, as exemplified by Sarah (disability adviser), students can decide the frequency of contact with the service:

“It's really their choice but if they really want somebody to kind of be looking out for them, so the named adviser would send basically two or three emails a semester saying ‘How are you doing? Do you need any support with such and such?’”

This approach is similar to that discussed in previous research by authors such as Macleod *et al.* (2017) who point out that developing an individualised learning plan covering the students' needs and the relevant adjustments tends to be the main outcome of the initial contact between disabled students and disability support services at HE. According to the description of the disability advisers who participated in this study, maintaining regular and appropriate communication is essential to their approach. This is a positive element to discuss as disabled students can be reluctant to request support due to fear of stigma or frustrations around the support provision process, some wishing they were treated better while requesting adjustments

(Getzel, 2008; Fleming, Plotner and Oertle, 2017). Therefore, building positive relationships during this process is essential to the sustainability of the partnership between disabled students and the disability support offices.

Disability advisers who participated in the study also mentioned that they generally work with a heterogeneous group of disabled students with different needs and diagnoses, such as hearing loss, epilepsy, or dyslexia. In general, disability advisers reported that they received overall positive feedback and perceived that disabled students were satisfied with the support and assistance provided. In this regard, Caitlin (disability adviser) expressed:

"[For] the majority of students, adjustments feel like a real weight off their shoulders. It's a relief to know there's going to be help and support available. Even if it's just a seven-day extension to the coursework, it's amazing how much that feels supportive to students".

This is something that highlights the positive effect of support on the experience of disabled students in HE. For instance, as addressed in Chapter 2, Schreuer and Sachs (2014) concluded that using accommodations positively correlated with different areas of the disabled students' educational journey, such as academic performance, participation in HE experiences, satisfaction and institutional perception.

Additionally, disability advisers in this study point out that although in all cases the support is individualised, some institutions also have disability-specific initiatives targeted at specific groups within the disabled student community. This is the case for autistic students, as some highlight that their departments provide specialised support strategies. In this regard, participants described comprehensive programmes supporting autistic students in different areas, such as providing smooth transitions into HE or promoting social and academic integration.

In this regard, Lois (disability adviser) expanded on her team's approach, which took into consideration previous feedback about the areas that autistic students might find difficult: *"We do sort of an introduction when the campus is quiet. (...) Everything that we've been taught in the past is a bit daunting [for autistic students], we try to sort of ease them into it."* Another disability adviser, Charlotte, mentioned taking a similar approach at her institution, where they focus on the promotion of social integration and avoiding social isolation, barriers that autistic students face in HE. In this regard, Charlotte adds that *"engaging students and social integration really*

early on in the university journey can be really key to their success in staying engaged and feeling part of like the university life”.

The support these institutions offer autistic students also includes promoting effective communication and providing a point of contact to autistic students, which could be particularly effective in supporting their mental health and promoting a proactive approach to tackling difficulties. Therefore, Charlotte hopes that her institution’s work in all these areas promotes the engagement of autistic students, as this type of support is *“integral, really, to their transition into university”*. Although this type of specialist support is available mainly to autistic students at her institution, Charlotte pointed out that, due to its success, it was being extended to other neurodivergent students, like students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). Hence, although this approach is not generalised across HE yet, there seems to be a positive trend of more autistic/neurodivergent-focused initiatives being introduced in the sector. These strategies are consistent with recent research that demonstrates that many autistic and neurodivergent students feel academically prepared to enrol in HE, but they lack social support, experience difficulties with their mental health, come across challenging transitions and face difficulties navigating institutional policies and procedures (Sarrett, 2018; Vincent, 2019; Clouder *et al.*, 2020).

Although it is unclear if these HEIs/disability support units purposively aimed to promote student retention, the strategies discussed above address areas that have been identified to enhance student progression and success. More specifically, as discussed in Chapter 2, key retention researchers such as Tinto (2003; Tinto, 2012) highlight the positive role of social and academic integration. Whereas Tinto’s work focuses on the general body of students, Kutscher and Tuckwiller (2019) agree that these two areas - based on faculty interactions, peer relations, family, and social and off-campus support - also promote the success of disabled students in HE. In addition, the need for planned transitions into HE is also supported by the literature, as it has proven to be a challenging area for disabled students (Madriaga, 2007; Vickerman and Blundell, 2010; Herridge, 2017; Castellano and Rosales, 2021). These strategies have significant potential in promoting retention amongst disabled students in HE due to the importance of effective transitions, which are closely linked to other student outcomes (Madriaga, 2007; Getzel, 2008; Vickerman and Blundell, 2010; Hanna *et al.*, 2014). This emphasises the need for these initiatives to be implemented across HE in Scotland.

Disability advisers involved in this research also discussed the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and the move to online delivery of their practice, which had a positive effect as it

eased attendance and improved the support provision process. More specifically, Caitlin (disability adviser) said:

“Students feel more supported, they're happier because they're not having to travel in (...) for an hour-long appointment, and it's only 15 minutes. So, they can (...) literally phone us from bed. Like they're still in their [pyjamas] and it works for them and around their student life”.

This view supports the findings of the survey conducted by the organisation Disabled Students UK (DSUK; 2022), which set out to evaluate the lessons on accessibility that HEIs could learn from the pandemic, as discussed in the literature review chapter. More specifically, participants in DSUK's survey mentioned that online access to support services was one of the positive practices that promoted increased accessibility. However, there is some contradiction between Caitlin's experience and the research available, as despite eased accessibility, support implementation became more difficult during the pandemic. As addressed in the literature review chapter (see Chapter 2), the findings of some, like Gin *et al.* (2022), illustrate how disabled students could not access effective support during the pandemic and still struggled a year after it started. Hence, considering the previous literature and this study's findings, for some disabled students, access to meetings with disability support services eased with online delivery, yet the implementation of disability support became more difficult.

Additionally, disability advisers who participated in the study also pointed out that one of the main weaknesses of their services is supporting students who contact them at the end of their studies or the academic year. According to Caitlin (disability adviser), at that stage, disability services have little capacity to help students access support, as there is not much time left, and all they can do is help students get extra time for exams or extensions. This help is appreciated by students, *“but there's often a bit of regret that they didn't come to the service a year earlier or two years earlier or right at the beginning of their studies”*. Caitlin also points out that these students might have had a *“really tough time”*, sometimes needing an interruption of studies, but *“if you had been signposted [earlier], you might not have taken an interruption because we could have put in enough support for you”*.

Thus, despite some weaknesses, the picture painted by disability advisers who were involved in this study is that of effective disability support services that take a holistic approach with a focus on building positive relationships with disabled students. This group of participants talked about disability support as a comprehensive process that included making accommodations to ensure effective access to support but also focused on the development of skills that can

support disabled students in their academic journey. Hence, their words and their work reflect a sense of responsibility towards disabled students and their success, where the service concentrates on helping students access the necessary support and accommodations but also promotes student growth and skills development.

However, from a feminist poststructuralist lens, and considering disabled students' narratives as discussed in the rest of the chapter, there is an indication that disabled students are often positioned in a passive role throughout the support process. This is because, according to authors like Dolmage (2017), disabled HE students are often understood as the recipients of accommodations from a series of institutionally predetermined strategies. Hence, while discussions with students about the support they need are common, disabled students' experiences illustrate a lack of meaningful collaboration beyond those predetermined support strategies. Hence, as argued by Rooney (2019) institutional discourses of inclusion do not necessarily lead to "*inclusive experiences*" (p. 45), as I will illustrate in the rest of this chapter.

Furthermore, this chapter will also illustrate how disabled students who cannot access adequate support via disability services are sometimes forced to take an active role in chasing these services to access accommodations. Yet, this puts the onus on the student and is a reminder of the hidden labour of disabled students (Hannam-Swain, 2018; Wertans and Burch, 2022), which I will discuss in the following sections. Therefore, I argue that it is necessary to challenge this binary where disabled students are positioned as passive receivers of support until their needs are not met, which is when they must become active seekers of someone/something that can help. In this regard, I argue that it would be beneficial to contemplate concepts like interdependence in the support provision process, creating enabling environments which consider elements of belonging, inclusion and reciprocity (Naudé, Nel and de Beer, 2024).

Furthermore, the discourse of disability advisers in this study focused on their work with *ideal* disabled HE students, as they mainly talked about their work with undergraduate disabled students who could easily provide medical documentation while there was little discussion of those who could not meet those criteria. Thus, while disability advisers did not refer to an *ideal* disabled student as such, their discussions reflected a specific and somehow narrow understanding of disabled students. This understanding aligns with a shared perception that most/all disabled students are a) undergraduate students and b) students who have access to medical evidence to certify at least one disability, chronic illness or neurodivergence before they enrol in HE. I argue that this narrow conceptualisation positions disabled students who

meet these specific standards as the norm within the sector, meaning that those who do not meet these standards are rarely talked about. Hence, I make my argument based on disability advisers' limited discussion about students who deviate from this norm. Another element that supports this argument is the clash between this *idealised* notion and the narratives of disabled students who participated in this study, most of whom did not meet the characteristics of the *ideal* HE disabled students, experiencing different forms of discrimination, as I will examine in the following sections.

Thus, while disability support services can help disabled students meet their aspirations, existing ableist notions of normalcy across the sector (see Goodall *et al.*, 2023; Dadvand, 2022) foreclose the capacity in which these services can help them thrive in HE. I argue that this issue strengthens the need to acknowledge the varied and diverse experiences of disabled students and the need to take an active role in supporting those who do not meet the ideal disabled HE criteria, as they are facing further levels of discrimination and marginalisation in a sector in which they are already under-represented (see McKinney and Swartz, 2020). This difficulty is also supported by the evidence indicating that the experiences of disabled students who do not meet those characteristics, such as postgraduate disabled students, those who do not have access to medical certification or those who become disabled later in life, have been greatly overlooked in practice and research (see Grimes *et al.*, 2019; McKinney and Swartz, 2020; Melián and Meneses, 2022).

While I want to acknowledge that these considerations are not intended to undervalue the positive role of disability advisers and disability support, they are relevant in this context. This is because, as will be illustrated in the rest of the chapter, disabled students who participated in this study focused on the difficulties they encountered while trying to access disability support, which had a detrimental influence on their well-being, foreclosing their capacity to meet their aspirations, and negatively affecting their retention in HE in Scotland. Therefore, both these areas and issues are illustrated in the following sections, where although the positive role of disability services in an inaccessible sector is recognised, the structural flaws of the system and how they influence disabled students are also addressed.

4.2. “They do help with certain things, but other things never happen”: difficulties related to disability support provision

The evidence shared in this section portrays that disability support can be one of the factors promoting the retention of disabled students. However, this evidence also shows that flaws

related to disability support processes impede disabled students' access to adequate support. Yet, there is an expectation for disabled students to be thankful for any support they get, despite its quality. The complexity of this situation, where disability support is essential for disabled students' success, but also inaccessible, is the focus of this section. Furthermore, this section also addresses how disabled students' perceptions sometimes come in confrontation with those of disability advisers, as shared in the previous section. Considering this, the rest of the chapter will highlight the difficulties experienced by disabled students who collaborated in this study, focusing on different areas of disability support access and implementation, as relevant, such as the impact of needing to provide medical certification or a lack of responsibility around support implementation.

Disability support plays a vital role in the experience of disabled students, but participants in this study also identify recurring difficulties with this process, which impacts the experience of disabled students in Scottish HE, sometimes shaping their intentions to persist or leave the sector. This is reflected in the words of Amelia (educator): *"I think it's quite rare for somebody to leave just because they can't do it. I think it's because they don't get the support they need to do it"*. Thus, accessing disability support is still essential for disabled students who face countless barriers in an inaccessible educational sector. Hence, whilst disabled students discussed several problems with disability support provision, they also identified important benefits.

One case where disability support had a clear positive impact on disabled students' retention is that of June (undergraduate student), who was referred to disability support services after experiencing mental health struggles. Although June had a previous history of mental health difficulties and other physical health conditions, she only learned that she could access support at her university after sharing her struggles with her programme leader, who told her about disability support. This meant June could access vital support to continue her studies as someone who had considered leaving her degree on repeated occasions. Thus, before accessing disability support, June's intentions were to leave her degree, something she shared with her programme leader:

"So, I just sent him an email and said 'I'm done'; because I've done it a few times: 'I'm done. I can't do this. I don't get it; really, really, difficult. And the lecturers and the classes are rubbish'. (...) If I even check my emails, I've probably got about 30 emails saying 'I'm done'. And this has been going on since first year".

However, June points out that this changed when she got in touch with disability services: *"It's actually the best thing that's happened because I've not threatened to quit since because there*

is more support than was there before". June could not promise she would not think about leaving her degree again in the future, and during our second interview she mentioned that she might take a year off, but the positive effect was undeniable. Thus, learning about disability services was a remarkably positive experience for June, because they gave her *"all the tools to continue. (...) I never knew that existed. It wasn't until I had the actual breakdown that I found out. And it's been great; It's made a total difference"*.

However, although it had a positive outcome, June's experience highlights a recurring issue in the support provision process: difficulties in finding information about disability support. This theme was recurrent in Rooney's (2019) work, as participants were confused about how to access disability support, some not learning about it until they failed one or more modules. Similar to what happened to June, participants in Rooney's study learned about these services via academic staff but also highlighted ambiguities about the information shared by HEIs, which can become a barrier to accessing disability support. Hence, Rooney emphasises the need to increase awareness and educate staff about these services and offer continuous information about the support available. This means disability support services could take a more proactive approach, *"not just leaving it for the students to stumble around to try and find"* (Rooney, 2019, p. 41). Thus, as addressed in chapters 1 and 2, although great progress has been made around support provision, it remains a complex realm (Smith, Woodhead and Chin-Newman, 2021).

The case of June shared above offers a clear illustration of the positive impact of disability support on disabled students' retention, and it also shows how constructive student-lecturer relationships can help overcome barriers such as a lack of information about disability support (Schreuer and Sachs, 2014; Farr-Wharton *et al.*, 2018; Lopez-Gavira, Moriña and Morgado, 2019; Moriña and Orozco, 2020; Newman *et al.*, 2021). This is a reminder of the importance of supportive and disability-aware faculty, who can refer students to the right services before it is too late. Yet, as Moriña and Cotán Fernandez (2017) highlight, this is sometimes the result of goodwill and personal interest. Thus, a collaborative approach including disability services, students, and teaching staff seems essential to identify the needs students have and the best way to address them (Claiborne *et al.*, 2011; Fossey *et al.*, 2015), meaning that the support and information offered by faculty are not the result of goodwill but of a widespread understanding of disabled students' needs and the support available.

Despite the positive impact of disability support, difficulties experienced by disabled students who participated in this study sometimes seemed to weigh more than the positives. This is reflected in various experiences and in the predominant discourse as they talked about

inaccessible, inefficient, complex and rigid services, which can become a source of stress in themselves (Atkins, 2016). The experiences shared by participants that help support this claim are varied. For instance, Kevin (former undergraduate student) received academic skills and exam support from tutors, which, although beneficial at first, ended up being detrimental to his academic performance:

“I kind of enjoyed [the tutors] for a time in the beginning but mostly it was like friendly conversation, (...) I think maybe part of the idea was that it was meant to be to help [me] socialise, (...) [but] over time the [tutors] seemed to become more of a liability than an actual help”.

Yet, Kevin never complained because these friendly interactions were a positive reward. Additionally, June and Colin (undergraduate students) never had access to the adapted furniture that was supposed to be provided to them, as agreed with disability support services. Moreover, Nicole (master’s student) had to chase different services for a great part of her programme to request one of the accommodations in her support plan, but never received a response. Furthermore, Kate (PhD student) was left without support for more than 16 months while her Disabled Students Allowance (DSA) was being processed.

Broadly speaking, these struggles were the result of the current medicalised and legalistic approach taken by HEIs, which places the focus on legal compliance rather than on students' needs, implementing the minimum legally required accommodations to avoid being sued (Dolmage, 2017). Moreover, legislation that equates inclusion to the idea of reasonable adjustments leads to an understanding of access as an issue of legal compliance (ibid). This puts disabled students in a position where educators and administrators who are under legal pressure decide which accommodations, from the institutionally approved catalogue, can be implemented (Dolmage, 2017). This approach and the practices and discourses linked to it create a system of oppression defined by Dolmage as *academic ableism*, leading to oppressive and exclusionary practices, where HE is still seen as “*a place to sort society based on the education of the ‘deserving’ few, rather than as the place to elevate society based on the education of all of its citizens*” (2017, p. 62). When looking more closely into the evidence generated in this study, the creation of categories and hierarchies within disabled students (for example, students who have access to medical certification) is one of the ways in which this oppressive system is enacted. Moreover, a lack of responsibility and ethics of care taken by different stakeholders is also a consequence of discourses and practices that put the focus on

compliance rather than on students' needs. In the rest of the chapter, I turn to address these constructs and their role in disabled students' educational experiences and retention.

4.2.1. Hierarchies

According to the data generated in this study, disabled students in Scottish HE confront significant hierarchies that are not always obvious but that shape their educational journeys, putting them at higher risk of exclusion. This section focuses on the two most salient hierarchies discussed by participants and the effect they have on the experience of disabled students in Scottish HE concerning their retention. These two hierarchies, as expressed by participants, depend, first, on the capacity to provide medical certification about one's disabilities or chronic illnesses and, second, on whether or not one is an undergraduate student. The section is divided into two subsections addressing each of these two hierarchies.

4.2.1.1. "Disability services can't do anything for you without a formal diagnosis": hierarchies based on access to medical certification.

According to participants, providing medical evidence is central in the first contact between disabled students and support services. As discussed by Lois (disability adviser), ways of providing evidence of disability include a *"school report or an educational psychologist or a GP letter. So, depending on the disability, really"*. However, there is evidence pointing out the negative effects of this requirement, which could cause emotional difficulties and make disabled students feel illegitimate (Mullins and Preyde, 2013; Coughlan and Lister, 2018). Still, according to the words of disabled students who participated in this study, providing medical evidence is often a strict prerequisite to requesting and accessing disability support. For authors like Dolmage (2017) or Tobias (2023) these procedures are the result of a medicalised, legalistic and deficit-based approach guided by the medical model of disability. This means that only students who can provide medical evidence of a physical, cognitive, or mental health condition can request specialist support and receive accommodations. As addressed above, Dolmage (2017) argues that this approach could be linked to treating disability and disabled students *"in a legalistic, minimalistic manner designed to avoid getting sued"* (p. 27).

Moreover, evidence generated in this study suggests that this medicalised and legalistic approach identified by Dolmage (2017) creates two opposite binaries among disabled students, as those who have access to medical certification when entering HE are positioned higher in an apparent hierarchy. This means they are shown more positive attitudes and have easier access to support than those who do not have access to medical evidence. Considering current

discourses and practices discussed by participants, having access to medical certification when commencing HE is one of the features of the *ideal* disabled student conceptualised across the sector. It must be acknowledged that while this might be the most common group of students who contact these services, the expectation that all disabled students who request support will have access to medical evidence puts those without diagnoses at higher risk of exclusion and attrition.

This hierarchy is illustrated across the different evidence provided by disabled students who participated in this study. For instance, for some students, accessing medical certification seemed easy and straightforward, only referring briefly to this phase. For example, June (undergraduate student) said: *"I had to get a letter from the doctor and all that kind of stuff"*. Others, like Joe and Henry (undergraduate students), did not even refer to this phase of the support provision process, as they were able to quickly provide medical certification due to having received recent diagnoses or support in previous educational levels. Although a causal relationship cannot be established, it must be noted that most participants who could access and provide this type of documentation made an overall positive evaluation of the role of disability support offices and of their academic experience.

Yet, others like Lauren (former undergraduate student), who was unaware of her disabilities while attending HE, and did not have access to any supporting documentation, had a more problematic time. More specifically, Lauren's educational experience was permeated by personal and health difficulties, which meant she faced continuous struggles, having to leave some of the courses she started before completion. Whereas Lauren points out that she was usually met with the sympathy and understanding of lecturers who *"seemed to respond intuitively"* to her needs, she also faced negative attitudes as some staff members were *"judgemental, dismissive"* and disliked her.

Looking back, Lauren wishes that someone had noticed her difficulties and had signposted her to professionals who could offer extra help. As Lauren points out:

"Not all students are aware they have a disability, and those that do won't always disclose this for fear of rejection or retribution. (...) Had I had appropriate support in place, (...) I may have been able to cope better".

Lauren's feelings resonate with Cage and Howes's (2020) findings, who, as addressed in the literature review chapter (Chapter 2), described how autistic participants in their study wondered what would have their HE experiences been like if they had known they were autistic.

Like Lauren, participants in this study felt this would have helped them understand why they struggled and allowed them to access support (ibid).

Hence, having medical certification as a prerequisite can be problematic as it ultimately leaves certain disabled students without support and at risk of attrition and educational exclusion. This prerequisite also ignores difficulties linked to accessing medical diagnoses, which, as reported by DSUK (2022), can be a complex and slow process. Thus, students who struggle but do not have a diagnosis or do not want to share it, cannot access support, preventing them from accessing specialist services (Redpath *et al.*, 2013; Thompson-Ebanks, 2014; Fossey *et al.*, 2015; Newman *et al.*, 2021).

Another example is shared by one participant in Bones and Ellison's study (2022) who avoided seeing medical professionals due to the trauma associated with repeated assessments and tests. This meant that they could not obtain medical certification to access disability accommodations at their university in the US. Hence, these examples illustrate that the prerequisite of providing medical evidence to access disability support positions those like Lauren and potentially many more, lower in a hierarchy that already reflects the ableist notions of HE.

Thus, this prerequisite is part of rigid support provision processes that prioritise compliance over human needs (Brown and Leigh, 2018), even when students who do not have access to medical certification are at immediate risk of withdrawal. This is the case of Tiffany (PhD student), who tried to access support while facing severe struggles during her PhD. However, Tiffany had not received any diagnosis at the time, which meant she could not get any help. These circumstances encouraged her to start an assessment and evaluation process that led to different diagnoses, including autism. Tiffany's experience exemplifies the difficulties faced by females on the autism spectrum who are less likely to receive a diagnosis or do so much later than males (see Zener, 2019; Estrin *et al.*, 2021). Thus, while Tiffany felt that having access to medical certification was positive in her academic journey, her experience is a clear demonstration of how current disability support models do not always lead to the effective inclusion of disabled students (Atkins, 2016; Rooney, 2019), and might offer little help to those at risk of attrition:

"It has been invaluable being able to show people that piece of paper and say, 'Well, actually, this is why I'm having difficulties'. Unfortunately, (...) disability services can't do anything for you without a formal diagnosis. So even if you say to them, 'I'm struggling with all of these things, and I'm going to quit', you're not going to get that support".

Therefore, medicalised approaches to support provision are still dominant across HE in Scotland. Yet, this approach aligns with accommodation discourses that focus on policy compliance, only providing support that is acceptable according to these policies' requirements while dismissing human and individual needs (Dolmage, 2017). This approach lacks the flexibility needed to work with diverse students and leads to the implementation of accommodations that tend to be the minimum legally required, shaping the educational experiences of disabled people: *“that’s a difficult way to learn, and a difficult way to live”* (Dolmage, 2017, p. 27).

Moreover, Tiffany’s words highlight the negative experiences related to disability certification and disclosure (see Kendall, 2016; Pearson and Boskovich, 2019; Bones and Ellison, 2022). Hence, I argue that Tiffany’s remarks emphasise the need to eliminate disability disclosure as a requirement to access inclusive education. Her experience also evidences the need for trauma-informed policies and practices across HE to avoid re-traumatisation and to provide effective provision for (disabled) students who might have lived experiences of medical trauma (McChesney, 2022). Considering this, McChesney (2022) advocates for the use of trauma-informed approaches through the lens of Universal Design for Learning (UDL).

The features that make McChesney argue this are, first, the anticipatory approach of UDL, which focuses on foreseeing the potential needs of students and responding to them by offering alternative modes of expression, engagement, and representation (Capp, 2017; CAST, 2018). In relation to trauma-informed approaches, McChesney (2022) calls for the recognition of the prevalence of trauma, particularly amongst disabled people, and the need to develop practices that avoid discrimination and (re)traumatisation (see Scottish Government, 2023 for more information about the implementation of trauma-informed approaches across different system and workforces). Thus, the application of trauma-informed approaches through the lens of UDL involves the implementation of regular practices (not one-time strategies) that are safe and supportive for those with experiences of trauma in HE (McChesney, 2022).

Another participant whose experience illustrates the hierarchies created by current approaches to support provision is Kate (PhD student). Kate has lived most of her life with a particular health condition that was diagnosed more than 20 years ago. Since Kate had to relocate to do her PhD, she experienced significant delays in accessing updated medical evidence that could corroborate the needs she has had for more than 20 years, which took particularly long as it happened during the COVID-19 lockdowns. This caused *“massive frustration”* and confusion because Kate felt her credibility was taken away and put into the hands of a General Practitioner

(GP) she had never met before to “*verify, you know, I've lived with [this condition] for like about 22, 23 years...*”. While Kate understands that “*these systems have to be in place*”, she also identifies the reason why they exist: “*People can't just make stuff up*”. Further into her analysis, Kate identifies the underlying discourse that guides this practice:

"No one's saying 'Look, you are a liar, so you have to go and get this form signed so that we'll believe you', but that's essentially the reason why. Because if my word were sufficient, we wouldn't be in this position".

Hence, Kate’s experience reflects an existing HE culture of mistrust towards disabled people (DSUK, 2022), a narrative that positions disabled students as liars, who, as Dolmage (2017) elaborates, are seen to be “*faking it, jumping a queue, or asking for an advantage*”. This discourse creates various hierarchies and power dynamics. The first one determines who is more worthy of accessing support (those who have access to medical certification), but also who is more trustworthy, as medical professionals who might not know the student are positioned as more credible. Authors like Podlucká (2020) have argued that HEIs often focus on implementing the law when it comes to implementing support for disabled students, something that, according to Dolmage (2017), is aimed at avoiding getting sued. While that could explain Scottish HEIs’ focus on requesting medical evidence from disabled students, DSUK (2023) highlighted that the Equality Act (2010) does not list it as a requirement to access disability support. Hence, the rationale behind this prerequisite could be a shared misinterpretation of the current legislation. Thus, I argue that the culture and underlying discourses of mistrust perpetuate discriminatory practices and policies that create pervasive hierarchies and prevent many disabled students from accessing support in HE, leading to what should be supportive practices to fail.

4.2.1.2. “Does this count for me? Because I am a postgraduate”: hierarchies based on level of study.

A second hierarchy identified in participants' discourses is between undergraduate and postgraduate students, as the former are also positioned higher in the hierarchy to access disability support since they are seen as the norm and ideal users of disability support services. However, this neglects the experiences of many disabled students, often dismissing the needs and struggles of disabled postgraduate students, who, against shared beliefs, still need and seek disability support (Farrar, 2006). This section explores how this hierarchy shapes the academic journey of postgraduate disabled students (master’s and PhD) who experience

discrimination due to not being perceived as *ideal* disabled students, helping shed light on a severely under-researched area.

Support provision for master's students: a race against time

Only three students whose most recent HE experience was their master's degree (two were enrolled at the time of interviews and a recent graduate) participated in this study. However, their words illustrate the hierarchy between undergraduate and master's students and have great value in the current discussion, particularly considering that research exploring the experiences of disabled master's students is scarce.

More specifically, Nicole (master's student) discussed at length her efforts to have one of the accommodations in her support plan implemented. These efforts entailed months of searching for someone to implement the accommodation or to explain why it was not possible. Nicole's experience exemplifies the additional labour (Hannam-Swain, 2018) that disabled students take on to have their needs met amidst support processes that can be slow and complex. It also illustrates one factor that is not often considered in existing research, which is that disabled master's students have less time to address these difficulties due to the shorter duration of their programmes, compared to undergraduate and PhD students whose courses last for three or four years. For instance, although Nicole's programme was only one year, she was involved in a months-long discussion to get the accommodation implemented. This is not something every disabled master's student might be able to endure, particularly if it takes place during most of their degree. Yet, according to Nicole, disability support services do not always recognise that waiting times like this can negatively affect disabled master's students. Thus, Nicole believes that the complexity and length of this process may discourage master's students from seeking support:

“[Disabled master's students] go to this disability department, and [the service] provide[s] them with absolutely nothing, no help whatsoever. (...) They're only here for a year, so, it's like 'Why bother?' (...) 'Why should I put myself out there and keep having to chase things up and keep having to contact [disability services] for the bare minimum and not get that much out of it?’”

Nicole's story is consistent with the evidence discussed by organisations like DSUK (2022), as disabled students who participated in their survey also experienced delays in support provision and needed to chase disability services repeatedly to access support. Similarly, Coughlan and Lister (2018) point out that disabled students tend to face a higher administrative burden than

non-disabled students and that disability-related processes are the most challenging, particularly if external organisations are involved. These difficulties could lead to increased stress, reduced mental health, and worsened disability-related symptoms (ibid). Still, something that was not considered by Coughlan and Lister (2018) or other research reviewed was the effect of these issues on students spending a shorter amount of time in HE, such as master's students.

Another experience that raises questions about hierarchies in support provision for disabled master's students is that of Nina, who was interested in booking her university's accessible accommodation. However, Nina was told undergraduate students had priority in booking this type of accommodation: *"If I had planned to live in their accommodation but an [undergraduate student] had decided to go there last minute, I would have lost the accommodation"*. Nina does not mention the reasons why undergraduate students had priority, but this is another reminder of how disabled master's students are often overlooked, being an afterthought and facing exclusionary practices.

Hence, Nina and Nicole's experiences illustrate how disabled master's students can be involved in a race against time to access (effective) disability support within the duration of their programmes, which gives them fewer opportunities to negotiate and access adjustments. While this time limitation could be considered a reason to give master's students priority in support provision, current discourses and practices create a paradox where what happens is exactly the opposite and disabled master's students experience additional discrimination as their opportunities to access support decrease.

Support provision for PhD students: navigating the unknown

Participants in this study had a shared belief that disabled PhD students were not effectively accommodated in HE in Scotland as there is reduced awareness about the support available for this group of students. Furthermore, there is a narrative supporting that disabled PhD students do not need support, either because they are aware of their needs and have developed coping strategies during their previous years in HE or because, if they made it to PhD level, they do not need support. While this area has not been researched in depth, these beliefs were recognised by Farrar (2006), who acknowledges that these narratives dismiss the complexity of the experience of disabled PhD students. Yet, as this chapter demonstrates, disabled PhD students have support needs due to the differences between a doctoral degree and other educational programmes and because they are involved in an ableist system that creates numerous barriers, as discussed above.

Furthermore, discourses that do not acknowledge that disabled PhD students have educational support needs, dismiss the existence of students who become disabled later in life, positioning them in opposition to the *idealised* disabled student who enters HE with access to medical certification. This was the case for Stella, a PhD student who became disabled at the end of her undergraduate degree. At the start of her PhD, Stella's health started "*inhibiting*" her studies, and she was left confused as the routes to access support "*weren't completely obvious*" as all resources were catered towards undergraduate students. Stella managed to get valuable help from her institution after taking the initiative to contact disability services. However, she did this hesitantly, wondering, "*Does this count for me? Because I'm a postgraduate*".

Although being a postgraduate student was at the centre of Stella's concerns regarding who could access disability support, the fact that she acquired her symptoms while already in HE increased this confusion, as people in similar circumstances were also underrepresented in the information she could access about disability support. Stella's experience highlights the difficulties of students with newly acquired disabilities as they try to understand how their condition relates to their education. It also illustrates that not all disabled students would be familiar with their support needs when they approach disability services as some might still be adjusting to the impact of their health conditions or impairments: "*I think it's difficult to, like, explain to somebody what's going on and how you need more support when you, yourself, it's all new to you*".

Thus, unclear information and a lack of awareness are still a persistent barrier for disabled PhD students (Redpath *et al.*, 2013; Lane, 2017) who might not be aware of the resources available to them. Moreover, Stella's experience illustrates the importance of acknowledging the diverse and dynamic experiences of disabled students, including those with newly acquired conditions, something that is rarely addressed in the literature. This lack of evidence is addressed by McKinney and Swartz (2020), who studied the experiences of HE students with congenital and acquired disabilities in South Africa. These authors found that some HE students with recently acquired disabilities struggle to accept their new diagnoses and symptomatology, which can be traumatic, impacting their retention and resilience in HE. These circumstances also shaped their confidence to request support and enrol in their preferred area of study (*ibid*). Hence, while these students might represent a smaller number within the disabled student community, it is necessary to acknowledge their circumstances, and the support disability services could provide to a group that is underrepresented and marginalised in multiple ways.

Nevertheless, even when disabled PhD students are aware of disability services, they are not always able to access adequate support (Spier and Natalier, 2023), since, according to participants in this study (disability advisers, current PhD students, and lecturers who were former PhD students), many disability support services are not equipped with the tools to support doctoral students. For instance, Morgan, a lecturer and early career researcher diagnosed with a learning disability during her PhD, addressed this. During her PhD, Morgan reached out to the disability support services at her institution and was told that they had *“never worked with a PhD student before”*. Although Morgan managed to get high-quality support via the service in the end, she acknowledged that *“master’s and PhD students get offered the same as undergraduate students; (...) a pre-predicted menu of things”*. This is supported by Richard, a current PhD student, who mentioned that *“all of the systems that are in place, it’s always very catered for the undergraduate population”*. According to Richard, this meant disability support services *“had to shoehorn in what I needed into an undergraduate formula”*.

Hence, a more tailored approach is necessary to support disabled PhD students. Still, this is far from what has been available to participants in this study. For example, Tiffany faced significant difficulties during her PhD, prompting her to contact an academic skills adviser at her institution to help her manage the open-ended nature of the degree. Yet, the support she received was very *“cursory”, “superficial”* and not relevant to her struggles. This caused some tension and confusion for Tiffany, who believes that there is a misconception about the support needs of disabled students as at PhD level: *“I don’t know if this is because I’m at PhD level and people just sort of think ‘Well, you’re doing a PhD, it can’t be that bad. Like, just get on with it. Like, what’s the problem?’”*

This ties in with Farrar’s (2006) argument which highlighted that there is often a shared perception about disabled postgraduate students not needing support due to two main misconceptions. In the first place, Farrar argued that disabled postgraduate students are expected to have learnt how to manage their needs in previous levels of education. Secondly, Farrar maintained that if a disabled person reached doctoral education, there was a shared perception that it was because their needs were not significant (ibid). Still, as is reflected in Tiffany’s experience, a PhD can present a series of unexpected challenges, exacerbating the needs of disabled students. Or, as in the case of Stella, disabilities can be acquired while already being in HE. Yet, existing misconceptions and hierarchies and the resulting lack of attention given to this group of students, could be leading to a lack of confidence and ability among support services to provide the tailored support they need. This is something perceived

by Tiffany, who believed the academic skills adviser “*was quite happy to get rid of me*” once the support provision ended.

Moreover, the (limited) available literature portrays similar challenges as disabled PhD students are not particularly satisfied with the resources offered to them. For instance, data shared by Neves (2022) in the ‘Postgraduate Research Experience Survey 2022: Sector Results Report’ (PRES) point out that disabled postgraduate research students (PGRs) in the UK are overall less satisfied than their non-disabled peers and are more likely to experience difficulties accessing health and well-being support. Moreover, Neves (2022) reports that although the overall levels of satisfaction increased for the general sample of the survey, that of disabled students declined compared to previous years, creating a 14% gap between the two groups in 2022. More specifically, in 2022, 83% of the general sample was satisfied with their HE experience (82% in 2020 and 81% in 2021), while 72% of disabled students in 2020 and 69% in 2022 reported being satisfied. The areas in which disabled PGRs are less satisfied refer to “*My institution values and responds to feedback from PGR students*” (48% versus 64% of the general sample); “*I have access to a range of seminars in my research area*” (55% versus 66% of the general sample), and “*The support for my health and well-being meets my needs*” (56% versus 68% of the general sample) (ibid).

In line with Neves’ findings (2022), disability advisers involved in the current study also acknowledged that one of the weaknesses of their services is the support they can offer PhD students. More specifically, Caitlin (disability adviser), believes that the adjustments offered to this group of students “*are minimal and not overly helpful*”, mostly revolving around thesis writing, which dismisses the complexities of the doctoral process. The circumstances of disabled PhDs become increasingly difficult due to their blurred status as, although still considered students, PhD candidates often take the role of staff members, teaching, tutoring, and marking. Therefore, according to Caitlin, sometimes the support that a PhD student can access is closer to “*Access to Work or work-based adjustments rather than disability-based adjustments*”. While this study focuses on the experience of disabled students, it is worth noting that HE is also a difficult terrain to navigate for disabled staff, who constantly face ableism and marginalisation (Brown and Leigh, 2018). Hence, disabled PhDs taking these simultaneous roles experience increased levels of discrimination, impacted by ableist practices that are targeted at students and staff.

As noted by Spier and Natalier (2023, p. 1369), accommodations are often “*unavailable, ineffective or irrelevant*” for PhD students, who, as a result, must make adjustments to navigate

ableist environments while working on their doctorates. In these circumstances, the role of supportive PhD supervisory teams is crucial in navigating this unknown territory, as although not necessarily disabled, they have travelled the PhD path before and can provide guidance. One example is Mark's experience, who felt starting a PhD was intimidating, but having a supportive supervisor eased these feelings. In this regard, Mark believes his supervisor understands him, *"is open to new solutions"* that promote accessibility and offers support *"in terms of research, but also (...) he understands my disability, and his expectations (...) are realistic"*. This is also the case of Kate, who has experienced countless challenges related to the support provision process. However, Kate's supervisory team is *"supportive and helpful"*, provides reassurance and proactively helps her navigate the different stages of the PhD while managing her health needs. Kate's supervisors also advocate for her amidst a complex support provision process, helping her navigate unknown territory: *"My supervisor is going to attend my needs assessment because my supervisor is concerned that I'm not getting the support that I need"*. For Kate, the positive work environment and supportive supervisory team were key elements that encouraged her to pursue her PhD.

Therefore, positive supervisory relationships are essential to compensate for the inconsistencies and *"cracks in other parts of the support system"* (DSUK, 2023, p. 85). Although participants in this study did not discuss negative supervisory relationships, it is worth noting that the opposite – supervisors with ableist attitudes – could damage the success and progression of disabled PhD students (Vergunst and Swartz, 2022; DSUK, 2023; Spier and Natalier, 2023). Moreover, although the positive impact of PhD supervisors is illustrated in these experiences, the fact that they are sometimes the only, or the main, point of contact and support for disabled PhD students means that if supervisors are not available, this group of students is at higher risk of facing difficulties. This is the case of Tiffany, whose supervisor was on leave for a long period, which left her with limited resources for guidance and support. As a result, Tiffany faced serious challenges and struggled to find someone who could help, making her wonder, *"How did I fall through the cracks so badly?"* Tiffany's words illustrate the precarity experienced by disabled PhD students, which stems from depending on one person's (or very few people's) grace to access research and education (DSUK, 2023).

DSUK (2023) reports that disability services that cannot effectively respond to the needs of disabled PhD students and supervisors who might not have enough knowledge of disability also fuel this precarity. Hence, the organisation calls for safeguarding systems that oversee the doctoral process to ensure disabled PhD students have someone to turn to when supervisory support is not effective or available (ibid). Thus, the evidence provided in this subsection calls

for a recognition of the needs of disabled PhD students who face ableist cultures and practices. Moreover, I argue that this evidence could be used to boost more profound changes in the doctoral process, which would address relational aspects of education and student needs. These changes could also challenge existing structures towards more collaborative and inclusive approaches, where the PhD student experience does not only depend on a reduced number of people.

Along similar lines, some, like Gravett (2021) and McChesney (2022), acknowledge an increasing interest in changing a system that has long reproduced hierarchies, power imbalances and neoliberal ideas of performativity and productivity, which are not accessible to all in the increasingly diverse doctoral student community. Gravett (2021) also discusses how different approaches to the doctoral process, including the PhD by publication route, create more room for diverse and non-hierarchical collaboration. Others like McChesney (2022, p. 6) argue that trauma-informed doctoral supervision could help “*stretch boundaries*” and help build “*truly inclusive and person-centred*” supervisory practices. Although research into the implementation of these approaches is still emergent, these types of alternatives could help build research cultures that consider doctoral students as whole human beings with complex experiences and value their well-being (ibid), something that can reduce the precarious circumstances often experienced by disabled PhD candidates.

Therefore, this study illustrates the need to challenge current narratives and acknowledge the precarity of disabled PhD students. This group of students are not only entering an unknown, complex and demanding level of education and research but is doing so in discriminatory educational systems that do not recognise their needs and place them low in the hierarchy of those who deserve support. Yet, their needs and how to face them are unclear or unknown to stakeholders in the support provision process. As a result, the role of supervisors is essential to help PhD students navigate this unknown territory. Nevertheless, wider networks of support and collaboration are recommended because if supervisors are the only point of support, disabled PhD students are put again in a precarious position.

4.2.2. Responsibility

Although existing professional discourses construct the disability support provision process as straightforward, the experiences of disabled students are more complex, as the evidence shared here illustrates. Some complexities are related to not having access to medical evidence as a prerequisite to requesting support, as seen in the previous section. However, disabled

students also come across difficulties related to support implementation, which arise even when the support has been agreed upon. That is the focus of this subsection, which explores the barriers that delay or affect support implementation resulting from a lack of responsibility from different stakeholders in the disability support provision process. This section also addresses how disabled students often face a lack of care and compassion while navigating these difficulties, often left without support and without the emotional understanding they would appreciate in such circumstances. This evidence demonstrates that, paradoxically, and in line with the findings of others like Tinklin and Hall (1999) and Atkins (2016), initiatives thought to promote inclusion often become discriminatory, illustrating a recurring issue in this chapter as policy compliance is favoured over students' needs.

***“They do help with certain things, but other things never happen”*: difficulties related to support implementation**

Undergraduate students involved in this study point out variabilities in support implementation as they cannot always access the accommodations that had already been discussed. The reasons why this happens were unclear, but a lack of responsibility and accountability regarding support implementation was commonly discussed. This section addresses how this lack of responsibility and accountability shaped the experiences of disabled students in this study, who struggled to access support considered essential for their retention.

One experience that illustrates this issue is that of Colin (undergraduate student), who, referring to disability support services, said: *“They do help with certain things, but other things never happen”*. More specifically, Colin needed an adapted chair to prevent pain but never got access to it. Instead, he had to take a cushion to class to try to ease the pain, because *“at the end of the three hours, I could hardly walk”*. Yet, Colin never knew who should have been responsible for providing the adapted chair. Additionally, June (undergraduate student) had to repeatedly remind her lecturers that she needed longer class breaks to go for a walk to help ease physical pain, as despite being contacted about June's needs, some were not aware of this accommodation. However, June was confident about her circumstances and outspokenly reminded the teaching staff about her needs as necessary. Yet, her experience highlights another gap in the support provision process, as not all educators are aware of disabled students' adjustments and needs, which becomes even more complex in large cohorts (Kendall, 2016). Once again, the onus is put on disabled students to access adjustments. However, this approach is not suitable for all disabled students because, as Colin points out,

“you're basically singling yourself out there. And most disabled people don't want to be singled out. And we'd rather put up with the pain then”.

As discussed in the literature review (see Chapter 2) similar difficulties have been observed in previous research, such as Fuller *et al.*'s (2004) and Fuller, Bradley and Healey's (2004) studies, which discuss how weaknesses in communication systems mean that lecturers are not always aware of their students' needs. Redpath *et al.* (2013) and Kendall (2016) found similar difficulties in communication and reported the frustration felt by disabled students having to self-identify and remind educators of the support they needed continually. This evidence illustrates that when relevant stakeholders do not take responsibility for implementing adjustments, disabled students must take on this responsibility to access education effectively, increasing their stress and anxiety, which is something that their non-disabled peers do not face (Madriaga, 2007).

Additionally, Felicity (master's student) experienced difficulties accessing mental health support at her institution as the mental health counsellor she was supposed to be meeting failed to attend their arranged appointments. Felicity tried to contact the counsellor to understand what happened, but never received a response, and no one claimed responsibility for what happened. This proved to be a challenge for Felicity, who *“was struggling at that time”*, and she wondered, *“How am I supposed to get support if you're not even answering the phone?”*. This situation led to a feeling of frustration as Felicity understood she would not get the support she needed, but would have liked *“at least an explanation”*.

Additionally, Nicole (master's student) discussed the difficulties she experienced when she realised exams in her programme had been scheduled on consecutive days. Nicole raised this issue with disability services because her support plan included avoiding exams on successive days. However, Nicole was met with unclear information and a lack of responsibility from those who were supposed to help. Support services said they were going to try to address the issue, but they could not guarantee anything. Nicole kept fighting back to get answers and a clear action plan, which led to a 6-month email chain which did not provide any clarity.

Consequently, Nicole did not feel like she was taken seriously: *“I went to all the places that I was meant to go to, but I wasn't listened to”*, and was frustrated as she could not track if the institution had taken responsibility to implement the adjustment. According to Nicole's experience, email chains can dilute this responsibility as discussions keep being dragged on and actions keep being postponed while nothing gets done. As an alternative, Nicole would like to see systems that track the progress of complaints (and support implementation), providing

"concrete evidence" that requests reach the right services and demonstrate that *"people have done what they said that they were going to do"*.

Moreover, for Nicole, these hurdles represent a form of discrimination as they illustrate a narrative where some accommodations (and disabilities) are considered more important than others. For example, Nicole compares her request with the existence of accessible rooms for wheelchair users. If in a case like that, Nicole adds, a wheelchair user is told *"that they can't guarantee that they'll get an accessible room, like, that's discrimination"*. Hence, Nicole's efforts in trying to get her accommodations implemented were her way of trying to understand and resist exclusionary practices and underlying discourses that deem some accommodations more valid than others. With this aim, Nicole asked her institution's support services: *"Is this a blanket policy that all disabled students, that you can't guarantee it for any disabled student? Or is it just in this circumstance?"*. To support this action, Nicole adds: *"I kind of wanted to know that because I was like, okay, am I not disabled enough to need this? Or do they just not consider it?"*. However, *"they didn't reply"*. These silences speak volumes, and I would argue that they are another way to avoid taking responsibility.

The result of this lack of accountability from the staff tasked with addressing Nicole's request was that Nicole made it her responsibility to find a solution, which took a considerable amount of time and energy. However, in one of her reflections, Nicole recognises that not all disabled students can afford to constantly fight and advocate for something that should be standard practice. This point is supported by authors like Wertans and Burch (2022), who argue that not all disabled students can pay the toll that resisting these exclusionary practices takes.

Furthermore, according to these authors, these types of practices, which do not provide effective support to disabled students, are normalised and reflect *"commonplace and normalised ableist notions"* across the sector (Wertans and Burch, 2022, p. 67). These ableist practices put disabled students at risk of internalising the underlying discourse that indicates that their needs are not recognised or understood, leading them to avoid seeking support (ibid).

Additionally, Nicole's experience reflects the disempowerment faced by disabled students, who are not always involved in decision-making processes related to disability-specific policies and support practices (Beauchamp-Pryor, 2012). Although the difficulties linked to implementing Nicole's adjustment must be acknowledged, as it would imply coordination between several modules, the approach taken to face this situation is an example of what Rooney (2019, p. 38) described as *"simplistic"* and *"superficial"* approaches to inclusion. These approaches to

inclusion avoid challenging predominant institutional practices and structures of power, ultimately reproducing inequality.

Cases like Nicole's fit into what Gibson (2015, p. 879) deems "*a misunderstood and misrepresented form of 'inclusion'*". More specifically, Gibson adds that in these cases "*'inclusion' becomes about attempts to induct that which is 'different' into already established forms and dominant institutional cultures*" (ibid). After all, Nicole pointed out that most students in her cohort shared her concern about having exams on consecutive days. Hence, why not turn her request into a broader conversation about alternatives to scheduling exams consecutively? This could create an opportunity to discuss alternative and inclusive assessment that do not exclude diverse students, preventing them from demonstrating their knowledge and abilities (McArthur, 2016; Tai *et al.*, 2023). For instance, (Tai *et al.*, (2023) argue that online examinations offer greater flexibility, providing students with more choices regarding exam locations, timeframes for completion, and access to resources, something positively valued by disabled students. Yet, Nicole's experience illustrates superficial approaches to inclusion, which focus on accommodating specific individuals instead of recognising the potential of disability when it comes to challenging the status quo and creating transformation (Dolmage, 2017). Thus, I argue that more critical approaches are necessary to do this, as it requires a commitment to challenging current policies and practices rooted in the medical model of disability. I also advocate for pedagogical approaches that foster responsibility to act on the many possibilities that result from responding to disabled students' needs. This, I argue, can promote inclusion across HE in Scotland and have a positive influence on the retention of disabled students. I turn to address this argument in more depth in chapters 5 and 6.

"That wider context in which you're asking for help just gets a bit lost": power, responsibility and Disabled Students' Allowance

Accessing some support services, like Disabled Students' Allowances (DSA), which is an external disability-related procedure, has been identified by participants in this study (including disabled students and disability advisers) as one of the main difficulties in the support provision process. Hence, the discourse of disabled students and disability advisers around this process aligns as these two groups of participants deem this system ineffective and inaccessible. This section focuses on how participants' experiences once again portray the paradox of how DSA, a system established to ensure equal access to education, becomes a significant barrier and source of stress for disabled students, often due to a lack of responsibility from the stakeholders involved. Thus, I argue that DSA, as currently implemented in Scotland, creates

structures where responsibilities are blurred between parties, hindering effective support provision and disabled students in a dangerous limbo as their wider experiences are not considered.

According to Johnson *et al.* (2019, p. 8) DSA, which only applies to UK-domiciled students, is defined as:

“payments (neither means-tested nor repayable) to help with essential, additional expenditure a disabled student incurs while studying, because of their disability (which includes long-term health conditions, mental health conditions, or specific learning difficulties such as dyslexia)”.

Yet, participants in this study have a shared acknowledgement of the difficulties related to DSA, deeming it inaccessible. One example is Kate’s experience, who, as a PhD student, returned to HE a decade after finishing her master’s degree due to her love for learning. However, Kate’s attempts to access support via DSA proved to be a constant struggle as it became a 16-plus-month battle during which she had to fill out several forms and send countless emails that did not get her anywhere. This delay was due to several issues, such as being given the wrong advice, experiencing delays in accessing updated medical documentation after relocating and having difficulties in communication with her institution’s disability support services and with the DSA staff. Hence, the DSA process has been onerous and stressful for Kate due to the bureaucratic burden that left her without support for more than half of her studies, but also because of the lack of interim support she was offered during this period.

According to Kate, this period was also characterised by a significant lack of care and regard for her circumstances, as no one (except for her supervisors) took responsibility for helping her access support. During this time, Kate was never offered an alternative solution while the support was being processed through DSA, leaving her “stuck” as her needs had not vanished. Kate found this to be

“incredibly frustrating, and it’s difficult because (...) I don’t want to sound ungrateful that the support isn’t [being offered] because it is. But because I haven’t been able to benefit from it [due to significant delays]... I feel quite frustrated”.

Kate’s frustration is supported by the words she shared during the participants’ feedback stage (as discussed in Chapter 3), as these delays felt like a cog that brought her PhD-related aspirations to a halt, something that non-disabled students do not have to face. Yet, as discussed above, Coughlan and Lister (2018) found out that disability-related external

processes are one of the most significant challenges experienced by disabled students in HE, causing negative emotional responses (ibid). Moreover, the DSA-related discussions in this study align with the difficulties covered in previous research, such as Addis' (2020) work, which concludes that this system, meant to reduce inequalities for disabled students in HE can become one of its most significant barriers.

Furthermore, Kate considered that the approach taken by disability support services at her institution was inflexible and lacked a *"caring connection"* because *"that wider context in which you're asking for help just gets a bit lost"*. Consequently, the process becomes *"very much like transactional, like 'You give us the form, we'll do an assessment, DSA will sort the [support]'"*. Yet, Kate feels like this context must be considered while support is negotiated and implemented, as disabled students' needs and the barriers they face do not disappear during that time (see Bones and Ellison, 2022). Hence, an external process like DSA appears to relieve HEIs from the responsibility to provide support as that is now the duty of those who process DSA applications. Therefore, anonymous administrators are responsible to approve or refuse support requests, which means that the wider context mentioned by Kate gets easily lost. Thus, Kate's experience supports the evidence shared by the Disabled Students' Commission (DSC) in 2021, as addressed in the introductory chapter, since 76% of students who experienced delays in support provision were not offered any alternative or interim support. Considering this, I support DSC's repeated call (Disabled Students' Commission, 2021b, 2021a, 2022, 2023) to ensure HEIs offer temporary support to those struggling to access support via DSA, as Kate did. Moreover, Kate's overall experience trying to access support also resonates with the *"additional labour of a disabled PhD student"*, as described by Hannam-Swain (2018, p. 138). Although the experiences of Hannam-Swain and Kate differ in certain areas, they both struggle with systems that are supposed to be of help but become stressors. For both, the DSA process has been *"the biggest headache"* (Hannam-Swain, 2018, p. 140), making them both consider giving up. In Kate's words:

"I just felt like I'm just going to cope by myself and not deal with it, you know? I think the PhD is hard enough without having extra battles on top and having just moved and everything. It's like 'I'm exhausted', so I don't have that extra kind of thing in me to sort of argue and push for things, as I might otherwise".

Once again, support provision processes are often so complex that not all disabled students can pay the emotional and physical toll that they take (Wertans and Burch, 2022). These

practices instantiate discourses that maintain that disabled students' needs are not valued or understood (ibid).

Moreover, while disabled students and disability advisers who participated in this study did not always come from the same institutions, most of them discussed difficulties around the DSA process, which they believed is not the most effective way to provide support for disabled students in HE. One example of this is Charlotte's (disability adviser) words: *"DSA funding plays a huge part in some of the struggles that our department has in supporting students. (...) I would say that it is not a good system; it is often not supportive when it needs to be"*. Expanding on these struggles, Charlotte highlights that the DSA can be a slow process, which means that *"students are studying without the necessary equipment or support for a while before the DSA comes through, and I think that's an issue for disabled students"*. Other disability advisers like Lydia, agree with Charlotte, thinking that *"[DSA] it's a ridiculous process and it's an unnecessary process, really. It should be far more straightforward"*.

Disabled students' struggles with DSA echo Dolmage's (2017, p. 80) argument regarding the existing HE *"attitude of indifference toward the individual, and a refusal to provide support until this support is legally mandated"*. As Dolmage argues, HEIs' approach to accommodations and accessibility focuses on compliance (with legislations and policies), and accommodations are often perceived as charitable actions. Furthermore, disabled students are expected to be thankful and not complain, regardless of whether they are effectively accommodated (ibid). These arguments are reflected in Kate's words, who feels like she should be grateful for a support she has not been able to access, and that has become a source of stress. They are also reflected in the focus that the disability support office at her institution has on compliance with policies rather than on supporting her as a student who is left stuck with no support for an unacceptable length of time.

Yet, according to Shaw (2024), recent DSA procedures give more responsibility to HEIs, as they respond to the institutional duty that the Equality Act (2010) places on HEIs to provide reasonable adjustments. This is criticised by some, like the National Union of Students (N.U.S.; as cited by Shaw, 2024), which maintains it was an attempt to reduce the Government's commitments towards disabled students. However, disability theorists like Oliver (2013) emphasise the impact that economic factors can have on the support and benefits offered to disabled people, something particularly relevant considering recent austerity measures aimed at reducing states' social welfare (Farnsworth and Irving, 2018). In this regard, Soldatic and Morgan (2017) point out that neoliberal austerity measures implemented across different

countries have placed disability at the centre of debates that aim to reduce welfare for disabled people (Soldatic, 2011). This illustrates the negative discourses around welfare and benefits for disabled people have increased in the past 40 years (Briant, Watson and Philo, 2012). Moreover, the pervasive influence of neoliberalism across HE has meant that HE disability inclusion has also been shaped by notions of institutional and individual performativity, while welfare and support diminish (Peruzzo, 2022, p. 483).

Existing difficulties with DSA have pushed recent reforms to the system, which were announced and implemented - although quietly - in February 2024 (Merritt, 2024). According to the Merritt (2024) and the Thomas Pocklington Trust (2024), these reforms are aimed at improving the overall DSA process, enhancing quality and accountability and tackling weaknesses like long waits, multiple points of contact, duplication of processes, lack of information about the progress of applications and the lack of clear complaint procedures. These changes are based on the introduction of two new support providers that act on behalf of the Student Loans Company (SLC): Contact Associates (Capita) and StudyTech, which will work within allocated areas of England and Wales (Merritt, 2024; Thomas Pocklington Trust, 2024).

Hence, at present, these changes do not apply to Scotland or Northern Ireland, although they apply to English and Welsh students whose universities are in these territories. According to Merritt (2024), the overall DSA policy is not altered, but the background process changes as students whose application is approved will liaise directly with the new support suppliers. Thus, these changes to DSA are welcome if they manage to tackle existing difficulties around support implementation and accountability. Yet, there is already uncertainty about their effectiveness as SLC does not seem to have a solid quality assurance process in place (Merritt, 2024).

Although I have not been able to identify plans for implementing these changes in the Scottish HE context, I wonder what implications they might have for the future of DSA provision in Scotland. In either case, accountability and responsibility must be a key element of any DSA reform to ensure timely and high-quality support provision so disabled students in HE can access education and fulfil their aspirations within the system.

Therefore, considering the present data, I argue that there is a need to consider the role that responsibility plays in the disability support provision process, something that is inherent to the power dynamics present in such a process. According to Tronto (2021), being responsible for others implies having some power in certain circumstances; without that power, responsibility fades away. In the case of disability support provision, it means that those working within the services have the power, skills and knowledge to support disabled students but also have a

responsibility to help them access effective and timely support. However, as this study shows, that is not sufficient to ensure disabled students are not discriminated against in HE. This illustrates Tronto's argument (2021) that responsibility is not enough for care and supportive practices to be effective because it emerges from the ability to enact power. Thus, amassing great power as a result of having responsibility could harm practices of care. Therefore, I argue that although a sense of responsibility is essential for disability support provision, care must also be an inherent element in these processes. Still, as participants' experiences indicate, the caring element that is meant to help prioritise students' needs often fades in the name of staff's responsibility to adhere to regulations and policies. Hence, while this section explores the key role of responsibility in the present context, the next chapter enhances this discussion by addressing how care has also been identified as a crucial construct in the retention of disabled students in Scottish HE, influencing the quality of support and education and impacting their progression.

4.3. Participants' suggestions for change

Participants in this study often discussed how to address the different issues concerning disabled students' inclusion and retention. This willingness for change aligns with the second research question in this study, as I aimed to identify in which way stakeholders involved believe there is room for improvement within HE to promote the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. Thus, this section offers an overview of participants' active contributions to bringing inclusion into the sector, addressing areas like the need to raise awareness about disability support services, enhancing accountability across these processes and the need for more collaboration between disability advisers and educators.

The need to increase awareness about disability services available was a common concern, as a lack of information is a recurring barrier preventing many disabled students from accessing support (Vickerman and Blundell, 2010; Redpath *et al.*, 2013; Lane, 2017). One example is Stella's (PhD student) call for more clarity about the services and support available, particularly for specific groups of students like postgraduate disabled students. Consequently, Stella believes that "*a sort of case study*" or "*testimonial*" would illustrate the support HEIs can provide: "*Here are the services which are for you; this is what they do*".

Others like Joe (undergraduate student) were concerned about the length and complexity of the DSA process. Thus, in line with Stella's call for more effective communication regarding the support available, Joe believes that HEIs should "*emphasise that these things really should be*

done months in advance to make sure everything's in place before you start". Joe's concerns are supported by existing evidence, as a review of DSA revealed that 60% of disabled students did not know about it until they enrolled in HE, and that there is confusion about who is eligible to apply, which leads to students deferring or avoiding their DSA application (Johnson *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, as demonstrated in this study, delays and difficulties in accessing support can have a particularly detrimental effect on master's students who spend a shorter amount of time at their institutions. In this case, Nicole (master's student) proposes that master's students (and *"people who are there for a short period of time"*) are prioritised to ensure they receive the support promptly, considering these time constraints.

Additionally, as discussed above, disability advisers mentioned that one of the weaknesses of their service is supporting students who contact them when it is too late. Concerning this, Caitlin (disability adviser) mentioned that her team is looking at *"changing the name of our service. (...) I think they're looking at 'Disability and Inclusion', which is good because it's covering other areas, but not taking away disability"*. Approaches like this could mean that disabled students who do not want to share their disability and those who do not have a diagnosis can contact these services before it is too late. This strategy could also help challenge the hierarchies described in this study. Although this is a small step, I believe it is a positive strategy to foster an ethics of care, putting students' needs above compliance.

Nevertheless, the data illustrates that difficulties do not stop after support is agreed upon, as other barriers can arise (Atkins, 2016; Addis, 2020), particularly for postgraduate disabled students as illustrated in this chapter. In this regard, Morgan, now a lecturer and researcher, but once a PhD student, believes that a more individualised approach to support is needed for postgraduate students who *"need a far more tailored approach because of the independent nature of the study that they're doing"*.

The difficulties related to existing support models mean that participants, particularly disability advisers, believe that current approaches need to be redesigned. For example, Charlotte (disability adviser) thinks *"that the whole DSA system needs to be overhauled"* and maintains that HEIs would benefit from alternative ways of managing this support. Lydia (also a disability adviser) agrees with Charlotte's suggestion and adds:

"Instead of allocating the funds directly to the individuals, they would allocate it to the institutions (...) because we know who needs help; we know who has a disability but doesn't have a bit of paper to prove it".

While this strategy could be difficult to attain and its effectiveness needs further evaluation, placing resources within HEIs could shift some of the power dynamics currently influencing the DSA process. Allocating these resources for HEIs to administer could reinforce existing power dynamics between disability advisers and disabled students. Yet, it could also reduce the power imbalance with anonymous DSA administrators who do not have direct interaction with disabled students and who might not develop a sense of responsibility and care towards them. Additionally, Lydia's words align with participatory budgeting approaches, which when applied to education imply that the members of the educational community come together to determine how they will use a part of a budget (Bartlett and Schugurensky, 2021). Moreover, participatory budgeting can promote civic engagement, accountability, effectiveness, community welfare and school democracy (ibid). Therefore, applying this approach to the distribution of funds allocated to disability support could foster additional accountability and responsibility within the process. While this is not a call to eliminate DSA, it is a call for a necessary discussion to find strategies that ensure disabled students in Scotland and the rest of the UK can successfully access support.

Additionally, according to participants, one factor that is important in delivering effective support practices is the existence of in-house teams, which could help face some of the difficulties currently experienced around the support provision process. According to Charlotte (disability adviser), having in-house support teams means that *"there's much more opportunity for kind of supporting each other, for growing each other's skills and for making sure that we're meeting a certain kind of level of support"*. Tiffany (PhD student) agrees with this approach and maintains that training and awareness are essential for effective in-house provision. However, if in-house provision is not possible, Tiffany believes that outsourcing could still be an alternative if done well: *"create links in the community with some sort of support service, (...) and now that everything's [online] it doesn't even need to be local; a national service or something"*.

Furthermore, it is common for disability services to liaise with educators to discuss and implement adjustments. However, this is not always straightforward as disability advisers believe that fear, lack of awareness and an excessive workload sometimes make educators resistant to implementing accommodations. Disability advisers recommend enhancing the collaboration with educators by using understanding and clear communication, focusing on the importance of inclusion and creating opportunities to discuss accessible educational practices. Lydia (disability adviser) believes that these difficulties stem from a lack of understanding of each other's roles:

“I think some other people who work in disabilities have never been in a classroom, so they think ‘Oh no, just do this, just do that, and that’ll make life much easier for you, for the students’. But trying to do that actually in a classroom it’s really difficult (...). I also know how easy it is to forget to do these things when you go into a classroom”.

Therefore, there is a gap between disability services and educators, as the former may not always understand the practical implications of adjustments and the latter might perceive accommodations as a barrier to high-quality pedagogical practice. This happens at Charlotte’s (disability adviser) institution, but she wishes there was more collaboration:

“The disability team is not included in conversations that academic development teams have which I find very surprising because (...) inclusive practice as a model of learning, (...) the core of it comes from disability support”.

Yet, Charlotte and her team’s expertise in inclusive teaching and learning is not recognised, despite their *“really good understanding of accessibility”* and their work in close contact with students. This disconnect is discussed by Little, Pearson and Gimblett (2023) who believe that the relationships between disability support services and educators should be strengthened and that the role of disability advisers should be better known, highlighting their capabilities in promoting accessibility. These authors also believe disability support staff should be included in the delivery of inclusive pedagogical training to educators in HE (ibid).

Thus, I argue that the distance between these two areas is one of the current barriers to effective educational inclusion and that it is necessary to build bridges between them, recognising their interdependence. Considering this need, I propose the creation of communities of practice in which disability advisers, educators, educational developers and disabled students can collaborate. According to Wegner (2011) a community of practice is made up of people who take part in a cooperative learning process within an area of mutual interest. Thus, they can enhance teaching, learning and research activities within HE, support learning for new members of staff, speed up responses to existing needs, enable new ideas (Dei and van der Walt, 2020) and foster non-hierarchical collaboration and transformation beyond institutional constraints (Bickle *et al.*, 2021). They can also create a space to promote social justice in education by identifying and critiquing discrimination and power imbalances across the sector (Hakkola *et al.*, 2021). However, more research is needed in this area to determine the value of communities of practice within the area of disability inclusion in HE.

Additionally, although the attitudes of educators seem to be increasingly positive and supportive, participants highlight the need for institutional support to promote inclusive educational practices. More specifically, some educators like Morgan point out that they never received formal training about promoting the inclusion and success of disabled students in HE: *“I’m absolutely stunned that I haven’t had any formal training at all”*. Moreover, Helen (educator) feels like the onus is on individual staff to identify how to make their practice more accessible rather than responding to an institutional approach to inclusion:

“[HEIs] need to look at how they support accommodations and that maybe not all of the burden is with the lecturers because then it makes it a really individual experience. Because it really depends on how engaged your lecturers are. I think there should be some way of either through disability services or some service, (...) but having training and support I think would be really helpful”.

This evidence aligns with the work of authors like Hansen and Dawson (2019), Cameron and Billington (2017), Little, Pearson and Gimblett, (2023), who acknowledge that educators might lack the knowledge to understand the needs of disabled students, particularly those with invisible disabilities, feeling anxious and unprepared to provide support. Some, like Moriña and colleagues, recognise that a lack of institutional support can be an obstacle to inclusive practices, putting the responsibility on individual lecturers’ kindness (Moriña, 2015; Moriña Diez *et al.*, 2015; Collins, Azmat and Rentschler, 2019; Hansen and Dawson, 2019; Bunbury, 2020). Yet, some like Helen (educator) maintain that HEIs often implement reductionist accessibility strategies following a checklist approach, which means faculty might not understand the rationale behind the need to promote inclusion, seeing it as the need to *“comply with these weird rules that someone made up”* instead of *“this is accessibility, and this is why it’s good”*. Considering this landscape, participants like Charlotte (disability adviser) propose HEIs make *“long-term investments”* towards inclusion instead of implementing *“short-term fixes”*, which she believes is short-sighted and could be detrimental to the success, progression, and retention of a significant group of students, including disabled students.

4.4. Conclusions

The present chapter has addressed this study’s research questions. More specifically, it analysed how cultures, discourses and practices related to disability support provision can fulfil or foreclose disabled students’ aspirations and shape their retention. In this regard, the chapter

has illustrated the existence of two different discourses. The first one refers to disability advisers who have an overall positive consideration of the effectiveness of disability support provision. Yet, the discourse of disabled students who participated in this study constructs these processes as complex, lengthy, and ineffective, often leaving them without the support needed and causing stress and extra effort. Hence, after doing a more in-depth analysis of the evidence generated in this study, participants' experiences illustrate a landscape where, although disability support provision is still essential to disabled students in HE in Scotland, they have to grapple with a flawed system.

According to my analysis, these flaws and complexities stem from the prevalence of the medical model across the sector, guiding policies, and practices where the focus is on legal compliance, meaning that HEIs concentrate on supporting disabled students who can comply with existing policies and practices. In this landscape, disabled students are positioned as passive recipients of support, depending on the established criteria and accountability of others, who, unfortunately, often fail to take responsibility and show an ethics of care to ensure disabled students can access the support they need. This leads to the creation of complex and ineffective systems and practices that often underpin the implementation of inconsistent support and overlook disabled students' human needs.

Furthermore, these practices and underlying discourses have created hierarchies where some disabled students seem to find it easier to access disability support than others. These practices are supported by an idealised conceptualisation of disabled students, based on them being undergraduate students with access to medical certification. More specifically, according to my analysis, disability support provision practices are designed for this idealised notion of disabled students, meaning that those who do not adhere to that ideal standard are often overlooked. These dynamics put postgraduate disabled students and students who cannot provide medical certification in an even more precarious position, where they face additional levels of discrimination in an already ableist sector. This is something that has a negative impact on disabled students' educational experience, hindering their aspirations and progression.

Although there is not a single strategy to face these difficulties, to address the second research question, the chapter offers a discussion of participants' recommendations to face these barriers. These recommendations look at improving disability awareness across HE and increasing the recognition of the dynamic nature of disability and the varied experiences of disabled students. Moreover, participants call for an increased sense of responsibility around the support provision process to avoid being left without support. With the same aim in mind,

participants also propose a reconceptualization of the DSA process that allows more direct collaboration between HEIs and disabled students, and the existence of in-house support provision services, rather than relying on external agencies.

Thus, this chapter has demonstrated how a medicalised and compliance-focused approach to support provision is leading to the discrimination of disabled students in Scottish HE, foreclosing their aspirations and having a negative effect on their educational experience and retention. Whereas I do not aim to provide one single answer or solution to all the difficulties shared here, in the general discussion, I address strategies that could help challenge the power imbalances and hierarchies created by this approach as a way of easing disabled students' access to support provision in order to promote their retention and success. Furthermore, in the next chapter, I examine educational and attitudinal practices that can promote the inclusion and progression of disabled students in Scottish HE, potentially reducing their need to request individual accommodations by challenging the inherently ableist notions of the sector. Finally, in the general discussion, I turn to examine how these two findings chapters complement each other, but also to challenge some of the constructs discussed here, such as the ideal disabled HE student.

Chapter 5: Pedagogy: Choices and Care

The second area of interest in relation to the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland, as identified in this study, is that of pedagogy, which is the focus of this chapter. To address this study's first research question, this chapter uncovers how pedagogical cultures, discourses and practices shape disabled students' experiences in HE in Scotland and influence their retention. Moreover, due to the hopeful and applicable nature of this chapter, it also addresses the study's second research question, as it explores in most sections, ways in which participants believe there is room for improvement to foster the inclusion and retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland.

The chapter starts by discussing how neoliberal principles create educational cultures and discourses that promote hyper-productivity and overworking in HE, which disregards disabled students' complex experiences. Therefore, this chapter examines how neoliberal traditions shape HE in Scotland, creating a sector that is not designed for disabled people as it is often characterised by a lack of care and consideration towards disabled students' human experiences. This means that disabled students are required to fit into narrow standards to feel like they belong in HE.

Yet, when discussing the impact of teaching and learning on the retention of disabled students in HE, the common discourse among participants (disabled students, disability advisers, and educators) was that of resisting and challenging these narrow, neoliberal notions through the adoption of care-based approaches that recognise and value the diverse human experiences of disabled students. Care-based approaches proposed by participants are, first, enacted through an active demonstration that disabled students and their learning are valued in HE in Scotland. Moreover, participants discuss the need to adopt anticipatory strategies for inclusive education based on providing choices for students and adopting the principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) as hybrid learning gains relevance in the post-pandemic HE landscape. Yet, the data also shows the need to prioritise disabled students' sense of belonging in the era of digital and hybrid learning.

Consequently, this chapter demonstrates the need for critical, care-based pedagogies across HE in Scotland. I argue that care-based approaches can help challenge neoliberal ableist notions that exclude disabled students, having a negative impact on their retention as they can promote cultures, discourses and practices that allow disabled students to meet their

aspirations and thrive in HE. Hence, in line with Feminist Poststructuralism (FPS), this chapter demonstrates ways to challenge the status quo and considers ways of doing things otherwise (see Chapter 3). Moreover, I consider that, although this study focuses on the experiences of disabled students, the approaches discussed here can promote inclusion broadly, benefiting a wide range of students across the sector. I also argue that these practices could help challenge some of the exclusionary practices discussed in the previous chapter, as the need for individualised accommodations (and the difficulties related to them) is likely to decrease if pedagogies of care are implemented across the sector.

5.1. “The experience of a disabled student is just relentless, it's never-ending”: The influence of neoliberalism in HE in Scotland

The data generated in this study illustrates the experiences of disabled students in a HE sector described as harmful, stressful, and sometimes vicious, characterised by an ableist culture of performativity and overworking. This means that, according to participants, the HE system in Scotland is not designed for disabled people, as it often prioritises policy compliance over disabled students' aspirations and retention. However, participants positively value HE environments that care about their students' needs and learning. This perception is so meaningful that perceiving that an HEI cares about their students can influence the decisions disabled students make when they choose their programmes, being more drawn towards HEIs perceived as care-focused. Considering these elements, this section starts by exploring the impact of neoliberalism in HE in Scotland and how it negatively influences the experiences of disabled students, often foreclosing their aspirations and impacting their retention. Secondly, the section examines how caring approaches in HE in Scotland can mitigate this influence and foster inclusion for disabled students, helping fulfil their aspirations and promoting retention.

The difficulties relating to educational practices and disability support services, as shared in the current and previous chapters, illustrate that HE policies and practices are not always designed for a diverse body of students. Concerning this, Felicity (master's student) believes that the current Scottish HE sector is not “*designed for disabled people. I don't think that the current way of teaching is designed for disabled people*” because “*it is extremely stressful and it's challenging*”. Some of the reasons Felicity gives to support this belief are that the current sector is “*high-stress; it's high-intensity. It's multiple assignments after multiple assignments*”. Furthermore, Felicity believes the HE environment “*is one of the reasons why students get*

unwell” because “it’s really stressful, and it doesn’t really consider the well-being of the student”.

According to Felicity, it all stems from the “*overworker culture and able-bodied culture*” as students are pressured to want “*to have a part-time job and then you want to be in [university], and then you want to do volunteering, and then you want to be in societies, and then you want to be literally like helping everyone in the world*”. Yet, this tendency does not consider the circumstances of disabled students, and according to Felicity, it is “*infuriating because it’s like, ‘Do realise how much you’re asking of, like, an able-bodied person?’ Imagine how much you’re asking of a disabled person*”. Furthermore, Felicity believes that in this culture of overworking, there is no time to look after oneself, and:

“when you do take a day off because of the overworking culture, you feel really bad, you feel terrible, especially if it’s a mental illness because it’s like you think ‘I’m just being lazy’ like you use all this rhetoric that’s like in the media amongst your peers, amongst your parents of ‘You’re being lazy’... and it’s really cruel. It’s really, really cruel, but it’s rife, at least in Scotland. Like, from what I’ve noticed is that everyone feels like they have to overwork”.

The overworking culture, as defined by Felicity, has been discussed by authors like Brown and Leigh (2018) who acknowledge that it is widely accepted across the sector. Felicity’s belief also aligns with the work of others like Nieminen (2022) and Dolmage (2017) who argue that HE is not designed for disabled people. Moreover, Felicity’s words provide an in-depth depiction of the current “*uncaring neoliberal, competitive and individualising HE system*” identified and described by Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild (2024, p. 1) and how it can impact disabled students. Giroux (2010, p. 185) maintains that neoliberalism is the current engine running HE, which is leading to the predominance of what he calls, influenced by Agamben’s work “*bare pedagogy*”. Within this bare pedagogy, individuals are constructed as “*a new kind of market-driven individual (...) that abstracts economics and markets from ethical considerations*” (ibid). According to Giroux, bare pedagogy eliminates values like criticality and civic responsibilities from education. In this scenario, compassion and moral responsibility are disregarded as people’s needs and the affective and emotional sides of education are ignored while the market is prioritised (Grummell, Devine and Lynch, 2009; Giroux, 2010). Furthermore, Goodley *et al.* (2014) maintain that the ability standards defined by neoliberal ableism can be observed in the context of HE through the expectation of student bodies that are made out of economically productive and active citizens and individuals. Gibson and Cook-Sather (2020) argue that these

neoliberal ideas and the focus on performativity and personal success that currently characterise HE clash with and can damage inclusive policies and practices across the sector.

This is all reflected in Felicity's words as they effectively portray the effect of the neoliberal, bare pedagogy that strips HE of its critical, moral and civic responsibilities and the harm it causes to disabled students. Thus, Felicity's words are also an illustration of the accumulating challenges disabled students face in the current HE landscape, which include:

“ableism, whether explicit or implicit, (...) then you've got internalised ableism, so you've got the ableism that you've learned that you reflect on yourself. And then you've got the overworker culture and then you've got the abled-body culture, which expects you to only get respect if you present as abled. And then you've got your own challenges of your disability. (...) And then on top of that, you've got the usual [university] stress and then on top of that, you've got financial stress. (...) You've got to budget, you've got to mask, you've got to, you know, ensure that you present a different way, you've got to look after yourself”.

Felicity's experience is a multifaceted one and a solid reflection of the current HE ableist culture in which disabled students are, according to her words, *“thrown to the side and told that they're not valuable and people don't recognise like that you're doing so much”*, meaning that *“the experience of a disabled student is just relentless; it's never-ending”*. This is another example of the additional labour of disabled students, which was discussed in the previous chapter as part of the experience of PhD candidates (see Hannam-Swain, 2018).

The never-ending challenges experienced by disabled students are discussed in previous literature (Madriaga, 2007; Vickerman and Blundell, 2010; Fichten *et al.*, 2014; Moriña, 2015, 2017; Kilpatrick *et al.*, 2016; Moriña, Sandoval and Carnerero, 2020) and some like Gibson (2015), argue that many disabled students who have been supposedly included in HE, in reality, face challenges, disappointment and failure. Hence, Felicity's experience is a representation of neoliberal ableism's influence on HE where *“narrow and normative ability expectations”* (Wertans and Burch, 2022, p. 60) determine who belongs in HE. Therefore, considering the effect of neoliberal trends in HE and how they shape disabled students' experiences, authors like Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild (2024) call for socially just pedagogies where care for oneself, care for others, meaningful connections and partnerships are paramount. Along similar lines, Gibson and Cook-Sather (2020) propose the concept of politicised compassion as a process of politicising education and fostering collaborative discourses that result from student-faculty partnerships. According to these authors, politicised compassion could be a catalyst for

discourses and practices that lead to *“meaningful social justice and equity”* (Gibson and Cook-Sather, 2020, p. 17).

These discussions are further supported by this study’s data as the experiences of participants emphasise the positive influence of caring HE approaches on easing the journey of disabled students in HE. More specifically, according to the data, HEIs perceived as caring could be one of the main factors disabled postgraduate research (PGRs) students take into consideration when selecting the institution or programme where they decide to undertake their doctoral degree. For instance, feeling *“like the people there really care”* was one of the elements that meant Tiffany (PhD student) *“was sure it was where I wanted to go”* from the moment she applied for a PhD studentship. This caring element is something Tiffany has seen in practice after the application phase, as her supervisors and the rest of the teams with which she engages are *“all about, you know, practical skills and developing people, really people-focused”*. This has led her to be satisfied with her choice: *“I am happy that I came here”*.

Still, the participants' experiences in this study often reflect common uncaring approaches at different levels of HE in Scotland, which has a negative influence on their journeys, foreclosing their aspirations and putting them at higher risk of early exit. Participants like Kate (PhD student) became aware of this while trying to understand why she was not met with more compassion and support while experiencing significant delays in getting the support she needed. In relation to this, Kate mentioned that a lack of care across disability services must be the result of cultural, structural and organisational issues, and not only due to individual attitudes. This is because Kate does not believe that disability support services *“don’t care or anything like that”* because *“that doesn’t make sense”*. However, Kate acknowledges that a caring connection with disability support services is crucial for the retention of disabled students:

“When you've got vulnerable students, and you don't have that personal connection, disability services might make the difference between that student, you know, staying kind of on the track they want to be on, or falling off”.

Echoing Kate’s words, Amelia (educator) believes that the absence of caring pedagogy *“is one of the reasons why people don’t stay”*; another reason is that *“people are let down by the system; the ones that don’t finish”*. More specifically, Amelia highlights how unclear information, faulty systems, and difficulties in communication are the circumstances that let down people in the sector. One example provided by Amelia is the automatic email responses students receive when they contact professional services, which *“have standard responses of five days, 10 days, to get back to students, and I just think that's absolutely shocking”*. Amelia acknowledges this is

a result of the current culture as professional services are overworked and under pressure, but she points out that these timeframes can affect students who need support. In this regard, Amelia believes that HEIs need “*to put its money where its mouth is and put resource in where it matters*”. Therefore, I argue that neoliberal conceptions of performativity are behind services that prioritise procedures and structures over students’ needs as illustrated by Kate and Amelia’s experiences. According to Wertans and Burch (2022), the focus of these services on quantifiable results is not conducive to supportive environments for a wide range of HE students, including disabled students.

Another area in which neoliberal principles and a lack of caring approaches are reflected is in HEIs’ approach to student recruitment and retention. In this regard, Cara (educator) maintains that her institution is focused “*on recruitment and admissions*”, aiming to get “*the next and next*” student, but it has “*not actually spent the time trying to keep [current students] (...) and we lose half of them*”. Thus, for Cara, her HEI “*need[s] to know our students more, not just our applicants (...) because they’re our students and we have a duty of care towards them, and this is a big part of their life*”.

Cara’s words illustrate the marketisation of HE, also driven by the neoliberal ideology across the sector (Alajoutsijärvi, Alon and Pinheiro, 2021), as students are seen as customers for HEIs to accumulate. However, there is a paradox because, according to Cara, her institution does not consider students’ (their *customers*) needs once they are recruited, which could lead to enhanced academic experiences (del Cerro Santamaría, 2020) and potential retention. Along these lines, Thomas (2012) argues that from an ethical point of view, HEIs have a social responsibility to enable their students to succeed; yet, the role of this social responsibility is unclear in neoliberal HE. However, it must be noted that neoliberalism might not be as pervasive across HE in Scotland because the nation’s government covers tuition fees for home undergraduate students, as addressed in Chapter 1 (Scottish Government, 2024). This means that HE students in Scotland are less likely to be perceived as customers, as opposed to other systems such as those of the United States of America (see del Cerro Santamaria, 2020). Yet, despite this, data generated in this study demonstrate that neoliberal notions of marketisation and performativity do exist in the sector and shape the experiences of disabled students, opening an avenue for research to understand the unique HE landscape of the nation.

The influence of neoliberal principles in HE in Scotland can also be seen in the advice students receive regarding their progression within the system. For some, early withdrawal might be the best option as this would allow them to enrol in an alternative programme. Yet, some

institutions might be more interested in retaining the students for the whole year without considering their needs. In this regard, Sally (educator) mentioned that if a student is struggling with their degree, it might not always be in their best interest to stay in their programme as they might lose some of the government tuition funding in a course that does not suit them and which they might leave later. Considering the Scottish funding approach, home students are funded for four years plus one (Scottish Government, 2024), which, according to Sally, means *“you're allowed to make a mistake. So, you're allowed to repeat a year”*. Hence, if students realise their current programme is not the best option in their first year, they *“can come back and they've still got four years of funding”*. However, Sally acknowledges that different institutions have different approaches, and some might focus on getting *“a student a degree”*, whereas others will focus on getting *“them passed for the whole year”*, mainly to avoid the financial consequences of a student's early exit. According to Sally, retaining students for the whole year is easy: *“You just make them pass”*. Nevertheless, this approach is not appropriate if the aim is to help students fulfil their aspirations and promote attainment, success, and progression. In that case, Sally adds: *“If you want them to get a degree, if you want them to get a first or a 2:1 if you want them to get a good honours degree (...), then you need to be a bit more long-term”*.

Cara's and Sally's beliefs and concerns were covered by Thomas (2012) more than ten years ago, who recognised that HEIs have a duty towards their students and that they must elaborate strategies to support their progression and completion. Moreover, Thomas acknowledged that with an increasingly diverse body of students, UK institutions showed an increased interest in maintaining and improving their retention rates. From a financial angle, institutions are interested in retaining students to avoid financial losses. But as seen above, from a moral standpoint, Thomas (2012) argues that HEIs have an obligation to enable students' success and while citing the words of Bamber and Tett (2001, p. 15), Thomas defends that *“the implications of offering access to nontraditional students do not end, but rather begin, at the point of entry”*. Yet, with the marketisation and massification of HE (Hornsby and Osman, 2014), institutions are facing significant challenges in getting to know and respond to the needs of their large student bodies (Giannakis and Bullivant, 2016). Thus, it can be argued that the needs of many students are being disregarded, which once again leads to the marginalisation of certain groups, as the neoliberal and ableist notions across the sector only privilege those who can adhere to these competitive and individualistic tenets (Madriaga *et al.*, 2011; see Dolmage, 2017; Wertans and Burch, 2022). This means that as many students, like disabled students, do not fit into the standards of the system, their needs are not effectively considered in HE, maintaining

oppressive and exclusive practices that have a negative influence on their experiences, aspirations and retention.

Therefore, neoliberal notions in Scottish HE have a considerable negative influence on the experiences of disabled students across the sector due to the multiple ramifications of a system that prioritises competition and narrow ways of being a student. Hence, it is easy to see why disabled students struggle in a sector that encourages overworking without caring about student well-being and which has disregarded its social responsibility towards existing students in favour of accumulating new recruits. Yet, as illustrated in this section, care towards students and their needs is an alternative to challenge the negative influence of neoliberalism on disabled students in HE in Scotland. I will expand on this in the rest of the chapter as I examine how caring approaches can be implemented across the sector. There, I will use the data generated in this study to support my argument that caring educational approaches can help challenge discriminatory practices and resist power imbalances that result from HE's neoliberal ableism, fostering cultures, discourses and practices that help fulfil the aspirations and promote the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland.

5.2. “[If] you feel like they don't care about you... you're not going to want to stay in”: The need to value disabled students as whole human beings

Lack of consideration towards the complex experiences of disabled students was a common theme discussed by participants in this study, which led to discriminatory educational practices. Alternatively, disabled students who participated in this study valued educational cultures and practices that recognise them as whole human beings with complex life experiences, which reflected care and interest toward them as students and as human beings. Alternatively, the practices and attitudes that demonstrated indifference and disrespect toward them and their diverse experiences had a negative influence on their experiences, foreclosing their aspirations and retention. Thus, this section illustrates the importance of seeing all students, and particularly disabled students, as whole human beings whose experiences expand beyond the classroom, impacting how they engage with education. Acknowledging this could foster more inclusive educational cultures, discourses and practices that promote the retention of disabled students in HE.

Class and exam arrangements were one of the circumstances in which participants perceived a lack of care and consideration for student diversity. For instance, Felicity (master's student)

believed that the short time between exams and assignment submissions and the excessive length of classes can be detrimental to the academic experience and performance of disabled students. According to Felicity, consecutive exams and deadlines can harm students' mental health, and having to attend lengthy classes with no breaks can hinder their energy and focus levels. These difficulties have also been noted by authors like García-González *et al.* (2021), who highlight how tight class schedules and lengthy exams became a barrier for disabled students in their investigation exploring HE in Spain. For example, participants experienced *"tiredness, effort and pain"* after exams, some being unable to complete their work due to pain. While García-González *et al.* (2021) report that accommodations were put in place to tackle these barriers, participants in their study reported that these were not always effective.

Additionally, Nicole (master's student) believes that the approach taken in relation to assessment and feedback can be an opportunity for educators to reflect their caring attitudes. One example provided by Nicole is a specific module which ran for two terms, and in the final assessment, *"they had a little section where they said, 'We want you to write how you've implemented your feedback from last term in this piece of work'"*. According to Nicole, this was a useful and interesting element which demonstrated that the educators:

"Really care to see how, like, the trajectory of the student and how you might have improved since the previous term. (...) And obviously, it shows that they really care about the teaching element and how you're improving as a student and as a researcher".

On the contrary, Nicole felt like the other modules of her master's lacked that caring element, as well as relevance and consistency because they *"felt a little bit, like, just submit this random bit of work, and we'll get the marks back to you at some point"*. Hence, Nicole's words highlight how assessment interactions can impact the student experience and strengthen connections between students and faculty (Schwartz, 2019). More specifically, Schwartz (2019) argues that personalised feedback can be interpreted by students as a sign of extra attention and consideration to their work, and as a commitment to enhance student learning.

Furthermore, Felicity (master's student) believes that the teaching approaches taken by educators can shape the retention of disabled students: *"The way that you're taught definitely impacts how you're retained"*. At first, Felicity hesitated whether this related to disability; however, she concluded that different approaches can be enabling or constraining for disabled students, as lecturers who do not follow the *"traditional"* and *"value-free"* approach to teaching *"tend to be softer and a bit more understanding and empathetic"*. This means Felicity feels

more freedom to be who she is without having to mask: *“I don't need to be the civil abled-body person constantly”*, which has a positive influence on her HE experience.

According to Migueliz Valcarlos *et al.* (2020), critical scholars like bell hooks have argued that HEIs can simultaneously foster oppression and emancipation. In Migueliz Valcarlos and colleagues' analysis of this issue (2020), the authors maintain that the neoliberal and Western knowledge production traditions followed at many HEIs are one of the ways in which oppression is exerted within these institutions. More specifically, the authors centre their attention on the neoliberal ideas of competition and individuality and on the Western traditions that adopt seemingly neutral, universal, and objective viewpoints engrained in capitalist and patriarchal ideas (Migueliz Valcarlos *et al.*, 2020). In this case, the authors maintain that HE practices rooted in these ideas *“privilege dominant curriculum, bodies, and ways of knowing that effectively oppress the histories, knowledges, and experiences of those from nondominant backgrounds”* (p. 346). These practices and approaches are what Felicity calls the *“traditional”* and *“value-free”* ways of teaching that marginalise her as a disabled student, foreclosing her educational experience and aspirations.

Yet, Felicity maintains that educators who take a more critical and relational approach to pedagogy allow her to express herself more freely, making her educational experience more meaningful. For instance, Felicity highlights the positives of collaborative and dialogical educational practices that value the knowledge and experiences of (disabled) students: *“I think it's really nice to have the lecturer recognise your opinion is insightful and to learn from it, and so you just learn from them and to have this as like a collaborative environment”*.

Alternatively, Felicity adds that

“if lecturers are quite apathetic... and you feel like they don't care about you, they're only there to do their job, you're not going to want to stay in. That's not going to be a factor, especially if you're a disabled student. You're going to feel like they don't care about you”.

Felicity's words illustrate the positive impact of educators who demonstrate that they care about students' learning and belonging in (higher) education (Schwartz, 2019). These words also demonstrate the value of putting the pedagogical focus beyond *“getting through the course material”* and valuing the diversity of students' experiences (Hamington, 2021, p. 70). Therefore, pedagogical approaches that are characterised by care can be more inclusive and challenge existing hierarchies in the student-teacher relationship in HE (ibid). Moreover, according to

Hawk and Lyons (2008), lecturers who fail to demonstrate a caring and respectful attitude towards students could lead them to perceive that they and their learning have been given up on. This is something that could result in students' lower self-esteem, disengagement, and difficulties with course completion (ibid). Moreover, in their review of the literature, Migueliz Valcarlos *et al.* (2020) argue that pedagogies that value students' personal experiences and connect them to their programme's content can help legitimise their emotions and cultural values. These authors highlight that feminist scholarship supports these pedagogical approaches, highlighting the importance of engaging with and valuing different viewpoints, relations and complexities (Miller, 2005; Lai and Lu, 2009), which Migueliz Valcarlos *et al.* (2020, p. 352) recognise can be tools to challenge what is traditionally considered "*knowledge and knowing*". Therefore, these approaches could potentially challenge oppressive practices like the ones described by Felicity, and foster HE cultures, discourses and practices that are inclusive by default, acknowledging and celebrating the diverse experiences of disabled students in HE.

Yet, the evidence generated here demonstrates that disabled students are not always shown respect to be their own person in HE in Scotland. In this regard, Felicity believes that in her institution, disabled and neurodivergent students are treated with more respect if they mask, which highlights an important dilemma:

"If you don't show your symptoms, people don't take your disability seriously because they're like 'you seem fine'. But then when you do show your symptoms, you're labelled as crazy, irrational; you receive comments such as 'Are you off your medication?'"

However, Felicity believes that disabled students should not need to mask to be treated with respect: *"I don't think that students should have to mask. It's exhausting, it's tiring. Why do we have to fit into your standards?"*

Masking is a term employed by the autistic community to define the concealment of personal features to "*fly under the radar*" or "*appear normal*" to avoid stigma (Miller, Rees and Pearson, 2021, p. 331), although some aspects of masking are shared by people who are not autistic and identify as neurotypical (ibid). The consequences of masking include exhaustion, stress, burnout, mental health difficulties, a disconnection from oneself, socialisation difficulties, and being invalidated or disregarded by others (Miller, Rees and Pearson, 2021; Radulski, 2022). However, according to Felicity, there is a "*constant double-edged sword for disabled people*" in HE, due to the implicit pressure "*to mask to get their basic respect*". Nevertheless, having to constantly mask in educational contexts means students like Felicity do not show their true

selves, and other people are “*never going to view me as ill as I am*”. Yet, if Felicity un.masks, suddenly, she does not fit “*the civilised standards that you have been socialised into*”, which is likely to affect the way she is treated at her HEI. In this regard, Felicity expands:

“Disabled people just like any other marginalised group... they have to work hard to fit into the norm to get basic, decent respect. And because the norm has been kind of set up as this white able-bodied, cis, male perspective; and I know people are starting to challenge it but like, you have to almost like tone-police yourself to get basic respect. And I do that as a disabled woman and as a woman in general and as a queer woman. You know, there's all these multiple factors where it's like you have to fit into the sort of heteronormative, able-bodied, cis-gendered standard, and if you don't, you're not going to be heard; you're going to be labelled as irrational”.

Perceiving environments as stigmatising can be related to masking (Miller, Rees and Pearson, 2021), as described by Felicity. For example, participants in the study conducted by Syharat *et al.* (2023) expressed that they masked and avoided disclosing their neurodivergence due to fear of negative treatment and discrimination and acknowledged that academic culture and educators’ attitudes impacted their experiences. Hence, educational practices and environments that are not perceived as respectful or caring force disabled, neurodivergent and even neurotypical students to mask and hide their identities due to fear of being marginalised. Felicity’s experiences demonstrate how current educational cultures are linked to power and shaped by the impositions of dominant groups (Freire, 1985), which in the UK’s HE promotes a sense of ableist normalcy (Madriaga *et al.*, (2011). These educational cultures privilege very specific and narrow ways of being that fit into the criteria of the dominant groups and lead to the marginalisation of those who do not meet these criteria, discrediting their experiences and aspirations (Freire, 1985).

Henceforth, Felicity’s words illustrate how those students who do not fit into the characteristics valued by Western, neoliberal, and patriarchal HE traditions need to camouflage their true selves to fit into the sector. While Felicity acknowledges cultural changes toward a more positive landscape, her appreciation is supported by some, like Shefer (2021, p. 174), who recognises that some “*bodies, peoples and knowledges continue to feel out of place*” in HE. Furthermore, Shefer argues that colonialist and patriarchal ideologies that dominate contemporary educational practices and environments foster spaces that are unsafe for many students and staff, leading to exclusion and marginalisation. This oppression, Shefer argues, is more significant for certain “*bodies and identities*” (ibid). One example of how this applies to

disabled students is Felicity's experience, as shared above, as she felt the need to mask to be respected by peers and faculty. Not masking meant that Felicity felt unsafe and feared being stigmatised. Felicity's experience illustrates what Freire (1985) defined as specific modes of domination since disabled students, who are perceived as different, are oppressed and their very essence suppressed in HE. This recognition calls for resistance and highlights the need for critical educational approaches that challenge these power dynamics and discriminatory cultures, discourses and practices. In relation to this, Spulchre (2023) maintains that acknowledging disability as a dimension of inequalities and oppression allows for more intersectional praxis in HE, promoting social justice. Adopting an intersectional approach to disability inclusion and support means that the complex identities of disabled students are acknowledged and valued, not forcing disabled students to behave a certain way to receive basic support and respect.

As a consequence of facing discrimination in HE, Felicity values educational environments that are *"safe and ensure students were respecting other students"*. Respect for oneself and for others is a relevant concept in the context of caring pedagogies, also understood as pedagogical respect (Hawk and Lyons, 2008). According to Hawk and Lyons (2008) it is important that educators respect students and care about their learning, as not doing so could lead to lower levels of student satisfaction and higher attrition rates. Alternatively, if students feel cared for and respected, there can be an expectation for more effective student learning, engagement, satisfaction and lower attrition rates (ibid).

Tiffany (PhD student) also discussed teachers' attitudes when talking about one episode that took place while she was doing her (online) master's degree. More specifically, Tiffany recalled how she experienced difficulties related to workload management and engagement with online materials, which meant she had to request extensions during her programme. However, when these difficulties arose, Tiffany was accusatively approached by educators threatening to remove her from the programme, reflecting a negative discourse about students who do not meet the criteria and expectations of HE: *"Well, you haven't [checked any of the materials online] ... so get back to me or we're kicking you off the course"*. In this case, Tiffany wished educators did not assume that students in these circumstances have *"done something awful"* and are not engaging with the material because they are *"bad [people]"*. Instead, she would like to see a shift where educators do not assume the worst of students, are more understanding and give students the benefit of the doubt as there are many reasons, including disability, why they might be struggling. Although Tiffany acknowledged more positive cultures and attitudes in recent years, she wished that at that time she had been approached more compassionately,

such as: *“Listen, I've noticed that you have not accessed the material. Is everything okay? Is there anything you need?”*.

Tiffany's words call for a recognition of students as human beings who exist beyond their classroom, having to deal with circumstances that might impact their educational engagement. This was also the case for Lynsey (PhD student) who faced difficulties while doing her master's during the COVID-19 pandemic. Lynsey needed extensions to submit her work due to her health and family circumstances, but she had a more positive experience requesting these extensions. Lynsey's educators understood her needs and the struggles linked to the pandemic:

“There were a couple of times that I did need extensions, and they kind of gave me an extension over the extension time that they would give to everybody else, which was really positive because then you had a lot going on... without requesting a doctor's letter, because obviously everything was difficult to get by at that point”.

This desire to see students as whole human beings is recognised by bell hooks, who acknowledges that students want educators to be aware of their complex lives and not simply see them as *“seekers after compartmentalized bits of knowledge”* (2014, p. 15). This recognition could be essential when working with disabled students, as educators should understand the impact that chronic illness and bodily impairments will have on the educational experience of disabled people despite environmental (and educational) adaptations (Shakespeare and Watson, 2010).

Moreover, I consider that Felicity's and Tiffany's experiences, as discussed in this section, are another illustration of the idealised notion of disabled students (see Dadvand, 2022) which currently dominates HE in Scotland. This notion is reflected by the double-edged sword described by Felicity as disabled students are only respected if they mask. Hence, I would argue that more compassionate attitudes and discourses are necessary, recognising that disabled students' lives extend far beyond the classroom. This could be the first step towards a cultural shift in which the worst is not assumed of students, and (disabled) students are allowed to discuss their circumstances and create a dialogue that promotes inclusive and supportive cultures and practices.

Along similar lines, Lydia (disability adviser) wondered, *“Why can't people not just be nice”* to students, as it *“would solve so many problems”*. Lydia adds that being understanding and empathetic could be a way of supporting disabled students:

“You just need to understand that it's tough for them, and actually, you can do a lot of good for the student. You can be really helpful for the student just by being there for them and asking them ‘How can I help?’ (...) That's exactly what we should be doing in education. We shouldn't be saying, ‘Why did you miss that deadline?’ we should be saying, ‘How can I help?’”.

However, Lydia believes this approach is not particularly prominent across HE in Scotland yet, and she considers a culture change necessary for it to be broadly adopted. Therefore, Lydia believes that more empathy and communication are needed in the sector to help the adoption of caring and helpful approaches. Authors like Noddings (2012) have also addressed these points, highlighting the importance of listening to students for the implementation of an ethics of care in education. According to this author, opening opportunities for dialogue and truly listening can help build trusting relationships with students, which would help tackle students' expressed needs with *“empathic accuracy”* (Noddings, 2012, p. 775) to avoid misunderstanding their struggles.

While trying to understand why some educators appear to have more approachable and caring attitudes than others, Sally (educator) believes that some academics in HE might not see themselves as educators but only as researchers or scientists. According to Sally, these academics are *“not here to deal with people. They're here to do research. (...) That's probably what they think their job is, but that doesn't help the students who don't know where to turn to when they're struggling”*. Thus, Sally believes there are difficulties in academics managing the pastoral part of their job

“because they don't answer their emails, they don't know how to cope with it, but now they're supposed to be nice, and they're supposed to understand the students”.

However, Sally is not sure how *“a nuclear physicist would understand a 17-year-old”*.

While this is not necessarily what happened to Tiffany, or the only reason educators might not show caring attitudes, Sally's words illustrate a disconnect within the role of faculty who prioritise research over pedagogy without being aware of the impact this might have on students.

Reflecting on Sally's words, it is problematic that some HE academics do not see themselves as educators despite being involved in teaching and learning activities. This belief can foster problematic educational attitudes, cultures, and practices, as faculty who do not perceive themselves as educators might overlook the human and relational elements essential for

meaningful learning and student growth (hooks, 2014). Thus, care and respect are essential to promote deep learning (hooks, 2014), and according to Noddings (2012, p. 772), educators need to discern when their focus should be on teaching and learning or students' needs for "emotional support, moral direction, or shared human interest". Hence, as discussed by Guzzardo et al. (2021, p. 51) "doing more than teaching" is essential to promoting student engagement and motivation. Doing more than teaching is defined by these authors as being flexible, caring, responsive, available, and engaged (ibid). Yet, it is unlikely that faculty who do not see themselves as educators would be willing to make care, responsibility, or compassion part of their educational practice.

Therefore, the present data illustrates how current educational cultures, discourses and practices create a limited understanding of HE students in Scotland, particularly of disabled students whose experiences beyond the classroom are not always acknowledged and considered. This landscape creates HE environments in which disabled students' whole humanity is not valued, and there are multiple pressures for them to fit into the narrow traditional and neoliberal standards currently shaping HE in Scotland. This leads to discrimination and marginalisation and reflects once again the idealised conception of disabled students across the sector, making them feel unsafe and forcing them to hide their true selves. Considering these circumstances, caring and relational educational approaches gain relevance in the creation of HE systems that enhance the experiences of disabled students in HE in Scotland, enabling them to meet their aspirations and promoting retention. According to the data, care can be enacted via educational practices that demonstrate that disabled students and their learning matter, by opening dialogues to understand the needs of disabled students, and by adopting positive and helpful attitudes, all of which would demonstrate that the whole experiences of disabled students are valued on HE in Scotland. The following section explores another strategy that demonstrates that the experiences of disabled students are acknowledged and valued in HE: promoting choice by taking an anticipatory approach to inclusive education.

5.3. "It's about choices": Promoting choice by taking an anticipatory approach

Disabled students who participated in this study highlight the impact of rigid pedagogical practices on their educational experiences. These inflexible practices do not acknowledge the diversity of the student body and maintain existing hierarchies and power imbalances in the

teacher-student relationship, having a negative impact on the progression and retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. However, participants - including disabled students, educators, and disability advisers - resist these dynamics by proposing alternative pedagogical approaches that value student diversity more effectively. These alternative pedagogies take an anticipatory approach to inclusion and diversity and are enacted by providing multiple options for engagement, expression and representation, aligned with the principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL; CAST, 2018).

Yet, different examples illustrate the existence of rigid educational practices which do not consider student diversity are provided by Anthony (PhD student) and June (undergraduate student), who struggled with oral presentations. Considering this, during his undergraduate degree Anthony avoided modules where part of the assessment depended on oral presentations. However, later in his education, when he had more confidence, Anthony had opportunities to discuss alternatives to oral presentations, such as recording them beforehand, which eased his experience. Similarly, June struggled with oral presentations, but one time she had the initiative to record her part of a group presentation in case she could not deliver it in person: *"I said, 'So I'll record my part. It means I'm still taking part, still giving my thing well'"*. This measure was welcomed by the rest of June's work group, who also decided to record their parts *"just to ensure that all the eventualities are covered"*. Although this strategy could be considered an active way of resistance to the teacher-student hierarchy, June's lecturer also welcomed the initiative. According to June, the educator appreciated the group's creativity and mentioned that it was *"a brilliant idea"*.

Difficulties with oral presentations are discussed by Tai (2023), who acknowledges that despite them being a valuable alternative to written assignments, oral presentations can be stressful for students and can put neurodiverse students and those with respiratory, language and verbal production difficulties at a disadvantage (Fuller *et al.*, 2004; Waterfield and West, 2006). Thus, although there are benefits to using this form of assessment (see Akimov and Malin, 2020; Grieve *et al.*, 2021), it is essential to provide different options for action and expression to accommodate diverse students, one of the critical guidelines of UDL (CAST, 2018). This can help enhance students' skills to demonstrate knowledge and increase the type of learners who are more likely to succeed (*ibid*).

Fostering more opportunities for discussion with disabled students can be another strategy to bring inclusion to the sector (DSUK, 2022). Creating these opportunities where disabled students become active subjects in the learning process can show them that they matter to

educators, which enhances student engagement and motivation as discussed in the previous section (see Schwartz, 2019). Thus, by using these strategies, faculty can challenge existing hierarchies and power imbalances where educators are positioned as the active subjects who design and implement educational activities and students are perceived as passive recipients who only have the option of doing what they are told. Yet, this is something that experiences like June's clearly contradict, demonstrating that disabled students can bring positive change to HE, paving the way for more inclusive practices that value student diversity.

Additionally, I could argue that what June and Anthony did was advocate for the use of different means of engagement and expression in order to meet the requirements of an educational task they found inaccessible. This is something that aligns with the principles of UDL, an approach supported by educators who participated in this study, who see it as a strategy to promote inclusion in Scottish HE. For example, lecturers like Amelia believe that the key to promoting inclusion is considering students' individuality and "*providing choices*", which she equates to high-quality teaching and considers to be the short version of what is known as UDL:

"It's about choices. It's not about forcing everybody to do things the same way. It's not about saying 'you must do an assessment in a certain way because that's the way most people like it done'".

In this regard, Amelia expands:

"So, my argument has always been that what is good for somebody with additional support needs is probably good for everybody. So, it's probably just good teaching. So, I've argued that - this is all long before Universal Design for Learning came along - and for me, it's just about that person in front of me".

Amelia's conceptualisation is very close to the principles of UDL, which is based on providing multiple means of engagement, representation, and action and expression (CAST, 2018). By offering these multiple options across the learning process, UDL acknowledges that learners will be motivated to learn by different stimuli, that there is not one means of representation that will be ideal for all learners and that expression might look differently to different people. Hence, this is a framework that acknowledges student diversity and aims to promote student engagement, enhancing student and staff satisfaction and improving learning experiences for disabled and non-disabled students (Cumming and Rose, 2021; Black *et al.*, 2015; Tobin, 2019).

According to LaRocco and Wilken (2013), increasing diversity within HE will inevitably lead to educational challenges; however, it can also foster environments where opportunities for

inclusion go beyond individualised adjustments. Individual adjustments are an essential part of inclusion (Sachs and Schreuer, 2014; Oliver, 2013), yet, universal approaches to student support are gaining relevance due to their positive influence on the experiences of disabled students in HE (Newman *et al.*, 2021). UDL is one of the frameworks that promote these broader opportunities for inclusion, as it is characterised by proactively considering how educational practice can be designed to address the wide range of diverse human needs (McGuire, Scott and Shaw, 2003; Hays and Handler, 2020).

For Dolmage (2017), principles of Universal Design (UD) acknowledge existing bias in design practices. If applied to HE, this idea emphasises that pedagogical practices have traditionally been designed for a particular group of students while disregarding others, something that supported the sector's prioritisation of narrow ways of existing and learning (Wertans and Burch, 2022). This narrow understanding is also linked with a notion of normalcy that associates non-disabled people with the norm, acknowledging how HEIs position "*non-white, working-class and/or disabled students*" as non-traditional (Madriaga *et al.*, 2011, p. 190). This is something that, according to Gibson *et al.*'s (2016) argument leads to a HE culture where those who look for equity, accessibility and educational success are oppressed and discriminated against. Alternatively, according to Dolmage (2017), practices that focus on UD, like UDL, advocate for the multiple possibilities different spaces can offer, considering a diverse group of people and not focusing on one single type of human. Hence, for this author, UDL is an issue of social justice as it addresses the need to involve everyone in conversations that "*create space*" (Dolmage, 2017, p. 132).

Moreover, although not using the UDL terminology, another educational approach based on providing different choices and means for engagement and expression was supported by educators like Morgan. More specifically, Morgan and her colleagues use a "*multi-sensory approach and a multi-activity approach*", which, although not specifically thought to accommodate disabled students, tries to cater for as many students as possible. In this regard, Morgan highlights the use of physical elements like their "*body, the tone of voice, all sorts of things to keep students engaged*". In addition, they "*use a lot of films (...) to portray real-life scenarios and real-life situations*". According to Obaid (2013), a multi-sensory teaching approach encompasses learning strategies that address two or more senses to process or express information, considering the maximum number of senses in the learning and teaching process to utilise the learners' cognitive abilities, which could lead to improved academic performance (Diverse Learners, 2015; Newman, 2018). Authors like Morgan and Klein (2000) or Mortimore (2003) (as cited in Newman, 2018) support multisensory teaching approaches as a

suitable strategy for dyslexic learners but maintain it could benefit all students, enhancing their learning experience and being a response to the increasing diversity and individual needs within HE. Thus, according to Newman (2018, p.12), multi-sensory teaching could challenge the “one size fits all” approach to education.

Hence, educators who participated in this study agreed about the value of providing different educational options, leading to more inclusive educational practices. However, the idea of promoting choice and providing different means of expression, engagement and representation requires that educators take an anticipatory approach to ensure learning design is inclusive by default instead of solely including modifications as a reaction to students’ needs or requests (Saha-Gupta, Song and Todd, 2019; Cumming and Rose, 2022). This anticipatory approach is something that characterises Amelia’s and Helen’s practice as they try to be proactive in their educational practice. More specifically, Amelia focuses on anticipating possible scenarios and planning accordingly:

“Create 100 ‘what-if scenarios’ and think about ‘What if this happened?’, ‘What if that happened?’, ‘What if you had a student like this?’, ‘What would you do?’ and try to mainstream as much of it as you can”.

Similarly, Helen (educator) believes that providing basic levels of accessibility by default makes her teaching more accommodating and inclusive. Consequently, Helen delivers most of her teaching online, with captions, and provides a recording of most sessions (unless personal experiences are shared). Additionally, Helen encourages students to engage in different ways during synchronous activities, giving them the choice to have their cameras on or off and providing varied options for them to engage by using the chat or speaking up. Another strategy used by Helen is ensuring her teaching materials, like PowerPoint slides, meet accessibility requirements that can be used for students who use screen readers. Therefore, taking an anticipatory approach means that disabled and non-disabled students are more likely to access education without having to request accommodations. This is one of the reasons Helen puts her focus on promoting accessibility and providing different access choices:

“I hope it helps them engage without (...) having to explain over and over. I know how tiring that is from my own experience, having to basically re-disclose things to people. (...) I hope (...) they don't feel like they have to share; they can still engage, you know, because (...) they might just want to come and experience a session without the hassle of explaining why they want subtitles or why they want slides in advance”.

This is an area of relevance to Helen, who has a chronic illness and often needs to self-identify repeatedly, understanding the difficulties that this entails for disabled students. Furthermore, Amelia talks about the same idea as Helen but gives it a name: “*mainstreaming [accommodations]*”, which, according to her, means that the most common individualised adjustments, usually implemented for disabled students, become available to the whole body of students. This strategy includes giving all students access to live class recordings or ensuring everyone has access to class materials in advance. In line with Helen’s approach, Amelia’s focus is on “*building-in inclusion so that fewer people have to ask for additional support*”, reducing the need for disabled students to disclose and request adjustments and the burden associated with these processes.

Thus, Helen and Amelia’s efforts focus on addressing the scenarios where the individualised accommodation system does not necessarily lead to inclusion and equality (Beck, 2022). Having to continuously re-disclose a disability has been described as one of the barriers faced by disabled students in HE (McKinney and Swartz, 2020). According to Smith, Woodhead and Chin-Newman (2021), approaches that require students to re-disclose and re-request adjustments regularly cause discomfort and might lead to higher chances of facing discrimination and stigma. Thus, reducing the need for disabled students to share or re-share their needs addresses institutional and educational barriers that individual accommodations tend to overlook (Hutcheon and Wolbring, 2012). These educators’ efforts also challenge the power dynamics that arise from having to present medical evidence to fully access education (Devlin and Pothier, 2006). As addressed in the previous chapter, these dynamics are the result of the medicalised conception many HEIs have of disability, which is reflected in their disability support policies (see Hutcheon and Wolbring, 2012). Although these policies tend to be enough for institutions to comply with policy requirements, they also contribute to power imbalances in the relationships between disabled students and educators or the university as a whole (ibid). According to Devlin and Pothier (2006, p. 197), this puts disabled students in an “*adversarial position*” because if they do not disclose their disability and provide the necessary documentation, their educational experience and aspirations could be endangered.

Taking an anticipatory approach is also supported by disability advisors like Charlotte, who believes that “*there is a number of ways that the university could rethink inclusive practice*”. As part of their role, Charlotte’s team tries to persuade educators in their institutions to adopt this method, spreading the idea that:

“working inclusively is for the benefit of all students, not just disabled students. Any adjustments that you make for disabled students will be beneficial for all students and actually, in the long run, reduce your workload, reduce student struggle, reduce students dropping out or failing”.

Moreover, Charlotte’s words echoed Dolmage’s (2017, p. 118), who states: *“design for disability and benefit all”*. Hence, there is a clear connection between implementing principles of UDL in HE as a tool for inclusion and the need to be proactive and take an anticipatory approach. This proactivity and anticipatory essence of UDL are the features most valued by Dolmage, who believes it is reflected by the verb *design*. More specifically, the main reason Dolmage (2017) likes UDL is *“because of the verb – design”* (p. 118), which denotes the active nature of the approach, as it aims to anticipate and respond to students’ needs. However, Dolmage argues that UD is not just a way of doing things, it is also about reshaping theory, discussions and priorities, and it is also about creating new opportunities for community, agency and better pedagogies. Furthermore, this author sees UD as a strategy to plan, envision and anticipate the future, recognising that disability is inherently part of our world, which in an educational context opens opportunities for educators to (re)design spaces and pedagogies (see Dolmage, 2017). This conceptualisation of disability, Dolmage argues, challenges ableism within one of the most ableist institutions: HE. Therefore, UDL can be a strategy to transform HE as a sector and promote cultures, discourses and practices in which disabled students can thrive and achieve their aspirations.

According to Beck (2022), in recent years, bodies like the Office for Students (OfS) and the Disabled Students’ Commission (DSC) have supported the elimination of learning barriers across England’s HEIs through the adoption of sector-wide, anticipatory strategies to support the inclusion of disabled students. This approach comes with the aim of reducing the focus on reasonable adjustments, what the OfS considers to be a system that aligns with the medical model of disability, aiming at fixing the student’s difficulties instead of addressing structural barriers to education (Office for Students, 2019). Thus, the OfS is currently placing attention on the promotion of inclusive practices as a core institutional element to restructure cultures and practices across the English HE sector. This alternative approach aligns with the social model of disability, which OfS endorses as *“the most effective way that universities and colleges can respond to the needs of disabled students”* (Office for Students, 2019, p. 1).

However, although the social model of disability could lead to fewer individual accommodations, prominent researchers in the field of disability maintain that despite the

increased accessibility provided by adapted environments, bodily impairments and their impact on the lives of disabled people cannot be ignored as disabled students' needs will remain despite environmental adaptations (Shakespeare and Watson, 2010). Hence, it is important to acknowledge that individual adjustments will always be necessary across HE. Still, as OfS maintains, when those accommodations are needed, institutions that have adopted an anticipatory approach to inclusion could have an increased capacity to respond to students' individual needs (Office for Students, 2019). Along the lines of the discussion in Chapter 2, Doyle and Robson (2002, as cited in Collins, Azmat and Rentschler, 2019) argue that the social model of disability applied to education highlights the need for educational spaces and practices to be rethought to foster student learning, development and growth, going beyond individual impairments. Moreover, Evans *et al.* (2017) argue that taking an anticipatory approach is one of the strategies that can help make educational communities more welcoming and value *"the multiple dimensions of students' identities and experiences"* (p. 194).

Therefore, this study provides evidence to support the adoption of anticipatory approaches that consider educational inclusion in a holistic way, based on providing choices and on the principles of UDL. The evidence indicates that this approach could help restructure a system that currently perpetuates power imbalances and discrimination towards disabled students. Yet, the question of how accepted these approaches are across HE in Scotland remains unanswered. However, the evidence generated in this study suggests that discriminatory practices are still common in the sector and that considering inclusive education from an anticipatory approach is still an aspirational task. Therefore, in line with the discussion in the literature review chapter, I argue that there is a need to consider transformative and critical approaches across the sector, something that I will turn to address in the next chapter (see Chapter 6).

5.4. *"I would love to see that stay"*: Hybrid learning as a tool for inclusion

Disabled students who participated in this study addressed the benefits of hybrid educational practices, which many considered a valid, more inclusive alternative to full-time on-campus learning. Thus, participants' discourse around hybrid learning was positive and hopeful overall, as some of the terms used to describe this approach were *"accessible"*, *"useful"*, and *"encouraging"*, and many saw it as a strategy to be kept in Scotland's post-pandemic HE. Thus, this section addresses how online and digital learning tools promoted inclusion for many

disabled students involved in this study, fostering cultures and environments in which their aspirations can be fulfilled.

Digital tools demonstrated to be invaluable during the COVID-19 pandemic, which prompted an emergency move to online and distance learning in March 2020 since these tools enabled access to education during a time of uncertainty and isolation. As HE transitioned out of the pandemic and lockdowns, online learning was supplemented with on-campus instruction, and while this is not a new approach, these circumstances led to the increased popularity of hybrid approaches to teaching and learning (Ulla and Perales, 2022). Although there is not an established consensus about the definition of hybrid learning, according to Ulla and Perales (2022) existing definitions encompass the planned combination of online and on-campus synchronous and asynchronous educational activities (Garrison and Kanuka, 2004; Watson and Murin, 2014; Baker and Spencely, 2023). Moreover, these definitions emphasise the purposive use of technology to address students' needs and increase the effectiveness of the learning environment and students' control of their educational experience (Linder, 2017; Khaled Essa, 2023). Consequently, the main value of hybrid teaching is its capacity to create interactive learning spaces that increase students' autonomy and control over the key elements of the learning environment: *"time, place, path and space"* (Khaled Essa, 2023, p. 189).

According to participants in this study (students and staff), hybrid delivery could be a way of increasing accessibility in HE in Scotland. In this regard, Stella (PhD student) said:

"Having things in sort of hybrid, it does make things a lot easier for people. (...) I definitely see the opportunity in making things online in terms of making them more accessible. (...) I would love to see that stay".

Similarly, for Kate (PhD student), the fact that *"technology has been embraced and it's kind of been pushed forward"* is *"really encouraging"*. Regarding specific strategies that promote accessibility and inclusion, participants highlight the role of recorded and online learning materials, which allow them to learn from home and, often, at their chosen time and pace. These elements were crucial for disabled students who need to manage health conditions that can, for example, impact energy levels, as they have the flexibility of engaging with the learning materials when they feel their best. For instance, although June (undergraduate student) prefers on-campus learning, she finds online delivery beneficial because it eliminates the environmental barriers found around her institution. Hence, online learning opportunities mean that June *"can be comfortable in my own home"* while attending lectures.

Likewise, learning from home helped those who find commuting difficult. Thus, not having to travel to campus regularly and the impact that could have on their health means they are in a better position to engage with education. This is the case of Kate (PhD student), who believes that

“it would be impossible for me now to manage that journey, like, daily or weekly. (...) The impact on my health would mean I had much less capacity to do the workload of the PhD”.

Along similar lines, Nicole (master’s student) says: *“If I had to go into [university] every day for an in-person part, I think I'd get really kind of fatigued, and I'd burn out really quickly”*. However, the fact that most of the learning in her master’s took place online with some on-campus activities, meant that Nicole could make the most of the in-person learning opportunities, feeling like she *“can bring a little bit more to the table”*.

Furthermore, others like Tiffany (PhD student) discussed how digital tools can promote choice and inclusion for students experiencing mental health challenges:

“Digital accessibility [is] good for people with mental health issues and people who maybe wake up one day and they can't physically get out of their bed, but they can still attend your lecture... And people with limited mobility not having to go to a 9:00 a.m. lecture on a packed train”.

As discussed in the literature review chapter, these experiences are supported by previous research as some, like Manase (2021), acknowledged that students with learning disabilities in their study benefited from online engagement, as they felt on-campus delivery limited their learning abilities. Similarly, Bones and Ellison (2022), as addressed in Chapter 2, discussed how online learning during the pandemic allowed disabled students to plan how to use their spoons. Although this term was not used by participants in the current study, the spoons metaphor is used by disabled people to *“describe the limited amounts of energy they possess”* (Bones and Ellison, 2022, p. 29). For some students in Bones and Ellison’s research, not having to travel to campus had a significant positive impact on their health as they had more control over their *spoons*, with some feeling better than ever as they could effectively prioritise their health, having more energy to dedicate to their learning. Similarly, participants in Dube and Baleni’s study (2022) discussed the positive effect of learning from comfortable places. Likewise, not having to commute to their institution and navigate its inaccessible physical environments helped reduce tiredness (ibid). Therefore, online learning might become the preferred choice for

some disabled students for as long as physical educational environments remain inaccessible. Although some people prefer to learn on campus, this might be prevented by the need to navigate inaccessible spaces, limiting disabled students' opportunities to make choices in their academic journey.

According to participants, digital learning tools also offer increased opportunities for engagement with the learning material, improving accessibility. For example, online lectures increased Nicole's (master's student) class attendance. Additionally, if she misses a live lecture, Nicole *"can just go back and watch it, and which is obviously really, really, useful. And especially for revising (...) it's massively helped"*. Moreover, recorded lectures also help Nicole's focus as *"being in a lecture hall would be really distracting"*, but recorded lectures allow her to engage with the material at her preferred pace: *"I have to listen to everything on double speed because I get distracted very easily"*. This is something that becomes very easy with recorded lectures, but would not be possible without them. Additionally, participants (including students and educators) recognise that recorded lectures could help ensure that live teaching materials have captions, which are necessary for Deaf students and can support students with processing difficulties and international students for whom English is not their first language. These perks are acknowledged by researchers like Manase (2021), whose South African study demonstrates that students with learning disabilities benefited from online learning, which helped them avoid the distractions of the physical classroom. Additionally, having access to recorded lectures meant they could pace their learning without time pressures and had enhanced access to assistive software. However, as acknowledged in the literature review chapter, Manase (2021) recognises that individual students are impacted differently by learning conditions, with some benefiting from online and hybrid learning and some finding it a struggle. These experiences are echoed by educators like Morgan, who also believe that online and asynchronous resources give students more control to adjust the materials to their needs:

"The digital format means that all of the teaching and learning resources are completely and utterly adjustable by the student. (...) It's so much more straightforward online (...) to be able to ensure that our learning resources are as accessible as possible".

As addressed in this study's literature review, Fichten *et al.* (2009) discussed the increased opportunities provided by e-learning, which allowed disabled students to access digital resources independently without support. Although the element of adjusting learning materials has not been widely discussed in the literature, authors like Verdinelli and Kutner (2016) highlight that online learning gives disabled students an additional sense of control over their

educational experience. The autonomy of adapting learning materials to one's needs could also lead to this increased sense of control these authors mentioned, which they link to an augmented sense of academic achievement and self-efficacy, having a positive impact on the persistence of disabled students in HE (ibid).

Hence, I would argue that making digital learning tools and hybrid learning a part of regular practice in HE in Scotland can alter current power dynamics as (disabled) students gain autonomy and effective access to education. Introducing online and digital learning as standardised practice in the sector could help position disabled students as active subjects with more control over how they access education, reducing their need for individual accommodations. This is supported by some like Sullivan and Moriarty (2009) and Freeman and Jurow (2017) (as cited in Sullivan, 2021) argue that this increased independence might require a rethought of the teacher's role, which from a critical pedagogy standpoint would be accompanied by a move towards less hierarchical power relationships within the online classroom, encouraging teacher's and students' simultaneous learning.

Considering the benefits of hybrid learning, educators like Amelia believe that providing lecture recordings in combination with synchronous learning activities is one of the main changes that should be kept in HE after the pandemic: *"That's the best blend as we come out of COVID"*. Other educators like Helen agree with Amelia, believing that the options provided by hybrid delivery *"did open up more learning opportunities"*, promoting inclusion for disabled and other groups of students: *"It's not just for inclusion around disability; it's for people with caring responsibilities, travel..."*. Yet, although Helen and Amelia tried to promote hybrid educational practices before the pandemic via online synchronous and recorded lectures, due to the positive impact these can have on the student experience (Brooks *et al.*, 2014; Morris, Swinnerton and Coop, 2019; Bordes *et al.*, 2021; Srinivasan, Ramos and Muhammad, 2021) they were met with resistance. This means that for some like Helen, who *"had argued for things to be online (...) for a while"*, the pandemic became a unique opportunity to accelerate this transformation as otherwise, *"it would have needed more convincing"*.

Similarly, other educators like Sophia believe that despite the tragedy of the pandemic, it created opportunities for change, accelerating innovation across the Scottish HE sector. In this regard, Sophia says:

"I found the pandemic (...) made me stop; it made me think more about what I was doing. It made me more creative, and (...) we lost a lot of the things that we did (...) because we always did, as opposed to doing things because it's maybe the best way".

Along the same lines, Amelia (educator) believes that the pandemic *“forced us to look at options that we might not have bothered to consider or put off considering for a longer period”*. Relatedly, Helen (educator) says that if the educational practice is designed with hybrid learning in mind, *“it can be as good”*. Thus, participants’ discussions align with Ferri, Grifoni and Guzzo (2020) and Srinivasan, Ramos and Muhammad (2021) who recognise that the pandemic was an opportunity to accelerate educational change.

Nonetheless, participants’ words indicated the existing resistance to accepting hybrid learning as a part of post-pandemic HE in Scotland. This was echoed by Morgan (educator), who believes that

“people are quite desperate to get back to the way things were, rather than learning the lessons of the pandemic (...). And it just seems that there's a big run back to campus, and I'm not sure that's the best way forward”.

Along similar lines, students like Tiffany believe that returning to complete on-campus delivery would dismiss the inclusive potential of hybrid learning, leading to further exclusion:

“able-bodied, neurotypical people are making these decisions for the many, and it's really short-sighted. (...) It's really ableist, to be like ‘Oh, we can get back on campus, so let's do it’... Well, not everyone can”.

Similarly, Kate (PhD student) was frustrated by *“this getting-back-to-normal rhetoric, because normal wasn't working for a lot of people before the pandemic”*. In this regard, Helen wonders why *“we can't go proper hybrid. Like why we don't embrace all the good things from both and try and keep them both”* instead of treating hybrid learning (and working) as *“replacements”* during an *“emergency”*. Therefore, digital and online resources are valuable tools to ensure learning resources are accessible and inclusive for a wider range of students. Thus, although the COVID-19 pandemic generated undeniable collective trauma, there seem to be educational lessons to be learned from this difficult time, which could help promote inclusion and accessibility in HE (DSUK, 2022).

Hence, educators and students in this research believe there is value in maintaining a hybrid approach in post-pandemic HE in Scotland. This evidence supports research illustrating that some disabled students had better access to education during the pandemic, as many of the barriers encountered previously were eliminated (DSUK, 2022; Bones and Ellison, 2022). These findings also reinforce existing literature that sheds light on HE as an intrinsically ableist sector, where marginalising practices, hierarchies and power imbalances are common (see Dolmage,

2017; Brown and Leigh, 2018). Hence, it is understandable that an experience like the COVID-19 pandemic that brought the sector to a halt and made us rethink educational practices and spaces became an opportunity for change. Therefore, going back to *normal* is not an option for many (DSUK, 2022). Although technology and digital learning tools will not magically erase discrimination from HE (Koseoglu, 2020; Xiao, 2021), they must be understood as a strategy to improve accessibility to HE and as a way to acknowledge students' diverse experiences.

Authors like Koseoglu (2020), citing Ahmed (2017, p. 110), acknowledge the importance of access as a necessary requisite to "*enter a world*" - in this case, online and hybrid learning can be considered one of the keys disabled students can use to enter the world of HE. However, Koseoglu (2020) recognises that access does not equal social equity due to the structural discrimination caused by, for example, ableism. In this regard, Selwyn *et al.* (2019) argue that online and distance education can be spaces that promote both emancipation and neoliberal oppression. However, if learning technologies are used critically, under participatory pedagogic approaches, their potential to create emancipatory spaces increases (see Migueliz Valcarlos *et al.*, 2020; Selwyn *et al.*, 2020). Thus, Koseoglu (2020) advocates for feminist virtual pedagogies that acknowledge the variability of the student experience and do not assume all students learning online fit into the abstract idea of a self-reliant, completely autonomous male student, which is the dominant narrative within online education discourses. In this regard, Koseoglu (2020) calls for feminist pedagogies that focus on educational relationships and take an ethical stance to support students and tackle the inequalities and vulnerabilities that some, like disabled students, face while learning in a hybrid mode.

Thus, while the potential for inclusion of hybrid learning has been illustrated in this chapter, many obstacles have also been described by the literature. These obstacles include disabled students' lack of access to technology, limited disability support, reduced course satisfaction, motivation, and capacity to focus, additional workload and difficulties in accessing academic support (Hussein *et al.*, 2020; Means and Neisler, 2021; Gin *et al.*, 2022). Other difficulties include a lack of social engagement and a sense of belonging (see Bones and Ellison, 2022; Manase, 2021). Hence, the online learning experiences of disabled students are contained in a continuum where positives exist alongside negatives. This spectrum is vividly identified by the metaphor found in Goegan, Lee and Daniels' study (2023), where one participant defined it as a rollercoaster.

This spectrum is also reflected in the current study, as although most participants benefited from hybrid learning, some experienced difficulties. This was the case for Mark and Richard

(PhD students), who preferred to work on campus, as this helped them avoid distractions and increase social engagement. Similarly, June (undergraduate student) focused on the negative impact that online learning had on her feelings of social integration and sense of belonging. This is important as social integration and a sense of belonging have been recognised as key elements of the student experience, having a great influence on retention (see Chapter 2; Kirk, 2018, Farr-Wharton *et al.*, 2018). As this was a key topic of discussion for participants, I will turn to examine the difficulties related to developing a sense of belonging and hybrid learning in the following section.

The evidence discussed in this section demonstrates that hybrid learning must be considered as a tool for inclusion in HE in Scotland, although the effective implementation of hybrid learning is not an easy task. Thus, it is important that HE educators make critical use of it, considering its potential to perpetuate the exclusion and discrimination of disabled students. Moreover, the data also demonstrates that despite its observed benefits and that the COVID-19 pandemic acted as a catalyst to implement digital innovation in the sector, there is resistance across HE in Scotland to make hybrid learning a common practice. However, it is also necessary to address the difficulties related to online and hybrid learning, particularly concerning disabled students' social integration and sense of belonging.

5.5. “Do they even realise I'm gone?”: Spaces, relationships and sense of belonging

The evidence provided in the previous section illustrated how digital learning tools and hybrid delivery enhance the experiences of disabled students in HE in Scotland and promote their inclusion and retention. This discussion has contextual significance because the interviews that make up the primary data generated in this study were conducted during and shortly after the COVID-19 pandemic (2021 – 2022) when most of the HEIs involved were still working mostly online. Yet, while there was a general agreement about the positive effect of hybrid learning on accessibility across the sector, participants also discussed its negative influence on disabled students' sense of belonging. In this regard, disabled students who participated in this study talked about experiencing isolation and disengagement while learning online. Likewise, educators recognise students' struggles to learn remotely and in isolation, which they believe impacted disabled students' learning experience and progression. Moreover, both groups of participants recognise the importance of relationships and spaces in developing a sense of belonging, and how online learning might reduce natural opportunities for engagement with

peers and faculty, hindering the development of student identities and sense of belonging. Thus, the section illustrates the importance of considering disabled students' sense of belonging when implementing online and hybrid pedagogical strategies.

For former students like Nina (who had recently graduated with her master's degree), being part of small classes was essential to boost her academic satisfaction because working in smaller groups meant that *“lecturers could know you better”* and *“it was easier to talk to students and then be included in class activities”*. These factors meant Nina *“loved the master's more than my bachelor's degree because I felt it was smaller groups”*. This social connection with peers and educators was essential for an effective educational experience in the case of Nina. However, being included in class activities and knowing educators better became a challenge during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly while students adjusted to online learning. Hence, although some would like to see a hybrid approach maintained in post-pandemic HE, others highlight the lack of social engagement they felt while learning online. This is the case for June (undergraduate student), who says:

“I don't like online learning because when you're sitting in your house, you're too distracted. You know, a lot of lecturers don't mind if you put your camera off. So, you know that half your class is not engaging. And when you go into breakout rooms, [other students] are not engaging”.

Thus, June prefers learning on-campus because *“there's more people; you get to meet with your classmates. They're not just somebody on the other side of your screen”*; this lack of engagement and peer connection made June's first year *“very, very difficult”*. Social integration was a construct covered in this study's literature review (see Chapter 2) as it has been widely accepted as a key factor in the promotion of disabled students' persistence and retention in HE (see DaDeppo, 2009; Mamiseishvili and Koch, 2011; Fichten *et al.*, 2014; Koch, Mamiseishvili and Higgins, 2014; Kutscher and Tuckwiller, 2019).

The importance of social integration was first addressed by Tinto (1975) in relation to the retention of the general body of students. It gains relevance for disabled students as those who feel isolated and who do not engage in extra-curricular and peer activities are more likely to exit their programmes before completion (Mamiseishvili and Koch, 2011; Kutscher and Tuckwiller, 2019). Yet, according to previous research, not many disabled students get to take part in this type of activity (Koch, Mamiseishvili and Higgins, 2014). Thus, it is necessary to consider the effect that online and hybrid learning can have on the opportunities for disabled students to participate in social events, particularly considering that, as the data discussed here

demonstrates, remote engagement is not as effective in building social connections between students. Therefore, June's words illustrate the problematic balance between the advantages of using digital and online learning tools, which increase accessibility, and their disadvantages due to their negative influence on social engagement and sense of belonging, which is the essence of this and the previous sections.

Furthermore, June's words illustrate another dilemma since, as she points out, some students are reluctant to turn on their cameras during synchronous online learning activities, something she found detrimental to social connection. While Castelli and Sarvary (2021) report on several benefits of having cameras on during synchronous online learning as identified by previous research, including better communication and collaboration or the development of a sense of belonging, students might have good reasons to avoid doing so. These reasons include difficulties with internet connection, concerns about letting their peers see their home environments or lack of private learning spaces (Castelli and Sarvary, 2021; Gavaldon *et al.*, 2022), which means that not making "cameras on" a requirement is "*the best student-centred policy*" (Castelli and Sarvary, 2021, p. 3566).

Thus, mandating students to turn on their cameras is not an accessible pedagogical decision which does not align with the UDL principles since it does not offer students different options for engagement (CAST, 2018). Still, June's struggles due to lack of social connection were significant and did not happen in isolation as other students echoed similar feelings. In this regard, Kevin (a former undergraduate student) faced increased feelings of isolation and depression during the pandemic, something fuelled by the "*lack of human element*", which hampered his learning experience and overall HE journey:

"The lockdowns made me feel my own internal isolation and (...) made me feel really disconnected from the course where, without a person physically in front of me, I just couldn't really connect to it or understand. So, it [kind of] didn't really feel like I'm even really on a course in a way. Like it just felt less impactful on a computer".

Relationships with academic staff also became an important element in relation to belonging. One example is Nicole (master's student), who recalled her difficulties engaging with lecturers while learning online as it caused a detachment between students and educators, making it challenging to build meaningful connections. Hence, Nicole felt the onus was on the students to try and bridge that gap:

“There's a bit of a disconnect (...) with the academics because you're not there and you're not engaging with them as you would like if you were doing in-person lectures (...). You could catch them and have a chat or ask questions and things. Whereas I think now (...) unless you make like a real effort to have a conversation with them or reach out, you really are just like a face (...) on a screen”.

However, this disconnect can have a significant influence on students like Kevin, for whom the pandemic made them feel isolated and disconnected, making him believe that his absence would go unnoticed when he had to leave his degree before completion: *“Do they even realise I'm gone? (...) I'm not really sure... I wouldn't even know how they feel; if they even noticed it's happened”.*

Additionally, Tiffany (PhD student), who unexpectedly had to do another online degree as she started her PhD during the pandemic and could not access her HEI's physical campus, discussed how different approaches to online learning can affect students' sense of belonging. Thus, when Tiffany, who had completed HE online programmes, compares her pre- and post-pandemic online HE experiences, she maintains that she felt a stronger sense of belonging in the latter: *“I guess I've accidentally done another distance degree. But yeah, it's completely night and day”.* According to Tiffany, during her previous online degrees, little consideration was given to building connections between students and educators, which meant that Tiffany felt like an anonymous student:

“At my last [university], even though I was there for like almost four years, (...) there was no real sense of belonging. And frankly, I was worried when I asked for a reference for my PhD (...) that the programme leader wouldn't know who I was. (...) I mean, I went to my graduation, but even then I was just a face in the crowd. (...) I didn't feel like I was at [university]. It felt like a means to an end”.

Although not as prominent as social integration with peers, academic integration also plays a key role in the experiences of disabled students, acting as a protective factor towards disabled students' persistence and retention (Koch, Mamiseishvili and Higgins, 2014; Newman *et al.*, 2021), as discussed in Chapter 2. According to Bovill (2020a) there is a large body of research illustrating the benefits of fostering HE staff-student relationships. This body of literature highlights that consistent and positive interactions between students and educators are associated with improved students' academic outcomes, autonomy, satisfaction, engagement, motivation and personal and intellectual development (see Hoffman, 2014; Bovill, 2020a). Moreover, Bovill (2020b) argues that educators who promote positive relationships as part of

their online or on-campus practice could help build meaningful and inclusive learning spaces that can benefit all students. Yet, excessive workloads and, recently, the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic have had a significant impact on staff-student relationships, which might be at risk of deteriorating due to the limited opportunities for meaningful interactions (Hoffman, 2014; Wallace *et al.*, 2021).

When looking for the reasons hindering social connections while learning online, some participants highlighted the crucial role of course inductions, something that not all considered when pivoting to online learning. In this case, June (undergraduate student), discussed how, despite the “*weird experience*” of starting university online during a pandemic, her institution did not put much effort into making the transition to online learning more manageable. In this regard, June criticises that they “*never done inductions. (...) Basically, it was ‘This is your first class, It’s online. Join the Zoom link’. And there were like 120 people in the class all on Zoom*”. Similarly, Nicole (master’s student) recalls: “*There wasn’t really a lot of induction events*” and “*they didn’t really offer very much kind of to meet other people, (...) which I think is a shame because that would have really encouraged a lot more interaction*”.

Furthermore, educators like Cara also argue that difficulties related to developing a sense of belonging while learning online could be traced back to the lack of induction periods during the pandemic. In this case, Cara noticed that during her first on-campus lecture after the lockdowns were lifted, “*the atmosphere in the room was really kind of awkward and tense, and students weren’t really talking to each other*”. When Cara asked, students said, “*no, we’ve never met*”, despite being “*halfway through year two*”. However, after doing “*a kind of a mini-induction, they started talking to each other. They kind of started talking and engaged*”.

Therefore, despite being identified as a strategy to ease students’ transitions to online and distance learning (Forrester *et al.*, 2005), induction periods were neglected during the COVID-19 pandemic, as not much evidence exploring this area has been identified. One of the few studies identified which addressed inductions during the pandemic was Kyne and Thompson’s (2020) work. These authors discussed their concern over the effect of cancelling inductions during the COVID-19 pandemic, as it could impact the social and collaborative relationships students tend to build during this phase.

The experiences discussed in this section illustrate the importance of creating virtual spaces for social connection when physical spaces are not available. According to Ahmed (2014), our interactions with the spaces and bodies that surround us shape our sense of belonging. Hence, if online and hybrid learning reduce the available spaces for spontaneous interactions, HEIs will

need to create opportunities that foster connections between students and between students and faculty. This is what Tiffany's HEI did, creating virtual opportunities for engagement by organising "*check-in meetings, virtual coffees and everything; every effort has been made to reach out to all the students and just make sure there's a point of contact*". These strategies made Tiffany feel like she belonged: "*I feel like I'm at the [university] even though I'm just in my room, just typing away*". This could be because, as part of their emergency response to the pandemic, Tiffany's institution put extra effort into connecting with students, most of whom were not meant to be learning online and all of whom were experiencing a world-changing, traumatic event. Hence, Tiffany's experience illustrates that her institution was aware of the impact of belonging and emotions on students' learning experiences and of the relational nature of learning (Bovill, 2020). Her enhanced sense of belonging resulted from meaningful interactions (Thomas, 2012), which, although could not take place spontaneously in physical spaces, were encouraged by the creation of digital ones.

Nevertheless, while initiatives like that taken by Tiffany's HEIs are positive, they also highlight a power imbalance as it is educators and administrators who can easily create opportunities for engagement, as opposed to (disabled) students, who struggled to create spaces in which they could connect with peers and faculty. One example is shared above by Nicole, who had to make "*a real effort*" if she wanted to have a conversation with her lecturers. Hence, these dynamics highlight how belonging to HE is "*shaped by space and power*" (Carruthers-Thomas, 2021, p. 5) as HE can be a place of social relations determined by the traditional and patriarchal academic discourses and traditions that govern the sector. These elements, Carruthers-Thomas (2021) says, create power dynamics where some groups and individuals are "*more in charge*" (Massey, 1994, p. 149) than others, and those in charge create "*flows and movement*", but "*others don't*" (ibid).

The words of educators involved in this study echoed those of disabled students as they recognised the difficulties students experienced while learning in such unusual and isolated circumstances. According to Cara (educator), this issue impacted students' learning experience:

"They were missing the peer support and the support that they get from other students. And they just weren't able to understand and take in the knowledge in the same way that they would do if they were in the classroom with their laptop or a pen or asking people, (...) they just couldn't process in the same way".

This is something supported by Morgan (educator), who believes that relational aspects are an important part of HE, but were out of reach for disabled students while learning from home:

“All students, but [particularly] students with disability, who’d benefit from a closeness to other people to be able to feel that they’re developing an identity, as part of developing identity is about learning with others and socially constructing that learning. But [for] some students and I don’t know if it’s about disability, but some students absolutely could not do it”.

Similarly, Sally (educator) worries about the effect of online asynchronous learning on student connection and belonging: *“If you’ve got a lecture and you can watch it whenever you want, you’re not really there. (...) Then they’ve not got that sense of belonging”*. In this regard, Sally wonders, *“If you can do everything online in the middle of the night, then how much of a belonging do you feel?”*. Sally worries that this lack of sense of belonging and potential isolation that some students feel could be hindering their progression and retention:

“What have you got to keep you there? You don’t have that sense of belonging that you should have to keep you there. I think [because] your degree is [going to] be tough, and if you don’t have a support mechanism and you don’t have a sense of belonging then it’s very easy just to stop coming”.

Hence, Sally thinks that synchronous online activities could be beneficial to ensure students are *“there online at the same time, and they can chat to each other”*, promoting social engagement. Otherwise, Sally believes that *“when the course gets difficult, they’ll be struggling academically, and they’ll have no friends. (...) They’ll just be sitting in their bedroom on their own”*, which can be *“really tough”*.

These educators’ beliefs match previous research findings, which highlight the essential role of spaces, interactions and community building in the learning experience of HE students, something that was impacted during the COVID-19 pandemic. One example is Mulrooney and Kelly’s (2020) study as these authors argue that feelings of belonging decreased during the COVID-19 pandemic among HE students and staff at the UK institution where they developed their research. Likewise, Prodgers, Travis and Pownall (2023) describe how students who participated in their investigation felt separated and isolated from their peers due to not being able to *“see, meet and share space with fellow students”* (p. 1225). Hence, participants in that study considered that being part of a group and experiencing studying as a communal experience was crucial to their learning, which became difficult or impossible during the

pandemic (ibid). Thus, current findings also demonstrate the importance of considering spaces and relationships during hybrid or online learning and paying particular attention to disabled students' sense of belonging as a strategy to promote persistence and retention. After all, according to Tinto (2003), "*students who learn are students who stay*", but if the learning experience of disabled students is affected by lack of engagement and isolation, then how meaningful is that learning experience, and how could this impact their educational aspirations?

Yet, although it is worth noting that participants like undergraduate student June and PhD students Anthony, Richard and Mark believed that their sense of belonging improved when learning on campus, this was not always the case, particularly when on-campus environments are not accessible. For example, Colin (undergraduate student) talked about how he wishes break times were extended when learning on campus so he could have enough time to go for a coffee with his classmates and be back on time for the rest of the class. This is because classrooms are located far from the canteen, and the way to them is not entirely accessible. For Colin, having this extra time would mean he could

"feel as if I'm part of the whole thing rather than feeling as if I'm not part of it because I can't go for a coffee with the rest". Yet, when learning from home, Colin felt he did not have "that problem. When I was learning at home, I was able to sit with a cup of coffee".

Hence, it should not be taken for granted that on-campus learning promotes increased levels of sense of belonging for disabled students, as physical barriers are still an issue for concern (Agarwal *et al.*, 2015; Wertans and Burch, 2022). Thus, while physical inaccessibility remains, the disruption it causes to disabled students must also be considered across teaching and learning plans to promote the engagement and participation of all students (Yusof *et al.*, 2020). According to Wertans and Bruch (2022), the additional labour of disabled students who have to navigate inaccessible educational spaces can take a significant energetic and emotional toll, leading to feelings of frustration and a lack of sense of belonging. These additional efforts could also cause "*the internalisation of oppression*" (Wertans and Burch, 2022, p. 69) as exclusion and discrimination become an accepted reality for disabled students. Hence, for disabled HE students, ineffective physical accessibility is not only a matter of access but an issue of belonging, participation and engagement (ibid).

The evidence portrayed in this section adds to the existing research discussing the importance of relationships and spaces in the development of students' sense of belonging, a vital factor for student persistence and retention. Furthermore, this evidence illustrates some of the

consequences of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, which shifted the spaces available and temporarily erased some of them. While in some cases, the creation of virtual spaces helped face these negative consequences, in others, it was not sufficient as disabled students struggled with the lack of human element and opportunities to join and create spaces for engagement. Thus, in line with Carruthers-Thomas' (2021) analysis of student retention, it is necessary to ask what (physical and virtual) spaces disabled students currently occupy in hybrid HE, and what does that imply for their sense of belonging? These questions gain relevance when considering disabled students' diverse identities and how hybrid ways of educational engagement could impede student inclusion, participation and belongingness (Thomas, 2012). Consequently, while I believe there are multiple benefits to the implementation of online and digital learning tools in post-pandemic HE in Scotland as an instrument to enhance access and inclusion, these tools cannot be considered an easy fix or a solution to all the barriers and ableism in the sector (see Koseoglu, 2020; Xiao, 2021). Hence, I support Xiao's view (2021, p. 141) of a post-pandemic educational landscape defined by "*care, inclusion and equity*" - the value of which is demonstrated in this chapter - and in which technology is a "*but a means, not an end*".

5.6. Conclusions

In this chapter, I have examined the need to promote care-based pedagogical approaches across a sector defined by neoliberal ableism. Therefore, this chapter has helped address this study's research questions as it illustrated how existing cultures, discourses and practices foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE and can hinder their persistence while addressing strategies to challenge them and address some of the sector's areas for concern.

Thus, in this chapter, I illustrated the narrow conceptualisation of disabled students, whose complex experiences are not always considered in the design and implementation of educational practices across HE in Scotland and how current cultures and discourses perpetuate these discriminatory practices, which means the system is not designed for disabled students. However, the chapter has also illustrated how participants resist these ableist notions across HE in Scotland by advocating for practices that acknowledge diversity amongst students and recognise disability as an intrinsic part of the human experience. In this regard, I, and most participants, believe that this calls for a reconceptualization of the sector to challenge and address current hierarchies and power imbalances.

Thus, this chapter focuses on the positive potential of adopting care-based pedagogies across HE in Scotland, fully valuing disabled students' experiences and existence and creating room for meaningful collaboration and relations between learners and educators. This is reflected in educators' commitment to take an anticipatory approach to inclusion, foreseeing students' needs and responding to them. Although their focus in the context of this study was to enhance disabled students' learning experiences and aspirations, there is a recognition of the positive impact this could have on all students across the sector. Moreover, while I acknowledged and examined its dangers in relation to disabled students' sense of belonging, the evidence positions hybrid learning as a tool to promote accessibility across Scottish HE. Hence, according to the data, the increased use of digital and online learning tools came as a hopeful sign of transformation within the sector, being one of the main lessons to be learned from the COVID-19 pandemic.

In this landscape of more flexible and varied modes of learning and engagement, relationships and spaces gain relevance, as it is important to create enabling environments that support the development of disabled students' sense of belonging. Moreover, it is necessary to acknowledge that hybrid learning, like any other educational initiative, should be conceived with care and compassion and must be considered an instrument to enhance students' experiences, allowing them to thrive and fulfil their aspirations. Nevertheless, there is evidence of resistance around the sector to maintain hybrid learning approaches, which is perceived as an ableist decision that disregards its multiple benefits towards disabled students in HE in Scotland.

Therefore, this chapter presents hopeful and dynamic alternatives to current ableist educational cultures, discourses and practices and opens a discussion towards more caring and flexible pedagogies to resist current inequalities, enhance the experiences of disabled students and promote their retention. Furthermore, this chapter offers answers to some of the difficulties discussed in the previous chapter (Chapter 4), as the evidence demonstrates that disabled students in Scotland struggle to access disability support, while still facing countless barriers resulting from the sector's ableist notions which can foreclose their educational aspirations.

Thus, while I recognise and defend the importance of individual support, I argue that there are strategies to make the HE sector in Scotland more accessible and welcoming, and one in which disabled students can thrive in the same capacity as their non-disabled peers. This was demonstrated in the present chapter as the three groups of participants involved in the study

discussed the benefits (and necessity) of increasing choice, flexibility, compassion and care across the sector. In the following chapter, I turn to discuss these practices more broadly, considering their implications for educational practice across HE in Scotland and relating the alternatives proposed here to the challenges discussed in the previous chapter.

Chapter 6:

Discussion, Reflections, and Next Steps

Chapters 4 and 5 addressed the research questions in this study, using empirical data generated in this research while following a feminist poststructuralist (FPS) framework. More specifically, the two research questions these chapters addressed are as follows:

- **Research Question 1:** How do cultures, discourses, and practices fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland? How does this shape their retention in the sector?
- **Research Question 2:** In which ways do the stakeholders involved consider that there is room for improvement when it comes to promoting the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland?

In addressing these two research questions, in chapters 4 and 5, I identified two areas of interest in relation to the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland, which are disability support services and pedagogy. According to the data generated, these two spheres influence participants' experiences and determine their capacity in which the sector helps fulfil or foreclose their aspirations. Additionally, I argue that this study's findings also call for a more comprehensive understanding of disabled students' retention that considers how current cultures, discourses and practices help fulfil or foreclose their aspirations.

More specifically, the data analysed in this study demonstrate that current discourses across disability support in Scotland perpetuate a shared idealised notion of disabled students in HE. According to this idealised notion, most, if not all, disabled students in the sector are undergraduates and have access to medical certification, which means they can easily access disability support. Yet, the reality of the participants in this study demonstrates that disabled students who do not fit into those idealised criteria experience difficulties accessing support and face further discrimination and exclusion in the sector. This means that approaches aimed at supporting students often become a barrier in itself, emphasising how the sector is not designed for disabled students.

Thus, I argue that ableist notions are so ingrained in the sector that even the support provision process leads to the recurring discrimination of disabled students, particularly those who do not fit into the shared notion of the ideal disabled student. Hence, after the discursive and thematic analyses I did of these data, I argue that this discrimination results from a medicalised

and minimalistic approach where institutions favour compliance over human needs. Along similar lines, educational practices are often designed with a restricted understanding of what it means to be a student, not considering the complex human experiences of disabled students (Dolmage, 2017). Moreover, these findings also illustrate how there is often a lack of responsibility and care towards the complex experiences of disabled students, who are not valued across the sector. These difficulties are due to the neoliberal ableist ideas that prioritise narrow ways of being and succeeding, perceiving care and compassion as a weakness (Giroux, 2010; see Dolmage, 2017), underpinning current cultures, practices and discourses across the sector.

However, while this landscape creates systemic discrimination and marginalisation of disabled students, the data illustrates multiple examples of resistance that can help challenge the status quo and bring transformative change across the sector. More specifically, chapters 4 and 5 illustrate participants' willingness to promote care-based and inclusive anticipatory approaches to bring more inclusion to the sector. In this regard, participants discussed the need to value disabled students' overall humanity and learning to promote choice and a sense of belonging. I argue that adopting these approaches could bring innovation to the sector, promoting educational cultures, discourses and practices that enable environments that help disabled students thrive and fulfil their aspirations, instead of being a place of exclusion.

Considering these elements, in the current chapter, I address the cultures and discourses that sustain the discriminatory practices that discriminate against disabled students in the sector, as identified in chapters 4 and 5. I discuss these cultures and discourses in relation to existing evidence and their implications for educational practice and policy across HE in Scotland. However, while a more nuanced discussion of these elements was offered in the previous two chapters, in this one, I focus on the main elements identified within those cultures and discourses, which underly and shape different practices across the sector. The first of these two areas addresses the discourse of normalcy enacted through the idealised conception of disabled students. This discussion offers a more in-depth understanding of this notion in relation to the experiences of disabled students and proposes intersectionality as a strategy to disrupt said notion and discourse. The second area concentrates on care and responsibility as the key elements that I would argue should influence the sectors' cultures, practices and discourses to enhance the experience of disabled students. In this regard, I offer a discussion that proposes the critical integration of these two constructs across different areas of HE as a demonstration that the learning and aspirations of disabled students matter. Hence, this part of the chapter elaborates on the discussions of this study's findings, where participants advocated

for care-based pedagogies and increased responsibility as a strategy to challenge current discourses and practices that do not always acknowledge the complex experiences of disabled students.

Thus, in the context of critical, socially just and feminist pedagogies, these discussions address why it is necessary to put care and responsibility at the centre of educational practice to promote genuine transformation across HE in Scotland to promote the retention of disabled students, but also their opportunities to flourishing within the sector. Finally, the chapter ends by considering the implications of undertaking these approaches, as well as the multiple possibilities and challenges they present.

Furthermore, after conducting the analysis, I argue that a more comprehensive understanding of the retention of disabled students is necessary. Thus, as the current study illustrates, the retention of students like disabled students who still face marginalise in HE can be shaped by the cultures, discourses and practices that allow them to thrive in the sector, or that exclude them from effective access to education. Therefore, I argue that future studies of disabled students' retention acknowledge this complexity and consider the implications it can have on their persistence and on educational cultures and practice overall. Hence, this broader conceptualisation should go beyond graduation and completion rates and acknowledge how the sector helps disabled students fulfil their aspirations or forecloses these same aspirations and how this relates to retention and persistence. Thus, I believe this understanding of retention should reflect the complexity of the experiences of disabled students and that their retention can be shaped by the extent to which they can fulfil their aspirations of HE.

Additionally, expanding from the above-mentioned discussions, in the present chapter, I also offer reflections related to the research process itself and to the impact that these findings can have on research and practice. This is complemented by a comprehensive set of recommendations aimed at different members of the educational community; recommendations that were developed from participants' suggestions for change, and from the ones I developed after conducting this research project. With this, I also address the study's second research question and explore how participants believe there is room for improvement when it comes to promoting the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland.

Considering these findings and conclusions, the present chapter extends previous discussions in relation to both research questions by analysing the implications and multiple possibilities for change that the present findings open within HE in Scotland. The first part of this discussion concentrates on my argument for adopting an intersectional approach to help challenge the

idealised notion of disabled students. The second part addressed the need for care- and responsibility-based approaches across the sector. In the third place, the chapter addresses the multiple possibilities and challenges of implementing these approaches in HE in Scotland, which is followed by my reflections regarding the study's strengths and limitations. The chapter ends with recommendations made to the educational community across HE in Scotland and the final chapter conclusions.

6.1. Towards intersectionality: Challenging the idealised disabled student notion

The data generated in this study illustrated existing discourses that demonstrate a shared idealised notion of the identities of disabled students in the sector. I argue that this notion leads to practices that value a narrow conception of the disabled student experience. According to these findings, this is something that can be reflected in the sphere of disability support but also in teaching and learning, as some participants believe that the HE system is designed for those ideal disabled students without considering more diverse experiences. As argued in the previous chapter, I maintain that this notion, in which some students' identities are perceived as the norm and others are silenced, leads to the discrimination and neglect of those who do not meet these shared criteria, creating a series of harmful hierarchies. Thus, in this section, I will offer a more detailed discussion of the idealised conception of disabled students identified in this study, detailing some of the criteria that make up this idealised notion and how neoliberal principles perpetuate this conception in HE in Scotland. In the second instance, I will address the need for an intersectional approach to challenge this idealised and often pervasive notion.

6.1.1. Understanding the idealised notion of disabled students in HE

Madriaga *et al.* (2011) highlight the negative impact of an existing sense of normalcy within the United Kingdom's (UK) HE systems, which the authors argue results from eugenics and positioning non-disabled students as the norm. This sense of normalcy is also the result of neoliberal agendas dominant across HE that promote a logic based on corporatisation and hyper-productivity (Bozalek, 2021). Consequently, HEIs respond to market and corporate-oriented principles and cultures that sustain values of competitiveness (see Cairo and Cabal, 2021), something to which only specific (most likely non-disabled) students can adhere. Madriaga *et al.* (2011) acknowledge that these notions of normalcy in HE result in hierarchies that are a sign of oppression and, therefore, should be rejected.

Thus, while this study echoes Madriaga *et al.*'s (2011) understanding of normalcy, it also portrays a further conceptualisation of the term within the HE disabled student community. While Madriaga *et al.* (2011) highlighted the divide between disabled and non-disabled students, my conceptualisation goes a step further as, in this case, the binary happens within the disabled students' community, positioning some as *ideal* disabled students and others as *non-ideal* disabled students. Thus, this creates a further hierarchy in which disabled students who do not meet the idealised criteria shared across HE face disadvantages in comparison to non-disabled students but also to *ideal* disabled students. This binary and the additional hierarchies it creates lead to the othering of disabled students who do not fit into the shared ideal standards of what the HE in Scotland sector believes it means to be a disabled student. Thus, this notion influences discourses and practices that position, once again, disabled students as outsiders. This is seen in the previous chapters' discussions of how disabled students who do not meet certain criteria, such as being postgraduate students who do not have access to medical certification, are perceived as *non-ideal* disabled students and experience additional discrimination.

The concept of ideal/idealised student has been previously discussed in the literature, but mainly highlighting the able-bodied (*ideal*) and disabled (*non-ideal*) students as binary opposites. For instance, as addressed in the literature review (see Chapter 2), authors like Nieminen and Pesonen (2022) discussed the concept of ideal students in HE, which are those who can meet the sectors' ability standards and are, therefore, the ones worthy of belonging in it. Moreover, Goodall *et al.* (2023) also acknowledged that young, motivated and non-disabled students were the ones considered ideal across the Norwegian HE sector, linked to the sector's focus on productivity and performance.

Likewise, Dadvand (2022, p. 1245) talks about how the "*globalising politic of neoliberal capitalism*" has led to the construction of an "*ideal(ised)*" student subject that informs educational practice worldwide. This author argues that these globalising neoliberal politics mean that educational practices, relations and subjectivities are informed by the market-driven principles of neoliberalism, which understand individuals as mere economically productive actors. Moreover, according to Dadvand (2022), although areas such as care and education had traditionally been out of the reach of the market, they are now increasingly permeated by market-driven assumptions. Thus, the neoliberal influence in these areas reshapes educational caring relations which are now regulated by academic performance and standards (*ibid*).

Although Dadvand's study (2022) focused on the experience of James, a disabled secondary school student in Australia, I believe that similar discourses are in place behind disability support policies and practices in HE in Scotland and presumably in others around the world. Hence, these policies and practices are designed from an idealised conception of what it means to be a disabled student in HE. These idealised disabled students are those perceived as more likely to meet academic standards and, therefore, more likely to become productive market subjects. According to the current study's data, some of the main elements that can construct this idealised notion of disabled students are having access to medical evidence and being an undergraduate student, elements discussed in depth in chapters 4 and 5.

Yet, a closer exploration of the data shows that other elements of this idealised notion include disabled students who are perceived as passive, thankful receivers of support and have conditions that do not fluctuate over time. These elements of the idealised notion of disabled students were not discussed in depth in the previous chapters because more data will be needed for an effective analysis. However, the preliminary evidence available illustrates that disabled students who are perceived as grateful for any support received, regardless of its quality, could also be perceived as *ideal* disabled students, in contrast to those who do challenge existing support when it is not adequate. Such is the case of Kate (as discussed in Chapter 4), who felt she was expected to feel thankful for support she had not been able to access due to delays and was met with disregard and a lack of compassion when challenging the circumstances that were hampering support implementation.

Additionally, the exam support that Kevin, a former undergraduate student (see Chapter 4), received from tutors became a distraction instead of an aid. Yet, Kevin never complained about this because these tutors were friendly. But I wonder what would have happened if Kevin complained and stopped being the grateful disabled student, satisfied with the support provided he was thought to be. Would he have been involved in an endless chase like Nicole (see Chapter 4), who was part of a six-month-long email chain searching for someone who could implement the exam accommodation discussed in her support plan? I do not have an answer to this. Still, the evidence shows that when students like Kate or Nicole stopped being passive and thankful for what they got, they did not find a solution to their problems; instead, they encountered more barriers and a lack of accountability.

In this regard, Dolmage (2017) maintains that (non-ideal) disabled students who cannot easily adhere to established policies and practices (such as DSA or the institutionally approved list of accommodations, as discussed in Chapter 4) are not seen as the thankful, passive recipients of

support they are expected to be. Hence, the challenges of disabled students who do not meet the idealised standards of what it means to be a HE disabled student are a reminder of how socially constructed knowledge about what is reasonable and acceptable around disability accommodations in HE can contribute to “*maintaining systems and structures that control and exclude marginalised populations such as people with disabilities*” (Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016, p. 86). Thus, these circumstances require us to consider the effectiveness of current disability support systems and structures, examining their role in promoting inclusion or perpetuating exclusion and challenging them by implementing much-needed change. Suggestions for change were widely discussed by participants and are covered in chapters 4 and 5 and will be expanded in section 6.5. of this chapter.

Moreover, not considering disabled students with conditions that fluctuate over time as part of that idealised notion of what it is to be a disabled student means that sudden changes to disabled students' health are not considered in the design of support policies and practices. One clear example, described by Nicole in Chapter 4, refers to appointment cancellation policies. More specifically, Nicole acknowledged that mental health appointments taking place on campus at 9:00 in the morning, which require a 24-hour cancellation time, do not consider the changing needs of those who would most benefit from these appointments. As Nicole mentioned, crises can occur suddenly, limiting disabled students' capacity to attend or cancel appointments. Yet, according to Nicole, not attending or cancelling on time could lead to support removal without considering the circumstances that inhibited students' attendance or cancellation. Thus, support policies like this benefit ideal disabled students whose health does not fluctuate, but discriminate against those in different circumstances who risk losing support.

Considering the above discussion, I can say that this study's findings also align with the work of scholars like Youdell (2006), who acknowledged that (co)existing discourses construct understandings of students that can lead to educational inclusion or exclusion. Thus, Youdell argues that certain “*constellations of identity markers*” (2006, p. 2) become a representation of the “*ideal learner*”, seen as more likely to achieve educational success, according to policies and dominant discourses (ibid). On the contrary, other categories of identity markers are not equated with this view of academic success, thus positioning some students as “*impossible learners*” (Youdell, 2006, p. 2). Thus, students' identities are gathered in these constellations, creating possibilities or constraints depending on the student's identity and leading to practices that give students a higher or a lower status depending on those constellations of identity markers (ibid). Therefore, these subjectivities are created by existing discourses of who are the

ideal or the impossible students and can have significant consequences on educational inclusion and exclusion (Youdell, 2006).

In this study, the identity constellations linked to undergraduate disabled students in possession of disability medical evidence create an ideal disabled student categorisation who is seen as the norm and who is positioned higher (or lower) in the hierarchy to access disability support. Furthermore, ideal disabled students are also those who can comply with existing disability support policies since they are the ones who can easily adhere to existing systems and structures. Yet, disabled students who cannot provide medical evidence or disabled postgraduate students are left in dangerous limbos as they cannot comply with these normative procedures. One example that illustrates these circumstances is the case of Kate (as discussed in Chapter 4), who could not access support until she provided updated medical certification due to relocating to do her studies. Similarly, Lauren (please see Chapter 4), a former undergraduate student, could not access any specialist support as she did not have any medical diagnoses while she struggled in HE. Moreover, Richard (as explained in Chapter 4) was only offered support targeted at undergraduate students despite being a PhD candidate.

These examples demonstrate that when there is an idealised conception of disabled students, human needs can be neglected in favour of compliance with normative practices and discourses. I argue that this is a result of existing expectations for all disabled students to meet specific standards of who needs support in HE. Hence, these dynamics create further categories where the focus is not on what kind of support is needed but on who can provide medical evidence and how fast they can get it, or on who is an undergraduate disabled student who can use the existing accommodations plan, and not what specific accommodations this student needs. Thus, the needs of those who cannot adhere to these standards fall into the background, which, as the evidence shows, puts disabled students at higher risk of discrimination, foreclosing their experiences and aspirations, and having a negative influence on their persistence and retention.

The idealised conception of disabled students is also reflected in the lack of information and awareness available to people who become disabled later in life, perhaps while being in HE. This case was discussed by Stella (PhD student), who became disabled at the end of her undergraduate degree and found very little representation and information that could indicate whether or not someone in her position could access disability support. Therefore, neoliberal ideas of normalcy and of ways of being as such addressed by Dolmage (2017) could be supporting the notions behind these policies and practices, only designed for idealised

conceptions of disabled students. This approach disregards the changing and dynamic nature of disability (ibid).

Hence, this study highlights how different norms, practices and discourses around Scottish HE can act as obstacles for disabled students, impeding inclusion and affecting disabled students' intentions to persist. This idea is similar to that discussed by Gregersen and Nielsen (2023), who argue that HE's implicit norms represent specific student ideals, which act as invisible barriers to diverse students, such as mature students in Denmark. More specifically, these authors used qualitative methods such as participant observation, semi-structured interviews and video diaries to explore how Danish students experience and navigate spoken and unspoken norms within their educational programmes. In this regard, Gregersen and Nielsen (2023) concluded that students in HE, particularly under-represented students, are in a constant state of negotiation with these implicit norms, which can hamper under-represented students' educational engagement as not all can meet the ideals shared across the sector. The ideals described by Gregersen and Nielsen (2023) refer to the expectations that learners should dedicate their entire lives to being students, which mature students with other identities and responsibilities cannot always meet. Although those ideals are different from the ones addressed in this study, there are certain parallels between both investigations as they help identify unspoken norms that hinder the experiences of HE students, like mature students and disabled students.

Therefore, the current study enhances previous theory and literature discussing how shared educational cultures and discourses of normativity can lead to the discrimination of disabled students. Thus, this study enhances Youdell's (2006) discussion about students' identity constellations by exploring identity markers that are relevant to the experience of disabled students in HE. It also adds to Dadvand's (2022) conceptualisation of idealised disabled students, portraying how it is enacted in HE. Moreover, this study expands Gregersen and Nielsen's (2023, p. 89) discussion about HE "*norms and ideals*" by examining how they apply to the experiences of disabled students.

Thus, this study demonstrates that disabled students are not just being othered in HE in Scotland due to non-disabled students being positioned as the norm (Reutlinger, College and Steffensmeier, 2015) but also because the current support policies and practices designed for an idealised conception of who can be a disabled student. This illustrates how existing ableist cultures, discourses, and practices promote further othering within the disabled student community as disabled students who do not meet the idealised conception of what it means to

be a disabled student in HE are experiencing further discrimination. Consequently, this shared idealised notion about disabled students is enabling discriminatory support practices, which, instead of providing inclusion, become a source of stress and exclusion. I would argue that being aware of this conceptualisation and resulting hierarchies can help identify existing narratives around normalcy and ideal/non-ideal students in areas like disability support and how they influence existing practices and hierarchies that might lead to the discrimination of this group of students. Identifying these narratives and practices can allow us to examine their inherent bias to then address these pervasive hierarchies so that all disabled students can have equal access to support and education. This resonates with Kate's reflections covered in the methodology chapter as part of the first research question's justification (see Chapter 3). In this case, Kate talked about how not being able to access support in a timely and straightforward manner "*caused the whole thing [her PhD and dreams] to grind to a halt. Disability services do indeed have the power to fulfil or foreclose on PhD [experiences]*". Thus, addressing these barriers is something that could enable the fulfilment of disabled students' aspirations in HE, promoting persistence and retention.

6.1.2. Intersectionality as a strategy to challenge the idealised notion of disabled students

Considering this landscape in which some disabled students are perceived as ideal and others as non-ideal, it is important to revisit Youdell's (2006) work, which argues that subjectivities where students are positioned in certain ways, such as ideal/impossible students, result from discourses that create an illusion where these notions are perceived as natural. However, the author adds (ibid) that because these subjectivities result from discursive practices, they should not be taken as fixed identities but rather as subjectivities that can be challenged and shifted. Thus, there is a need to challenge the idealised notion discussed here by recognising that the existence of *ideal* disabled students is an abstract conception rather than a reality (Bones and Ellison, 2022).

Challenging this notion involves the recognition of the complex experiences of this diverse group of students and a shift away from the medicalised conception of disability common across HE to comprehend the unique and complex experiences of disabled people (Shaw, Chan and McMahon, 2012). It also requires adopting an intersectional lens that considers and values varied aspects of the disabled student experience (Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016). This adoption would also entail the recognition that the number of disabled postgraduate students is increasing (DSUK, 2023), that there is a great number of disabled students who decide not to

share their disability status (Newman *et al.*, 2021) and that some do not see themselves as part of the disability community (Vallejo Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016).

In the context of this study, taking an intersectional approach means that a more personalised approach to disability support services is needed, as although current practices across Scottish HE are based on individualised discussions with students (see Chapter 4), these might not always effectively consider the personal circumstances of disabled students. Hence, the boundaries of those practices should be stretched, and a fully personalised approach must be taken. This is because although the current disability support provision systems adopt an individualised stance, they respond to the needs of an idealised conception of disabled students instead of trying to meet students' genuine needs. Thus, adopting an intersectional approach could help promote the reconceptualization of existing policies and practices that do not consider the nuanced and complex realities and identities of disabled students and make them truly personalised.

Additionally, I argue that the idealised conception of disabled students and the hierarchies it leads to are sustained by discourses and practices where disabled students' experiences are not valued as part of students' complex humanity. These dynamics are supported by discourses and cultures in which learners are perceived to be only interested in isolated fragments of knowledge instead of being seen as whole human beings (hooks, 2014), something that, according to bell hooks (*ibid*), causes a significant disconnect between students and educators. Thus, it is necessary to consider students' wide range of experiences, such as disability and chronic illnesses, and the impact these can have on their learning experience. Moreover, this deconstruction is linked to the need to acknowledge that "*there is much that teachers don't know or don't understand about their students*" (Kerschbaum, 2014, p. 2), and I would add that there is much that disability advisers do not know about disabled students.

Hence, the value of adopting an intersectional lens across disability support services and across pedagogical approaches in HE in Scotland is that it opens a broad range of possibilities for interpretation (Kerschbaum, 2014). This means that disabled students would not be considered only in terms of isolated identifiers (*ibid*), such as being an undergraduate/postgraduate student or someone who does/does not have access to medical certification. Instead, they should be seen as "*the embodiment of a complex set of identifications that must be considered together, rather than independently from one another*" (Kerschbaum, 2014, p. 10).

Therefore, adopting an intersectional approach would mean that certain classifications or isolated identifiers would not determine educators' and disability advisers' perceptions of and attitudes toward students (Kerschbaum, 2014). Instead, it would mean that the overall needs of disabled students, considering their multiple identities, are considered across the disability support and educational processes. To do this, it is necessary to raise awareness about disability as a dynamic and changing construct (see Dolmage, 2017) and to dispel the existing culture of mistrust towards disabled students requesting support (as discussed in Chapter 4) for the harm it does. This gains additional relevance when discussing the experience of disabled students in HE, as the intersection of varied socially constructed identities with different disabilities leads to a unique range of lived experiences (Vallejo Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016). For example, class or gender can influence students' ability to obtain one or more diagnoses (Vallejo Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016), which, as discussed in Chapter 4, could lead to delays, alterations or dismissal.

However, the research exploring the experiences of disabled people from an intersectional lens is limited, as disability is often conceptualised as an isolated, unitary concept, and the intersection of different identities like race or gender is not often comprehensively examined (see Vallejo Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016). This problem is also present in the current study, as discussions addressing different identities based on other identity markers, such as gender, were scarce across the interviews. Similarly, discussions that considered other identities based on, for example, ethnicity were limited due to the lack of diversity as most participants were white Scottish. However, other identity markers of disabled students, such as being undergraduate/postgraduate students and having/not having access to medical evidence, have been widely discussed (see chapters 4 and 5), shedding light on the many layers of the experiences of disabled students in Scottish HE.

This reinforces Vallejo Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer's (2016) discussion of previous literature, which acknowledges that the disabled student community is heterogeneous, with a significant presence of invisible groups within this community. Thus, this highlights the need for the non-essentialisation of disabled students, which implies having a profound understanding of the differences among and across disabilities (ibid). Therefore, there is a need to understand who is currently seen as *other* within the disabled student community. Hence, adopting an intersectional approach also acknowledges that the identities of disabled students that might have a more significant impact on their academic journey are not necessarily the most evident or researched ones. According to Vallejo Peña, Stapleton, and Schaffer (2016), not all students fit in specific and established categories, but the needs of all students must be addressed,

regardless of their identities. Thus, this calls again for the need to challenge the notion that some disabled students are *ideal* and others are not and to take a proactive approach to ensure they can all access high-quality and inclusive educational experiences, resisting and challenging ableist discourses, cultures and practices in which some disabled students are positioned as more deserving than others.

Although McKinney (2018) acknowledges the difficulty of changing these rigid structures from the inside, they also recognise the importance of making small changes. Consequently, I argue that taking an intersectional approach, being open to a broad range of interpretive possibilities, and acknowledging the variable and dynamic experiences of disabled students could be one of those small changes towards educational inclusion. As discussed in Chapter 5, from an educational practice standpoint, this could be reflected in the adoption of an anticipatory approach to educational inclusion via, for example, the use of UDL or the adoption of hybrid learning approaches in which students are provided with recorded lectures they can adapt to their needs. Through a disability studies lens, this would also mean creating environments where difference is not the object of discrimination and where disability is accepted as an “*always-everywhere*” dynamic and changing construct (Dolmage, 2017, p. 73). This dynamic conception would help to increase awareness about disability as something that continuously changes and evolves over time, meaning that some people can be disabled for a certain period (Vallejo Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016). It also means understanding that the impact of impairment changes over time, intensifying and abating in a complex interplay with stressors and supports in people’s lives. It would also raise awareness about people who become disabled later in life, including when they are enrolled in HE, which, as discussed in Chapter 4, is an under-represented group struggling to access support while being part of an already marginalised community.

Hence, an intersectional approach could help challenge the traditional emphasis on unity and homogeneity that leads to the silencing of the experiences of those facing multiple marginalisation (Evans, 2022). This would allow educators and disability advisers to recognise that disabled students are likely to have more than one oppressed identity, which leads to complex forms of discrimination (Vallejo Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016). I argue that this is another reason to shift away from narratives of idealised disabled students and consider the intrinsic existence of difference within the disabled student community. Once disability is accepted as an inherent part of the human experience and seen from an intersectional lens, inclusion would mean, according to Dolmage (2017), the existence of difference. This assumption would imply a cultural shift as a disability would not be seen as something that

must disappear from academia (ibid), directly influencing discourses about inclusion and the resulting ableist policies and practices. Instead, Gibson (2015) argues that education must create space for difference as a strategy to boost general understanding and innovation in educational practice.

Adopting this lens could also mean that disabled students who cannot comply with current systems and structures of disability support would not be (additionally) othered and marginalised, as their varied experiences would be accepted (and not ignored or resisted) as part of a culture of difference. Hence, postgraduate students would not be an afterthought in the disability support provision process, and the circumstances of their studies (for example, duration and nature of the programme, level of autonomy) are fully considered when discussing support and accommodations. Moreover, acknowledging these varied identities and the impact that something such as chronic health conditions can have on students' educational engagement or that some people become disabled later in life. Thus, this could mean that students who are not performing as expected would be given the benefit of the doubt and could be approached with care and compassion instead of with judgment and punishment. One example of this is Tiffany's experience (as discussed in Chapter 5), where educators in her module threatened to expel her from her master's degree because she struggled to engage with the provided material.

Although, some, like Evans (2022), recognise that disability has been a construct under-researched from an intersectional stance, the author also recognises the growing interest in this research field and the increasing interest and awareness of disability as an intersectional matter (ibid). Yet, Evans (2022) acknowledges that intersectionality does not happen in isolation and requires the consideration of different factors like power dynamics, discourses of exclusion and ableism, being part of broader efforts to promote social justice movements. Vallejo Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer (2016, p. 94) recognise that a social justice approach must be taken to "*embrace intersectionality*". These authors define social justice as a framework based on the reflection "*on one's actions and the world*" (ibid). In a HE context, this could be translated into the promotion of critical and socially just pedagogies. Hence, authors like Madriaga *et al.* (2011) support Giroux's (2003) and Goodley's (2007) calls for critical and socially just pedagogies to challenge the existing sense of normalcy. This approach is seen by the authors as an alternative that values difference and acknowledges students' (and educators') dynamic identities, continuously moving, changing, and "*becoming learners*" (Goodley, 2007, p. 324). This approach, Madriaga *et al.* (2011) argue, would also encourage a movement beyond minimalistic

teaching and support provision as it is seen as an issue of justice and fairness, not a matter of compliance.

Therefore, this study illustrates the need to adopt an intersectional approach across HE in Scotland to challenge the idealised notions around the experiences and identities of disabled students in the sector. This would help challenge existing discourses, policies and practices that other disabled students in comparison to their non-disabled peers and to the disabled students who meet the idealised notions addressed in this section. Hence, I argue that this idealised notion of the experiences of disabled students is shared and reproduced across different areas of HE in Scotland, such as among policymakers, disability advisors or educators. Questioning the pervasiveness of this notion would lead to accepting and embracing the multiple identities of disabled students, which could be a catalyst to rethink policy and practice towards a sector that values students' differences.

Moreover, I propose this intersectional approach as participants in this study themselves highlighted how critical and socially just pedagogies, based on care and responsibility can be an alternative to exclusive discourses and practices across HE in Scotland. Thus, in line with the proposals of Madriaga *et al.* (2011), Giroux (2003) and Goodley (2007), as seen above, I advocate for using socially just pedagogies as a strategy to do so. Further particularities of how these pedagogies could be implemented in HE are discussed in the last section of this chapter. There, I focus on the importance of putting human needs over compliance and how there is a need to implement ethics of care and responsibility as strategies to challenge current ableist discourses and practices that lead to the marginalisation of disabled students in HE in Scotland, foreclosing disabled students' aspirations and having a negative influence on retention.

6.2. Care and responsibility

The findings discussed in the previous chapters illustrate a scenario in which disability support policies and practices across HE in Scotland focus on the students' disabilities and medical diagnoses rather than on their needs as human beings and as students. This comes as a representation of the medical model still dominant across the sector and despite the evidence calling for anticipatory approaches to inclusive education (Beck, 2022). As discussed in these chapters, the focus on disability documentation rather than on disabled students' educational needs can lead to exclusion. Moreover, the unfair impact of these practices is more significant for disabled students who are not seen as *ideal* disabled students, who then face multiple

layers of discrimination. Hence, this creates a landscape where this specific group of students is sometimes left without the support needed to access education effectively, but also sometimes without the pastoral or emotional support that could help them face the absence or delay of support.

Additionally, the data illustrates that pedagogical approaches often disregard the complex experiences of disabled students, who are sometimes treated with a lack of respect and consideration. Subsequently, participants in this study discussed the need to adopt more caring pedagogical approaches in which disabled students are fully valued as individuals, and their complex experiences are taken into consideration across the design and implementation of educational and support practices. To do this, participants reflected on the key role that caring attitudes and responsibility can have as a demonstration that the experiences and struggles of disabled students matter and are considered in all areas of education. Thus, this section discusses care and responsibility in relation to the aspirations and retention of disabled students in HE.

6.2.1. Care

Considering this study's findings, I argue that part of the HE community across Scotland proposes using caring pedagogies to challenge neoliberal and ableist notions that lead to discrimination across the sector. In line with Dadvand's ideas (2022, p. 1246), I understand care as relational, being represented in daily and common spaces and relations, and not as part of formal narratives of care as "*service provision*". Thus, the current study's findings support the emerging work calling for more critical, feminist, caring and hopeful pedagogies to face the current challenges across the "*uncaring*" (Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild, 2024, p. 388) neoliberal, post-pandemic HE landscape (Koseoglu, 2020; Xiao, 2021; Lemon, Harju-Luukkainen and Garvis, 2023; Lopez, 2023). However, while this literature often considers the student body in a general way, my findings provide a more nuanced and closer understanding of the role that these pedagogies play in the educational experience of disabled students. They also demonstrate the importance of the affect and relations in the promotion of the retention of disabled students in HE, an area that, as I addressed in this study's literature review, has been underexplored (Moriña, 2019).

In relation to this, Moriña (2019) discusses the importance of using pedagogical strategies that consider relational aspects like students' motivation and emotions and the importance of showing students that they matter and belong in HE. Moriña also maintains that, according to

the educators who participated in her study, these strategies are targeted at the whole body of students, benefiting all and not only disabled students. This discussion aligns with that of O'Brien (2010), who argues that, from a pedagogy of care lens, there is a need to honour students' humanity and make a commitment to seeing them flourish. According to Collins-Warfield *et al.* (2023), caring pedagogy is embodied by paying attention to students' needs, views and motivations and building a trusting relationship where there is a desire for students to thrive. These elements were key in the experiences shared by participants as disabled students valued being seen as whole human beings, and staff (disability advisers and educators) acknowledged the need to adopt caring, supportive and accommodating attitudes as a key strategy to promote the retention and success of disabled students.

According to Noddings (2012, p. 772) care is based on reciprocity between the one who cares and the "cared-for"; but for the caring relationship to be successful, the "cared-for" must respond positively. Without this response, care does not exist, independently of what educators do (see Collins-Warfield *et al.*, 2023). This is reflected in this study in the experiences of participants like June and Felicity, who valued their educators' attentiveness and caring approaches, which showed they cared about students' needs and dignity. They did this by being engrossed (Noddings, 2012), paying attention and responding to students' needs, ensuring that they were approachable and creating educational spaces that were safe for disabled students. In these cases, students appreciated these attitudes, which they saw as elements that promote retention. See, for example, the experience of Lynsey (Chapter 5), whose educators gave her additional extensions to submit her coursework during a difficult time without requesting any evidence, or that of Kate (Chapter 4), whose PhD supervisor stepped up when her institution was unable to provide effective support. The opposite - disabled students perceiving their learning experiences and success did not matter - had a negative effect on their sense of belonging, which plays a key role in student retention (Thomas, 2018). This is illustrated by Felicity's (master's student) words in Chapter 5: "*If lecturers are quite apathetic... and you feel like they don't care about you, they're only there to do their job, you're not going to want to stay*".

For other students like Nicole, a caring attitude was also reflected in practices like assessment, as some educators used it to demonstrate they cared about students' learning and progression. This example shows how a practice that is often perceived as inaccessible (Nieminen, 2022) and as a source of anxiety (Senel and Senel, 2021) could help improve the relationship between teachers and students (Schwartz, 2019). This example goes in line with what I described in Chapter 5 as educators' caring pedagogies, which emerged from their commitment to making their practice more inclusive for all students, reducing disabled students' needs to request

accommodations and individualised support. Educators like Helen, Morgan and Amelia did this by providing choices and taking an anticipatory approach to inclusive education (see Chapter 5). However, their initiative required them to challenge traditional educational practices based on on-campus delivery, which was often met with resistance from the wider educational community as their colleagues were reluctant to teach online and implement alternative assessment forms. Nevertheless, their commitment and the COVID-19 pandemic helped them boost these changes. Thus, I believe the work of these and other educators who participated in this study embody the tenets of critical care pedagogies, which require the confrontation of *“taken-for-granted educational practices’ and look for opportunities to ‘imagine new possibilities to teach and serve students in ways that go beyond mere content”* (Yellow Horse and Nakagawa, 2020, p. 353 as cited by Collins-Warfield *et al.*, 2023, p. 5).

Hence, while in line with Moriña’s (2019) findings, I maintain that promoting caring pedagogies in HE is beneficial for all students, my study also illustrates that this approach has an increased positive potential to promote the retention of a specific group of students, such as disabled students. Therefore, I believe this calls for the adoption of critical care pedagogy, as, according to Collins-Warfield *et al.*, (2023, p. 6) *“there is not a one-size-fits-all approach to care”*. Moreover, students from traditionally marginalised groups need distinct forms of care in comparison to their peers (Antrop-González and De Jesús, 2006; Dadvand and Cuervo, 2020; Collins-Warfield *et al.*, 2023), which I argue applies to disabled students.

Although caring pedagogies can benefit all students, considering the countless challenges experienced by disabled students in HE (Vickerman and Blundell, 2010; Redpath *et al.*, 2013; Moriña, 2019), I maintain that the HE educational community must consider how these approaches can be particularly beneficial for this diverse and often marginalised group of students. However, Dadvand and Cuervo (2020) argue that current understandings of care are influenced by neoliberalism, which has taken the focus away from the person and put it on academic performance, ideas of self-care, accountability and reporting. Behind performative care practices, there are ableist notions that put some abilities over others and disregard the existence of those who do not possess the skills deemed important (Wolbring, 2008; Dadvand, 2022). Moreover, these beliefs and assumptions that underpin performative conceptions of care portray what Foucault (1995) named *“regimes of truth”* (Dadvand, 2022). These regimes of truth lead to the exclusion of disabled students, as they constitute the *“social space and subjectivities”* that inform performative practices and ethics of care with ideas of *“who qualifie[s] as subjects of recognition in care work”* (Dadvand, 2022, p. 1246).

While Dadvand's (2022) ideas are developed around the experience of one autistic student attending mainstream secondary school in Australia, I argue that these ideas can also apply to HE as the notions discussed by that author are reflected in the difficulties experienced by participants in this study. For example, Kate (PhD student) did not receive the agreed support in a timely manner and was left feeling ignored and vulnerable (see Chapter 4). While she experienced significant delays in support provision, she was never contacted by her institution to provide interim support or to check on her well-being as she tried to cope without the necessary support. Moreover, as Kate was not perceived as an *ideal* disabled student because she was a PhD student, she might have been, according to Dadvand (2022, p. 1247) rendered as an "*unrecognisable care subject*".

Alternatively, participants who talked about promoting pedagogies of care were motivated by the importance of recognising that all students' needs matter and that a broader understanding of those needs is necessary. Therefore, according to participants, care could be enacted by adopting a positive, disability-aware attitude, appearing approachable to students, taking an anticipatory approach to inclusion and providing educational choices. Hence, in this case, care ethics is seen as a strategy to promote the inclusion and belonging of disabled students, reducing (but not eliminating) the need for further accommodations. This aligns with Tronto's (1993) understanding of caring, which implies a response to different needs and the need to challenge the needs that are (not) perceived as legitimate. Consequently, I consider that participants' argument for incorporating care across different levels of HE validates the existence of a broad spectrum of student needs, identities and experiences that can be expressed and responded to in many ways. This argument is also a reflection of how disability can be used to rethink common practices (Dadvand, 2022), such as the role of care across pedagogy and disability support. It also challenges notions of normalcy around practices of care as all (disabled) students are perceived to have equally important needs.

Hence, in this study, I demonstrate the negative impact of performative, one-size-fits-all care practices rooted in ableism and advocate for a critical ethics of care that recognises the varied and variable needs of disabled students across HE in Scotland. This critical ethics of care promotes meaningful care practices that are not paternalistic impositions based on charitable actions, which, although they result from good intentions, can lead to feelings of frustration (Wood, 2021; Dadvand, 2022; Noddings, 2022). Instead, care must be taken as a strategy to empower students' agency to address challenges (Wood, 2021).

Thus, the current findings demonstrate that participants had a shared understanding of the value of adopting a caring ethos, believing that emotions and relations play a key role in the retention of disabled students. Considering this, I maintain that it is necessary to see disabled student retention through a pedagogy of care lens. While all students would benefit from such an approach, I would argue that policies and practices relating to the inclusion and retention of disabled students, such as those aimed at promoting student engagement and a sense of belonging, must also acknowledge these elements. In line with the previous section's discussion, these policies and practices should also be developed from an intersectional approach where the multiple identities of disabled students are considered.

6.2.2. Responsibility

This study's findings illustrate that care and responsibility are important across different areas of the journey of disabled students in the strictly pedagogical realm but are also crucial in other areas, such as the disability support provision process. Therefore, this is another area in which I believe pedagogies of care and care ethics apply differently to the experience of disabled students. This is because it is them, and not their non-disabled peers, the ones who go through these processes. Processes which, as described by Kate (see Chapter 4), can become a cog bringing disabled students' educational journey and aspirations to a halt but are not experienced by non-disabled students who "*don't have a part that can stop the whole machine working*". Thus, as I discussed in Chapter 4, disability support provision plays a key role in the experience of disabled students in HE in Scotland. Yet, these complex processes are often flawed and linked to a lack of accountability and responsibility, foreclosing disabled students' capacity to access educational support and, thus, to fulfil their goals and aspirations. This section highlights the need to reconceptualise responsibility and accountability as key principles across different areas of HE to allow the fulfilment of disabled students' aspirations and promote their persistence.

In this regard, perceiving that staff took responsibility and cared to ensure disabled students accessed support and accommodations was positively valued by participants, and some, like June (undergraduate student), Claire (disability adviser) or Amelia (educator), considered that they had a positive impact on disabled student retention. However, many disabled students who participated in this study perceived disability support provision as a transactional process where the priority was the paperwork and not their educational needs. Hence, difficulties in accessing practical support and accommodations can become a common source of stress, but the lack of accountability, care and compassion disabled students often perceive from their

institution is also harmful. Consequently, I argue that the concept of care and responsibility should gain relevance across these services as disabled students who participated in this study, and potentially many more across Scotland, experience inconsistent support.

Moreover, Tronto's (2013) conceptualisation of care is not limited to dispositions. Instead, Tronto understands care as a relational practice that is divided into two phases. The first phase focuses on noticing, identifying or caring about needs; the second focuses on the action(s) required to meet those needs; this includes the responsibility of taking those actions. Thus, responsibility is seen by Tronto (1993, 2013) as the commitment to do something in order to meet the social needs identified, and it is a moral tenet at the centre of care ethics. These two phases can clearly be seen to be at play in this study as disabled students' needs are often identified by different members of the educational community, such as educators, programme leaders and disability support services. However, there is evidence of variable levels of responsibility for acting on those needs. This was reflected in different scenarios, such as when Nicole (master's student) was part of a six-month-long email chain trying to identify who could help her access a specific adjustment or when Tiffany's (PhD student) supervisors were unavailable and she could not find anyone who could provide support and when Colin (undergraduate student) never figured out who could help him access the accessible furniture he was told he could get. I argue that these circumstances also reflect a lack of ethics of care as, although recognised, the needs of these disabled students were not met. Moreover, in some cases, active actions were taken to avoid and pass on to someone else the responsibility to act on those needs (see the example of Nicole's email chain in Chapter 4).

According to Bozalek and Zembylas (2023), from a care ethics lens, responsibility is enacted by responding to and addressing care needs once identified. These authors also argue that responsibility takes into consideration what is deemed as (un)important (ibid). Thus, considering these definitions, I would argue that many of the experiences discussed in this thesis portray the lack of responsibility sometimes present in disability support provision, as the needs of disabled students are not effectively addressed, meaning that responsibility is not always enacted in those cases. This lack of responsibility can be one of the factors hindering disabled students' access to support. This claim does not take accountability away from existing ableist discourses and cultures; however, it does highlight that some of the practices within disability support processes ultimately lead to the discrimination of disabled students in HE in Scotland. One example of this is the need to provide medical documentation as a prerequisite to access support.

Still, as addressed in Chapter 4, Tronto (2021) argues that responsibility comes from power, which might hinder the caring aspect of certain support processes. One of these processes is disability support provision, as shown above. Therefore, Bozalek and Zembylas (2021, p. 55) advocate for the terms “*response-ability*” and “*response-able pedagogies*”, which are based on the “*relational practices of attentiveness, curiosity, responsibility, and being rendered capable*”, rooted in posthuman and feminist materialist traditions. Thus, being *response-able* implies shifting the power of the responsible subjects in different ways, requiring them to be more perceptive, curious, and patient to interact with the wider world (Bozalek and Zembylas, 2021; Tronto, 2021). Moreover, it demands a willingness to face uncertainty and acknowledge concealed and convoluted realities that are part of current ways of enacting power, care and knowledge creation and transmission (Tronto, 2021). For Bozalek and Zembylas (2023), *response-ability* is also based on welcoming and facilitating responses that are attuned to specific situations, where all parties involved are seen as capable, and is an ethical and political strategy to resist established boundaries in daily practices. Although I will keep using the term responsibility for clarity, I support Bozalek and Zembylas’ (2023) conceptualisation of *response-ability* and believe that these principles of responsiveness, curiosity, and responsibility should guide HE towards enhanced inclusion.

Thus, when considering the experience of disability support of some of the disabled students who participated in this study, I argue that taking responsibility means being more susceptible to the needs of disabled students, which might not always adhere to preconceived ideas of disability or of student identities. In line with this, I argue that there is a need to be sensitive to the multiplicity of experiences of disabled students, inquisitive about how to meet their needs, and patient in finding effective ways to address them. Moreover, I would argue that power dynamics should shift in the disability support provision process. The experiences and needs of disabled students should be valued more consistently, which could inform dynamic processes of disability support provision that are attuned and responsive to students’ needs. This would mean that all disabled students would be perceived, paraphrasing Dadvand (2022), as recognisable care subjects, and not only those who can meet the idealised disabled student notion shared across the sector. Hence, I maintain that, particularly while ableist systems and structures are in place, care ethics and responsibility need to be critical concepts across disability support provision services in HE. I argue that this can be a strategy to challenge and resist neoliberal ableist narratives where only the needs of certain (*ideal*) disabled students are important and deserving of being addressed.

These approaches, I argue, can promote the retention of disabled students by challenging ableist cultures, discourses and practices that limit disabled students' access to inclusive education. Instead, they could encourage a culture of responsibility in which all members of the educational community are accountable to eliminate barriers and promote inclusion. Hence, although there might be other strategies to enhance the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland, I maintain that care and responsibility can promote social justice and inclusion by fostering the adoption of intersectional approaches that acknowledge and value the multiple identities of disabled students. This approach can also promote retention by informing support policies and practices that are designed with disabled students in mind, ensuring effective and timely adjustments when needed. I argue that all this combined would lead to the creation of more inclusive cultures across HE in Scotland in which diversity is accepted, and disabled students can learn and flourish, promoting retention. In the next section, I address the implications of these findings and arguments for policy and practice across the sector. I do this while discussing the possibilities and challenges of implementing pedagogies of care to help promote the retention of disabled students in Scottish HE.

6.3. Possibilities and challenges

Doing this research has been difficult at times, as investigating the marginalising dynamics of a system I am part of has often left me feeling frustrated and hopeless: What can I do to prevent similar injustices in the future? Can things change? Is it possible to remove ableism from HE? Answering these questions feels like a naïve task, impossible to be addressed in such an enormous and convoluted sector. However, many other times, I felt optimistic and moved by the sense of hope that the participants shared with me, believing that change was possible. For bell hooks (2003, p. xiv), hope comes from witnessing others "*positively transforming their lives and the world around them*". I can see this drive to change one part of the world around us (HE in Scotland) in participants' words when they talked about strategies to promote inclusion and the retention of disabled students. According to Freire (2021), we need to be critically hopeful to change the world, as hope is necessary to avoid indifference and cynicism. Yet, Freire recognises that hope is not enough to achieve transformation but that it needs to be linked to practice. This sense of hope is what I wish to convey across this chapter and, in particular, across these final sections. Although I will also discuss difficulties, I believe much can be done to transform HE into a sphere where disabled people can flourish and thrive, far from the place of exclusion it often is. Hence, caring pedagogies, as discussed in previous sections and

chapters, can be considered a strategy to do things otherwise and, therefore, a pedagogy of hope (Walker-Gleaves, 2019).

This section will explore the multiple possibilities that could arise by challenging current discourses, practices and cultures, as discussed above. These multiple possibilities could emerge once we challenge the pervasive notion of the existence of an *ideal* disabled student and see caring ethics and responsibility as approaches to help meet the diverse needs of disabled students in HE. This section will also explore existing challenges related to the adoption of these strategies in the current neoliberal landscape, identifying tensions and potential areas of resistance. The discussion of these possibilities and challenges addresses this study's implications for policy and practice.

6.3.1. Possibilities

For authors like Dolmage (2017) and Dadvand (2022), reflecting on disability can help challenge and rethink existing policies and practices across sectors like HE, something also upheld by critical, caring, and hopeful pedagogies (Koseoglu, 2020; Xiao, 2021; Collins-Warfield *et al.*, 2023). As all these ideas converge in this study since I argue that they can open a series of possibilities to imagine “*worlds otherwise*” (Lopez, 2023, p. 794), to imagine HE sectors otherwise, where disabled students (and other members of the educational community) can learn and flourish. Hence, building on the previous section's discussion and in line with Walker-Gleaves's (2019) ideas, I argue that the role of care within HE should be acknowledged and discussed alongside the possibilities it could lead to. While there are multiple possibilities, I focus on those that could promote disability inclusion and retention in Scottish HE. Thus, I believe these possibilities could result from more compassionate cultures, discourses and practices that recognise the importance of affect in the teaching and learning relationship and the importance of care across all levels of the institution. Therefore, this section addresses the implications of the previous section's discussion, addressing some of the multiple possibilities that could result from that implementation and how they could help fulfil the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland and promote their retention.

One clear way in which I believe an ethics of care can be reflected in HE is in the adoption of Universal Design for Learning (UDL). For Dolmage (2017), UDL is a tool for transformation and hope that should be considered as a strategy to reject ableism and short-term fixes. Instead, it should be seen as a tool to value and respond to the “*unpredictable times and places of disability to come*” (p. 124). Additionally, one of the main advantages of UDL is its capacity to

respond to the changeable, which also means that there are multiple unforeseen benefits to UDL as it can respond to a wide range of circumstances (Dolmage, 2017). Hence, following the principles of UDL, based on providing multiple means of engagement, expression, and action (CAST, 2018; see Chapter 5 for a more detailed discussion), could help create classrooms and HEIs in which all students could have opportunities to learn (Dolmage, 2017). I argue that this enacts the principles of care as the learning experience of all students, regardless of their circumstances, is equally valued. Hence, disabled students should not need to adhere to the *ideal* notion conceived across the sector to have their needs met and to have fair access to quality education because multiple ways of being would have been considered in the design and implementation of educational practices. Hence, according to Karakaya (2021), care should be central in learning design, because, in line with Xiao's (2021) ideas, it is an essential launch point for social justice.

Additionally, promoting UDL across HE in Scotland would address the principle of anticipation discussed in Chapter 5, helping reduce their need to request accommodations and support. This is an essential element in the experience of disabled students as it could help reduce the need for disclosure and self-identification. This could enhance the HE experience of disabled students, levelling it to that of their non-disabled peers, who do not need to make any extraordinary requests to access teaching and learning. As previously discussed, inaccessible institutions and policies, characterised by lengthy and bureaucratic processes, force disabled students to undertake a considerable amount of hidden, additional labour (Hannam-Swain, 2018) that gets in the way of a successful educational experience. Therefore, implementing UDL across all HE levels could create multiple possible HE systems otherwise, characterised by educational practices that offer multiple means of engagement, expression, and action (CAST, 2018) that recognise students' varied learning needs, leading to change at different points in the system. Hence, implementing principles of UDL across HE in Scotland could help address current hierarchies and power imbalances in the educational relationship, and could help promote educational practices that are dynamic and respond to students' changing needs, opening more effective communication channels between learners and educators, with a focus on listening to disabled students.

Furthermore, Dolmage (2017) argues that UDL is a tool to respond to technological and spatial transformations without fear and reductionism, creating opportunities for multiple possibilities within the sector, which I believe is a key element of the post-pandemic HE landscape. While some of these possibilities did not lead to an improved educational experience for many students during the pandemic (Manase, 2021; Bones and Ellison, 2022; Goegan, Le and

Daniels, 2023), they stretched the boundaries of educational practices, leading to increased accessibility for many disabled students (DSUK, 2022). According to the findings of studies like the present one or the work of DSUK (2022), hybrid learning can be a tool for promoting inclusion for disabled students, who can be in more control of their educational experience and can manage their complex health needs more easily in comparison to full on-campus learning. In this regard, Koseoglu (2021) and Houlden and Veletsianos (2019) argue that technology can be a means to promote educational equity and liberation, enhancing the educational experience due to the flexibility it provides. Nevertheless, Houlden and Veletsianos (2019, p. 1005) point out that this flexibility cannot be considered “*neither universal nor neutral*” as digital learning is not an easy fix to all inequalities across the sector. In fact, it can also create new layers of exclusion and oppression as this enhanced flexibility assumes all students are independent and self-directed learners, which challenges the social and relational nature of critical and progressive pedagogies (ibid).

Moreover, I add that this assumption differs from the circumstances of disabled students who will have educational needs besides the accessibility that digital learning can provide. Thus, this study supports Houlden and Veletsianos' (2019) argument that implementing online and digital learning strategies must consider the structural barriers and inequalities students, like disabled students, face. This will require the rethinking of digital learning strategies to ensure they are not only aimed at presumed self-reliant and independent students (ibid) but instead consider the broader institutional context and students' diversity and needs. In line with Xiao (2021, p. 141), and as mentioned in Chapter 5, I believe that the future of HE in Scotland should make the most out of digital technology, considering “*a means, not an end*” while taking a critical approach and promoting care and inclusion as the key elements of education. Hence, if conceived with care and criticality and aiming towards UDL and inclusion, digital technology and online learning could also be a strategy to promote multiple possibilities of what HE could look like for disabled students.

Therefore, as discussed in the previous paragraph, it is essential to acknowledge that digital and online learning can be both a tool for inclusion and a tool for marginalisation for disabled students and other students in HE. Hence, maintaining care and equality at the centre of digital pedagogical practice could also help tackle some of the difficulties experienced by participants in relation to the sense of belonging while learning online.

Another way in which I argue that pedagogy of care could open possibilities across Scottish HE and promote the inclusion and retention of disabled students is through the adoption of

feminist trauma-informed care pedagogies. The prevalence of HE students who have experienced trauma is increasing, particularly after the COVID-19 pandemic and the collective trauma resulting, something that is particularly significant for marginalised groups, like the disability community (Wood, 2021). However, according to authors like Wells (2023) or Harrison, Burke and Clarke (2023), exposure to trauma can have a pervasive effect on students' educational experience in areas such as academic achievement or retention. Consequently, Carello and Thompson (2021) argue that it is necessary to implement trauma-informed approaches, spaces and services across HE. This is an argument that I support, as although discussions focusing directly on trauma were limited during interviews with participants, the traumatic effect of some of the circumstances they described was evident. For example, participants like Tiffany and Kate (PhD students) had repeated difficult experiences obtaining medical certification for their conditions, which I see as re-traumatisation. Additionally, Felicity (master's student) found that the neoliberal nature of HE, where overworking and narrow understandings of individual success are prioritised, led to endless pressures that marked her experience as a disabled student to the point that I would consider traumatic.

Hence, although trauma has not been a specific focus of this study, I believe it can be seen through many of the situations discussed in this thesis. This argument is supported by the existing evidence illustrating that disabled individuals are at higher risk of experiencing trauma, particularly after the COVID-19 pandemic (Kildahl *et al.*, 2020; Lund *et al.*, 2020). Considering this, the work of educators and researchers like Wood (2021) becomes particularly relevant, as it advocates for the adoption of feminist care pedagogies, which can shift the hierarchies in traditional HE educational relationships between teachers and students. For Wood (2021), practising care in education means embodying a deliberate, reflective and considerate linkage between theory and practice while paying particular attention to power dynamics. This approach, the author argues, challenges the exploitative nature of traumatic relations, meaning that the author considers care to be a crucial strategy in trauma-informed teaching practice. Hence, Wood (2021, p. 35) maintains that care in HE should go beyond "*wellness days*", and particularly after the pandemic, it should call for a radical rethought of teaching and learning.

Therefore, the current study's findings and discussions are consistent with Wood's (2021) approach, which proposes rethinking the boundaries of HE to create trauma-informed, caring spaces so disabled and other under-represented students can flourish in and outside the classroom instead of being at the margins. Moreover, some, like Davidson (2017), maintain that HEIs should take care-based trauma-informed approaches that recognise the impact that

traumatic experiences can have on students' learning. This recognition should be supported by institution-wide agreements to promote and protect the safety of students at all levels (ibid).

Although there is no consensus on implementing trauma-informed approaches across different sectors (Scottish Government, 2023), the six principles defined by the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA; 2014) are accepted as general guidance to instrumentalise these strategies. These principles are safety; trustworthiness, and transparency; peer support; collaboration and mutuality; empowerment and choice; cultural, historical and gender issues, which are reflected in participants' wishes for HE. More specifically, disabled students who participated in this study called for safe educational spaces where they can be respected while being their true selves. They also called to be trusted and be given the benefit of the doubt, without directly assuming that some difficulties they might experience with education are not the result of laziness, but that those could be related to complex life experiences. In addition, educators and disability advisors defend the value of peer support and collaboration so they can work together and learn from each other to promote inclusion. Participants also stressed the importance of considering the individual circumstances of disabled students, increasing the opportunities for choice in education and increasing disability awareness across the sector. Hence, trauma-informed care pedagogies could lead to disability-aware collaborative practices to promote safety, empowerment and choice for disabled students,

Another concept related to UDL and trauma-informed practices is compassion, as it embodies much of what I believe could bring positive change to Scottish HE. According to Hamilton and Petty (2023), compassion can be conceptualised in many ways, but these authors argue that definitions of compassion share two key components. The first component is an inclination to perceive suffering without criticism of those suffering; the second component is an inclination to intervene in order to avoid and reduce that suffering (see Halifax, 2012; Gilbert, 2019). Promoting compassion across educational institutions could help create a supportive environment for disabled students, as well as other members of the educational community who experience common human experiences like illnesses or bereavement (Bakelants *et al.*, 2023). Yet, some factors like the fast pace and high demands of the sector or the complexity of communication systems can hinder compassion across HEIs (ibid). This study also discusses these elements as participants like Nicole (master's student; see Chapter 4) or Tiffany (PhD student; see Chapter 4) mentioned difficulties related to communication systems while trying to access support. Others like Felicity (master's student; see Chapter 5) addressed the impact of the high-stress HE environment, which promotes a culture of overwork that does not

consider the circumstances of disabled students and can have a pervasive effect on their well-being.

Therefore, promoting compassionate communities across HE could foster more inclusive environments that could benefit not only disabled students and staff but also others experiencing difficult circumstances (Bakelants *et al.*, 2023). For Bakelants *et al.* (2023), this can be achieved by ensuring processes and systems are clear, by increasing flexibility in support provision policies, or by creating opportunities for anticipatory support. For Hamilton and Petty (2023), UDL could also be a tool to promote compassion across HE. Although Hamilton and Petty (2023) acknowledge that disability support services can be compassionate, they remind us that, although unintentionally, these systems might be rooted in deficit thinking, which focuses on addressing personal difficulties instead of structural barriers. Thus, in line with previous discussions in this section and previous chapters, UDL can be perceived as a compassionate pedagogy that promotes flexibility and choice to increase accessibility for all students (Hamilton and Petty, 2023).

Gibson and Cook-Sather (2020) also advocate for promoting compassion across HE, particularly as a response to failed attempts to promote inclusion, like the ones discussed in Chapter 4. In this case, the authors propose politicised compassion as an approach based on collaboration between students and educators as a strategy to promote inclusive pedagogies and social justice across the sector. Politicised compassion considers power dynamics and strives to amplify the voices of students and educators as a result of solidarity in the form of pedagogical collaboration that can help address inequalities (*ibid.*). Gibson and Cook-Sather (2020) also highlight the potential of politicised compassion for students to express their multiple identities and create, alongside educators, spaces that appreciate and value those identities. Hence, politicised compassion is also a pedagogical stance that can create countless possibilities for disabled students to flourish and succeed in HE as their humanity and unique experiences are considered an essential element of HE, instead of something to be erased.

Therefore, caring, compassionate and trauma-informed pedagogies could help redefine HE in a way that promotes the retention of disabled students, as it would foster the creation of safe spaces where disabled students' multiple identities and complex life experiences are recognised and appreciated. It would also mean that there is a commitment to take responsibility for responding to students' needs and creating educational environments that all students can benefit from while maintaining educational rigour so disabled students and their

peers can achieve their aims while thriving in HE. I believe that doing all this would lead to a cultural and narrative shift to challenge current discourses where the needs of some disabled students are more valid than others or where disabled students have to demonstrate they are trusted to access education. However, the benefits of such a shift would also apply to other members of the educational community, such as non-disabled students or disabled staff. Hence, I believe that feminist, caring, trauma-informed pedagogies could lead to fruitful possibilities that could create a more just and inclusive Scottish HE system. All this helps us imagine a futurity of disability in HE as something that is acknowledged and accepted and where differences are celebrated and conceived as an opportunity to stretch the boundaries of educational practice and of the structures of the system itself.

6.3.2. Challenges

The data generated in this study has illustrated the need to consider a series of elements, such as intersectionality, care and responsibility across different areas of Scottish HE, to promote the retention of disabled students. As discussed in the previous section, this could open multiple possibilities to foster effective inclusion and create environments in which disabled students (and staff) flourish, benefiting the whole body of students. However, it would be naïve not to acknowledge the current HE landscape, which means there is (still) limited room for implementing and developing these approaches. Yet, I believe that, albeit slow, profound change is possible. In this section, I discuss some of these challenges to acknowledge them and consider them while promoting more caring, compassionate, and responsible HEIs. This section also includes suggestions to address these challenges, as only stating the problem would not align with the hopeful element of the chapter.

One of the first challenges I can reflect on is that there is no single way to make all educational practices inclusive for all students. Paraphrasing Xiao (2021), what is accessible education for some may be inaccessible for others, yet, care can promote educational inclusion as it is a prerequisite to equity, which is necessary for the attunement needed to identify and meet students' needs. Considering this, care should be a tool to demonstrate to students that they and their learning matter (ibid). These ideas are what I support in this thesis, as the evidence demonstrates the importance of valuing students' needs and whole experiences and paving the way towards inclusion. In addition, Xiao (2021) argues that if students perceive that they matter and are seen as capable and valued within HE, they might be motivated to advocate for themselves. However, for care to promote equality, it must be mutual, so beyond caring for students, students should also be encouraged to care for each other (ibid). I believe this could

help bring positive change to HE as it would challenge existing power dynamics and position disabled students as active subjects in promoting inclusion. While this will not lead to a formula that promotes accessibility for all, it would help promote disabled student-led approaches to inclusion and retention.

Another crucial challenge I wish to address relates to the boundaries of HE staff's capacity to implement all the desired changes discussed in this thesis. It is impossible to do it all, particularly in the predominant HE culture of what Perisic (2021, p. 9) calls the “*age of neoliberal exhaustion*”, succinctly captured by Felicity (master’s student) in Chapter 5. Although Felicity’s account referred to students, there is extensive evidence that faculty and other HE workers are also affected by this phenomenon. According to Griffin (2022), this landscape leads to increased workloads that HE faculty in Western countries cannot effectively meet, and which take a significant toll on their work-life balance. In this scenario, we are observing a decrease in staff’s mental well-being and a surge in burnout and workplace-related stress, while the need to support students’ mental health increases (Margrove, Gustowska and Grove, 2014; Gulliver *et al.*, 2018; Fontinha, Easton and Van Laar, 2019). This has a particularly negative impact on disabled academics, who are experiencing additional exclusion within a system that, even before neoliberalism, was not designed for disabled people (Olsen *et al.*, 2020).

In the UK, the University and College Union (UCU; 2016, 2021) found that HE staff in Scotland face unmanageable workloads, responsibilities, and pressures while the demands and expectations of students rise. Therefore, while some like Guzzardo *et al.* (2021) argue that “*doing more than teaching*” is necessary to demonstrate to students that educators care about them and their learning, “*doing more than*” can often seem impossible for HE workers who are already overworked and overwhelmed. Consequently, conflicting feelings arose while I wrote the previous sections, and although I am aware of these pressures, I am also arguing to increase HE professionals’ workload somehow. While the backbone of this section (but also of the whole chapter and study) is hope, I cannot but feel hopeless when facing the reality of HE.

Thus, adopting an ethics of care can open a series of possibilities from multiple perspectives and challenge neoliberal notions in post-pandemic Scottish HE. Yet, this same scenario leaves limited capacity (in terms of time, energy, and resources) to enact such possibilities. How can one do more if one is already experiencing stress and exhaustion? How can one care for all and each student when student numbers are high and time is limited (Walker-Greaves, 2019)? As Blackie, Case and Jawitz (2010) argued, caring about students, having a feeling of personal

responsibility and valuing their whole humanity can be unattainable when working with, for example, over 100 students.

Yet, this conflict, where strategies to improve student well-being increase the already excessive workload of staff, illustrates existing narratives that position student and staff well-being in opposition (see Brewster *et al.*, 2022). However, Brewster *et al.* (2022, p. 549) argue that HEIs could foster staff and student well-being by taking a “*whole university approach*”, which is supported by others like Brewster and Cox (2023). Therefore, this calls for a holistic approach that promotes cultural, structural, and institutional changes to support well-being across the entire educational community instead of reactive and detached interventions (Brewster *et al.*, 2022). As Hughes and Spanner (2019) argue, HE is an interconnected environment where the well-being of one group (staff) can impact the well-being of another group (students). Hence, although I recognise that it is impossible for many across HE in Scotland to do more, implementing whole-university caring and compassionate approaches, as argued in the previous section, could be a way of resisting the challenges imposed by neoliberal demands. This could open up possibilities to help increase the well-being of the educational community as a whole, benefiting disabled students as key members of that community.

Another constraint, as noted by Walker-Gleaves (2019), is that being caring is often conceptualised as a personal trait. This echoes Sally’s (educator) question in Chapter 5, as she wonders how a nuclear physicist can relate to a 17-year-old. This, I believe, illustrates the impossibility of every member of the educational community being caring or being caring in a way that is effectively perceived and responded to by students. However, Walker-Gleaves (2019) hints at the need to explore how being caring can be conceptualised and transmitted. Finding ways of doing this means that care becomes more than a personal characteristic and becomes something that can be learned and enacted. Although I believe there must be, at least, a personal interest in the relational nature of education and the roles of care and responsibility, evidence-based training and awareness can pave the way for it.

As discussed above, caring pedagogies could open possibilities to create more compassionate HEIs and according to Hamilton and Petty (2023), educators are in a privileged position to foster compassion for all via educational spaces. However, as happens with other relational elements like care (as seen in Chapter 5), compassion is not always acknowledged in HE in favour of neoliberal ideas of competition and individualism (Giroux, 2010; Maxwell, 2017; Hamilton and Petty, 2023). This means that creating environments that foster compassionate pedagogies is not an easy endeavour and one that faces many institutional barriers (Hamilton and Petty,

2023). Nevertheless, Peterson (2019) concludes that the representation of neoliberalism within HE means that stress, precarity and dread have become key parts of life in academia, something that limits relational aspects and values like compassion or sympathy. Yet, Peterson (2019, p. 264) also argues that it is precisely in a landscape of “*anxiety, precarity and fear*” where we most need “*compassion, kindness and humility*”, which could offer hope and healthier environments. Hence, these same virtues and values can be powerful tools for transformation (although not the only ones) as, if they guide policy and practice, the courses of action within HE will not always be the most cost-effective or competitive but the most caring, compassionate or beneficial for all (Peterson, 2019).

Hence, in line with the words of Peterson (2019), the key to overcoming the challenges imposed by neoliberalism is to strive for mutual caring, collegiality and closeness. Hope is also a central element of this proposal, as Peterson argues that it is the engine that helps refuse to be part of the relentless neoliberal structure. Working together with decency and acknowledging our shared humanity is what Peterson (2019) believes is needed for more hopeful ways of working in HE. However, in order to do this, more empirical research that illustrates the possibilities of hopeful approaches is needed (ibid). I consider that this study provides one of those examples.

Thus, these factors (care, responsibility, hope) can also create educational spaces that foster the development and flourishing of disabled students and lead to increased retention. This is another way in which I address this study’s research questions, offering a further illustration of how cultures, discourses and practices (although more encouraging than the ones discussed in chapters 4 and 5) can help disabled students fulfil their aspirations and shape the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. Moreover, the chapter illustrates ways in which improvement could be brought to the sector to foster disabled students’ retention. Thus, care and responsibility can be some of the antidotes for the exclusionary cultures, discourses and practices examined in previous chapters, as they help demonstrate that the needs of all disabled students must be valued and considered across HE. Thus, they are also a way to resist ableist and neoliberal discourses where only certain ways of existing, learning, working and succeeding are valid. I argue that care and responsibility, in conjunction with hope, create multiple possibilities for Scottish HE to become a sector for all disabled people to flourish and not one that is known for its exclusionary practices and discourses. Hence, we need care and responsibility, but we also need hope to take action and keep building this sector. My suggestions for doing so can be found in section 6.5. of this chapter, where I address recommendations for policy, practice, and research developed from participants’ suggestions

for change as covered in chapters 4 and 5, intending to promote the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland.

6.4. Strengths and limitations

Reflection and analysis have been key to developing this research, as I regularly evaluated my work and the study's progress before taking further steps. As the research process ends, I believe it is essential to discuss the project's main strengths and limitations. Thus, this section offers my reflections on the study's main contributions and boundaries, helping illustrate the preliminary impact of this research and areas to be considered in the future.

What I consider to be the main strength of this research is that it extensively considers the perspectives of different members of the educational community, such as disabled students, educators, and disability advisers. This element responds to one of the criticisms made about previous literature exploring the retention of disabled students, which tends to focus on one of these groups but rarely on all of them (see Collins, Azmat and Rentschler, 2019). Thus, while I focused on exploring the experiences of disabled students, which guided the data analysis and discussion process, I believe there was a need to take a broader look at the HE in Scotland in order to consider the context in which the student experience takes place and how these elements interact. Moreover, working with these three different groups from a critical angle gave me the possibility of investigating existing and conflicting discourses and the impact they have on the retention of disabled students. Additionally, although the number of participants and the qualitative nature of the study do not allow for a broader generalisation, the fact that 29 participants contributed to this research means it offers a rich qualitative analysis of the topic. The result of taking this approach was the generation and analysis of a rich and valuable dataset pertaining to the retention of disabled students, a severely under-researched area.

The methodological approach I took in this research is what allowed me to generate such rich data and critical analysis. While this approach was not novel in its design, combining in-depth, semi-structured interviews with an FPS epistemological stance has proven to be effective. This approach allowed me to offer a detailed analysis of current and relevant practices, discourses, and cultures, as well as strategies to challenge them and the multiple possibilities of transformation to which they could lead. This means this research offers a more critical, comprehensive and nuanced investigation of the role of educational cultures, discourses and practice in retaining disabled students. This investigation supports my argument for a more comprehensive conceptualisation of disabled students' retention that covers the whole

educational experience, exploring the capacity in which HEIs can help fulfil or foreclose disabled students' aspirations.

Furthermore, the pandemic and post-pandemic context (November 2021 – July 2022) in which the data generation phase took place required me to take a particularly flexible approach to data generation. This resulted in my using different interview formats (please see Chapter 3), such as online interviews, face-to-face interviews, phone interviews or instant messenger interviews, which have contributed to the field of inclusive research. As a researcher, this approach allowed me to adhere to the COVID-19 safety measures existing at the time, but also that I could adjust to participants' needs and preferences during interviews. Thus, using different interview formats meant participants could take part in their preferred way, choosing their most suitable approach to communication and confidentiality. Hence, while I initially thought that COVID-19 restrictions would hinder the data generated in this study, I now believe it opened a series of possibilities that meant participants could get involved in this study more meaningfully. I am confident that this led to them being more comfortable and at ease during the interviews, leading to the extensive dataset I am lucky and thankful to be able to work with.

Hence, the main strengths of this study are its contributions to knowledge, which resulted from a methodological approach that allowed me to investigate participants' experiences in depth and through a critical lens. One of these main contributions is the examination of cultures and discourses and how they shape the retention of disabled students in Scottish HE. This has led to the identification and analysis of modifiable factors not widely considered in the previous literature about the retention of disabled students, such as the pervasive notion of apparent *ideal* disabled students and the effect this has on those who do not fit with that notion.

Additionally, this study highlights the key role of relational aspects like care and responsibility in the retention of disabled students, which have not been widely discussed in previous literature either.

Another strength of this study is its applicability and potential to promote reflection and influence policy and practice. This has been demonstrated repeatedly during different stages of the research process. For example, as addressed in Chapter 3, several participants expressed their interest in the topic and how it had made them reflect on their experiences as students and as HE professionals. Some participants also manifested their interest in the study findings due to their applicability to their professional practice. Therefore, in line with my ethics application, I shared a summary of the research results with them and gave them the opportunity to provide feedback on the study and findings. Participants who responded to this

call for feedback were satisfied with the study's findings and discussions, believing they were relevant and necessary and covered all their concerns.

In addition, I have been able to use these findings to inform the design and delivery of a co-production Mental Health Literacy programme I have been involved in at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Although this was not done formally, some of my findings, such as those related to the experience of postgraduate disabled students and to the importance of care and responsibility, have influenced areas of this programme. For instance, I was vocal about the struggles of disabled postgraduate students, such as their difficulties identifying which institutional services they could access, which meant the programme extended its audience to postgraduate students, and the resources that resulted from the programme now signpost to disability-specific support. This programme has received positive feedback across the institution, as students believe it should have been included in the curriculum much earlier. Faculty across the institution are also interested in the workshop and have asked to participate, which means some sessions have been delivered to staff, and more are planned in the future.

However, this study is not without its limitations. The one I consider to be most significant is the small number of disabled people formerly enrolled in Scottish HE who participated in the study (N = 3). I was deeply interested in reaching out to more participants who met these characteristics, as I consider their input essential to studying the current topic. Still, I was not capable of meeting this aim. In hindsight, I should have been more creative and persistent in the recruitment phase, identifying more effective means of communication and points of contact to ensure I could do so.

Another limitation I can reflect on is that this research has not been as collaborative as I would have liked it to be. While I was designing this project, I envisioned more sustained collaboration, following a participatory, participant-centred research approach, and the use of more creative strategies such as diary methods. Yet, due to a series of circumstances, such as the pandemic, which called for limited social gatherings, delays in the data generation phase or considering that participants were already volunteering a great amount of time, I decided that only using in-depth semi-structured interviews was the most accessible and feasible strategy. Yet, this meant the data analysis process was solely conducted by me, limiting the extent to which participants could have been involved in this process, and increasing the likelihood of data misinterpretation (see section 3.7 in Chapter 3 for a more detailed discussion of this difficulty).

In line with this, I must note that the challenges arising from power dynamics during the research process and my own experiences and identities are likely to have influenced this

study's data analysis and might have led to data mis- or re-interpretation (see Gibson *et al.*, 2017; Gibson *et al.*, 2018; see section 3.7 in Chapter 3 for a more detailed discussion). This is another one of this study's limitations, as participant involvement in phases of the research process, such as study design and data analysis, was limited. While I considered these difficulties in the data generation, data analysis and writing up stages, readers must also take this into account when engaging with this thesis.

Finally, an additional boundary of my research comes in the form of the themes discussed in this thesis. Although it offers a comprehensive overview of the data generated, due to the time and resources available, it was not possible to cover all areas of relevance addressed during interviews. I will consider these aspects and other unexplored ones in future publications related to the data generated in this research.

6.5. Recommendations and next steps

According to bell hooks (2003, p. xiv), when we only identify a problem without focusing on practical resolutions, "*we take away hope*", as a critique that does not address potential solutions reflects a cynicism that can help "*sustain dominator culture*". However, recognising the problem while also expressing what we (can) do to face the issue is necessary for bringing change about and encouraging resistance (ibid). A common denominator across the interviews I conducted for this study was that participants consistently proposed alternatives and talked about ways to challenge what impacted the retention of disabled students across Scottish HE. Hence, despite the complexity of their experiences, participants remained hopeful that change was possible and took an active role in articulating this, which helped address this study's second research question.

This section compiles this study's recommendations for policy, research and practice, which were developed from participants' suggestions for change as addressed in chapters 4 and 5, alongside my own recommendations after conducting this research. This approach was inspired by the work of Goldstone and Zhang (2021), who shared student-led policy solutions in their investigation of postgraduate students' experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. Developing the study's recommendations from participants' suggestions for change aligns with my epistemological approach because, by taking an FPS stance, I focus on the voices of participants, as according to authors like Aston (2016), their lived experiences are necessary when challenging the status quo. Moreover, this study's call for hopeful change aligns with FPS' optimistic search for transformation (Ollivier, 2022). In this sense, developing recommendations

in this way also fills me with hope, as they illustrate what could be possible and are a testament to participants' willingness to transform HE and, by extension, their lives and the lives of others.

Although this study mainly addressed structural difficulties (in the form of excluding cultures, discourse, and practices), it also investigated the importance of individual actions in resisting and challenging those difficulties. Therefore, similarly to the approach taken by Hughes and Spanner (2019), these recommendations are not intended to be prescriptive, as I acknowledge that all institutions are unique and diverse. On the contrary, I align with the FPS principles of uncertainty and ambiguity (Baxter, 2008) and recognise that these recommendations do not provide fixed answers to the questions addressed here. Instead, they intend to portray points of tension identified in this study and the opportunities to do things otherwise. These recommendations provide broad guidelines that can be adapted to the different needs of the sector, institutions, groups and individuals. Therefore, I acknowledge that there is a need to address structural issues leading to exclusion, but also the existence of good practices across the sector, and that the key to tackling exclusion is the collaboration between all members of the community towards the shared goal of inclusion for all.

6.5.1. Recommendations for policymakers

Evidence supports the need to develop institution-wide approaches to inclusion and well-being (see Hughes and Spanner, 2019). However, this cannot be achieved without strong sector-wide support (*ibid*). Therefore, considering current findings and previous literature, I make the following recommendations for policymakers:

- In line with the work of Brewster *et al.* (2022), the impact of policies on the well-being of the educational community must be considered, and student support should be acknowledged as an integral part of all staff with student-facing roles. Hence, collaboration between institutions, policymakers, and sector-leading organisations like Advance HE, Vitae, and the UK Council for Graduate Education is necessary to promote effective and sustainable change.
- The current DSA system poses several difficulties for disabled students, ultimately being an inaccessible procedure for many. A review and update of the DSA process seems necessary. Based on the evidence discussed in this thesis and the recommendations made by participants, one way of doing this could be by allocating funds directly to HEIs, which they can distribute amongst disabled students. This would mean that disability support services can process all support directly for students, which could lead to more

individualised negotiation processes, leaving more room for trust, care and responsibility.

6.5.2. Recommendations for HE management

According to the current data, the role of HEIs as a whole is crucial in the promotion of disabled students' inclusion and retention, particularly considering the relevance of institutional cultures, discourses and practices. Considering this, I make the following recommendations for those in positions of management within HE in Scotland:

- The need for whole-university approaches that promote inclusion and well-being (Hughes and Spanner, 2019) is as fitting as ever in a post-pandemic landscape where many of those involved in HE are experiencing stress, anxiety and precarity. These approaches should address and tackle the current HE landscape in which staff and students are overwhelmed and overworked and the specific impact this has on disabled individuals. The overall humanity and experiences of the educational community members must be respected and valued for these strategies to be effective. Hence, evidence-based institutional approaches that promote care and compassion could have a positive impact on well-being across HEIs, benefiting all those involved and promoting inclusion. Intersectionality should also be considered in these approaches to recognise and value the different identities of students. This could also promote the retention of disabled students in HE and pave the way for those pursuing careers within HE.
- Considering the difficulties related to student retention, this should be an area considered as important as student recruitment. To do so, it is recommended that proactive and preventive initiatives be considered as much as possible. To develop proactive strategies to promote retention, it is essential that HEIs generate and use data to know the needs of the student body. Although reactive and crisis approaches to promote retention will always be necessary due to unforeseen circumstances, it is recommended that they are not the common practice. Care, compassion and responsibility should be at the centre of all retention strategies.
- Strategies to investigate student retention, particularly the retention of disabled students and other marginalised groups, should take a comprehensive conceptualisation of the construct and consider students' broader experiences and aspirations and how these shape their retention and progression in the sector.

- The impact of educational cultures and practices on the retention of disabled students has been demonstrated. Hence, the promotion of university-wide educational strategies to promote inclusion is paramount. This is particularly relevant considering that many disabled students do not have access to medical documentation, some are not aware of their needs, and some choose not to share their needs and disabilities with their institutions. Consequently, adopting care-based strategies such as UDL and Trauma-Informed Pedagogies is recommended. These strategies could help build inclusion across all educational practices, considering the needs of all students and promoting safe spaces for all to learn without the need for individualised adjustments. Flexibility, choice and hybrid learning should be key elements within these strategies.
- There must be a recognition that some of the current cultures, discourses and practices across HE exclude disabled students from the learning experience and can impact their retention. Thus, it is necessary to acknowledge that some disabled students experience additional discrimination due to their multiple identities amidst the current prevalence of neoliberal ideological norms across the sector. These discriminatory elements must be identified within HEIs alongside strategies to eliminate them.
- There is extensive evidence showing that providing medical evidence as a prerequisite to access support can be an exclusionary practice, particularly for disabled students who do not meet idealised criteria, as discussed in this study, such as postgraduate disabled students. Thus, it is recommended that HEIs eliminate medical evidence as a prerequisite to access institutional disability support. Alternatives, such as written testimonies from students, could be considered. This strategy could help those who do not have easy access to medical certification to access the required support in a timely and effective manner. It could also be a way of implementing care-based and intersectional approaches in which the needs and identities of all students are acknowledged and valued.
- To adopt institution-wide inclusive, care-based, and intersectional approaches, training and development opportunities must be provided to all staff across HEIs. It is suggested this training covers disability awareness, inclusion, UDL, and Trauma-Informed approaches and highlights the relational aspects of education with a focus on care, compassion and responsibility towards students and other members of the educational community. Training opportunities should also explore and aim to tackle academic ableism, discourses and practices that are currently excluding disabled students in HE.

This can also have a positive impact on disabled members of staff, particularly for those with invisible disabilities and undisclosed ones, thus improving the system as a whole.

- Specific attention should be paid to all postgraduate research programmes to equip supervisors, disability support services and study skills departments with knowledge and skills to support disabled PhD candidates. This should be supported by creating strong networks that ensure different support streams for these candidates to reduce precarity and uncertainty.
- Consultation and collaboration with disabled students is necessary and should be at the centre of any strategies aimed at promoting inclusion. Therefore, more opportunities for collaboration and consultation should be created where disabled students can play an active role in developing inclusive policies and practices. However, these opportunities should not take advantage of the time and energy of disabled students and should consider their varied and often complex needs when they ask them to collaborate. Compensation should be considered for effective and continuous contributions.
- Collaboration can also be a strategy to promote inclusion. Some of the evidence discussed here addresses the disconnect between different educational community members, such as educators, academic development teams, different schools and divisions, disabled students and disability support services. Hence, it is recommended that more opportunities be provided for these units to collaborate and use their expertise to bring positive educational transformation. Promoting the creation of communities of practice could be a strategy to embody this aim for collaboration. Their work should inform innovation and transformation across each HEI.
- Access to physical and online spaces remains indispensable to promote participation. Thus, while in this study, I have focused on the educational side of disabled students' inclusion, the evidence shows that this is impossible if disabled students struggle to access learning spaces (Wertans and Burch, 2022). Therefore, it is recommended that accessibility be promoted across virtual and physical campuses. This includes the creation and maintenance of educational spaces that can be accessed by individuals with different physical needs, physical classrooms that can be easily adapted and additional spaces all can access and enjoy (such as cafes and green areas). Digital accessibility should also be ensured by using inclusive software that helps create high-quality educational experiences.

- The input of disabled students should be central in these collaborations and should be at the centre of any strategies aimed at promoting inclusion. Therefore, more opportunities for collaboration and consultation should be created so that disabled students can play an active role in developing inclusive policies and practices. Disabled staff should also be at the centre of these collaborations.
- Opportunities to identify inclusive practices are also paramount. Therefore, platforms should be available for educators to disseminate good, accessible practices regularly. The input of disabled students should be considered in the evaluations of these practices.
- It is recommended that accessibility be promoted across virtual and physical campuses. This includes the creation and maintenance of educational spaces that can be accessed by individuals with different physical needs, physical classrooms that can be easily adapted and additional spaces all can access and enjoy (such as cafes and green areas). Digital accessibility should also be ensured by using inclusive software that helps create high-quality educational experiences.
- Follow-up protocols must be in place for students who leave their degrees before completion. These protocols should be based on providing information about their future options and any support students might need at this stage. Opportunities for feedback about their educational experience should also be included in these protocols. The circumstances of the students must also be considered, and trauma-informed approaches must inform these protocols.
- A reconceptualisation of the doctoral process is recommended in order to consider the varied needs of disabled PhD candidates and increase their access and participation at this level of education. This reconceptualisation should consider adding flexibility in terms of completion mode (for example by promoting the use of varied formats such as thesis by publication and more collaborative research approaches) and timeframes to make the PhD process more accessible for disabled people. It should also promote cooperative ways of working, leading to a collaborative approach that can help develop effective support networks for PhD candidates. Tackling key difficulties experienced by PhD candidates, such as the increased prevalence of anxiety and depression (Rooij, Fokkens-Bruinsma and Jansen, 2021), should also be considered in this reconceptualisation.

6.5.3. Recommendations for educators

Due to difficulties related to support access, a wide educational approach to inclusion is necessary. Consequently, it is recommended to consider inclusion in all stages of the educational process. According to this study's findings and participants' recommendations, this could be done by adopting an anticipatory approach as covered in the Equality Act (2010), building inclusion in all educational practices to ensure as many disabled students as possible can access education effectively without having to request individual accommodations. Flexibility and choice should be at the centre of these practices. This would benefit most students, regardless of their circumstances. The following recommendations are aimed at promoting educational cultures, policies and practices that can promote a broader approach to inclusion:

- Implementing principles of UDL, ensuring teaching and learning provide different means of engagement, representation and action, and expression (CAST, 2018).
- Adapting the principles of Trauma-Informed Practice (safety; trustworthiness and transparency; peer support; collaboration and mutuality; empowerment and choice; cultural, historical and gender issues; SAMHSA, 2014) to teaching and learning.
- Considering the increased accessibility that hybrid and blended learning can bring to disabled students and how this can be embedded in regular practice.
- Acknowledging the importance of spaces and relations in the promotion of students' sense of belonging, particularly when learning online.
- Consulting with all students, but particularly disabled students, to ensure the reconceptualisation of these practices responds to their needs.
- Consulting with all students, but particularly disabled students, in the development of inclusive practices to ensure these meet students' needs.
- Acknowledging the relational aspect of education, the importance of care and responsibility, and the effect they might have on the experience of disabled students.

This could be enacted by:

- o Recognising that some of the current cultures, discourses and practices exclude disabled students from the learning experience and impact their retention.
- o Being aware of the varied experiences and identities of disabled students, not assuming there is an ideal standard.
- o Acknowledging that some disabled students might experience additional discrimination due to their multiple identities amidst the current neoliberal ideology across the sector. In this landscape, it might be necessary to "*do more*

than teaching” in order to support disabled students who experience difficulties accessing support.

- Understanding that not all disabled students can provide the documentation required to access individualised support under current systems.
 - Acknowledging that the number of disabled students in the classrooms is likely to be higher than formally recorded.
 - Recognising the value of students' experiences and learning and honouring their humanity.
 - Being aware of the institutional support and resources disabled students can access and signpost as appropriate.
- Being aware of the institutional support and resources students in crises can access and signpost as appropriate
 - Collaborating with other members of the educational community, such as disabled students, disability support services and academic development, in order to enhance inclusive practice. This can be done, for example, through the creation of communities of learning.
 - Recognising that the PhD journey is complex for disabled students, supervisors should consider their circumstances as disabled PhD candidates might struggle to find effective support must be considered throughout the supervision process. Hence, it is important to recognise the crucial role that supervisors play in helping disabled PhD candidates in navigating this stage. Supervisory relationships based on trust, care, compassion and responsibility are recommended. Appropriate responses based on care, compassion and responsibility should be provided.
 - While this study focused on disabled students' experiences, I also acknowledge that staff's personal well-being is a necessary condition to provide effective support to students, including disabled students. Hence, it is essential to care for oneself to care for others. While this includes individuals' actions to protect personal well-being, it could also be done by promoting strategies that help challenge current cultures, discourses and practices that have a pervasive effect on staff's overall health and well-being.

6.5.4. Recommendations for disability support services:

The positive role of disability support is undeniable. However, the evidence discussed in this thesis illustrates that some of the current support practices and underlying discourses are

leading to the exclusion of disabled students who do not meet particular standards based on an idealised notion of disabled students. Yet, support provision for all disabled students who need it is necessary for the promotion of the retention and progression of disabled students in HE in Scotland. According to the present findings, some strategies that could help do so are as follows:

- Ensure all systems are designed with all disabled students in mind. This can be done by:
 - Reviewing and updating, if necessary, existing support strategies to ensure they are appropriate for postgraduate disabled students (master's and PhDs).
 - Consulting with disabled students during this review process. Extended collaborations should be compensated.
 - Reviewed strategies should consider:
 - The limited time that master's students spend doing their degrees and how this impacts the support provision process. Fast tracks might be considered for this group of students.
 - The open-ended and autonomous nature of postgraduate research programmes and the implications that have for support provision.
 - The changing symptoms associated with certain health conditions, which might not allow disabled students to attend nor cancel appointments with enough notice.
 - The difficulties disabled people can experience accessing medical evidence.
 - The development of alternatives to medical evidence as a prerequisite to access disability support.
 - Increase awareness of the services and who can access them. This can be done by:
 - Creating effective information resources that detail what services are available, who can access them, how and how long this might take.
 - These information resources should pay particular attention to representing the multiple identities of disabled students. Thus, these resources should aim to reach out to under-represented groups like disabled postgraduate or disabled mature undergraduate students.

- These resources and communications strategies should also represent the often changing (not fixed) nature of disability. Hence, these resources should also acknowledge that people can become disabled later in life or that accessing a medical diagnosis can be a difficult process. Still, support should be available for those who need it and respond to disabled students' personal circumstances.
 - Some strategies like case studies available on institutions websites or on leaflets could help students get a more comprehensive insight into the characteristics of the support that can be negotiated.
- Create opportunities for collaboration with other members of the educational community, such as academic development teams, to promote institution-wide inclusive practices.
- Promote disability awareness across the institution.
- Ensure care, compassion and responsibility are at the centre of all practice. This includes:
 - Considering the effect of ableism on the educational journey of disabled students.
 - Acknowledging and addressing the flaws in support systems.
 - Offering alternative or temporary support for disabled students who experience delays and difficulties accessing adjustments and accommodations.
 - Challenging existing ableist policies and practices, while putting students' needs over compliance.
 - Adopting an intersectional approach that ensures disabled students' complex experiences and identities are considered across disability support practices.
 - Ensuring there are regular check-ins with disabled students across the duration of their programmes to corroborate the effectiveness of existing support or the need for further adjustments. These check-ins could also be an opportunity disabled students' persistence and whether there is room to support them complete their programmes.
- Staff's personal well-being is a necessary condition to provide effective support to students, including disabled students. Hence, it is essential to care for oneself in order to care for others. While this includes individuals' actions to protect personal well-being,

it could also be done by promoting strategies that help challenge current cultures, discourses and practices that have a pervasive effect on staff's overall health and well-being.

6.5.5. Recommendations for disabled students

Although I recognise the struggles and additional labour of disabled students in HE, I believe disabled students are active subjects capable of bringing positive change to HE. Therefore, while I reject HEIs placing the responsibility on disabled students to promote inclusion, I consider disabled students to be the best suited to make inform the educational inclusion process, as this thesis demonstrates. While I recognise that these recommendations might not be accessible to many, they contribute to the collaborative approach to inclusion I take in this study to which disabled students are crucial. Based on this, I make the following recommendations:

- **Self-care:** protecting one's well-being is essential during HE and should be above any of these recommendations. Self-reflection is necessary to understand how to best care for oneself and this might include avoiding being involved in activities that go beyond what is strictly related to the programme one is enrolled in. That includes dismissing recommendations like the ones made here.
- **Reflection and advocacy:** self-knowledge and self-reflection can help disabled students understand their needs deeply, facilitating communication and self-advocacy skills. Hence, understanding one's own needs and rights and being up to date with HEIs duties regarding inclusion is essential in order to advocate for oneself. Using the resources offered by institutions and holding them accountable if this support is not effective can also help challenge exclusionary practices and attitudes.
- **Collaboration:** seeking out or creating opportunities to collaborate with other members of the educational community, such as staff, other disabled students and allied non-disabled peers can be a valuable opportunity to enhance inclusion. Being part of communities for learning, societies or unions can be valuable platforms to influence policies and practices in HE and promote the inclusion and retention of disabled students. This could help challenge traditional power relationships across the sector.
- **Awareness:** for some, discussing their disability-related lived experiences can be a powerful tool to challenge ableism in HE, although this is not suitable for all. However, when possible and freely chosen, disabled students' platforms, such as social media or

daily interactions, can be used to raise awareness about good and exclusionary practices across HE.

- **Participation:** HEIs might already be promoting initiatives for students to take part in. Making the most out of these opportunities and using them as platforms to challenge exclusionary practices can also be valuable towards more inclusive HE.
- **Creation:** where these opportunities are not available or are not accessible, disabled and non-disabled students can create them as a strategy to challenge current power dynamics and exclusion.

6.5.6. Recommendations for future research

This research has helped enhance the evidence available in an under-researched area, addressing key areas to consider in the investigation of disabled students' retention. However, the boundaries of this study have also opened opportunities for further research:

- Although this research illustrates cultures, discourses and practices that influence the experiences of disabled students in HE and shape their retention, this evidence is part of the still-growing critical literature exploring the topic. Thus, it is recommended that more research be conducted in this research strand, identifying other cultural and discursive elements key to the experience of this group of students.
- It is also recommended that this research strand considers other elements of the identities of disabled students, such as gender, ethnicity and maturity, and takes an intersectional approach. This would enhance the research body that explores the experiences of disabled students through an intersectional lens. It could also help illustrate other identity markers of what constitutes the idealised conception of disabled students in HE.
- The experiences of those who had to leave HE before graduating are under-represented in the research studying the retention of disabled students. Therefore, there is a need to represent these voices more consistently across this research field, as it could add evidence around the factors that lead to the early withdrawal of this group of students. It could also help fill the gap surrounding the implications that early exit of HE has on disabled people's life chances and trajectories.
- It is recommended that future research examining the retention of disabled students in HE adopts a comprehensive understanding of retention and considers students' overall experiences and aspirations, as proposed in this study.

- Since the current research findings have concentrated on the broad experiences of HE disabled students as a heterogeneous group, these findings could be supported by similar research that focuses on the experiences of more specific groups of disabled students (for example, autistic and neurodivergent students or students with chronic health conditions). This narrower research focus could shed light on the specific ableist cultures and discourses impacting these specific groups of students and led to the development of more specific intervention strategies.

6.6. Conclusions

This study analysed the cultures, discourses and practices that help fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland and how this relates to their retention. The data generated demonstrates that disability support services and pedagogical approaches play a crucial role in the experiences of disabled students in HE in Scotland. Moreover, the data also illustrated that these two areas are permeated by neoliberal notions of normalcy that favour narrow ways of being and learning (see Madriaga *et al.*, 2011) and promote an idealised understanding of the experiences and identities of disabled students (see Dadvand, 2022). Considering these, the findings also portray the need for a more comprehensive understanding of disabled students' retention, moving away from a quantitative focus on year-to-year progression. Instead, these findings highlight the importance of considering how HE cultures, discourses, and practices shape their overall experiences and help fulfil or foreclose their aspirations. Additionally, this study portrays the need for pedagogies of care that consider and value the whole human experiences of disabled students to help face the challenges across the current “*uncaring*” (Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild, 2024, p. 388) neoliberal, post-pandemic HE landscape (Xiao, 2021; Lemon, Harju-Luukkainen and Garvis, 2023; Lopez, 2023).

Consequently, I advocate for the deconstruction of the current idealised notion of disabled students across HE in Scotland and propose the need to adopt an intersectional approach instead. This intersectional approach can promote wider recognition of the diverse experiences and identities of disabled students in HE and the acknowledgement that disabled students are likely to have more than one oppressed identity, which leads to complex forms of discrimination (Peña, Stapleton and Schaffer, 2016). Hence, once disability is accepted as an intrinsic part of the human experience and seen from an intersectional lens, inclusion would mean, in line with the ideas of Dolmage (2017), the existence of difference.

Moreover, the data generated portrays the importance of responsibility and care across areas such as disability support and pedagogical practice (see Guzzardo *et al.*, 2021). Hence, I support the adoption of an ethics of care in which responsibility plays a key role across HE in Scotland, which could be a strategy to bring transformation and increased inclusion to the sector. This ethics of care and the importance of responsibility are reflected in participants' call for adopting an anticipatory approach to educational inclusion, promoting hybrid learning and valuing the whole human experiences of disabled students.

Considering this, I believe that adopting care-based pedagogies can lead to a series of multiple possibilities that can promote inclusion across Scottish HE, fostering cultures, discourses and practices in which disabled students can persist and thrive. In line with the data generated, these possibilities, as discussed in the chapter, could include the promotion of anticipatory approaches to educational inclusion, as well as the promotion of compassion across HE or the adoption of trauma-informed pedagogies. However, implementing such strategies puts additional demands on HE workers, particularly on disabled ones, who, amidst the current neoliberal landscape, face excessive workloads (Griffin, 2022) and experience exhaustion (Perisic, 2021). Still, in line with Peterson's (2019) words, the key to overcoming the challenges imposed by neoliberalism in HE is to strive for mutual caring, collegiality, and closeness. Hence, I argue that adopting an intersectional lens and promoting care and responsibility, in conjunction with hope, can create multiple possibilities for HE in Scotland to become a sector that helps fulfil the aspirations of all disabled people (students and staff) and promote their retention.

Furthermore, this chapter has aimed to address the study's second research question by illustrating the different ways in which participants believe there is room for improvement across HE in Scotland to promote the retention of disabled students. Stemming from participants' suggestions for change, and supported by my own recommendations, the chapter also illustrated several recommendations for policy, research and practice, which call for a more caring and responsible sector that values the complex experiences of disabled students. While these recommendations are not intended to be prescriptive, they offer broad guidance on strategies that could help promote HE sectors and institutions that create inclusive cultures, discourses and practices that allow disabled students, disabled staff and their non-disabled peers to meet their dreams and aspirations while promoting persistence. This aligns with the aims and findings of the study, as I advocate for HE systems in which disabled students can flourish and thrive.

Chapter 7: Conclusions

Student retention is a widely studied phenomenon, characterised by being a complex area of study and practice. Yet, as the Literature Review (Chapter 2) shows, little attention has been given to the retention of specific groups of students, such as disabled students, and the existing accounts tend to take a quantitative approach that does not explore the complexity of the topic in-depth and critically. Therefore, my aim with this study was to contribute to these areas and enrich the body of evidence that can help promote the retention of disabled students in HE and particularly in Scotland. Considering this, this study has analysed how HE cultures, discourses, and practices help fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in HE in Scotland and how this relates to their retention in the sector. Additionally, I have addressed ways in which way stakeholders consider that there could be improvements across the HE sector in Scotland to foster the retention of disabled students. Therefore, I have addressed the research questions that guide this research thanks to the collaboration of 29 participants and by using a qualitative study based on the use of semi-structured interviews guided by a Feminist Poststructuralist (FPS) epistemological framework. This research approach is supported by the limited evidence available about the experience of retention of disabled students in HE, and particularly by the need for a more critical exploration of the issue to help us understand the underlying elements that sustain exclusionary practices across the sector.

As a result, this study offers some key results in relation to the retention of disabled students in HE in Scotland. First, the current research findings demonstrate that a more comprehensive understanding of disabled students' retention is necessary. I argue that this conceptualisation should go beyond year-to-year progression and also consider the overall experiences of disabled students and how the capacity in which they can fulfil their aspirations shapes persistence and retention. Thus, retention should not be simply measured quantitatively by the number of students who progress from one year to the next but also by the overall quality of their experiences and whether discrimination in the sector is foreclosing their dreams and aspirations.

Furthermore, this study uncovered that the areas of Disability Support and Pedagogy play a crucial role in disabled students' experiences in HE in Scotland, influencing the capacity in which they can fulfil their aspirations in HE in Scotland and shaping their persistence and retention. Moreover, the study revealed that there is a pervasive notion of normalcy across the

sector that prioritises narrow ways of being and learning, constructing an idealised understanding of who can be a disabled student in the sector. According to these shared notions, ideal disabled students in the sector are mainly undergraduates and have access to medical certification to corroborate their conditions and needs. Students who do not adhere to those criteria (postgraduate students and students without medical certification) are positioned lower in the support provision hierarchy, which means they experience significant difficulties accessing adjustments and accommodations.

These *non-ideal* disabled students face exclusion and discrimination in the sector because the support provision process becomes a source of stress, which can have a negative impact on their health and well-being, and because their access to education is hampered by these circumstances. Moreover, *non-ideal* disabled students who face difficulties are met with a lack of care and responsibility, leaving them in a precarious position that puts them at higher risk of an early exit and forecloses their aspirations. Yet, participants in this study believe that care-based pedagogical approaches could challenge these circumstances and the neoliberal principles that underpin them. Furthermore, I argue for a more comprehensive recognition of the importance of responsibility and care across areas such as disability support and pedagogy to help bring transformation and increased inclusion to the sector.

Thus, according to the present data, care-based pedagogies can help create a HE sector in which disabled students' complete human experiences are valued, providing additional flexibility and control over their educational experiences and valuing their sense of belonging. Additionally, I argue for the need to adopt an intersectional approach that helps deconstruct the current idealised notion of disabled students across the sector. This intersectional approach can promote wider recognition of the diverse experiences and identities of disabled students in HE. Anticipatory approaches to educational inclusion and hybrid learning are essential to enable this shift. Moreover, the multiple possibilities opened by these approaches could also include the promotion of more compassion across HE and the adoption of trauma-informed pedagogies. Thus, I conclude that adopting these approaches opens a series of multiple possibilities that can promote inclusion across Scottish HE, fostering cultures, discourses and practices where disabled students can persist and thrive.

Nevertheless, I acknowledge that implementing such strategies puts additional demands on HE workers, particularly on disabled ones, who, amidst the current neoliberal landscape, already face excessive workloads (Griffin, 2022) and exhaustion (Perisic, 2021). Still, in line with Peterson's (2019) words, the key to overcoming the challenges imposed by neoliberalism in HE

is to strive for mutual caring, collegiality, and closeness. Hence, I argue that adopting an intersectional lens and promoting care and responsibility, in conjunction with hope, can create multiple possibilities for HE in Scotland to become a sector that helps fulfil the aspirations of all disabled people (students and staff) and promote their retention.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Ethical Approval Letter

30/08/2021

Dear Patricia Castellano Verdecia,

Your application 16290: Retention of disabled students in higher education, submission 14002, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. The following comments have been made by the reviewers and are intended to be discussed with your supervisor to improve the study.

Title	Comment
Where will the proposed research take place?	Good consideration has been made about the locus of the interview, but perhaps also ensure the public space also affords some privacy for the interviewee in case any sensitivities might be disclosed.
Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with such issues:	I'm glad you recognise this - it adds further weight to the previous point about taking care over your choice of setting for the interview.
Please provide details of other groups	I'm just wondering if as part of your recruitment you may have some participants with fluctuating capacity to provide informed consent. How will this be navigated?

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Appendix 2: Participant recruitment flyers shared on Twitter/X

PHD PROJECT:
RETENTION OF DISABLED STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

PARTICIPANTS WANTED

Are you a disabled student currently enrolled in Scottish higher education?

If you answered **YES** to the above question, I would like to hear from you!

My research focuses on the impact of **teaching and learning practice** on the **retention of disabled students in Scottish higher education**.

Participating in this project would mean taking part in **two interviews** - a few weeks apart - **which will focus on exploring your experiences in higher education**. Each of these interviews is expected to last approximately **1 hour** (online or in-person), but we can **adjust this process** in any way you want (e.g. email interview).

My name is **Patricia Castellano** and I am a PhD candidate at the **University of the West of Scotland**. If you want to learn more about the project, email me at or message me on **Twitter** at

You can also register your interest using the **QR code** below, which will take you to an online form, and I will contact you.

Thank you!

PHD PROJECT:
RETENTION OF DISABLED STUDENTS IN HIGHER
EDUCATION

PARTICIPANTS WANTED

Are you **disabled** and were formerly enrolled
in **Scottish higher education**?

Did you have to **leave higher education**
before completing your studies?

If you answered **YES** to the above questions, I would like to hear from you!

I am researching the **impact of teaching and learning practice** on the **retention of disabled students in higher education**.

The voices of disabled people who had to leave higher education are **not frequently included** in the literature. Hence, I believe your perspective is essential to address the difficulties related to the topic.

Participating in this project means taking part in **one interview**. This interview will focus on your **experience in higher education**. **The interview** can be **online or face-to-face** and would last approximately **1 hour**. We can also **adjust this process** in any way you like (e.g. email interview).

My name is **Patricia Castellano** and I am a PhD candidate at the **University of the West of Scotland**. If you would like to express your interest in the project you can email me at or message me on Twitter at

You can also register your interest using the below **QR code**, which will take you to an online form, and I will contact you.

Thank you!

PHD PROJECT:
RETENTION OF DISABLED STUDENTS IN HIGHER
EDUCATION

PARTICIPANTS WANTED

Do you **teach in Scottish higher education?**

or

Do you **work at the disability services** of a
Scottish higher education institution?

If you answered 'yes' to any of those questions, I
would like to **hear from you**.

My research focuses on the **impact of teaching and
learning on the retention of disabled students in
higher education**.

I am interested in knowing more about **your
experience regarding inclusive education and
teaching disabled students**. Thus, I would like to invite
you to an **interview**. This interview can be **online or in-
person** and will last approximately **1 hour**.

My name is Patricia Castellano, and I am a PhD candidate at the
University of the West of Scotland. If you would like to express your
interest in the project or get **more information**, you can **contact me**:

Or register your interest and
I will contact you:

Thank you!

Appendix 3: Participant Information Sheet

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET:

PhD research study: retention of disabled students in Scottish higher education.

Hello,

My name is Patricia Castellano, and I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. If you have received this form because you have shown interest in participating in my research project. If you are interested in getting involved, it is important that you read the following information detailing the project's scope, how it will be developed, and other relevant information. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to contact me at: [REDACTED]. I will explain this better below, but I just wanted to remind you that any involvement you have in this project will only be voluntary and that you can decide to withdraw your participation at any time. Also, I will keep any information you share with me confidential and anonymous.

More details about my research are as follows:

What is the study about?

Low retention rates seem to be an issue of concern amongst disabled students in higher education (HE). While many factors impact those rates, I am interested in understanding how pedagogical practice shapes disabled students' intentions to persist. I believe that teaching and learning practice is an important aspect of the student experience in HE, and it is essential to understand its role in this matter.

Who can participate?

The understanding of disability that I have adopted for this project is broad, which means that I am interested in talking to all those students who identify as disabled.

This includes, but is not limited to autistic students, students with mental health difficulties, students with chronic health conditions, students with physical and/or sensory impairments, or students with learning disabilities. Additionally, I would also like to talk to students who do not have specific diagnosis but identify as disabled due to their lived experience.

This is independent of whether you are actively seeking diagnosis at the moment, whether you have been refused assessment or diagnosis, or whether you are not interested in seeking diagnosis. If you are part of the disability community, your experience matters, and I would like to talk to you.

Additionally, I wanted to clarify that having gone through disability disclosure at your institution is not a requirement to participate in this project.

How could you be a part of it?

I will use semi-structured interviews to explore the topic stated above, and if you decide to participate in my study, I will invite you to one interview/two interviews. These interviews will take place approximately three weeks apart (although this is flexible) and, if conducted synchronously, are expected to last around 60 minutes each. If you decide to go ahead, I will adapt to you, and we can have those interviews in your preferred way – virtually, via email, chat, over the phone, or face-to-face if we adhere to Covid-19 safety measures. If you would like to conduct the interviews asynchronously (via email, for instance), you can feel free to follow the timeframe that works best for you.

What might happen during the interviews?

During the interviews, I will ask questions about how you perceive teaching and learning practice might be shaping your experience at HE, amongst other related topics. There are no wrong answers. I just want to understand your experience better. One example of the questions I might ask is “How has your experience at university been so far?” During the second interview, I will mainly follow-up on topics we discussed in the first interview. However, I might ask other questions.

If a sensitive topic arises at any point, you will have the opportunity to take a break, change the subject, or withdraw your participation from the study. I do not wish that these interviews became a negative experience for you.

In addition, I would like to record both interviews, if conducted synchronously. However, I will transcribe what we said as soon as possible and will make sure the transcription is anonymised as far as possible. If there are video recordings resulting from the interviews, I will delete them as soon as possible. As a backup, I will keep the voice recordings until I finish working on this project, but I will only work with the anonymised interviews’ transcripts to conduct the data analysis. Only you and I will have access to data that might easily reveal your identity. Alternatively, if you do not wish me to record the interviews, I could take notes of what we discuss. This will help me remember the topics we covered. If the interviews are conducted via email or chat, I will analyse the email exchange or chat log.

How can you opt-out if you change your mind?

You can decide to leave the study at any point, without providing a reason and without any consequences. I just ask that you let me know. After you do so, I will delete and destroy any information you provided during your involvement in the project. Once I do this, I will forward you a withdrawal form to sign as evidence of your wish to withdraw your participation and of my duty of deleting all the information related to you.

How will I use the information you share?

After the interviews, I will analyse the information you shared with me to understand better how teaching and learning practice might be influencing your experience as a disabled student in HE. Afterwards, I will use this analysis for my PhD thesis, and it

might also be included in other academic and research documents. I will anonymise all the personal information you provide and will disguise it to reduce, as far as possible, the chances of your identity being revealed. I would like to use pseudonyms to refer to you as a research participant in the outcomes of this project. I will also change or conceal the names of other people, places and institutions to reduce the likelihood of your and other people's identities being revealed.

Additionally, if relevant, I would like to include details such as your field of study and other elements that could support data analysis. However, I will not do this without your consent. Therefore, I would like to discuss with you your preferences regarding data anonymization. In this sense, I would like us to work collaboratively to reach a point where you are comfortable with the treatment I will do of the information you provide. This discussion could address the possibility that you might like me to adopt more robust strategies to reduce the chances of your identity being revealed. Alternatively, you might wish me to include specific personal details that would help amplify your voice in the study. If your preferences ensure compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), I will gladly respect them during data analysis and dissemination. If the results of this discussion differ from the aspects I cover in the general consent form, I will provide you with an individualised consent form to reflect your preferences.

Additionally, I would like to share your interviews' transcripts with you, as well as the analysis I do of the data. This will help ensure that you agree with how I am handling the information you shared with me. If you are interested, I can also share the project's progress with you and its outcomes once it is finished. Just let me know in the consent form.

Although I will work to protect your privacy, I must be clear that there is always the possibility that someone - including yourself or those close to you - manages to recognise your words. Guaranteeing total anonymity is a near-impossible task. Still, I will do everything that is in my hand to treat your data in the best way to keep your identity safe and respect your privacy. If we have not done so yet, or if you wish to discuss this issue again, please let me know, and we can talk about it.

I also wanted to mention that as a PhD student, I have limited influence in making changes that could lead to better retention rates. However, I will use the outcomes of this project to spread information and increase awareness amongst those who are in positions of power that might lead to significant changes in this regard. I will do this through academic publications and the creation and dissemination of guidance and strategies that institutions can use – amongst other resources.

How do I know that this information will be kept safe and confidential?

Any information that you give me will be stored electronically under a pseudonym and in password-protected files. In addition, when I process your data, I will make sure to delete and disguise any details that might give away your identity. Any printed documents will be kept in locked cabinets within the premises of UWS. The voice recording of the interviews will be kept until this research project is finished (expected to be after summer 2023). The interviews' transcriptions and printed documents will be safely kept for five years after the project's end, and then I will delete and destroy these. Only you and I will have access to data that might easily reveal your identity - during the interviews, while processing the data, and when

you review your interviews' transcripts.

What do you need to do if you want to participate?

If you are satisfied with this information you can read the consent form, and sign it and forward a signed copy to me if you agree with the statements provided there. If you have any additional queries before signing the consent form or would like to discuss any aspects of the research and your involvement (confidentiality, anonymity, etc.), do not hesitate to contact me at [REDACTED]

Data protection:

If you wish to discuss data protection directly with the University of the West of Scotland, you can contact dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Ethical review:

This project has been reviewed and accepted by the Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland on 30/08/2021.

If you have any other questions or issues, you would like to discuss, or if you would like to receive this information in an alternative format, do not hesitate to e-mail me at [REDACTED]

Additionally, you can also contact the supervisory team overlooking the development of this project by contacting Dr Beth Cross on [REDACTED]

Thank you very much for reading this form!

Appendix 4: Consent Form

PhD research study: retention of disabled students in Scottish higher education.

If, after reading the Participant Information Sheet and discussing further issues with the researcher (Patricia), you want to participate in the project, please sign and return this form as a way of corroborating your voluntary participation.

Statements regarding consent to participation and data handling.	Reply options (yes or no)	
1. I hereby declare that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet (PIS).	YES	NO
2. I declare that I understand the purpose of the study and had the opportunity to discuss any concerns with the researcher.	YES	NO
3. I understand that participating in this study involves taking part in two interviews with the researcher.	YES	NO
4. I consent to take part in this study by participating in two interviews with the researcher.	YES	NO
5. I understand that I will not obtain a direct benefit from my participation in this study.	YES	NO
6. I give my consent for the interviews to be recorded and for the audio recording to be safely stored for the duration of this project (the year 2023).	YES	NO
6.1. Only if you chose NO in the previous question: I do not consent to have my voice recorded during the interviews, but, alternatively, I give my consent for the researcher to take notes of what we discuss for data analysis purposes.	YES	NO
7. I consent for the interviews' audio recording to be transcribed by the PhD researcher for data analysis purposes.	YES	NO
8. As explained in the PIS, I consent for the information I provide to be anonymised and treated confidentially as far as possible and understand that complete anonymity cannot always be guaranteed.	YES	NO
9. I understand that some parts of my interview might be directly quoted in the documents derived from this study but will always be disguised to reduce the risk of my identity being revealed.	YES	NO
10. I agree to keep this consent form safely stored, at least during the duration of the study. The researcher will do the same with a copy of it.	YES	NO
11. I understand that I am entitled to access the information I provide at any time I wish while it is being stored.	YES	NO
12. I understand that I can withdraw my participation in the study at any time, without the need to provide a reason and without consequences.	YES	NO

Follow-up:

Statements concerning contact and follow-up after the interview.	Reply options (yes or no)	
I would like to receive the analysis of my interviews transcripts once it is completed.	YES	NO
I would like to be contacted in the future regarding the progress and results of this project.	YES	NO

After engaging with the information shared above, I _____,
agree to voluntarily participate in this research study.

- Signature of the participant:
- Date:

Researcher: Patricia Castellano, PhD student, University of the West of Scotland.

- Signature of the researcher:
- Date:

If you have any other questions or issues you would like to discuss, do not hesitate to send me an e-mail at _____

If you wish to contact the supervisory teams overlooking the development of this project, you can do so by emailing Dr Beth Cross at _____

Thank you very much for your collaboration!

Appendix 5: Interviews Schedules for Disabled Students Currently Enrolled in HE

First interview

Topics guide:

- Current and past experiences in HE.
- Teaching and learning practices as risk or protective factors towards persistence and retention.
- Perceptions of their role as a student and the role of their higher education institutions.
- Examples of good practices.
- Conflicts or tensions with peers and staff.
- Intentions to persist or withdraw.

Questions:

- 1) What are you studying at the moment?**
- 2) What led you to start working on this Project?**
 - What would you like to get from your PhD? What do you hope to do after you finish?
 - How are you finding it?
- 3) Can you tell me more about your experience of higher education?**
 - What did you do for your undergrad and masters?
 - How was your experience then?
- 4) In both cases, you undergraduate and postgraduate degrees, was university different from what you expected? Why?**
- 5) How did you find the teaching and learning experience?**
 - What did you find more valuable from the teaching you receive? What kind of teaching/learning experiences do you benefit from the most?
 - Are there some teaching styles that you find challenging?
 - How accessible do you find the teaching and learning experiences where at your institutions?
- 6) Do you wish you had support during your undergraduate and postgraduate degrees? What do you think would have helped?**
- 7) Has the pandemic had an impact on your experience of higher education? In which way?**
- 8) How do you hope things will be in the future?**
- 9) I am aware that you are going through a diagnosis process at the moment, and it might be very early days, but how are you finding this process?**
- 10) Do you feel like it might have a positive impact on your experience as a PhD student? What about on your experience as a lecturer?**
- 11) Have you experienced any major difficulties while in higher education?**

12) Have you ever thought about leaving your degree? If you have, why?

- What led you to consider that option? How can that be changed? Did you share your concerns with anyone? Did you talk to anyone at the university? Did you receive any support?

13) What do you think institutions in Scotland can do to prevent disabled students from leaving their studies before graduating?

14) Do you think institutions have learned any lessons from the pandemic?

15) Is there anything else you would like to add?

Second interview:

Topics guide:

- Follow-up of relevant topics that might have arisen in the previous interview.
- Changes in the participants' intentions to persist or withdraw since the first interview.
- Changes in their awareness of the impact of pedagogical practice on their intentions to persist.
- How they believe that teaching and learning practices could support retention and success in the future.
- Recent experiences in HE.
- Demographics.

Questions:

1) Do you think your teaching/learning experience could be improved? If so, how?

2) If there is anything you are not satisfied with in terms of teaching and learning practice? How do you feel about that?

3) Do you believe there something you, as a student can do to improve things?

16) Prompts: Talk to management? Student Inion?

4) How is your relationship with teaching staff?

17) Prompts/follow-up:

18) Do you feel supported? Can you talk to them about the adjustments that you need?

19) Do you feel lecturers take accessibility and disabled students into account? Is there anything you would like them to do differently?

20) What would you say is the most positive thing you've come across during your time at this institution?

5) What do you think could be making disabled students drop out at higher rates than non-disabled students? How do you feel about that?

6) How has university been lately? I remember you mentioned BRING UP RELEVANT TOPICS FROM THE PREVIOUS INTERVIEW.

7) Have you been enjoying your course lately?

21) Follow-up: Anything in particular that you would like to mention?

- 8) **Do you believe this degree is taking you closer to your goals?**
- 9) **How's the teaching/learning been?**
- 22) Follow-up: Any changes from when we last met? (in terms of delivery mode, content, etc.)
- 10) **Are you having more face-to-face teaching/interaction? How are you feeling about that?**
- 11) **Regarding support, have you been able to access what you needed?**
- 23) Follow-up: Have there been any changes to the support you needed in the last term? How do you feel about that?
- 12) **Have there been any changes to the way you view teaching practice?**
- 24) Follow-up: The work educators do? The quality of the teaching experiences?
- 13) **How accessible do you think teaching/learning has been lately?**
- 14) **How do you feel about teaching and learning at your institutions? What impact do you think it can have on your experiences at university?**
- 25) Follow-up: Do you think it has the potential to affect your decision about staying or leaving higher education?
- 26) Do you think it could affect other disabled students' persistence in higher education?
- 15) **Do you think that changing the way teaching/learning is done at the university could help you graduate?**
- 27) Follow-up: in which ways?
- 16) **In our previous interview you mentioned that you had (or hadn't or are thinking) thought about dropping out. Do you still feel the same way?**
- 28) Follow-up: What do you think is impacting this decision? What made you change your mind?
- 17) **In the last interview, you mentioned that you'd change _____ about teaching/learning at your university. Do you still feel the same way? Would you add anything to it?**
- 18) **In regard to support. Have you accessed the ones you need?**
- 29) Follow-up: How supportive you consider the institution has been lately? How effective are the supports you had lately?
- 19) **Do you feel supported at your institution?**
- 30) Follow-up: Are there specific people who support you?
- 20) **How much do you perceive that the institution cares about disabled students staying in higher education? How do you feel about that?**
- 31) Follow-up: What about staff?
- 21) **If you ever felt like you were struggling and at risk of dropping out, what would you like your university to do?**
- 32) Follow-up: In terms of support, communication, etc.? And in terms of teaching? Have you got someone in mind you could contact?
- 22) **Is there anything else you would like to add or ask?**

Appendix 6: Interview Schedule for Disabled People Formerly Enrolled in HE

Topics guide:

- Experiences of HE related to teaching and learning.
- Event of withdrawal: sequence, what influenced the decision, participants' feelings, involvement of the HEIs, consequences, impact on their lives, etc.
- Elements that supported completion.
- Identification of problem areas that could be modified to make teaching and learning practice more supportive for disabled students in HE in the future.

Questions:

Thank you very much for being here today. I have just started the recording and will ask you some questions now. Please, feel free to let me know when or if you would like a break, and remember that your participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw at any point if you wish to do so. Would you like me to start the interview?

- 1) The first thing I wanted to ask you is about the university you were enrolled at, which one is it? What were you studying there? When did you start?**
- 2) Why did you initially decide to apply to university?**
- 3) What did you think about it when you started your degree?**
- 4) How was the beginning of your degree (first weeks, month, first year, etc.)? How did you feel?**
- 5) How did university compare to what you thought it was going to be like?**
- 6) Feel free to share as much or as little as you want, but could you tell me more about what happened?**
- 33) When did you realise you will not be going back?**
- 34) When did this happen?**
- 35) How did you feel?**
- 7) Did you have the opportunity to discuss this with anyone from your social network?**
 - Follow-up: Someone from the university? Did you get any support from the university?
- 8) Do you think something could have prevented you from dropping out?**
- 9) How supportive do you feel the university was in general?**
 - Follow-up: For example, what approach did they have about inclusion?
 - Or general attitudes towards disability and inclusion?
- 10) What do you do now?**
- 11) Would you like to go back to higher education? Or other form of education?**

- 12) If you do, how would you like things to be? What kind of supports would you like to see? What could make your experience more positive?**
- 13) I am specifically looking at the role of T+L, I wanted to ask you about this specifically. Is that ok?**
- 14) How did you find teaching at your institution?**
- Prompts: Was interesting? Engaging? Boring?
 - How did you feel about it?
- 15) Were there certain teaching styles you found challenging?**
- Follow-up: In which way?
- 16) Do you feel that the way in which you were taught played a role in your experience at university?**
- Prompts: For example, the format of the classes? Were they too long? Not engaging enough? Or was the material accessible?
- 17) What about your relationship with teaching staff?**
- 18) Do you feel like you gained positive skills or experiences during your time at your institution?**
- 19) Did you need any adjustments to support your learning during your time at university?**
- Follow-up: Did you have opportunities to discuss and negotiate these adjustments?
- 20) Were lecturers willing to make those adjustments?**
- 21) Was there a disability support office or a similar service?**
- Follow-up: Did you ever approach them?
 - How was your relationship with them?
- 22) Did you receive information about the disability support you could access?**
- 23) Did you feel supported at your university?**
- 24) Can you tell me about staff's attitudes at your university?**
- Follow-up: What about your peers?
- 25) Did lecturers make an effort to include everyone?**
- 26) Ever since you left higher education, have you engaged in other adult learning?**
- Prompts: Maybe college? Vocational training?
 - Follow-up: Is this something you would like to do in the future?
- 27) Is there anything intuitions could do better to support disabled students?**
- 36) Follow-up: To support their academic experience? To help them graduate?**
- 28) Would you mind guiding me through the process you had to follow to after you realised you had to leave your degree?**
- 37) Follow up: Did you have to officially tell your university?**
- 38) Did anyone reach out to you?**
- 39) Before it happened, did the institution realise you were at risk of early withdrawal?**

29) Do you think a different learning experience could have helped you stay in higher education?

30) If you could go back in time, is there anything you would like to change?

40) Follow-up: Either from you degree, your institution, the choices you made, etc.

31) Is there anything else you would like to add or ask?

Appendix 7: Interview Schedule for Disability Advisers Working in HE in Scotland

Topics guide:

- Role in supporting disabled students in higher education (HE).
- Implementation of accommodations and monitoring of their efficacy.
- Perceptions around the issue of disclosure.
- Attitudes about inclusion in HE.
- Knowledge and attitudes about disabled students' retention.
- Monitoring of retention rates.
- Next steps to support the retention of disabled students through teaching and learning practice.

Questions:

- 1) Could you give me an overview of your work at the Disability Team?**
 - Prompts: What are your main roles? Responsibilities?
- 2) How do you find your job?**
 - Prompts: Is there something you particularly like about it?
- 3) Do you consider the department has enough staff?**
 - Follow-up: And funding? And resources?
- 4) Could you tell me about the main means of communication and engagement that the office has?**
 - Follow-up: How is the service promoted so disabled students know about supports? How has this changed due to the pandemic?
- 5) How do disabled students normally approach you?**
 - Prompts: Do they email you? Come to the office?
 - Follow-up: How has this changed due to the pandemic?
- 6) Could you guide me into the process of support provision in your institution?**
 - Follow-up: How is the assessment done? Do you normally have a meeting?
 - Does the university require medical evidence to provide supports and adjustments? How has this changed due to the pandemic?
- 7) *If not mentioned yet:* How has this process changed due to the pandemic?**
- 8) What are the types of support students require?**
- 9) How long does it take for adjustments to be implemented?**
- 10) Are there general measures to ensure accessibility in the classroom?**
 - Prompts: For example, lecturers using microphones? Do they provide pre-recorded lectures? Do recordings have appropriate captions?
- 11) Thinking about lecturers, how is the general relationship with the support office?**
 - Follow-up: Are they open to learn about accessibility? How do you find it is to engage with them?

- How do they tend to respond to disabled students requiring adjustments?
What is their attitude towards inclusion? Do you perceive they make an effort in making teaching accessible?

12) Regarding disabled students, how is their relationship with the disability office?

- Follow-up: Do you find they are confident when it comes to asking for support?
How satisfied do you believe they are with the adjustments provided by the university and individual lecturers?

13) Could you identify any obstacles in the implementation of adjustments for disabled students in your institution?

- Follow-up: And facilitators?
- Prompts: Maybe positive attitudes, staff's knowledge of inclusive education, etc.

14) Once the adjustments and supports are implemented, is there a way to evaluate their efficacy?

- Prompts: Maybe receiving feedback from students and educators?

15) Regarding retention, do you know if the university monitors retention rates of the whole body of students?

- Follow-up: And for disabled students? Are you aware of any protocol to support disabled students that might be at risk of dropping out?

16) Is there anything you would change in how things work in the disability office to guarantee better responses for disabled students?

- Follow-up: And to improve the retention of disabled students?

17) Is there anything you think the university could do to support the retention of disabled students?

- Follow-up: And individual teaching staff?

18) Is there anything else you would like to add or ask?

Appendix 8: Interview Schedule for Educators Working in HE In Scotland

Topics guide:

- Most commonly implemented accommodations in the classroom and perception of their efficacy.
- Knowledge about disabled students' retention.
- Perceived impact of practice on the retention of disabled students.
- To what extent is retention considered throughout curriculum and class design and implementation.
- Attitudes towards inclusive education.
- Strategies to improve the retention rates of disabled students.

Questions:

- 1) I get to see what you do because I join the sessions that you run, but could you tell me about your job as a researcher developer?**
- 2) How was it before the pandemic started?**
- 3) How did you find the move to online delivery?**
 - Follow-up: How are things now?
 - How do you feel about the return to face-to-face teaching?
- 4) Have you got feedback from PGR students about online sessions? How do they find them?**
- 5) Are you frequently asked to implement adjustments?**
 - Follow-up: What kind?
- 6) Do you recall any accommodations you had to implement recently?**
 - Did those requests change during the pandemic? How?
- 7) How confident do you feel in implementing those accommodations? Do you have any support from the university? Is it enough?**
- 8) How did you find implementing supports during the pandemic?**
 - Prompts: Was it easier? More challenging?
 - Follow-up: Did you receive support from the university to do it?
- 9) Do you consider inclusion and accessibility when you are planning your teaching activities? And during delivery?**
 - Follow-up: For example, do you design material that might be broadly accessible from the beginning?
- 10) Do you feel like you have enough options to access training in inclusive education?**
 - Follow-up: Do you find it useful? Is there anything you are missing?

11) Many disabled students do not disclose their disability to their institutions.

Were you aware of this?

- Follow-up: Are you aware that some students might have hidden disabilities?
- This means they are less likely to ask for and access accommodations. Is there anything you think, you as an educator, could do to support the learning experience of these students?

12) Have you ever received any information about the retention of disabled PGR students?

- Prompts: As in a meeting or training, etc.?
- Follow-up: Is it something you would like to know more about?

13) Do you believe teaching and learning practice influences the experience of disabled students?

- Follow-up: How? And their retention?

14) How much you, as an educator, believe teaching staff could do to promote the retention of disabled students?

15) Is there something the university could do to promote the retention of disabled students?

16) Is there anything else that you think could help disabled students graduate?

17) Going back to the pandemic, if you could travel back in time and return to March 2020, what would have helped you make the move to online teaching smoother?

- Follow-up: What would have helped you make support provision easier? For example, what kind of support would you have liked to receive? What kind of knowledge would you have liked to have? What kind of training?

18) In terms of pedagogical practice, do you believe institutions have learned positive lessons moving forward?

- Follow-up: And educators?

19) Is there anything that you would like to see implemented long time?

- Follow-up: Is there anything that you believe should not remain?

20) Is there anything else you would like to add or ask?

Appendix 9: Research Summary Shared with Participants

Retention of disabled students in Scottish Higher Education: a brief summary

PhD candidate: Patricia Castellano

Supervisors: Dr Lindsay Coyle and Dr Beth Cross

1

Introduction

- These slides provide a brief overview of the study's findings, discussion and recommendations.
- I hope these are of interest to you and that this file creates an opportunity for further dialogue between us.
- I would be very appreciative of your input, so please feel free to share any comments, suggestions, or considerations you might have. I will then incorporate these into the thesis manuscript and make changes accordingly.
- Do not hesitate to get in touch at any point if you have any questions or concerns.
- Many thanks again for your time and collaboration!

2

Context

- Low student retention rates are a difficulty faced by many Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) worldwide (Manyanga, Sithole and Hanson, 2017).
- Some students, like disabled students, are at increased risk of early exit due to the barriers they experience in HE (Frank, McLinden and Douglas, 2020).
- Research exploring the retention of disabled students in HE is limited, particularly through a critical lens.
- **Research aim:** to investigate how current educational cultures, discourses, and practices help fulfil or foreclose the aspirations of disabled students in Scottish HE and how these shape their retention.
- **Methodology:**
 - Feminist Poststructuralist epistemological framework (Aston, 2016).
 - Semi-structured interviews (N=29): disabled students who were enrolled in Scottish HE at the time of interviews, disabled people who were formerly enrolled in Scottish HE, and staff working in the same sector.
 - Data analysis: Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021) and Critical Discourse Analysis (see Ollivier, Aston and Price, 2020).

3

Findings

- Two main areas of discussion:
 - **Disability support services:**
 - Hierarchies: idealised notion of disabled students
 - Responsibility: difficulties and lack of clarity around support implementation
 - **Pedagogical practices:**
 - Lack of care at the institutional level.
 - Need for pedagogies that promote an ethics of care based on:
 - Valuing disabled students as whole human beings.
 - Promoting choice by taking an anticipatory approach to inclusive education.
 - Using hybrid learning as a tool for inclusion.
 - Promoting the sense of belonging of disabled students in the era of hybrid learning.

4

Discussion

- Disability support services and pedagogical practices play a crucial role in the experiences of disabled students in Scottish HE.
- However, these two areas are permeated by neoliberal notions of normalcy that favour narrow ways of being and learning (see Madriaga *et al.*, 2011) and promote an idealised understanding of the experiences and identities of disabled students (see Dadvand, 2022).
- There is a need for pedagogies of care that consider and value the whole human experiences of disabled students to help face challenges across the current “uncaring” (Gravett, Taylor and Fairchild, 2024, p. 388) neoliberal, post-pandemic HE landscape (Xiao, 2021; Lemon, Harju-Luukkainen and Garvis, 2023; Lopez, 2023).
- There is a need to:
 - Deconstruct the current idealised notion of disabled students across Scottish HE and adopt an intersectional approach instead.
 - Adopt an ethics of care where responsibility plays a key role across Scottish HE.
- I argue that adopting an intersectional lens and promoting care and responsibility, in conjunction with hope, can create multiple possibilities for Scottish HE to become a sector that helps fulfil the aspirations of all disabled people (students and staff) and promotes their retention.

5

Recommendations

- Promoting collaboration between institutions, policy-makers, and different members of the educational community to promote sustainable change toward a more caring and compassionate HE.
- Student retention should be an area considered as important as student recruitment, with a focus on the retention of students at higher risk of early exit, such as disabled students.
- The adoption of care-based strategies such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and Trauma-Informed Pedagogies is recommended as they could help build inclusion across the sector.
- It is recommended that HEIs eliminate medical evidence as a prerequisite to access disability support and consider alternatives like written testimonies from students.
- Supervisors, disability support services and study skills departments should be equipped with knowledge and abilities to support disabled PhD candidates.
- Follow-up protocols must be in place for students who leave their degrees before completion.
- Adopt an anticipatory approach to inclusive education, building inclusion in all educational practices to ensure as many disabled students as possible can access education effectively without having to request individual accommodations.
- Consider the increased accessibility that hybrid and blended learning can bring to disabled students and how this can be embedded in regular practice.
- Disability support policies and practices should consider the circumstances of all disabled students, including master's and postgraduate research. They should also consider the changing symptoms of certain health conditions and the difficulties disabled people can experience accessing medical evidence.
- Ensure care, compassion, and responsibility are at the centre of support policies and practices. This includes offering alternative or temporary support for disabled students who experience delays accessing accommodations or creating systems that increase accountability in the support provision process.
- Consult with all students, but particularly disabled students in the development of inclusive practices to ensure these meet students' needs.
- Disabled students can take part in existing or create new opportunities for collaboration with members of the educational community, which can influence the development of policies and practices and challenge traditional power relationships across the sector.

6

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Thank you!

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